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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 4, Number 1, March, 2024 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remains indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Umar Sodangi
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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4, Number 3 to 6, 2024). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Associate Professor Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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An Assessment on Proliferation and Implications of Central Mosques for Friday Weekly Prayers in Bauchi Metropolis, Bauchi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Bauchi emirate was founded by one of the disciples of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī Mallam yā'qub ibn Dādi. Mosques being one of the symbols of religion and one of the most important institutions in any Islamic state were among other things established by Amir Yā'qub at some strategic places with a Central one in front of his palace. The mosque remained the only Juma'at mosque in the town for decades. However, in the late 20th and early 21st century, Bauchi started experiencing rapid proliferation of Juma'at mosques. This paper attempts to examine the trend of the proliferation of Juma'at mosques in Bauchi town and its implications using historical methods, primary and secondary sources, oral interviews, archival materials and other extant literature. The paper discovered that constant and sustained increases in population, urbanization, competition and contestation for the religious public sphere by the various Islamic groups and philanthropic activities of some wealthy Muslims, politicians and Government patronage are among the factors that lead to these phenomena. The paper finally recommends among other things the need for the regulation of the establishment of Friday mosque by the constituted authorities in conjunction with other religious bodies and organizations for the cohesion and harmony of the Muslim Ummah.

Keywords: Proliferation, Bauchi Emirate, Friday Mosque,

Introduction

Masjid is an Arabic word, which is simply translated to mean Mosque. A mosque is a building where Muslims worship (Hornby, 2022). The mosque, according to Abdul Fattah (2007) is the house or a specified place where Allah is worshipped. while (Yahaya, 2020) is of the view that a Masjid (Mosque) aisa place specially consecrated for all acts of sincere worship and submission to Allah which includes teaching and learning of religious studies and activities of preaching (*Da'awah*) and reconciliation of disputes or rifts. The importance of Mosque in Islam is so paramount that different verses of the Glorious Qur'an epitomize its usage by all Muslims' For example, as a cardinal importance to remember Allah therein, the Noble Qur'an states:

وَمَنْ أَظْلَمُ مِمَّنْ مَنَعَ مَسْجِدَ اللَّهِ أَنْ يُذَكَّرَ فِيهَا اسْمُهُ وَسَعَىٰ فِي خَرَابِهَا أُولَٰئِكَ مَا كَانَ لَهُمْ أَنْ يَدْخُلُوهَا إِلَّا خَائِفِينَ ۗ لَهُمْ فِي الدُّنْيَا خِزْيٌ
وَلَهُمْ فِي الْآخِرَةِ عَذَابٌ عَظِيمٌ

And who is more unjust than he who prevents (men) from the Mosques of Allah,
that His name should be remembered in them, and strives to ruin them? (As for)

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these, it was not proper for them that they should have entered them except in fear; they shall meet with disgrace in this world, and they shall have great chastisement in the hereafter (Q2:114).

The above verse according to Yahaya (2000) establishes the fact that Mosque in Islam has its origin.

The first Mosque to be established was the Masjid al-Haram (Ka'bah) in Makkah as established in the Glorious Qur'an, Allah (SWT) says:

إِنَّ أَوَّلَ بَيْتٍ وُضِعَ لِلنَّاسِ لَلَّذِي بِبَكَّةَ مُبَارَكًا وَهُدًى لِّلْعَالَمِينَ ﴿٩٦﴾

Most surely, the first House (of worship) established for mankind is the one of Bakkah [i.e.; Makkah] blessed and guidance for the (entire) world Prophet (3:96).

Building or establishing of mosque is one of the paramount duties of every capable Muslim individual or community, as they are told that they would earn huge rewards from Allah not only in this world but also in the hereafter. Prophet Muhammad is reported to have said:

“Whoever builds a mosque for Allah, Allah would build similar to it for him in paradise”(Muslim Book of Masajid Hadith Number 1218)

Another Hadith on the authority of Usman bin Affān goes thus:

“Whosoever builds a mosque where Allah's name is being mentioned Allah would build a house for him in paradise (Sunan Ibn Majah Kitabul Masajid wal jama'ah Hadith No. 735)

Mosques throughout the history of Islam have been solid institutions serving multiple functions that are not confined or restricted to spiritual matters alone. The roles of Mosques among Muslims extend to other socio-economic and political spectrums such as education, zakat collection and distribution charity and almsgiving, political mobilization, etc. In recognition of the important role of mosques among the Muslims, the Sokoto Jihad leaders used to emphasize the erection and maintenance of mosques in the appointment letters to the new Emirs appointed. Mallam *yā'qubu* ibn Dādi one of the disciples of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī, and the founder of Bauchi Emirate like other flag bearers was given a formal letter of investiture as the first Amir of Bauchi by Sheikh Uthmān bin Fūdī and the letter among other things states “...I command you to exert yourselves in repairing and maintaining mosques....(Yero (1999).

The first mosque built by Mallam *yā'qubu* was in Inkil town before the establishment of Bauchi town. However, with the establishment of Bauchi town, about twelve mosques were established at some strategic locations with a Central one in front of the Emir's palace which remained the only Juma'at mosque where the people of Bauchi metropolis and its environs trooped weekly to observe Friday prayers with Mallam Yaqub as the first Imam (Yero,1999). However, around 1820 perhaps due to the pressing and persistent task of running the emirate, Mallam *yā'qubu* had to appoint somebody to take over the office of the Imam in person of Mallam Bahago son of Mallam Adamu Maudo. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 11th March 2018).

Since the time of AmīrYaqūb, the institution of mosques in the Bauchi emirate has been under the office of the Chief Imam of Bauchi who supervises and regulates its establishment. No new mosque can be established except with the consent and approval of the Emir who sends the chief Imam or his representative to conduct prayers in the mosque as a mark of the Emir's approval. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 23rd November 2023).

The precedence set by Mallam *yā'qubu* where the emirate had a serious stake in the establishment and coordination of mosques and appointment of Imams remained in force over the centuries even after the colonisation of Northern Nigeria by British Emperors.

This according to (Abubakar 2021) greatly assisted in maintaining unity among the Muslim *Ummah* in the emirate.

This development, however, was to suffer some setbacks, especially from the 1980s due to many reasons culminating in the proliferation of Juma'at mosque in Bauchi Metropolis with its attendant consequences. This paper, therefore, traces the history of the establishment of the Friday mosque in Bauchi, the role of the Bauchi Emirate in this regard and the proliferation of mosques experienced since the 1980s.

Islam in Bauchi Emirate

Before the 19th century Jihād of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī, the region out of which the present Bauchi emirate was carved, was a predominantly pagan area (Sulaiman 1987 and Yero 1999). Islam was said to have been introduced to the Bauchi

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region from Borno and Hausa land as far back as before the 18th century through trading activities between the Muslim traders from Borno and the non-Muslim people residing in the region and the missionary activities of some Islamic scholars. One such Scholar was Mallam Ishāq who hailed from Borno and moved to Ganjuwa and later Jitar town. Coincidentally, it was this scholar who served as *yā'qubu's* first teacher and the one who took him and introduced him to Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī in Sokoto. This according to Umar (2016) has confirmed that there was Islam in the region only that its impact was negligible because its spread was considerably slow.

When Mallam Yaqūbu was commissioned as the flag bearer of the Bauchi region he was reinforced with learned scholars by Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī and charged with the command of waging a *Jihād* upon the Bauchi pagans. Yaqūbu was said to have first settled in Inkil town for about four to eight years before establishing Bauchi town where he engaged in the mass calling and conversion of the pagans to Islam through various means including sending his envoys to the leaders of the various pagan communities (Yero 1999). According to Sulaimān (1997), Mallam Yā'qubu embarked on extensive resettlement schemes aimed at boosting Muslim populations, providing defences for them as well as improving agriculture. The overall result was the emergence of new towns with absolute Muslim majorities serving at the same time as urban centres in the Bauchi emirate. These centers were in line with the overall Sokoto caliphate *Ribat* Policy which served as military garrisons against any possible attack on the territory and helped significantly in promoting mass literacy, urbanization, socialization food production and security throughout the caliphate. New towns such as Kafin Dulumi, Kafin Madaki, Rauta, Nasarawa, etc. were all established by the Bauchi emirate for this purpose. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 23rd November 2023).

Bauchi Emirate and the establishment of Friday Mosques

One important impetus to the growth of Islam in the Bauchi emirate was the way the area came to be proliferated with ranks of scholars over the years. Mallam Yaqūbu, in compliance with advice offered to him by Sultan Bello in his popular treatise, *Al-Ghayth al-Shu'ub fi Tawsiyati Amir Ya'qub*, was said to have recruited a considerable number of scholars with requisite qualifications who served in various capacities as scribes, special advisers or officials attached to the administration of justice, while others served as imams of mosques and disseminators of Islamic education. (Zailani N.D). He was said to have surrounded himself with the company scholars whom he consulted in almost every affair of state (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, May 3, 2018).

In compliance with the terms of his appointment, as mentioned earlier, Yaqūbu was said to have constructed Mosques in almost all the places he succeeded in bringing under his suzerainty. In Bauchi, the capital of the emirate for instance, about twelve mosques are said to have been strategically established at different locations plus a Central one in front of the Emir's palace. Whenever there is a vacancy in the office of the Imam it is the emir that has the sole right and responsibility to appoint a new one from among the learned scholars of the town after consultations with his council and after a careful assessment (Umar 2016).

The first person appointed as Imam of the Bauchi Central Mosque was Mallam Bahago son of Mallam Adamu Maudo next after him was Mallam Jibrilla, then Mallam Nurudeen son of Alqādi Mallam Qāsim, next was Imam Ahmadu, then Imam Muhammadu, then Imam Mahmood, then Imam Ahmad Bāban Inna son of Imam Mahmood, after him Imam Muhammad Inuwa Jahun then Imam Bala Ahmad who is the current chief Imam. (Ado Danrimi, personal interview, May 2018)

Since the time of 'Amīr Yaqūbu, the institution of mosques in the Bauchi emirate has been under the office of the Chief Imam of Bauchi who supervises and regulates its establishment. No new mosque could be established except with the consent and approval of the Emir who sends the chief Imam or his representative to conduct prayers in the mosque as a mark of the Emir's approval. This had been the system in the Bauchi emirate for decades until the early eighties (B. Baban Innah, personal interview, May 3, 2012).

Proliferation of Juma'at Mosques in Bauchi Metropolis

From the late 80s and early 90s to the present time, there has been a constant and massive proliferation of Juma'at mosques in the Bauchi metropolis a phenomenon which according to Cleo Cantone (2012) was not peculiar to Nigeria. Many factors have been identified as the brain behind these phenomena some of which include;

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1. Emergence of the Izālah Movement

One of the factors that led to the proliferation of Mosques in the Bauchi emirate is the emergence and activities of the Izālah movement or organization and the uncomplimentary and hostile attitude exhibited by the emirate council to the movement. Described by Lomier (1997), as one of the most influential and powerful reform movements in northern Nigeria, Formed by some Muslims in northern Nigeria to preach and uphold what they believe to be the correct doctrines, teachings and practices of Islam as enunciated in the Qur'an and the prophetic traditions.

The *Izālah* members in particular give preference to the building of their mosques because it serves as a centre for the dissimulation of their mission. When they decided to open their own separate Juma'at Mosque in Bauchi in 1978, they wrote a letter to the Emir of Bauchi through the then Chief Imam late Ahmad Mahmood Bāban Innah informing the emirate council of their intention. After inviting them for a discussion, the Emirate Council rejected their move based on the reason that the move would divide and foment trouble among the Muslim Ummah. (M. Gidado Umar, personal interview, May 3, 2013).

However, in defiance of the emirate council's order, the *Izālah* movement went ahead with their plan by opening their first Juma'at Mosque in Bauchi town in Gwallaga quarters in 1978, thus eroding for the first time the power of the emirate council of approving the establishment of Friday mosque. The Emirate Council on its part wrote a letter to the Nigerian Police seeking for the closure of the Mosque for fear of possible unrest. Consequently, the Mosque was closed down by the Police and the designated Chief Imam Mallam Gidado Umar and some other leaders of the organization were arrested and detained in police custody and later taken to court for prosecution. However, they were eventually acquitted and set free by the court.

The treatment meted out to the members of the *izālah* movement by the Emirate council which culminated in the court judgment in their favour made them perceive the Emiraterate council as being unsympathetic to their course as such they embarked on the establishment of more mosques in different locations throughout the Emirate without seeking approval of the Emirate Council. Some of these mosques include the Bākin Kura Mosque built by the Late Alhaji Abdullahi Mai Auduga at Bākin Kura quarters (which was later expanded and upgraded to Juma'at Mosque) and the Bukar N.T.C. Mosque built by the late Alhaji Bukar Birma at Bākaro quarters and several others. As the number of mosques kept on increasing the *Izālah* organization had to create a special directorate saddled with the task of regulation and co-ordination of the Mosques under its control, especially the Juma'at Mosque. This is a sharp contrast to the Mosques that are under the control of the Emirate councils

In 1991, a dispute which is seen by many as due to leadership tussle within the leadership of the movement erupted which led to the split of the movement into two factions. The dispute according to Lomier (1997) acquired a rather bitter note because of the stubborn adherence of both factions to doctrinal arguments leading to the mutual accusation of *kufi* and *shirks* by each side to discredit the other side. Just as the *Izālah* movement discouraged their followers from praying behind the Sufi or in the mosque's control, so also the warring *izālah* factions issued verdicts discouraging or even prohibiting their followers from praying behind their rival factions. A clear example is contained in a pamphlet titled: "*Hujjojin da suka hana bin wadanda suke bin Sheikh Isma'ila Idris Sallah daga Alkur'ani da hadisi*" (i.e "pieces of evidence from the Qur'an and Hadith against praying behind the supporters of Shaykh Isma'ila Idris") (written by one Umar Muhammad Nasarawa Sābon Pegi, Adamawa state, Nigeria and endorsed by the Adamawa state Chairman Council of Preachers under the Kaduna faction of the *Izālah*. (Gurama, 1999).

As each faction wants to dominate the religious space against the other faction, there emerges a new trend of a multiplicity of both Juma'at and five daily mosques in many communities in the Bauchi metropolis. There are instances where multiple Juma'at or five daily prayer mosques are cited within a particular vicinity where there is a need for only one. For instance, in the Kandahar quarter, it is estimated that there are not less than fifteen Juma'at and over twenty daily prayer mosques belonging to two different *izālah* factions. In the same Kandahar quarters there are two Juma'at mosques very close to each other and belonging to two different *izālah* factions. Along Gombe Road and Bauchi Central Car Park all in the Bauchi metropolis, there are two Mosques located opposite to each other.

According to Baban Innah (B. Baban Innah, personal interview, May 3, 2012), the number of mosques under the jurisdiction of the *Izālah* organization in Bauchi and its environs put together might outnumber those that are under the control of other Islamic organizations. This is a sharp contrast to the mid-seventies were there were only one Juma'at mosque in Bauchi.

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2. Population explosion and rapid urbanization

The constant and sustained population explosion coupled with rapid urbanization in the late eighties and early nineties in Bauchi led to the expansion of existing settlements and the emergence of new ones, especially outside the walled city of Bauchi. The primary factor responsible for this is the uncontrolled migration of people from rural areas and the neighbouring states. In 1991 and 2004 for instance, Plateau state experienced one of the bloodiest ethnic-religious crises that claimed hundreds of lives and rendered thousands of people homeless. There was also the Boko Haram crisis which ravaged Borno and some parts of Yobe state these fracas led many people to migrate to the neighboring Bauchi state which was closer in terms of proximity, especially Bauchi town and its environs for their safety. This phenomenon led to the emergence of new settlements in Baran Kandahar quarters, Bayan Airport quarters and a couple of others that are located outside the traditional Bauchi walled town, these provided opportunities especially for different Muslim groups to build new Friday and five daily prayer mosques in each of these new settlements.

3. Investment in Mosque building by some wealthy businessmen and politicians

Investment in the building of Mosques is one of the paramount duties that attract great rewards. Prophet (S.A. W.) was reported to have said

Whoever builds a masjid (mosque) for the sake of Allah, Allah will build something similar for him in Paradise. (ibn Majah Chapter hadith no.735)

The above quoted and similar hadith might have been one of the reasons that prompted Muslims, especially the well, to embark on the building mosque. In Bauchi metropolitan city as discussed earlier, the first Juma'at mosque owned by the izālah movement was a house donated by Alhaji Sule Mekanike, which was converted to Juma'at Mosque.

There was also the Late Alhaji Audu Mai Auduga, who built a Juma'at mosque for the izālah at Bākin Kura quarters, The Abu-Huraira Juma'at mosque, built by the Late Alhaji Nuru Jibrin, the late Alhaji Ishaqa Jibrin who built a Juma'at Mosque along Ran Road in Bauchi. Engineer Zubairu Ya'qub built a Juma'at Mosque at the G.R.A. behind Bauchi State Government House, Bauchi.

Besides these there are also some politicians and other government functionaries who built Juma'at mosques among them is; Mallam Isah Yuguda the former Governor of Bauchi state who built Umar bin Khattab Juma'at mosque at Rafin Albasa Quarters in Bauchi, the former Minister of the Federal Capital Territory and present governor of Bauchi state senator Bala A. Muhammad who built Uthmān bin Fodio Juma'at Mosque at G.R.A. also in Bauchi metropolis. Most of these mosques are handed over to the Islamic organizations to which the donors subscribe.

4. Official Government patronage

Official patronage by the government is another factor that aided the proliferation of Jum at mosques in Bauchi. There are some mosques such as the Kasuwar Shanu Juma'at Mosque, the Abdurrahman bin Auwf Juma'at Mosque at Zango quarters, the Ibrahim Bako housing estate Juma'at mosque and the Mallam Mai Tauhidi Juma'at mosque along Atiku Abubakar way and many more which were constructed by the Bauchi State government between 2021 and 2023 thus increasing the number of Friday Mosques in Bauchi Metropolis.

5. Donations from International Islamic organizations

These organizations provided funds for the purchase of land and the construction of mosques in both the rural and urban areas of Bauchi. For instance, two mosques and Islamic centres were built by the Revival of the Islamic Heritage Society Kuwait and donated to the Jamā'atu izālatil bid'ah in 2017. There is also *Ikhlās* Mosque built by the Mu'assatul Tanwiril Islamiy in 2018. There is also the Masjid Salmānūl Fārisy for the *Jama'atu Tajdidil Islam* in Inkil built by an international charity organization and many others.

6. Competitions among Muslim organization's

As mentioned earlier, the Jama'atu *Izālatil Bid'ah* organization gives preference to the building of a mosque which serves as the mobilization and propagation centre of their activities. Their defiance of the emirate council's directives as mentioned earlier had instigated other groups to follow suit. The Tijjaniya Muslim Brotherhood for the first time built their separate Juma'at mosque in 2008, at Makera quarters in Bauchi. The Jamā'atu Tajdidul Islam (J.T.I.) have their Juma'at Mosque in Inkil, the As'hābul Kahafi Warraqimi built their Friday Masjid in Kandahar Quarter, the Nasrullahil

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Fatih (NASFAT) have their own along Maiduguri road by Firo, the Ansārudeen Muslim Society have their own along Kofar wase road and many more.

Conclusion

Mosque has been an important Islamic institution in Bauchi from the time when Islam was consolidated up to the 21st century. The centrality and significance of the Juma'at Mosque make the traditional authority in Bauchi oversee all the religious activities that take place within it. The First Juma'at Mosque was located in front of the Emir's palace to effectively control the congregants and imams. Whenever a new mosque was to be established, it was within the customary jurisdiction of the Emirate council to approve; this has been the practice from the time of the First Amir Mallam Yakubu up to the post-colonial period.

Although the unsympathetic and hostile attitude of the Bauchi emirate council towards the *Izalah* movement led them to establish their mosque formation of the *Izalah* movement in the late 70s and early 80's other factors such as demographic change, rapid urbanization, and the emergence of new settlements as a result of ethno religious crisis in some neighbouring states, competition among other religious groups, patronage from Government, Politicians and other well to do have all contributed into the massive building of Juma'at mosques in every nook and crannies of Bauchi Metropolitan and its environs. The results of all these translated into the massive proliferation of Juma'at mosques and thereupon the massive fragmentation of the Muslim Ummah along doctrinal lines which jettisoned the customary power of the Emirate Council concerning the establishment of new mosques and went ahead to build their separate Juma'at mosques.

Recommendations

This paper wishes to make the following recommendations

1. There is a need for the government in liaison with the Emirate Council, local government authorities and Muslim Organizations to form a forum or set a guideline for the regulation and establishment of Mosques especially the Juma'at Mosque by various organizations for cohesion and harmony of the Muslim *Ummah*.
2. The emirate council's old tradition of regulating and guiding the establishment of Juma'at Mosques by each Muslim organization should be restored by the Government which should in liaising with representatives of all Muslim organizations set guidelines for the establishment of Friday Mosques.
3. The unguided freedoms of religion brought by democracy whereby politicians engage in the building of Mosques also need to be controlled by the government.

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Assessment of Attitude towards Acquisition of Chemistry Content Knowledge among Students in Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the attitude on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State. Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consists of all chemistry students in Federal College of Education Zaria. Sample size of 150 (50 Male and 100 Female) students were selected from Chemistry Department during the 2023/2024 academic session using simple random sampling technique. The study adapted Martha Tapia Attitude towards Chemistry questionnaires. The data collected were tested and analyzed using SPSS V 18. Descriptive frequencies, independent t-test and one-way ANOVA analysis at a confidence level of 0.05 were carried out. The study highlighted that the overall Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students' attitudes toward Chemistry were moderate however, there was no statistically significant differences based on their gender or level of study. The study therefore concluded that the decline in positive attitude of students towards chemistry as their level of studies increases could be attributed to the high demand that learning required at higher levels. It is recommended that Chemistry lecturers should made Chemistry vivid and easy to understand in order to motivate students' intellectual curiosity, which will in turn leads to learning enhancement regardless of their career of choices.

Keywords: Chemistry content knowledge, attitude, gender, level of study

Introduction

Students' academic success has been the focus of researches in science education. As such, effects of several innovative strategies such as inquiry and discovery learning, advance organizers, activity-based learning, and so on, were examined on academic achievement in science subjects. Perhaps, this is because inappropriate teaching methodologies was considered as a dominant factor adduced to students' under-achievement in sciences (Ngeme, 2016; Odhiambo, 2016). However, academic success may be directly or indirectly linked to many other affective factors which among others include attitude, self-efficacy, motivation, and anxiety (Wan & Ma, 2013). Attitudes, like achievement are crucial outcomes of science education as such, every teacher is charged with the responsibility of promoting students' positive attitude towards learning (Yunus & Ali, 2018). The concept of attitude has been widely debated over the years and one of the conclusions drawn was that attitude represents a multidimensional construct the cognitive, affective, and behavioral (Musengimana et al., 2018). Hence, attitude is a concept of belief which may be positive or negative and indicate like or dislike towards an item. Essentially attitude are considered nor to be resistant reform, that is, will students' attitude change through direct and indirect learning, observations. Experiences, and learning environment (Heng & Karpudewan, 2014).

Undoubtedly, gender as an important factor interacting with attitude towards science cannot be overlooked, especially with increasing emphasis on how to boost man power for technological development as well as increasing the population or females in the field of science and technology. The issue of gender differences in researches in science education is inconclusive. For instance, the studies of Heug and Karpudewau (2014), Ratarnun and Osman (2018) reported significant gender difference in students' attitude towards chemistry while Wahyudiati et al, (2020); Majere et al. (2012) no significant

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gender difference in student's attitude towards chemistry. It is therefore, a focus in this study to contribute to literature by exploring influence of gender on students' attitudes towards Chemistry.

Attitude is one of the popular hypothetical construct used to explain phenomena of ones' interest, the way people think, how they feel and how things are being carried out (Heng & Karpudewan, 2014). Hence, attitude could be a good predictor of students' choice of subject. Especially, in the context of science education where students favour certain science subjects. Essentially, while attitude have powerful effect on behavior, this same influence can also create attitudinal change. That is, attitude are not set in stone and can be reinforced. In view of this, this study is guided by the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). The TPB was proposed by Ajzen (1985) and posits that intentions are determinant of behavior which in turns depends on person's attitude, his subjective norms and the perceived behavioural control..

Having established that students' positive attitude towards chemistry is congruent to their achievement (Al-Mutawah & Fateel, 2018; Montes et al., 2018), teachers and stakeholders in education are compelled to understand and revamp students' attitude in order to support their achievement in chemistry. This is because, even though several instructional strategies were introduced to enhance achievement in chemistry, students' performance in Colleges of Education is still worrisome. This claim is evident in the haphazard trend in performance of students in chemistry in the Department of Chemistry, Federal Colleges of Education, Zaria 2020-2023 as shown in table 1 below, where many of the total enrolments in the years under review are failing and even those that are passing, most of them passed with low grades usually Ds and Es (Examination office, Department of Chemistry, F.C.E, Zaria, 2024), this could be the consequences of negligence of their attitude towards the subject. Attitude towards learning plays a central role in achievement in science. Positive attitude are considered to be the basis for optimism which in in turn enhance achievement through persistence and resilience (Mokoro et al., 2014).

Table 1: NCE Students Chemistry performance from 2019 to 2020

Academic Year	2020	2021	2022
NCE I			
Total (%)	384(100)	338(100)	472(100)
Pass (%)	247(64.32)	200(59.17)	282(59.70)
Fail (%)	137(35.68)	138(40.83)	190(40.30)
NCE II			
Total (%)	325(100)	331(100)	448(100)
Pass (%)	164(50.46)	165(49.85)	221(49.33)
Fail (%)	161(49.54)	166(50.15)	227(50.67)
NCE III			
Total (%)	336(100)	268(100)	375(100)
Pass (%)	171(50.89)	154(57.46)	208(55.47)
Fail (%)	165(49.91)	114(42.54)	167(44.53)

Source: Examination office, Department of Chemistry, F.C.E, Zaria, 2024

On the other hand, negative attitude could breed anxiety and consequently, worsen students' achievement in sciences. Hence, the factors influencing students' attitude towards chemistry should not be disregarded, Factors, such as teachers' characteristics, parental influence, grade level, gender, motivation, depression, anxiety, instructional methods, interest, classroom environment, perceived difficulty, relevance of curriculum and so on were considered to influence students' attitude towards chemistry. However, attitude, instructional methods, gender and grade level were prominent among these factors (Musengimana et al., 2021).

Objectives of the study

The objectives through which the aim could be achieved are to;

1. Assess the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria.
2. Find out the difference between level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria.
3. Find out the difference between level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria.

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Research Questions

- 1- What is the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?
- 2- Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?
- 3- Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consists of all chemistry students in Federal College of Education Zaria, during the 2023/2024 academic session, sample size of the study consist of 150 (50 Male and 100 Female) chemistry students across all levels. The sample size was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. A questionnaire was used to collect the data and was adapted from the Attitude towards Chemistry Index (ATCI) by Martha Tapia (Tapia, 1996; Tapia & Marsh, 2000b; Tapia & Marsh, 2004). The adapted ATCI consisted of forty questions and was answered based on a four-point Likert scale. The ATCI consisted of four Domains: The Motivation, Enjoyment, Value and self-confidence. There are five questions corresponding to the motivation domain, ten questions measuring Enjoyment and Value each and fifteen questions for Self-confidence domain.

The instrument was subjected to expert suggestions and comments which were incorporated before administering. Forty Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students from FCE Kano participated in the pilot study. Reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach's alpha reliability test which shows the instrument to be reliable. The participants' overall attitude was determined based on the total score of the ATCI. Possible scores range from a minimum of 40 to a maximum of 160 since a 4-point Likert scale was used. For analysis the ranges of scores were divided into 3 portions. Scores ranging from 40-80 indicated a poor attitude, 81-119 a moderate attitude and 120-160 a good attitude.

For research questions 1, means, percentages and standard deviation were used in the analysis and for research questions 2 and 3, independent samples T-test and One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were explored at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge among students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of general attitude

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
General Attitude	150	60	160	117.2	23.4

As seen in Table 1, the attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education students on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge was moderate (mean = 117.2). In particular, the majority of the population (63.7%) had moderate attitudes.

Table 2: Distribution of General attitude among participants

Score Range	Description	Frequency	%
40-80	Poor	25	10.1
81-119	Moderate	85	63.7
120-160	Good	40	26.2

When one considers the large range in score, 60-160 (Table 2) it is recognized that the attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education students on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge widely varies.

Research Question 2

Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between male and female students in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

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Table 3: Difference in General attitude based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	T	Sig.
Male	50	106.2	20.2	123	-0.476	0.635
Female	100	118.7	24.2			

Table 3 shows the difference in means and standard deviation as well as results from the T-test when considering the difference between the attitudes of male and female Chemistry. The females have better attitudes than males on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge however, this difference was not significant ($t = -0.476$, $p = 0.635$).

Research Question 3

Is there significant difference on the level of attitude exhibited on acquiring chemistry content knowledge between levels one, two and in Federal College of Education, Zaria?

Table 4: Difference in general attitude towards Chemistry based on level of study

Levels	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Df	F	Sig
NCE I	50	109.2	24.7	60	160			
NCE II	50	110.8	23.5	83	144	3,234	1.789	0.182
NCE III	50	112.7	21.3	80	154			

In terms of level of study (Table 4), there is a slight decrease in the general attitude of the participants as the level of study increased although this change was not statistically significant ($F[3,120] = 1.789$, $P = 0.182$).

Discussion of Findings

Result from table 1 shows that Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students have a combination of both positive and negative attitudes on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge. Table 2 further suggests that only 10.1% of the population had poor attitudes and 26.2% had good attitudes towards Chemistry. Moreover, the fact that only 26.2% of the population had an overall good attitude suggests that over 70% of the chemistry students do not have good attitudes towards Chemistry. This may explain why to lecturers it appears as if Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students lack some background in Chemistry. Table 3 shows that the females have better attitudes than males on acquisition of Chemistry content knowledge, however, this difference was not significant ($t = -0.476$, $p = 0.635$). This is not surprising since as opined by Ogunkola & Garner-O'Neale (2013) in the Caribbean there are no marked differences between males and females in various sciences including Chemistry in the area of achievement which can be linked to attitude although the relationship is complicated. This is in line with the work of (Frost et al., 1994; Orhun, 2007; Osborne et. al., 2003; Townsend & Wilton, 2003)

In terms of level of study (Table 4), there is a slight decrease in the general attitude of the participants as the level of study increased although this change was not statistically significant ($F [3,120] = 1.789$, $P = 0.182$). This finding agree with that of Leah Garner-O'Neale (2015), McLeod (1994) and Ozgun-Koca (2010) who suggest that as students' progress in school their attitudes towards Chemistry decline. It is expected that students will develop a better understanding of how Chemistry concepts are used overtime as they progress. When students are introduced to new theories they do not immediately have a complete understanding of the concepts, as students advance to higher levels, the previous Chemistry concepts and skills which were taught are reinforced thus helping to provide them with a better understanding; which should create a better attitude towards Chemistry as they progress through the levels. However, Ali & Reid (2012) also reported that as students grow older and more forward their attitudes tend to worsen due to increase in workload.

Conclusion

Among the Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students at Federal College of Education, Zaria, the overall attitude towards Chemistry depicted was moderate in the ATCI used. There was no statistical significant differences between gender or across grade levels as it relates to the overall attitude of the Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry students at Federal College of Education, Zaria, a decline in positive attitudes of students towards Chemistry was revealed as their level of study increases, and this was attributed to high demand that learning required at the higher levels and the low efforts that students make particularly due to the lack of motivation.

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Recommendations

1. Chemistry lecturers can play a significant role in bridging the gap in Chemistry between low input of the students and high demand from the workload by making Chemistry vivid and easy to understand, in order to stimulate student's intellectual curiosity which in turn leads to learning enhancement regardless of their career choice, this can also help to build self-confidence.
2. Chemistry lecturers can extrinsically motivate students by application of friendly presentations, utilization of analogies and co-relation with everyday life. This can help to bridge the gap between low input of the student and high demand of the workload.
3. Federal government should provide facilities such as laboratory apparatus and equipment, computers etc. necessary for the teaching and learning chemistry at NCE level, which if effectively utilized could contribute positively in influencing the attitude of students on acquisition of chemistry content knowledge.

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Assessment of Difficult Chemistry Concepts among Teachers and Students in Colleges of Education in North West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study conducted in Colleges of Education, North West, Nigeria assessed teachers' and students' perceptions of difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program. The study was guided by five objectives, five research questions and five hypotheses tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of confidence. Two validated questionnaires, the "Chemistry Teachers Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire" (CTIODCQ) and the "Chemistry Students Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire" (CSIODCQ) were used to collect data from 68 chemistry teachers (48 males 20 females) and 335 chemistry students (156 males and 179 females) in three conventional Federal Colleges of Education in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. The samples were drawn using multistage sampling technique from a total population of 82 chemistry teachers (58 males and 24 females) and 2071 students (964 males and 1107 females). The CTIODCQ and CSIODCQ had Cronbach reliability coefficient 0.71 and 0.74 respectively. The analysis was done using IBM-SPSS version 26.0, employing statistical methods such as mean, standard deviation, t-test, and ANOVA. The findings revealed that teachers generally found the 20-item chemistry concepts to be moderately difficult, with no significant difference in their responses ($F(2,1037) = 1.845$; $p > 0.05$). However, students perceived these concepts as difficult, with a significant difference in their perceptions ($F(2, 6196) = 13.321$; $p < 0.05$). There was no statistically significant distinction between male and female teachers' or students' perceptions of concept difficulty. The study recommended enhancing teacher training, curriculum review, and student-centered pedagogical approaches in Nigerian Colleges of Education to address these challenges.

Keywords: Assessment, Difficult, Chemistry, Concepts

Introduction

As a nation, Nigeria envisions to be one of the leading economies of the world. As at 2007, the country had a lofty goal of being one of the 20 most developed economy by the year 2020 which had come and gone. The vision was popularly christened vision 2020 (Inegbenebor, *et al.*, 2018). The industrialization desire of Nigeria has however not abated. Be that as it may, it is common knowledge however, that the secret of any nation's development lies in the stock and quality of her science and technological know-how. Anaeto, *et al.*, (2016), succinctly captured the fact, "Science and Technology hold the key to the progress and development of any nation. Technology plays a fundamental role in wealth creation, improvement of the quality of life and real economic growth and transformation in any society" (p.1).

Quality Science and Technology Education should be rooted on strong foundation at the basic level of education. The need to have quality education at that level demands that among others, skilled teachers of right quality and attitudes should mount the saddle of service delivery at that level. Colleges of Education, the third tripod of the tertiary education in Nigeria are mandated to train sub-degree teachers for the basic education sector (National Policy on Education, 2014). Products of this system are awarded the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), the minimum entry qualification into the teaching profession in Nigeria (National Policy on Education 2014). The Colleges are regulated by the National Commission for Colleges of Education, which also set the minimum academic standard as well as accredit the programs. The minimum curriculum for NCE awarding institution is called the Minimum Standard. The Standard is reviewed after every five years and the current one subsisting is the 2020 edition. Teaching science as an integrated whole and the need to produce specialist teachers had engendered the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) to undertake far reaching reforms to

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reposition Colleges of Education to deliver on its mandate so as to produce teachers of requisite stock and quality for the basic education level. Many Colleges of Education are hosted in the North West region of Nigeria, comprising seven states: Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Jigawa, Sokoto and Zamfara.

The central place of chemistry discipline in science as well as its import in national development had been expressed in grandiose terms (Muoneke *et al.*, 2021). Some regard it as a central science while others opined it is the mother of all science owing to its confluence and influence. Furthermore, chemistry education is rate as the gate way to the deliverables of national development and growth occasioned via science education enterprise. Chemistry is prided as having features that makes it such a fascinating and engaging subject to teach and these also contribute to it being a challenging subject for many learners (Taber, 2019). Many concepts in chemistry are important for learning and understanding how the world functions in daily life (Haruna, 2016). There is hardly any science discipline at the tertiary level that a credit pass in chemistry at the O'level is not a prerequisite for admission. This underscores the need for proper grasp of the subject at the foundation level. Sadly, literature of teachers and students' conceptual difficulties in chemistry abounds (Cleopas, *et al.*, 2023; Adum-Gyamfi & Asaki, 2023; Essiam, *et al.*, 2023; Oladejo, *et al.*, 2023; Obikezie, *et al.*, 2023; Anim-Eduful, & Adu-Gyamfi, 2022; Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022; Saadon & Abbood, 2022; Stroumpouli & Tsaparlis, 2022; Akaygum & Arkun, 2022; He, *et al.*, 2021; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021; Nartey & Hanson, 2021; Nkiko, 2021; Longyil & Agbo, 2020; Awaah, *et al.*, 2020; Montenegro & Cascolan, 2020; Kenni, 2020; Amoke 2020; Moyo, 2018; Jack, *et al.*, 2017; Jack *et al.* 2017; Agogo & Onda, 2014; Otor & Achor 2013; Edu, *et al.*, 2012). Analysis of available literatures showed that learners conceptual difficulties could be due to teachers related factors (Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki, 2023; Onu, *et al.*, 2022; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021; Nartey & Hanson, 2021; Kinyanjui, 2019; Weiss, 2019; Atuahene, 2019; Kretschmann, 2015) and learners related factors (Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2015; Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2014) among others. When learners are unable to develop an appropriate structure of chemistry concepts, conceptual difficulties which ultimately results in poor academic performance arises. Given the pervasive influence of chemistry, understanding of its concepts is imperative to producing the critical mass of science teachers and scientists needed to drive sustainable national development goal.

Teachers, owing to their expertise and requisite classroom experience, can offer valuable insights into challenging specific concepts, their teaching difficulties, and the learning gaps observed among students (Nwagbo, *et al.*, 2021). Students equally, through their individual learning experiences, can pinpoint specific concepts they find difficult and the factors underpinning these difficulties (Afolabi, *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, understanding the perceptions of teachers and students regarding difficult chemistry concepts in this context is crucial for enhancing pedagogical practices and curriculum development. By exploring these perceptions, educators can gain valuable insights into the underlying factors influencing the teaching and learning of challenging chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program, a course which is central to science and science related fields.

Chemistry is a fundamental science subject crucial for various science fields. However, students often struggle with the subject, leading to poor performance. In Nigeria, the Chief Examiners report on the West African Senior School Certificate Examination have consistently highlighted that students struggle with some chemistry concepts (Obikezie, *et al.*, 2023; Anim-Eduful, & Adu-Gyamfi, 2022; Kenni, 2020; Amoke 2020). Consequently, research efforts had been devoted to perceived difficult chemistry concepts. Studies span across difficult primary science concepts (Edu, *et al.*, 2012), secondary school chemistry (Oladejo, *et al.*, 2023; Nwagbo, *et al.*, 2021; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021) and undergraduate chemistry (Stroumpouli & Tsaparlis 2022; Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022; Awaah, *et al.*, 2020; Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2015). But research on conceptual difficulties in Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) chemistry curriculum in general and the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in particular has not received attention as evidenced by the paucity or no literature on such study. This research intends to fill that gap. The NCE program is crucial to training teacher manpower for the basic level of education. This study which aims at assessing the chemistry concepts pre-service teachers (students) and in-service teachers (lecturers) in Colleges of Education within North West, Nigeria, consider challenging is apt as its findings are vital to improving chemistry education and preparing quality future teachers for effective service delivery.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this research are to:

1. Identify chemistry concepts teachers in Colleges of Education perceive to be difficult to teach in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program;

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2. Identify chemistry concepts students in Colleges of Education perceive to be difficult to learn in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program;
3. Identify factors responsible for the teachers perceived conceptual difficulty in chemistry concepts;
4. Identify factors responsible for the students perceived conceptual difficulty in chemistry;
5. Determine gender difference on the teachers and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program.

Research Questions

The questions posited to guide this study are:

4. Are there concepts teachers in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?
5. Are there concepts students in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?
6. What are the factors responsible for the teachers' perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts?
7. What are the factors responsible for the students' perceived conceptual difficulty?
8. Do gender difference affect the teachers' and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program in colleges of Education?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

1. HO₁: Teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult;
2. HO₂: Students in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult;
3. HO₃: Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of Education;
4. HO₄: Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education;
5. HO₅: Gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted to assess difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard among teachers and students in colleges of education in North West, Nigeria. The target population for this study was 82 (58 males and 24 females), the total number of chemistry teachers and 2071 (964 males and 1107 females) the total number of chemistry students in the Federal Colleges of Education in the North-West, Nigeria. There are a total of five Federal Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria (National Commission for Colleges of Education, 2021). They are: Federal College of Education (T), Bichi, Federal College of Education (T), Gusau, Federal College of Education, Kano, Federal College of Education Katsina and Federal College of Education, Zaria. These Colleges are categorized into two types: conventional and Technical. The Conventional Colleges are three while the Technical are two. The Colleges were purposively used for the study because they have same source of funding and extant administrative documents. The three conventional Colleges (Federal College of Education, Kano, Katsina and Zaria) were randomly sampled for the study. A total 68 chemistry teachers and 335 chemistry students constitute the sample size (Israel, 1992).

Two research questionnaires, Chemistry Teachers Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire (CTIDCQ) and Chemistry Students Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire (CSIDCQ) were designed by the researchers for the study. The questionnaires have three sections A, B and C. Section A deals with the biodata of the respondents. Section B, containing 20 five Likert scale rating items, deals with chemistry concepts perceived too difficult to teach or learn in the 2020 NCE Minimum standard. The Likert scale range from 1 to 5, very difficult (5), difficult (4), Undecided (3), Moderately Difficult (2) and not difficult (1). For section C equally containing 20 five-point Likert scale items deals reasons why teachers and students perceive the chemistry concepts in the 2020 NCE Minimum Standard Difficulty to teach or learn. The responses range from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), strongly disagree (1).

The decision rule for section B was 1-1.49 not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. While for section C, 1-1.49 strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly

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agree. Two experts, one in Science Education and the other Chemistry validated the instruments for the study and the suggestions/ observations raised were effected on the instrument appropriately. After pilot testing, Split-half method was used in order to determine the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach was used to determine the coefficient values of 0.71 for the teachers' instrument and 0.74 for the students' instrument; thus the instruments were adequate for the study. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0.

Results

Research Question 1

Are there concepts teachers in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?

Table 1: Summary of teachers in colleges of education response on chemistry concepts perceived difficult in 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Dual nature of matter	68	2.19	1.37	MD
2	Nature of Ionic Crystals	68	2.27	1.25	MD
3	Dipole Moment and Bond Character	68	2.25	1.36	MD
4	Redox Reaction (balancing of redox reaction/predicting products at electrode)	68	2.08	1.37	MD
5	Polarization and Quantum mechanics	68	2.19	1.22	MD
6	Quantum number and Quantum mechanics	68	2.85	1.47	D
7	Stoichiometry and the mole concept	68	2.12	1.29	MD
8	Isomerism	68	1.33	0.76	ND
9	Carbonyl Compounds (Reaction mechanisms in organic chemistry), qualitative organic analysis or Functional group detection	68	1.92	1.23	MD
10	IUPAC nomenclature of organic compounds	68	1.4	0.82	ND
11	Hybridization	68	1.9	1.07	MD
12	Symmetry and Chirality	68	2.38	1.21	MD
13	Chemical Kinetics (first order and second order reactions)	68	2.35	1.34	MD
14	Activated complex, intermediate and transition state	68	1.98	1.09	MD
15	Equilibrium and second law of thermodynamics	68	2.29	1.26	MD
16	Heat and Temperature	68	1.61	0.87	MD
17	Phase changes	68	1.85	1.07	MD
18	Colligative Properties	68	1.83	1.02	MD
19	Partial molar quantities	68	2.37	1.1	MD
20	Real and Ideal Solutions	68	1.9	1.16	MD
Cumulative mean & Standard deviation			2.05	1.17	MD

Data source: Field survey 2023

MD means moderately difficult and ND not difficult. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. From the cumulative mean value of 2.05 which is within the range 1.50 -2.49, the teachers overall perceived the concepts to be moderately difficult.

Research Question 2

Are there concepts students in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?

Table 2: Summary of students in colleges of education response on chemistry concepts perceived difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program

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S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Dual Nature of Matter	335	2.24	1.62	MD
2	Nature of Ionic Crystals	335	2.56	1.51	D
3	Dipole Moments and bond Character	335	2.83	1.47	D
4	Redox Reactions(balancing of redox reaction / predicting product at electrodes)	335	2.84	1.59	D
5	Polarization and Polarizability	335	2.95	1.45	D
6	Quantum numbers and Quantum Mechanics	335	2.81	1.58	D
7	Stoichiometry and the mole concept	335	3.02	1.39	D
8	Isomerism	335	2.32	1.54	MD
9	Carbonyl compounds (Reaction mechanisms in organic chemistry) qualitative organic analysis or functional group detection	335	2.77	1.59	D
10	IUPAC nomenclature of organic compounds	335	2.15	1.50	MD
11	Hybridization	335	2.47	1.51	MD
12	Symmetry and Chirality	335	3.23	1.37	D
13	Chemical Kinetics (first order and second order reactions)	335	2.65	1.64	D
14	Activated complex, intermediate and transition state	335	3.03	1.54	D
15	Equilibrium and second law of thermodynamics	335	2.91	1.61	D
16	Heat and Temperature	335	2.45	1.55	MD
17	Phase Changes	335	2.85	1.35	D
18	Colligative properties	335	3.01	1.35	D
19	Partial molar quantities	335	2.90	1.36	D
20	Real and Ideal Solutions	335	2.55	1.54	D
Cumulative mean & Standard deviation		2.73	1.50		D

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: MD means moderately difficult and D means difficult. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. From the cumulative of 2.73 which is within the range 2.50 -3.49, it implies the students generally perceived the chemistry concepts difficult to learn.

Research Question 3

What are the factors responsible for the teachers' perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts?

Table 3: Summary of teachers' response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of mentoring by seniour colleagues	68	3.17	1.46	A
2	Lack of Collaboration and team teaching	68	3.33	1.35	A
3	Lack of post lecture review by a team of lesson observers	68	3.50	1.35	SA
4	Chemistry is complex and the concepts abstract	68	3.10	1.33	A
5	Teaching Techniques not learner-centered	68	3.33	1.17	A
6	Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich teaching	68	3.02	1.21	A

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7	Difficulty in English, the medium of instruction/communication	68	2.87	1.22	A
8	Lack of numeracy skills	68	2.90	1.29	A
9	Overloaded course content	68	3.60	1.35	SA
10	Confusing Technical Terms	68	2.65	1.17	A
11	Lack of Scientific Reasoning skills	68	3.15	1.29	A
12	Lack of interest and motivation towards teaching chemistry	68	2.90	1.38	A
13	lack of exposure to scientific language	68	2.63	1.25	A
14	Weak background in requisite knowledge	68	3.33	1.35	A
15	Not integrating ICT in teaching	68	3.54	1.34	SA
16	Inadequate exposure of teachers to problem solving	68	3.35	1.12	A
17	Lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life application	68	3.71	1.36	SA
18	Unconducive learning environment	68	3.88	1.35	SA
19	Lack of mathematical reasoning skills	68	3.23	1.18	A
20	Lack of higher order cognitive skills (Synthesis, application, evaluation)	68	3.33	1.32	A
Cumulative mean & Standard Deviation			3.23	1.92	A

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: SA means strongly agree and A means agree. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly agree. From the cumulative mean of 3.23 which is within the range 2.50 -3.49, the teachers generally agreed that the itemized factors were responsible for the perceived moderate difficulty of the concepts to teach.

Research Question 4

What are the factors responsible for the students' perceived conceptual difficulty?

Table 4: Summary of students' response on factors responsible for perceived conceptual difficulty

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of mentoring by the lecturers	335	3.31	1.48	A
2	Lack of Collaboration and team learning	335	3.51	1.35	SA
3	No feedback from peers	335	3.27	1.37	A
4	Chemistry is complex and the concepts are abstract	335	3.38	1.39	A
5	Poor teaching techniques	335	3.06	1.50	A
6	Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich learning	335	3.51	1.36	SA
7	Difficulty in English, the medium of instruction/communication	335	3.31	1.41	A
8	Lack of numeracy skills	335	3.48	1.28	A
9	Overloaded course content	335	3.72	1.38	SA
10	Confusing technical terms	335	3.46	1.29	A
11	Students lack of scientific/critical reasoning skills	335	3.47	1.31	A
12	Lack of interest and motivation of students towards chemistry	335	3.34	1.42	A
13	Lack of exposure to scientific language	335	3.43	1.40	A
14	Students weak background in requisite knowledge	335	3.61	1.30	SA
15	Teachers teaching strategy does not integrate ICT	335	3.06	1.41	A
16	Inadequate exposure of students to problem solving	335	3.36	1.33	A

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17	Lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life situation	335	3.44	1.33	A
18	Unconducive learning environment	335	3.22	1.37	A
19	Lack of mathematical reasoning skills	335	3.37	1.33	A
20	Students are generally in low order Bloom taxonomy cognitive skills	335	3.26	1.42	A
Cumulative mean & Standard deviation			3.38	1.37	A

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: SA means strongly agree and A means agree. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly agree. From the cumulative mean 3.38 within is within the range 2.50 -3.49 the students equally agreed that the itemized factors were responsible for the perceived difficulty to learning the chemistry concepts.

Research Question 5

Do gender difference affect the teachers' and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program in colleges of Education?

Table 5: Summary of mean score of male and female teachers and students perception of difficult chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean difference	decision
Male	204	2.73	1.48	0.01	difference does not exist
Female	199	2.72	1.52		

Data source: Field survey 2023

The mean of the males' perception of difficult chemistry concept is 2.73 while that of the females is 2.72. The difference in their means is 0.01 implying that difference does not exist in their perception of difficult chemistry concepts.

Hypothesis 1

Teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult

Table 6: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of perception of teachers' response on difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5.503	2	2.751	1.845	.159
Within Groups	1546.588	1037	1.491		
Total	1552.091	1039			

Data source: Field survey 2023

$F(2, 1037) = 1.845$; $p > 0.05$. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult is retained.

Hypothesis 2

Students do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult in colleges of Education

Table 7: Summary of One-Way Analysis of Variance of Students response on Perception of difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p (Sig level)
Between Groups	62.114	2	31.057	13.321	.000
Within Groups	14445.230	6196	2.331		
Total	14507.344	6198			

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Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 6196) = 13.321; $p < 0.05$. The $p < 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis students in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of education.

Table 8: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of teachers response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in Chemistry concepts among teachers in Colleges of Education

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p (Sig level)
Between Groups	10.118	2	5.059	2.896	.056
Within Groups	1811.781	1037	1.747		
Total	1821.899	1039			

Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 1037) = 2.896; $p > 0.05$. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of education is not rejected.

Hypothesis 4

Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education

Table 9: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of Students response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in Chemistry concepts among students in colleges of Education

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p(Sig level)
Between Groups	22.427	2	11.213	5.905	.003
Within Groups	11768.901	6197	1.899		
Total	11791.328	6199			

Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 6197) = 5.905; $p < 0.05$. The $p < 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education is rejected.

Hypothesis 5

Gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education

Table 10: Summary of t-test score of the Male and Female Teachers and Students on their perception of difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p (sig level)	decision
Male	204	2.73	1.48	401	0.04	0.404	not significant
Female	199	2.72	1.52				

Data source: Field survey 2023

[t(401) = 0.04; $p > 0.05$]. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis, gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result in table 1 showed that the teachers generally perceived the chemistry concepts to be moderately difficult. This finding aligns with that of Cleopas, *et al.*, (2023), Akaygum & Arkun (2022) & He, *et al.*, (2021). Only one concept quantum numbers and quantum mechanics (mean value = 2.85) was considered difficult to teach by the teachers. None of the

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concepts was perceived to be very difficult and the one-way analysis of variance of teachers' response on perception of difficult chemistry concepts, $F(2,1037) = 1.845$; $p > 0.05$ (Table 6) showed statistically significance difference does not exist in the teachers response. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the teachers' perception of difficult concepts is therefore not rejected. Researchers have ascribed the outcome of teachers' perception of difficult concepts to qualification (Kyado, *et al.*, 2021) and teachers' disposition (Nartey & Hanson, 2021). The students' responses (as shown in Table 2) indicated that they found the concepts to be challenging. The one-way analysis of variance on students' perceptions of difficult chemistry concepts (Table 7) revealed a significant difference, $F(2,6196) = 13.32$; $p < 0.05$, indicating variations in the students' perceptions. This finding is supported by Longyil & Agbo (2020), Awaah, *et al.*, (2020), Jack *et al* (2017) and Agogo & Onda (2014). It is intriguing that while the teachers generally did not perceive the concepts difficult to teach, the students perceived them difficult to learn. This finding is not unusual (Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2014). The students' response could be indicative of pedagogical issues on the part of the teachers (Adum-Gyamfi & Asaki, 2023; Essiam, *et al.*, 2023)) or students related factors (Nkiko, 2021; Montenegro & Cascolan, 2020; & Moyo, 2018). On critical analysis of the students' responses, the students perceived the concept of quantum number and quantum mechanics which were general and introductory physical chemistry difficult to learn. The teachers equally found them difficult to teach. These concepts poses challenge to other students (Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022).

On factors responsible for the perceived chemistry concepts difficulty, the cumulative mean of 3.23 (Table 3) shows that the teachers generally agree that the 20 items are factors responsible for their perception of chemistry concepts difficulty. However, five factors each having a mean score of 3.50 and above were strongly agreed by the teachers as responsible factors. The five factors are; lack of post lecture review by team of lesson observers (mean 3.50), Overloaded course content (mean 3.60), not integrating ICT in teaching (mean 3.54), lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life application (mean 3.71) and unconducive learning environment (mean 3.88). The result from table 6, $F(2,1037) = 2.896$; $p > 0.05$, shows that no significant relationship exists in the teachers' perception of factors responsible for the difficult concepts. Onu, *et al.*, (2022) had reported that integration of ICT in teaching was yet to be popular amongst teachers in Colleges of Education in the North West, Zone of Nigeria. Not integrating ICT in teaching (mean 3.54) by the teachers seems to be an issue of concern (Kinyanjui, 2019; Atuahene, 2019; Kretschmann, 2015). Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki (2023) in their work on factors contributing to teachers' conceptual difficulties in teaching high school organic chemistry identified four factors; tertiary exposure, professional collaboration, professional competence, and pre-tertiary exposure. Tertiary exposure is about the experiences and knowledge an individual teacher had from his or her university education.

Professional collaboration explains how the teachers develop their knowledge in both content and pedagogy through their continual engagement and participation in professional group, sharing experiences and knowledge. Lecture observation by lesson observers with the aim of having post lesson reviews is an integral part of the professional collaboration. So the finding from this study in an aspect is in agreement with that of Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki (2023) and also in line with Garcia and Weiss (2019) who claimed that teachers have limited access to some of the types of professional development that are highly valued and more effective.

The students on their part agreed that the 20 items (Table 4) were factors responsible for their perception of difficult concepts. They equally strongly agreed that four factors stood out: Lack of collaboration and team learning (mean 3.51), Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich learning (mean 3.51), Overloaded course content (mean 3.72) and Students weak background in requisite knowledge (mean 3.61). Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, (2015) underscored weak mathematical background as factor affecting students' conceptual progress in thermodynamics. Though the teachers and students differed on the factors they strongly agreed were responsible for their perception of difficulty they however converged on the factors of overloaded curriculum and lack of collaboration and team work. This result agreed with that of Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, (2014). While the no significant difference existed in the teachers' perception of factors responsible for the perceived concept difficulty (Table 9) $F(2,1037) = 2.896$; $p > 0.05$; the students result (table 9), $F(2, 6196) = 13.321$; $p < 0.05$ showed otherwise.

The result from table 5, shows no difference existed in favour of any gender in the gender perception of concept difficulty among teachers and students. The $p > 0.05$ (Table 10) implies that the hypothesis "Gender has no significant difference on the teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program" is accepted. The finding agrees with Oladejo, *et al.*, (2023), Nitereka, *et al.*, (2022), Saadon & Abbood (2022) and Otor & Achor (2013) where weak relationship or no relationship was established between gender and concept difficulty.

Conclusion

Assessment of difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 minimum standard among teachers and students in colleges of education in North West, Nigeria was studied. This study offers valuable insights into how the teachers and students in Colleges of Education in the North West perceived 20-item chemistry concepts drawn from the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult. Generally, the teachers perceived the 20-item chemistry concepts moderately difficult. They equally strongly agreed that five factors accounted for their perceived difficulty. The students on their part perceived the 20-item concepts difficult to learn. On critical analysis of the students' responses, the concepts of quantum number and quantum mechanics were perceived difficult to learn while the teachers equally found them difficult to teach. Both the teachers and students converged on overloaded curriculum and lack of collaboration and team work as factors accounting for their perceived difficulty. As regards gender effect, non-statistically significant difference existed on the teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard.

The findings underscored the need for targeted interventions, pedagogical strategies, adequate continuing professional development opportunities and training, to address the identified difficulties effectively as well as to enhance teachers' subject knowledge and teaching skills. Furthermore, the study revealed the significance of context-specific teaching approaches tailored to the needs and learning styles of students in colleges of Education in the North West.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. **Continuing Professional Development:** Targeted training and professional development opportunities for chemistry teachers to enhance their subject knowledge and teaching skills should be provided in our Colleges. Workshops, seminars, and refresher courses focusing on effective instructional strategies for difficult concepts should be organized on regular basis by the Colleges and or relevant professional bodies and teachers should be supported to attend.
2. **Minimum Standard review and Teachers Guide:** The periodic review of the Minimum Standard should take cognizance of research findings to ensure alignment with the learning needs and contexts of students in the North West region. The teachers' guide should incorporate relevant local examples, contextualize concepts, and simplify complex topics to facilitate better teaching and students understanding.
3. **Pedagogical Support:** Pedagogical support to teachers through the provision of teaching resources, lesson plans, lesson observation as enshrined in the accreditation toolkits should be well monitored by the Quality Assurance Directorate of the Colleges. Also instructional materials specifically designed to address difficult chemistry concepts, use of multimedia, hands-on activities, and real-life applications to make learning more engaging, accessible and students –centred should be entrenched in the Colleges.
4. **Digital Chemistry Contents.** Teachers should develop online digital chemistry contents with local examples. It is hoped that the students will relate better with such online digital contents than those developed by teachers from other climes.
5. **Assessment Practices:** In assessing learning achievement, it should be ensured that the assessment practices align with the learning objectives and difficulty levels of chemistry concepts outlined in the Minimum Standard. Furthermore, a variety of assessment methods, including formative assessments, quizzes, and practical demonstrations should be adopted to accurately gauge student understanding and progress.
6. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** The Directorate of Quality Assurance which among others has the role of monitoring curriculum implementation should monitor and evaluate teaching and learning processes to identify areas for improvement and measure the effectiveness of implemented interventions.

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Assessment of Digital Literacy and use of Scripted Lesson Plan among Secondary School Teachers in Benin Metropolis, Edo State

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Abstract

The study examined digital literacy and teachers' readiness to employ scripted lesson plans among Secondary Schools in Benin, Edo State. With the availability of a myriad of digital platforms for teachers, traditional techniques of instructing learners still pervade, even when it has become deficient. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population includes all secondary school teachers in public secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Benin Metropolis, Edo State. Sample size of four hundred and fifteen (415) teachers were drawn from the population using proportionate and stratified sampling Technique. A systematic questionnaire (Google form) prepared by the researchers was used to collect data. Two specialists validated the instrument. The reliability coefficients for digital literacy and scripted lessons were 0.786 and 0.813, respectively, using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test indicating the instrument were reliable. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and independent sample t-test statistic were used to examine the data generated. Under the 0.05 threshold of significance, ANOVA was employed to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that there is a favorable and significant association between digital literacy and scripted lessons. The findings further revealed no statistically significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence and preparedness for scripted lessons among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, age and experience. It recommended that government should broaden and deepen its digital literacy training and workshops for in-service teachers through continuous teacher professional development programs.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Teachers' Preparedness, Scripted Lesson.

Introduction

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in education is crucial in this age of technological innovation and expansion. As a result of technological innovation and expansion, teachers' perceptions of teaching and learning, as well as how they apply the curriculum in classrooms, have changed (Radhakrishnan, DeBoer, & Kimani, 2018). Technology appears to be the answer to more comprehensive and simple teaching and learning. During the 2019-2020 global lockdown induced by the infamous Covid 19, teaching and learning were possible, particularly in difficult regions. To support and facilitate teaching and learning, computers, mobile phones, Skype, teacher tube, Zoom, Google meet, school tube, web windows, video, PowerPoint, and other technologies were used (Duru, Eber, and Okezie 2022). These E-teaching and Learning systems enable the transmission of instruction and interaction between students and teachers via the Internet (Bubou, Offor, & Job 2021).

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) may have effect on the learning of students if teachers are able to demonstrate digital literacy and comprehend how to blend technology into the curriculum for teaching and learning. In order to communicate, generate, transmit, save, and manage information, schools make use of a wide variety of information and communication technologies (ICT), (Blurton, as cited in Zyad, 2016). In certain contexts, information and communication technology has also become an essential component of the teaching-learning interaction, which includes the substitution of chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, the use of smart phones and tablets by teachers, and the use of students' own smartphones or other devices for learning during class time. Additionally, techniques such as scripted teaching or scripted lesson and flipped classrooms have also become commonplace. As part of incorporating technology into education, scripted

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teaching which refers to an organized teaching and learning process with time allotments for teaching and frequently word-for-word scripts of what the teacher is to teach is advocated.

Also, commercial reading programmes with highly organized lessons, frequently with set time allotments for teaching certain abilities, and often with scripts of the teacher's every word is known as scripted teaching or scripted instruction (Lipson et al., in Mwandia & Mwanza, 2022). Curriculum materials that are scripted are those that have been prepared by professionals and teachers use them to deliver lessons, as it evolved out of an effort to give educators a standard by which to organize and coordinate their work (Doyle, in Mkandawire, 2022). The language, strategies, and attitudes that make up such a curriculum are essentially instructional scripts that teachers follow. In schools where teachers have not had extensive training, scripted education has been suggested time and time again as a way to standardize the level of instruction (Haruna, 2019). The components of a well-planned lesson include goals for student learning, units or lessons to cover, activities to provide, readings, materials, and methods for evaluating their progress. Opponents of such plans argue that they do not meet the diverse needs of classrooms and that they stifle professional development for educators (Mkandawire, 2022). On the other hand, proponents argue that it is the most straightforward way for educators to impart critical reading skills to their students.

According to Comeyras (quoted in Mkandawire, 2022), scripted instruction has its roots in the 1888 teacher's manual by Samuel and Adeline Monroe, which included reading readiness, phonics, and oral reading scripts. The instructor is expected to adhere strictly to the lesson plans in this style of teaching. The goal of this form of direct instruction is to help educators be more consistent in their lessons. Additionally, it aims at lessening the likelihood of incompetent educators providing inadequate lessons. It is designed to help schools with low standardized test scores by strictly following the script, hence, ensures that students grasp the material better and that lessons are presented consistently. A common argument against scripted instruction is the belief that anybody can conduct a class as long as they stick to the outline (Commeyras, in Mkandawire 2022). In contrast, some who advocate for scripted instruction submit that, similar to how an actor gives life to a screenplay, a teacher has the power and responsibility to infuse their lessons with authentic content (Commeyras, in Mkandawire, 2022). According to Kohl (quoted in Mwandia and Mwanza, 2021), scripted classes reduce teachers to delivery systems, which in turn lowers instructors' self-esteem and pride in their work because students view them as inanimate objects devoid of critical thinking skills and educational expertise. There is, however, some literature that support planned lesson/teaching. With test results continuing to plummet and many schools failing to fulfill requirements, many school administrators have turned to scripted curriculum/lesson/teaching to suit regulators/administrators' aims.

Advocates of scripted curriculum claim that employing a scientifically based curriculum will increase student success and enhance standardized test scores. The cornerstone of scripted lessons, according to Gunter and Reed (in Kang 2016), is built on the model, prompt, and check steps to assure subject learning. Scripted curriculum, according to Hiralall and Martens (in Hos et al 2020), may help eliminate disparity in the classroom. Teachers who are unsure about what, when, or how to teach can also benefit from scripted and limited curricula. The author claims that this type of curriculum guarantees that all students, irrespective of their location, the expertise of their teachers, or any other factor, are exposed to the same educational material. Also, according to Walsh in Kang (2016), scripted curriculum advocates believe that teacher-led training is more efficient and predictable when the teacher's statements and the child's expected replies are written. Watkins and Slocum (quoted in Kang, 2016) argue that scripted curricula do two things: first, it guarantees well-designed instruction; and second, it relieves the teacher of the responsibility of creating, evaluating, and improving education for each topic.

According to this author (Kang 2016), scripted programmes offer regular, predictable, organized, and systematic learning environments that can be supervised and trained to assure standardized instruction. Teachers should concentrate on the critical task of providing instruction and overcoming unforeseen circumstances, they stated, and thorough scripts are instruments that help them connect with pupils through the language in the scripts. It is pertinent to state that schools and classrooms employ scripted lesson plans to make up for shortcomings and ensure consistency in subject terminology, since they are designed to incorporate best practices. Scripted programmes, as stated by Boyer (in Kang, 2016), positively affect teaching practices.

Scripted lessons are meant to provide a clear, uniform, and thorough way of teaching that specifies what the instructor will teach, when it will be taught, and how it will be taught (Mwandia & Mwanza, 2022). Some teachers, however, deviate from the pattern that has been supplied to them. In scripted instruction, teachers are given all of the teaching tools, including physical objects, processes, tasks, and concepts. As a result, they lose their independence in the classroom. The lessons serve as a guide for teachers as they go through the process of implementing scripted lessons. It is challenging for educators who are not adept in digital technology to utilize this planned lesson. Students are better prepared to deal with ongoing technological change in society and the workplace when teachers are digitally literate and incorporate technology into their teaching

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(Goodwin, in Eikeland, 2016). The result totally may include that students can develop higher order thinking skills, have more creative and individualized ways to express their understandings, and have more opportunities to express their understandings.

There are teaching technologies as well as learning technologies. Teachers, students, and school administrators are the three key groups who profit the most from technology integration in education. Others include education ministries, future researchers, the corporate sector, and people of society who are less affluent and vulnerable (Keri et al, 2021). However, technology integration in Nigeria, particularly in Benin, has several hurdles. low internet services, low electricity supply, bad economy and its effects, high cost of ICT facilities, scarcity of ICT professionals, unwillingness of instructors, particularly older ones, to change, a lack of maintenance culture, and inadequate locally generated software among other issues. These obstacles make it difficult for teachers to be equipped to apply digital literacy and scripted teaching. These challenges, however, are not enough to discourage determined teachers and government officials who want technological integration in the teaching and learning processes in order to join the digital trend or be digital compliant, necessitating the need to assess teachers' digital literacy and scripted lesson readiness / preparedness in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.

Teachers are under increasing pressure to demonstrate digital competence in response to rising student expectations in the area of technology revolution in education, (Amhag, Hellström, & Stigmar, 2019). Governments worldwide have responded to these insights by launching campaigns and programmes aimed at enhancing educators' digital literacy. For instance, DigCompEdu, the European Framework for Educators' Digital Competence, was developed by the European Union (EU). According to Caena and Redecker (2019), DigCompEdu is a scientific tool that explains how instructors may be digitally proficient from a scientific perspective. Numerous contexts around the world have utilised the DigCompEdu to construct and evaluate digital capabilities (Caena and Redecker, 2019).

Leaving no one behind is the guiding philosophy of the SDGs, or Sustainable Development Goals. Opportunities for lifelong learning and equitable access to high-quality education are emphasised in the fourth Sustainable Development Goal on Quality Education. Teachers must be well-equipped to handle digital content in the classroom in order to keep up with the digital teaching and learning revolution. Students benefit greatly from the utilisation of ICT in the classroom because it enhances their capacity for collaborative learning and fosters the development of transversal skills. These skills are essential for success in the modern world and include, but are not limited to, the following: social awareness, problem solving, independence, responsibility, reflection, and initiative. If educators want to effectively incorporate ICT into their practice in order to navigate the digital age, they must have advanced degrees in teacher preparation. Some Nigerian schools have begun to include ICT into their curricula as a means of making students more tech-savvy, which is crucial for producing critical thinkers who can help their country compete in the global economy. It is necessary to evaluate the level of digital literacy among Edo state teachers as well as their preparedness for digital lessons in secondary schools in the Benin metropolitan area. This is because Edo state is rapidly becoming an e-governance and other e-complaints leader in Nigeria.

The era of digitalization in all spheres of human endeavours has come to stay. The educational system, particularly, teaching and learning have also been overtaken by this pervasive technological adoption. The successes accruable by the inclusion of these digital devices in educational system have been monumental. But the same success has not been gained in the outcome of students' academic performances in Benin. Hence, implementing digital-based instruction at the secondary school level is critical and this has motivated the government of Edo State to introduce scripted lessons for the entire teachers to be on the same page of lesson preparedness. Unfortunately, majority of these teachers are not literate in the use of Computers and may not have been subjected to in-service training to help them adjust to the modern devices. It is on this premise therefore that the researchers seek to investigate the digital literacy level of teachers and their preparedness of the use of scripted lessons in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis, Edo state where the government is digitally committed.

Objectives of the study:

1. To evaluate the level of digital literacy skills and teachers' preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.
2. To examine if there is difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

Research Questions:

1. What is the level of digital literacy skill and teachers' preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis?
2. What is the difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience?

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Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between digital literacy skill and scripted Lesson usage in teaching and learning process among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis
2. There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The Population includes all secondary school teachers in public secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Benin Metropolis, Edo State. Sample size of four hundred and fifteen (415) teachers were drawn from the population using proportionate and stratified sampling Technique. A systematic questionnaire (Google form) prepared by the researchers was used to collect data. Two specialists validated the instrument. The reliability coefficients for digital literacy and scripted lessons were 0.786 and 0.813, respectively, using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test indicating the instrument were reliable. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and independent sample t-test statistic were used to examine the data generated. Under the 0.05 threshold of significance, ANOVA was employed to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of digital literacy skill and teachers’ preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis?

Table 1: Description of the level of digital literacy skill of teachers in secondary schools in Benin metropolis

Variable	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Scale mean	Decision
Teachers’ assessment						
Of their level of digital						
Literacy skill	415	17558	39.55	9.60	50.00	low

Scale mean = ((4+3+2+1)/4) *20 =50

Table 1. Showed that of the 415 respondents, a mean value of 39.55, standard deviation of 9.60 and a scale mean of 50.00 were obtained. From the result, the mean value is less than the scale means and this indicate that the level of digital literacy skill of teachers in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.

Table 2. Description of the level of preparedness to use of scripted lesson in secondary schools in Benin metropolis

Variable	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Scale mean	Decision
Teachers’ assessment						
of their level of preparedness						
to use scripted lessons.	415	11399	25.67	4.14	32.5	low

Scale mean = ((4+3+2+1)/4) *13 =25.67

Table 2. showed that of the 415 respondents, a mean value of 25.67, standard deviation of 4.14 and a scale mean of 32.5 were obtained. From the result, the mean value is less than the scale means and this indicates that the level of preparedness to use of scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between Digital Literacy skill and scripted lesson usage in teaching learning process of secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis.

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Table 3: Correlation results of the relationship between Digital Literacy skill and scripted lesson usage

	Digital literacy	Scripted lesson
Pearson Correlation	1	.748**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	415	415

The result of table 3. reveals that there is a strong positive and significant relation between digital literacy skill and scripted lesson readiness. A breakdown down of the result reveals that the p-value is 0.00 and the correlation coefficient is 0.748 (74.8%). This means that the higher the digital literacy skill, the higher the readiness for scripted lesson

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

Table 4. Independent Sample t- test of Difference between Male and Female teachers in the level of digital literacy skill.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-Cal	p-value
Male teachers	113	1.88	0.33	413	0.46	.114
Female Teachers	302	2.00	0.52			

* *Significant at P < 0.05*

The t-value in Table 4.5 was 0.46, and the p-value was 0.114. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p > 0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. Based on this, the null hypothesis was retained, stating that there is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, while the alternative hypothesis, stating that there is a significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, was rejected. This means that there is no substantial variation in digital literacy skill levels among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.

Table 5. ANOVA test statistic of Difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teaching experience.

ANOVA						
Teachers' Experience	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	1.232	3	.411	1.793	.148	
Within Groups	100.744	411	.229			
Total	101.975	414				

The f-value in Table 4.6 was 1.793, and the p-value was 0.148. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p > 0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teachers' experience, was retained as a result of this. This means that there is no statistically significant variation in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teaching experience.

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Table 6. ANOVA test statistic of Difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teachers' age

Teachers' Age	ANOVA				
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.028	3	.676	0.976	.081
Within Groups	99.947	411	.227		
Total	101.975	414			

The f-value in Table 6. was 2.976, and the p-value was 0.081. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p > 0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teachers' age, was retained. This means that there is no statistically significant variation in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teachers' age.

Discussion of Findings:

The findings of this study shows that teachers in public secondary schools in Benin metropolitan have inadequate digital literacy abilities and are ill-prepared to employ scripted lessons. Also, it shows that there is a strong positive and significant relationship among digital literacy competency and scripted lesson. There is no significant difference in digital literacy skills among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender. It was also discovered that there is no significant difference in teacher readiness to employ scripted lessons based on gender.

The findings show that public secondary school teachers in Benin City lack digital literacy abilities and are unprepared to adopt scripted teachings. This study contradicts the findings of Kumari and D'Souza (2016), who investigated the usage of ICT in secondary school as well as teachers' digital literacy in India. They discovered that secondary school teachers' ICT use and digital literacy levels were average, however the current study indicated that teachers' digital literacy is low. Furthermore, the findings of Imhanyehor (2021), who investigated the viability of implementing digital literacy in primary schools and determined the availability and accessibility of electronic devices, as well as the barriers to its implementation in private primary schools in Benin City, contradict the findings of this study. According to the study's findings, 90.2% of teachers owned personal computers (PCs) and other electronic devices and were reasonably skilled in their use. This study, however, is consistent with that of Osaat and Nsereka (2012), who used the National Open University of Nigeria as a case study to investigate the effects of ICT on distant learning. They discovered that NOUN had not fully utilised ICT media, indicating that its faculty members were not technologically savvy.

Conversely, this study contradicts the findings of Arnold and Subaveerapandi's (2023) study on the use and purposes of ICT in the classroom, which looked into teachers' digital literacy abilities. Teachers in Zambia have access to digital devices and range in their degree of digital literacy from moderate to high, according to data collected from 20 schools in Lusaka. This study, however, is consistent with Omboto's (2022) investigation into the preparedness of teachers in Nairobi County, Kenya's public primary special schools to implement a digital literacy program. Omboto's study revealed that teachers in Nairobi County's public primary special schools and units were not sufficiently trained to carry out the digital literacy program (DLP) as intended. In contrast, Imhanyehor (2021) conducted research on digital literacy and the Nigerian primary school system and discovered that 90.2% of teachers had PCs and other electronic devices and were reasonably adept in using them. This study does not support his findings. Furthermore, this study contradicts the findings of Cote and Milliner (2017), a Japanese university report that surveyed digital literacy among EFL teachers and discovered that the majority of them felt highly comfortable using digital technology to enhance their instruction both within and outside of the classroom. This also holds true for Kumari and D'Souza (2016), who examined the use of ICT in teaching and learning by secondary school teachers in India and found that these aspects of the teachers' profession were mediocre.

Also, the findings show a substantial positive and significant relationship between digital literacy competency and scripted lesson preparedness. This indicates that digital literacy is a prerequisite or presupposes a planned course. Again, findings indicate no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence and preparedness for scripted lessons among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on gender, age, or experience in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis. The findings on teacher age are consistent with those of Keri, et al (2021), who investigated how age affected higher education instructors' use of ICT and discovered that age had no bearing on how teachers used ICT in the classroom.

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Similarly, Hassan and Abdullah (2013) discovered no statistically significant variations in ICT use between the two teacher groups based on age and experience in their study on the impact of teacher age, experience, and gender on ICT integration in language instruction. This result is consistent with their findings. Additionally, the outcome is consistent with Jegede's (2009) investigation of the ICT attitudes, competency, and use patterns of teacher educators, who discovered that age had no bearing on the amount of time Nigerian higher education instructors spend using ICT.

Regarding teacher experience, the results are inconsistent with those of Ohadiugha (2022), who examined the influence of gender and experience on the ICT skills of senior secondary education teachers, concentrating on ICT skills that facilitate the successful implementation of senior secondary school curricula. Ohadiugha's research revealed that experience plays a major role in the degree of ICT proficiency among teachers. The results of this study, however, are consistent with those of Ibrahim (2016), who examined factors such as gender, years of teaching experience, and educational background as potential indicators of secondary school teachers' proficiency in utilizing ICT in the classroom in Nigeria's Jigawa and Kano states. Ibrahim (2016) discovered that years of teaching experience had no discernible impact on teachers' proficiency in utilizing ICT in the classroom. Similarly, Hassan and Abdullah (2013) looked at how gender, age, and experience of teachers affected the use of ICT in language instruction and discovered no appreciable differences in ICT use between the two groups of instructors according to experience.

Regarding teacher sex and gender, the results of this study are consistent with those of Edeh, et al (2022), who examined gender disparities in teachers' digital literacy in the context of supporting students with functional diversity and found that gender has no appreciable bearing on teachers' abilities in this area. Similarly, the results are consistent with Ohadiugha's (2022) study, which examined the influence of experience and gender on the ICT proficiency of senior secondary education teachers. The study focused on ICT competencies that facilitate the successful implementation of senior secondary school curricula. The results indicated that experience plays a major role in teachers' ICT proficiency, while gender did not. Similarly, Guillén-Gámez, et al (2021) examined the gender gap in higher education teachers' digital competency in research work using a descriptive and comparative analysis, concluding that there were no appreciable differences in teaching staff members' levels of digital competence according to gender.

Additionally, the results of this study are consistent with those of Saibu, et al (2018), who investigated gender disparity and teachers' ICT literacy as predictors of chemistry students' academic performance in Lagos State, Nigeria, and found no relationship between teachers' gender and ICT literacy. The same is true for Ibrahim (2016), who examined years of teaching experience, gender, and educational background as predictors of secondary school teachers' proficiency with ICT in the classroom in the Nigerian states of Jigawa and Kano. The research findings indicate that gender has no bearing on proficiency with ICT. The same is true for Adnan, et al (2013), who looked into how age and gender related to the use of ICT in Pakistani educational institutions and found no relationship between a teacher's gender category and the amount of time they spend on computers each day. The results of this study, however, do not agree with those of Hassan and Abdullah (2013), who examined the impact of gender, age, and experience on ICT integration in language instruction and found that male and female teachers used ICT differently.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, instructors at public secondary schools in Benin metropolitan have a poor level of digital literacy and are less prepared for scripted lessons. In Benin, it was also discovered that there is a favourable and significant association between digital literacy and scripted lessons. As a result, teachers in secondary schools in Benin metropolitan should be equipped with adequate digital literacy skills in order to effectively and efficiently be prepared or ready for scripted lesson and function effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. In order to raise the level of digital literacy skills among teachers in Benin City, the current government, which has done a fantastic job of revolutionizing the education sector by introducing technology into teaching and learning, should expand and deepen the workshops and trainings for digital literacy for in-service teachers through ongoing professional development trainings.
2. To close the gap, the government should investigate the reasons behind the low level of digital literacy and scripted lesson preparation among public secondary school teachers in Benin City.

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3. Given the current high cost of living in the state and the country as a whole, the government should subsidize data for the teachers to lessen the financial strain and additional cost required to download scripted lessons from the server.
4. All secondary schools in Benin City and the surrounding areas should be able to access the free Wi-Fi that is already available in select areas of the state.
5. The government should help secondary school teachers to acquire less expensive android phones to enable the teachers be integrated into digital literacy and scripted lesson.
6. In order to keep up with current trends, expectations, and international best practices, the Edo State College of Education and other postsecondary educational institutions in the state tasked with training pre-service teachers ought to modernize their curricula and programs. In particular, they ought to focus on equipping teachers with the skills necessary to teach on any e-platform.
7. Due to the 21st century work place skills and expectations, a level of digital literacy competence should be a prerequisite for teacher recruitment into the public service.
8. Same study should be extended to other locality within Edo state also.
9. Lastly, government of the day should gazette his education reform tagged EdoBEST 2.0 to avoid being abandoned by any subsequent government for continuity and sustainability.

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Assessment of Factors Influencing Career Choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Assessment of factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja local government area of Kogi. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 7225(4648 males and 2545 female) senior secondary school students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Lokoja local government area of Kogi State. 500 (297 male and 203 female) constitute the sample size of the study selected using multistage sampling techniques. A research instrument titled “Influences on Career Choice Questionnaire (ICCQ)” was used for data collection. to ensure the validity of the instrument, face and content was ensured by expert while the reliability of the instrument was done using split-half formula with a reliability coefficient of 0.7. One research question and two research hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The data collected were analyzed using frequency count, mean, percentage and standard deviation to answer the research question and t-test analysis for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that peers, family, school, gender and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The study concluded that peers and family are the major factors that can influence the career choice of secondary school students. The study recommends that there is a need to review the career guidance curriculum to consider factors that influence students’ choices of careers.

Keyword: career choice, peers, family and secondary school.

Introduction

With a population of over 200 million, Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa. However, choosing appropriate career paths for its fast-expanding population presents serious challenges (Adeyanju, Mogaji, Olusola, & Oyinlola, 2020). An individual need to be aware of his talents and shortcomings in order to have a sensible and practical career. Comprehending them will enable him to accomplish his objective. His inspiration will come from his goal (Korkmaz & Kirdok, 2020). Making a career choice is a crucial decision that students make as they advance through secondary school. While some students from enriched environments begin this decision-making process early, for other students who struggled to come to grips with who they were and what they wanted to become in the future, the process begins much later. Adolescents' professional decisions are, of course, based on the knowledge at their disposal. In fact, a variety of internal and external factors may interact to influence students’ career selections in a timely or inefficient manner (Haruna, 2016).

Owusu, Owusu, Fiorgbor, and Kumah, (2020), claimed that Career refers to a person’s professional course or an occupation which he/she has to follow over a number of years, affording him/her the opportunity for progress as well as serving as his principal means of earning a living and in which he/she is generally recognised to have become fairly an expert in, through experience. Career is a life time pursuit for success Eremie & Okwulehie (2019). According to Oduh, Agbola and Eibhalemen (2020), “Making a decision concerning the selection of suitable career or occupation is one significant problem facing senior secondary school students and young adolescents in general. This may be due to lack of information, understanding, orientation, awareness, training and opportunities about activities in different careers or vocations”. This brings up the topic of choosing a career. The process by which a person decides, at a given moment, to pursue a particular profession or vocation after carefully weighing all of his options is referred to as career choice.

Choosing a career is one of the most important and challenging decisions a person will ever have to make because it is a developmental process that affects a person for the majority of their life. This decision should be made after considering the ramifications or requirements of entering the field of career. This is why a student needs to be systematically furnished with relevant career information to enable him/her make a realistic career decision (Ahmad, et. al., 2019). The complexities noted above about career choice have compelled many young people to seek assistance from members of the age group in an attempt to resolve the seeming impasse. This refers to the influence a peer group exerts on an individual that encourages the individual

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to change his or her attitude, values or behaviour to conform to such a group (Kirk in Oduh, Agbola & Eibhalemen2020). Also, apart from the influence exerted by parents, some students may want to identify with their friends in the class. Hence, they choose subject combinations which would lead to certain careers simply because a friend belongs to that particular group.

Obot, amalu, apebende and ogodo (2020) found out in their study of Peer group and career aspiration of secondary school students in Northern Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria that, peer group significantly influences students' career aspiration. A further consideration of their results show that, for all careers, average level of peer influence, has more students, followed by low level with the lowest number of the students falling under high influence. Also, the study conducted by Nwoka, Okafor, & Nnubia (2022) revealed that parental values and family background influence students' career choice to a great extent.

owusu, owusu, fiorgbor and atakora (2021) in their research on Career Aspiration of Students: The Influence of Peers, Teachers and Parents found out that what they want to be in future is influenced by their friends, their choices of courses are influenced by their friends and that the manner in which they learn is as a result of how their friends learned. This simply implied that overall the respondents agreed to most of the statements showing that peers had a great influence on the career aspirations of students. The study also revealed that parents had interest in the careers of their children and that their children do not take career decisions without their approval.

Yunusa, Jaafar, Ismail and Othman (2022), in their research on A Study on the Relationship between Family Peer Group Media and Career Decision Making among Undergraduates in Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that family (parents) has a significant relationship with career decision making. The study also found that peer groups have no significant link with career decision-making, of the students as seen by the result of the findings. Ajayi, Moosa, and Aloka, (2022), investigate the Influence of selected social factors on career decision making of grade 12 learners in township secondary schools in South Africa. The result of the study revealed that, there was a strong link between teacher influence and career decision-making, followed by the link between career information services and career decision-making, but peer influence had the weakest link with career decision-making. The influence of older siblings on students in Grade 12 had a considerable direct association with professional decision-making.

Chukwu, Ogidi, Akaneme, & Ilechukwu, (2022) in their study of factors influencing career choice among secondary school student in Aba North of Abia State found out The grand mean rating of the influence regarding peer group on students' choice of career is 2.9 and a standard deviation score of 0.40, which is higher than the benchmark of 2.5. By implication, students are influenced by their peers regarding career choice as revealed in item 20 with the mean score of 3.4. Peers' suggestions count in career choice. The grand mean rating with regards to the influence of parents on the student's career choice is 3.1 and the standard deviation of 0.58, which is higher than the benchmark of 2.5. By implication students generally submit to the influence of their parents regarding career choice. From the empirical review within the reach of the researcher, it was observed that not much work had been carried out on peers and family influence on career choice, especially within Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. This is the gap this study filled.

In today's world, selecting a career is often a challenge for students. For this reason, it is not unusual for students to enter careers that are not entirely suited to their abilities. On the other hand, peer group and parental background frequently play a major role in influencing a student's job decision. Due to peculiarities in their own lives, parents frequently push their children into pursuing family careers and other professions even though they lack the necessary skills. In the end, what typically happens is job discontent, poor performance, if not outright malfunction, frustration, and inefficiency, all of which contribute to a national economic catastrophe over time. Hence the need for the assessment of factors influencing career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja local government area of Kogi State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate

1. The influence of family factor on career choice Among Senior Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. The influence of peer factor on career choice Among Senior Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Research Question

1. What are the factors that influences choice of career among senior secondary school students in Lokoja Government Area of Kogi State?

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Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between Family influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. There is no significant difference between peer influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study consists of all Government senior secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria which is 7225 (4648 males and 2545 females) students (Source: Kogi State Science, Technical Education and Teaching Service Commission). The sample for the study consists of 500 (297 males and females 203) students selected from all the government owned secondary school in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling techniques. The first state was proportional sampling techniques for the respondent based on the number of student per school and the second stage is a simple random techniques for the respondents. The researcher instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher titled Influences on Career Choice Questionnaire (ICQ).

To ensure the validity of the instrument, face and content validities were ensured by experts while the reliability of the instrument was established by administering the instrument on 40 secondary school students Government Day secondary school Adankolo, Lokoja. Data collected were analysed using split-half Formula with a reliability coefficient of 0.7 hence the instrument was adjudged to be reliable for the study. The data obtained from the instrument was analyse using the descriptive analysis of frequency count, mean, percentage and standard deviation were used to answer research question raised for the study. The hypotheses generated were subjected to inferential statistics of t-test analysis and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the factors that influences choice of career among secondary school students in Lokoja Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 1: factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State

Influencing factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Rank
Peers	310 (62%)	100 (20%)	40 (8%)	50 (10%)	3.34	1 st
Family	150 (30%)	250 (50%)	30 (6%)	70 (14%)	2.96	2 nd
School	150 (30%)	130 (26%)	120 (24%)	100 (20%)	2.66	3 rd
Role Model	80(16%)	210 (42%)	100 (20%)	110 (22%)	2.52	4 th
Gender	70 (14%)	20 (4%)	100 (20%)	310 (62%)	1.70	5 th

Table 1 presents the factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The result shows that, with a cutoff mean of 2.50 for the rating scale, all the items had a mean scores above the cutoff except gender. This implies that peers, family, school and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State are shown in Figure I.

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Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between family influence and choice of career choice Among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to family influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, were computed and subjected to Statistical analysis involving t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test showing the difference between family influence and choice of career among secondary school students in Lokoja Local government Area of Kogi State.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t_{cal}</i>	<i>t_{table}</i>
Family factor	500	15.50	1.25	499	169.750*	1.960
Career Choice	500	6.76	0.56			

***p<0.05**

Table 2 shows that $t_{cal}(169.750)$ is greater than $t_{table}(1.960)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between family influence and choice of career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between Peers influence and choice of career Among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to peers' influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3.

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Table 3: t-test showing the influence of peers on career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t_{cal}</i>	<i>t_{table}</i>
Peers	500	15.50	1.25			
				119	128.340*	1.960
Career Choice	500	6.85	0.94			

***p<0.05**

Table 3 reveals that t_{cal} (128.340) is greater than t_{table} (1.960) at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between peer influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Discussion of Findings

The result shows that peers, family, school and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State while gender is least in terms of influence on the career choice of secondary school students. The finding agreed with Ajayi, Moosa, and Aloka, (2022) with as they found out that there was a strong link between teacher influence and career decision-making, followed by the link between career information services and career decision-making, but peer influence had the weakest link with career decision-making.

The finding of the study shows that there is significant difference between family influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. Most of the students were viewed as coming to school with predetermined careers which may be a result of interacting with the immediate environment and their parents' help in choosing their careers. This study is in line with Owusu, Owusu, Fiorgbor and Atakora (2021) who revealed that parents had interest in the careers of their children and that their children do not take career decisions without their approval. This therefore means that family members play a significant role in the choice of career of the young people. In this study, parental advice played a role in influencing career among sponsored students. Following closely were uncle's and auntie's advice on career choice.

The finding of the study shows that there is a significant difference between the peers' influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. As students interact with peers and friends, they share important information on career choices. Career guidance teachers were in agreement with student participants as they reinforced that career advice from friends was influential to students' choices of careers. The finding agrees Obot, Amalu, Apebende and Ogodo (2020) who revealed that peer group significantly influences students' career aspiration. A further consideration of their results show that, for all careers, average level of peer influence, has more students, followed by low level with the lowest number of the students falling under high influence. The results of this study concur with this since mentorship of the respondents by their friends, friend's approval of career choice and friend's advice were proved to have a great influence on their choice of career.

Conclusions

The essence of the study was to establish factors that influence the choice of career among students in lokoja local government area of kogi state. As reflected by the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the family has a significant role in influencing students' career choices. The study further concluded that peers have a significant role in students' choices of careers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on factors influencing the career choices of students, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is a need to review the career guidance curriculum to consider factors that influence students' choices of careers.
2. There should be a paradigm shift from the career guidance teacher as the sole provider of career guidance in schools.

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3. It is also recommended that clear policy on who should teach career guidance and the actual provision of career guidance in schools be put in place.

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Assessment of Instructional Facilities, Methods and Learning Outcomes in History among Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State

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Abstract

The study tends to examine the Assessment of instructional facilities, methods and learning outcomes in history learning among secondary school students in sokoto. The sample of the study consists of 306(Male 177 and Female 129) SS2 history students. This sample was arrived at by selecting six Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis using purposive sampling technique on the basis of if history is being offered in the schools, co-education and being a government secondary school, Simple random sampling technique was adopted to select students using an intact class. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain data and simple percentages were used to analyze results. The findings of the study revealed that: there is lack of adequate instructional facility. The techniques of instruction are mostly teacher-centered and the teachers - students' ratio is not encouraging for the students' population. The result of learning outcomes revealed that the subject content is mostly difficult for the students to comprehend. The level of interest exhibited by the students is not encouraging for learning history. Provisions for fieldtrips/excursions, experienced and qualified history teachers should be employed for teaching and learning of History in all Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis and beyond.

Keywords: Instructional methods, Instructional facility, Learning outcomes, and Students

Introduction

As a study of the past happenings, History draws on significant events of the past to inform the present and to safeguard the future, in effect, History does not study the past in isolation from the present, but relates intricately, the successes, achievements and failures of antecedent generations to the contemporary case and sets the stage for a better living in the morrow (Boadu, 2016). In this light, it is believed that History is a systematic account of the past events in relation to the present time in order to be able to predict the future for the purpose of shaping it for better. The goal of History teaching in schools is to help young people develop an integrated spiritual world, via assimilation of the ethno-cultural, national and universal values that have been developed in the course of historical development, and by giving them experience in defining themselves in relation to these values.

In Nigeria, the history teaching and learning has been changed over the years from time to time when it was a vibrant school subject to the time when it has become excised from the primary and junior secondary school curriculum(Jyothish, 2021). Soon, history became a favorite subject on the school's curriculum at independence in Nigeria. First at the university college, Ibadan and later, the University of Ibadan, began to review the school's curriculum to introduce aspects of Nigeria and African history away from the colonial history that was taught that paid much attention to the ancient world(Baba et al., 2022). History as a subject also feature prominently at the higher school certificate (HSC) program which sought to prepare students for admission to the universities. By 1966, the subject was among the most favoured subject at the HSC examinations and in which the candidates excelled. While the principal passes were English 244, Latin 3, Geography 269, Mathematics 88, and French 19, History recorded 414(Unya, 2022), However, the course of the teaching history was to be adversely affected by the events which followed the convening of the 1969 national curriculum conference followed by adaptation of a national policy of education and the subsequent arrival of the 6-3-3-4 system of education "the 1969 conference which was expected to bring hope

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to the country's educational system turned out to be the beginning of the decline of history teaching in schools. In the end, the curriculum reform which grew from that conference led to the reduction of the status of history (Rakhbar, 2021).

In Nigeria, the teaching and learning of History in schools is undergoing tremendous changing in terms of modernization, methodologies which can be understood only in the context of the subject. It is now clear that the process of History teaching and learning has become more varied and interesting, with a possibility for greater personal input. At the same time, it should be remembered that History education is based on a rich legacy. Further stated that, History teaching and learning in Nigerian schools has a long tradition, the indisputable achievement of the History as a subject and the methodologies used in teaching it have been recognized internationally. However, it should be noted that teaching and learning of History in schools has witnessed some changes over the years (Diso & Haruna, 2020). The changes have really affected the structure of History education, the principles for selecting subject matter and the instructional materials used to teach the subject. Baba *et al.* (2022), stated that recommended methods were not used by History teachers in teaching the subject, and even those used were not used appropriately. It was also revealed that instructional resources were not frequently used in History lessons because such resources were either not available at all or were inadequate. Also, Students were also found to possess negative perceptions about the subject as they regarded History as a compendium of facts to be memorized.

An effective History teacher does not rely on a single method of teaching (Diso & Haruna, 2020). Effectiveness is multi-dimensional rather than non dimensional. And that effective teaching of History involves setting conditions that make selected works more interesting (Jyothish, 2021). Effective instruction has a bearing on the interest of students and their motivation to learning History; and also influences them to make critical judgment on historical issues, and understand current events in the appropriate historical context (Alison and Alison, 2021). Rahbar (2021) observed that ambitious teachers have a good depth of understanding regarding their subject matter and consciously seek ways of connecting the subject matter to students' experiences. Effective History teaching thus, involves teaching in no single pattern, taking no single shape in teaching, and assessing students in no single fashion. Consequently, History as a subject which is being taught in senior secondary schools is facing a lot of challenges in terms of teaching facility, methods of instruction and students activity in response to the instructional process. The present study sought to investigate the effect of instructional facility, methods of instruction and learning outcomes in the teaching of History in Secondary Schools within Sokoto.

Research Questions

1. What is the current status of instructional facility for teaching of History as a subject in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis?
2. What instructional Techniques are being employed in the teaching of History in Senior Secondary schools in Sokoto Metropolis?
3. What type of learning outcomes were obtained in the teaching and learning of history among secondary school students in Sokoto Metropolis

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design according to Ali 2010a. The survey design seeks to document and describe what, present status of existence or absence of what is under investigation. The research population of this study comprises of 1842 (Male 1062 & Females 780) senior secondary school students from six schools. The sample size of this study is 306 senior secondary school students drawn from the study population of 1842. The research employed the stratification proportionate random sample technique. The bases considered for the selection were sex and socio economic status. Structured interview and on-the-spot observation were administered to collate the responses from the respondents on the different aspects of the research study. The information solicited includes responses on students' data such as age, gender, occupation of the parents, school and class of the students. Data regarding the subject of study (Teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools) in Sokoto Metropolis focuses on a variety of considerations. These range from instructional procedures/techniques, through availability of training facility to acquired skills, experiences and perceptions of the students on the subject matter and the instructional processes.

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Result

Research Question 1

What is the current status of instructional facility for teaching of History subject in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis?

Table 1: Percentage of respondents showing the status of instructional facility for teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto

S/N	Instructional Facility	Sample (N)	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
1	Text Books available	306	113	36.93	4 th
2	Library up-to-date	306	122	39.87	3 rd
3	Use of teaching aids	306	171	55.88	2 nd
4	Field Trips	306	66	21.57	5 th
5	Make improvisation	306	271	88.56	1 st

Table 1 shows the percentage responses in terms of instructional facility for the teaching of History. The result indicates a higher percentage of improvisation (88.56%) over other requirements. This is followed by the use of teaching aids in History classes (55.88). Library standard had 39.87%, text books had 36.93%, and the least, fieldtrips had 21.57%.

Research Question 2

What were the percentage responses regarding the style/techniques for the teaching of History in the Senior Secondary Schools within Sokoto?

Table 2: Percentage of respondents showing style/techniques of teaching History in the Senior Secondary Schools within Sokoto

S/N	Method/style of instruction	Sample N.	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
1	Student centered	306	102	33.33	4 th
2	Teachers availability	306	93	30.39	5 th
3	Regular Teaching	306	226	73.85	2 nd
4	Give and mark assignments	306	130	42.48	3 rd
5	Ask & answer students questions	306	254	83.00	1 st

Table 2 shows percentage of positive responses in terms of style/techniques for the teaching History. The style of asking and answering students' questions by the teacher had the highest response of 83.00% followed by regular teaching with 73.85%. Administering and marking of students' assignments ranks 3rd with 42.48%. Student centered teaching and availability of teachers for History had the lowest responses of 33.33% and 30.39% respectively.

Research Question 3

What were the percentage responses regarding learning outcomes/acquired skills from the teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto?

Table 3: Percentage of respondents showing learning outcomes/acquired skills from the lessons of History classes in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto

Sample (N).	S/N	Learning outcome/ Students response	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
306	1	Class interesting	256	83.66	3 rd
306	2	Content difficult to understand	199	65.03	4 th
306	3	School management show interest	151	49.34	5 th

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306	4	Teacher tolerant	258	84.31	2 nd
306	5	Delivers content appropriately	266	86.92	1 st

Table 3 shows percentage of respondents indicating learning outcomes from the teaching of History. Appropriate delivery of lesson have the highest response (86.92%) closely followed by the teachers' tolerance (84.31%) and students' interest in the lessons delivery (83.66%). Difficulty in understanding the subject however received 65.03% positive response and interest in the subject by the school management received 49.34% positive response.

Discussion of Findings

Availability and effective utilization of instructional facility is of paramount importance in the teaching and learning of any subject no matter how complex. The findings of this study revealed high level of improvisation of instructional materials for teaching of History with 88.56% report of improvisation by the teachers. This is a clear indication of lack or shortage of standard facility for teaching the subject. According to Rahbar (2021), modern methods and techniques of teaching History in school education system along with good teaching aids are vital requirements for effective curriculum implementation. The response on the availability of teaching aids merely indicates the use of maps, which are inadequate for contemporary teaching of the subject. With the report of low standard of library facility for history, presence of mostly outdated textbooks and lack of regular fieldtrips on the subject, the challenges for teaching of history seem enormous. Alison and Alison (2021) highlighted on the instrumental role of both instructional materials and information communication technology in the teaching and learning of History. Although students are allowed to ask questions and get answers from the history teachers, student centered teaching and availability of teachers for the subject had the lowest responses of 33.33% and 30.39% respectively. The research findings revealed that there are no enough history teachers. This trend leads to the teaching of History by other subjects' teachers without requisite training and skills in the area. In addition to the aforementioned, many history teachers capitalize on teacher-centered approach which limits students' capabilities. Because the students use to be passive with little or none participation, this eventually led to the shortage of students in the field of history.

On the use of instructional materials, the high negative response from the study points out the implications of possible wrong perception and poor understanding of history subject by the students. With regards to the excursion and field trip, the high negative response from the study means that, students are not visiting valuable historical sites which will arouse the interest of the students, which is also important in the retention of knowledge. Consequently, the students perceive history as just mere story and irrelevant to the modern time. Result shows high percentage of respondents for appropriate lessons delivery and teacher tolerance in History lessons. Respondents however reported much difficulty in understanding History lessons and low interest by the school managements in the teaching of the subject. Majority of respondents (83.0%) agreed that History teachers allow students to ask questions and also ask the students questions related to the subject matter being discussed. Although this is essential in improving the process of instruction in the subject, the student-centered instructional style by most teachers of the subject (33.33%) and unavailability of teachers of History in the schools (30.39%), is impacting negatively on the general performance of the students and the prospect of the course in general. In addition the lack of interest in teaching the subject on the side of school management was highly reported by the respondents. This indicates that the school managements pay little or no attention in the teaching of History as a subject in the senior secondary schools.

On the availability of history textbooks, mostly poor and outdated books have been reported by the respondents. This led to the problem of wrong perception and poor understanding of history by the students. With regards to the excursion and field trip, poor response means that, students are not visiting valuable historical sites which will arouse the interest of the students and it also aid the retention of knowledge. Consequently, the students perceive history as just mere story and irrelevant to the modern time. Concerning interest the interest by the school management about the teaching of History, This indicates that school management has little or no interest in history as a subject. It is apparent therefore, that, there is need for the adjustment of teaching method from teacher-centered to students-oriented, for the students to participate more. School management or the authority provide the available and modem history textbooks, then to provide fertile ground for the excursion and field trip to take place. Also, there is a need for the provision of the adequate and appropriate instructional materials.

Conclusion

The study revealed that, there is an acute shortage of qualified history teachers with sufficient teaching experience. It has also been found that, history teachers are overworked as they teach a large number of classes and other subjects apart from history. This affects their performance in the teaching of history. Poor interest of students and the schools management in the

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subject have been reported. This is probably because of inability of the authorities to provide the appropriate history textbooks relevant to the history as a subject. This problem is of course related to the problems of ill-equipped libraries discovered during the research. Another problem militating against effective history teaching and learning is that of instructional materials. Teachers in the schools surveyed mainly use maps neglecting the use of a variety of instructional materials such as pictures, charts. The teachers fail to use their expertise knowledge to make history teaching more interesting. This led to the assumption and belief by the students that history is mere stories and irrelevant facts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should include History as a core subject in the curriculum and make it compulsory for all students in secondary schools like other subjects such as Mathematics and English Language.
2. History should be made more interesting through well-trained History teachers who can teach the subject and make it interesting to the students.
3. There is need for consistence in Government policies that will cater for students needs in History as a subject in Nigerian secondary schools.
4. History teachers should not be overburdened with teaching of other subjects. They should be allowed to concentrate on history as their teaching subject.
5. The use of instructional materials is a very important, motivator as it arouses and sustains students' interest. The history teacher should use a variety of instructional materials and not just maps. Audio, audio-visual, pictures and charts as well as physical objects should serve as instructional materials for the teaching of History.

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Assessment of Instructional Materials and Teaching Methodologies on Implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Instructional materials and Teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two specific objectives. Two research questions and hypotheses, respectively. The Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The total population of the study was 737 stake holders comprising 102 head teachers, 588 Nomadic teachers and 47 quality assurance officers. The sample size was 248 stake holders (37 head teachers, 195 Nomadic teachers and 16 quality assurance officers). Data were collected using a structured questionnaire title: “Evaluation of the Implementation Nomadic Education Programme in Zamfara State of Nigeria (EINEP)” was adopted by the researcher, the questionnaire was validated by the experts in the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and after the pilot study, the data collected was statistically analysed for reliability co-efficient using Cronbach Alpha at a 0.05 significance level, and the reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data collected were analysed using bar chart to answer the research questions while Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to test hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that Instructional materials were not adequately provided for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State, Nigeria, among others. The study concluded that implementation of Nomadic education programme in Zamfara state was generally low. It was recommended that Governments at all levels should ensure that Nomadic schools are provided with adequate and relevant instructional materials.

Keywords: Instructional materials, Methods of teaching & Nomadic Education Programme.

Introduction

Education is the springboard for social and economic change and plays a major role in the socio-economic development of a nation. Education occupies an important place in most plans for economic and social development. It is important in human development as a supplier of the trained manpower as well as a requisite for the accomplishment of other development goals (Adebiye, 2014). The roles played by the educational sector stimulate the economic growth and development which explains why countries expend so much on education in order to enhance the level of literacy of their citizenry. This is why inequality of access to education and educational marginalization has serious effects on national development.

The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) as amended stated that the “Government shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities”. In this regard, the children of nomadic pastoralist, whose parents are contributing daily to the growth and development of the country’s economy, should not be left behind un-educated. The nomadic children should have access to formal education and efforts should be made to ensure that functional and productive education is provided to them.

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) demands that every Nigerian child should have full access to quality education at basic education level. However, the attainment of this objective is not easy as pointed Bolaji, Yusuf, Jekayinfa and Mofoluwawo (2010) to nomads who wander from place to place with no fixed home, makes it difficult to have their children enrolled in schools. The National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) (2012) is of the view that the movement of nomads is necessitated by their economic activities. These activities engaged by nomads is used to describe their ethnic, social and as professional group of people that move from one place to another in search for means of survival (Kratli,

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2011). According to Muhammad and Abbo (2010) posit that the Nigerian nomadic pastoralists are made up of the Fulani (5.3m), Shuwa (1.01m), Koyam (32,000), Badai (20,000), Dark Buzzu (15,000) and the Buduma (10,000). The Fulani are found in 31 out of the 36 States of Nigeria, while others reside mainly on the Borno plains and shores of Lake Chad. The migrant fishing groups account for about 2.8 million, comprising numerous tribes. They are found in the Atlantic coastline, the riverside areas and river basins of the country. These groups of people amongst others do not have access to functional education in the country over time. In the quest to remove the chronic illiteracy among this mobile population of Nigeria, the federal government of Nigeria introduced Nomadic Education Program (NEP) in 1986. The NEP was designed to provide the nomads with the relevant and fundamental basic education that would improve their survival skills. This was expected to provide them with the knowledge and the skills that would enable them to raise their productivity and income; as well as empower them to participate effectively in the socio-economic and political affairs of the country.

The main aim of nomadic education is to take education to the nomads. In this regard, a mobile system of education was designed to be used where the nomads are far from conventional nomadic primary schools or where the nomads are in continuous movement. Most of the Nomadic schools adopted the conventional fixed school system. The implication is that since the government cannot establish schools in every community, some of the nomads found themselves in communities with no nomadic primary school nearby.

After establishing nomadic primary schools in most states of the Federation by the NCNE, there has been a shortage of manpower as most of the teachers in continued to seek transfer to conventional schools. Educational resources have also been in short supply in most nomadic primary schools. Lack of adequate funding has been largely blamed for the inadequate educational resources. To make things worse, there seems to be a lukewarm attitude by supervisors of some of these schools in difficult terrains as supervision of schools in these areas leaves little to be admired (Akwe, 2018).

In a progress report on a nomadic education programme in Nigeria submits that classroom accommodation still remains the most acute problem of the nomadic education programme. While classroom furniture is lacking in the majority of the schools including the ones that have built classrooms, the report also points out that instructional materials such as chalk, chalkboards, textbooks, visual and audio aids are in short supply in most of the nomadic primary schools in the states. Thus, it is difficult to fully implement the curriculum for nomadic education in the centres that experience these challenges. Another disturbing factor capable of obstructing the implementation of the nomadic education curriculum is the unavailability of manpower (trained teachers) (Kana, 2012).

To implement is to put into action or operation a plan or a system, this according to Ivowi in Kolawole (2013) observe that implementation is the translation of theory into practice or a proposal into action. Curriculum implementation is a stage of putting into practice all that has been documented as curriculum in the classroom through the combined effort of the teachers, learners, school administrator, parent as well as interaction with the physical facilities, instructional materials, psychological and social environment of the school (Onyechu in Kolawole, 2013). Nomadic Education is the first six years of Basic Education provided to the children of disadvantaged nomadic populations in the country (FRN, 2014). This is formal education designed for the transmission of knowledge from one generation of nomads to another. In Nigeria, nomadic education was specifically established for nomadic children who did not have the opportunity to attend conventional schools because of their parents' occupation. It began during the colonial period but actual firm government involvement started in 1986 when it was officially introduced by the then military administration of General Ibrahim Babangida (Akpan, 2015).

Nomadic education as defined by Tahir (1997), is the informal education provided by the nomadic people within their cultural contexts as well as the formal and non-formal education provided by the nomads, national governments and international agencies aimed at promoting the culture of the nomadic peoples and equipping them with relevant knowledge and skills to empower them to develop themselves and their communities. This will also enable them to contribute to national development. Therefore, in considering the education of nomads for national development in Africa, the discussion will be centred on their traditional education, the attempts made by international agencies and national governments to educate them, and the structure and scope of the education provided for them in some African countries and how such educational provisions promote their culture and development in their communities and nations.

According to NCNE cited in Abbo (2011), the initiative into the NEP includes the activities and projects aimed at producing adequate and well-trained teachers for the NEP and to improve the quality of instruction. Prior to these initiatives, there were not enough teachers in nomadic schools to the extent that teacher: pupil ratio was as high as 1:80 in certain cases. The available teachers were mostly unqualified, poorly trained and inexperienced in dealing with the nomads. They had the background and training for teaching in the conventional school system suitable for the sedentary mainstream population since the teachers knew nothing about the nomadic groups and could not put their special needs and circumstances into proper focus.

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They used inappropriate and ineffective teaching methods and materials resulting in poor classroom interaction and low learning achievement of pupils.

Curriculum can be defined as the sum total of all systematically planned learning experiences prepared by the organization responsible for teaching a specific group for the achievements of an individual's specific goals and those of the society in general. Buckhadit (1998) and Lar (2010) observe that there is the need to design a functional curriculum for the nomads, which must be of symbiotic relationship with the target society the ideology of the nomadic culture, belief system and environment. According to them, it is the relevance of the curriculum that will change the attitudes of the nomads and motivate their children to respond to education positively. The NCNE has considered the development and institutionalization of relevant curriculum a priority in its effort to provide education for the nomads. The commission in developing the curriculum paid special attention to the fact that the nomadic pastoralists have peculiar needs, lifestyles, work rates and environment. Therefore, whatever should form the content of education for their children should consider these peculiarities. The commission adopted the existing primary school curriculum into the unique socio-cultural and economic pattern of life of the nomads.

The Nomadic Education Centre (NEC) located at the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, which is statutorily assigned the function of the curriculum development, carried out the development and adaptation of curriculum for the nomadic pastoralist according to Uyanga and Siddique (2000) the exercise involved adaptation from the existing national core curriculum for primary schools and subject areas thus: English, Mathematics, Primary Science, Social Studies, Hand Craft, Health Education, Islamic Religious Knowledge and Fulfulde.

Subject specialists and experts with sufficient knowledge of the culture, educational needs and problems of the nomadic pastoralists were utilized for the adaptation, process. In doing this, an attempt was made to make each objective child-centred and the contents were scrutinized for relevance with the objectives and the needs and condition of the nomads; irrelevant contents were removed or modified and replaced with more ones that are relevant. The main aim of the nomadic education curriculum is to make schooling more appealing to nomads as well as to transform pastoralist society more effectively.

Bruner (1973) says that the teachers work as a communicator, model and identification figure can be supported by wise use of a variety of devices that expand the experience, clarify it and give it personal significance. Agun (2000) refers to them as learning materials, the proper use of which helps learners to learn faster and better. Similarly, Obanya (1989) view them as didactic materials-things which are supposed to make learning and teaching possible while according to Johnson (1989) instructional materials are the collections and selection of resources (mechanical, otherwise) from available resources which are applied and integrated into a systematic process of teaching and learning to make learning effective. Ikerionwu (2000) refers to them as objects or devices, which help the teacher to make a lesson for the learner. Instructional materials, therefore, are concrete or physical objects which provide sound, visual or both to the sense organs during teaching (Agina-Obu, 2005). According to Abdullahi (2010), instructional materials are materials or tools locally made or imported that could make tremendous enhancement of lesson impact if intelligently used. In most cases, many learners have the difficulty in understanding certain concepts because of their level of cognitive operation, it is against this background that Jean Piaget postulated human beings to be classified along with sensory-motor, pre-operational, concrete and abstract cognitive levels.

On the importance of the usage of instructional materials in nomadic primary schools, Aliyu and Mohammed in Ogbondah (2008) stated that "the success of any educational programme depends on proper planning and the availability and utilization of resources. Therefore, a successful lesson has to do with effective use of instructional materials". Similarly, where the modern instructional materials are not available or cannot work effectively in rural areas for instance television and computers, Nomadic school teachers are to be creative in improvising instructional materials.

With regards to the provision of instructional/infrastructure the National Commission of Nomadic Education observed that there is an inadequate supply of instructional materials such as textbooks, exercise books, writing materials and copies of subjects-curricular. Similarly, facilities such as classrooms and furniture are grossly inadequate (Situation Report on Nomadic Education 2002). The teaching/learning style of the nomadic people must be understood by teachers and used to teach the nomads. Curricula/content Concepts must be illustrated using the objects and examples drawn from their culture and environment to make their learning easy and meaningful. This has guided the orientation and training of teachers and supervisors of nomadic schools organized by the National Commission for Nomadic Education. According to NCNE cited in Abbo (2011), the initiative into the NEP includes the activities and projects aimed at producing adequate and well-trained teachers for the NEP and to improve the quality of instruction. Prior to these initiatives, there were not enough teachers in nomadic schools to the extent that teacher: pupil ratio was as high as 1:80 in certain cases. The available teachers were mostly unqualified, poorly trained and inexperienced in dealing with the nomads. They had the background and training for teaching in the conventional school system suitable for the sedentary mainstream population since the teachers knew nothing about

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the nomadic groups and could not put their special needs and circumstances into proper focus. They used inappropriate and ineffective teaching methods and materials resulting in poor classroom interaction and low learning achievement of pupils.

The pedagogical teacher development initiatives for improving Nomadic Education Programme were geared towards achieving the following objectives: Produce and retain the critical mass of teachers needed to attain the goals of the NEP, train new teachers with nomadic backgrounds, re-train serving teachers to understand and appreciate the peculiar needs and circumstances of the nomads, acquaint teachers, supervisors and coordinators with the rationale, policy, objectives and strategies of the NEP, enhance knowledge, skills and competences of nomadic teachers through the use of innovative teaching methods and improve lesson delivery; improve classroom interaction and learning achievement.

There is Agency for Nomadic education in Zamfara State; the function of the Agency for Nomadic Education in the state is to impart knowledge and functional survival skills for improving the efficiency and productivity of the Nomads towards the realizations of specific national goals. The agency has also to do with the recruitment, appointment, promotion, posting, transfer, and discipline of the nomadic teaching and non-teaching staff of the schools under the agency. There are 49 Nomadic primary schools across the state with 169 academic staff. Enrolment of pupils stood at 4,723 – 3,209 male and 1,514 female in 2015. There are also 103 classes out of which 54 need renovation and require additional 66 classes. There are three tarpaulin classes supplied by the National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) in 2014, seven motorcycles for monitoring were supplied by the NCNE in 2013. Some textbooks and curricular models were supplied by the commission in 2015 Four Hundred and Fifty (450) core subject textbooks were also supplied in 2014 by the commission (ZSG, 2017).

Theories and Models are useful in programme evaluation because they provide a set of steps that could be followed in carrying out a proposed evaluation, they are very important in the understanding of concepts used in education, they are carefully selected in line with the topic. Therefore, the researcher reviews the theory of Human Capital Theory. This theory was propounded by a renowned economist called Adam Smith in 1776. Oni opines that human capital theory has gained currency since the time of Adam Smith, but its popularity was however, emphasized by Theodore Schultz in his 1990 presidential address to the American Economic Association (AED). Human capital theory is relevant to the study based on comprehensiveness, establishing procedures for maximizing the impact of study results on institutional decision making and investment in the education of the nomads/shepherds children. In addition, the theory of human capital which became popular after the Second World War has generated certain responses from many interest groups. No doubt the consequence of these responses has been the increasing investment in education as a means of accelerating the rate of economic growth of the society and this adopted the theory because of its relevance to the development of nomadic and shepherd schools educational programme in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Also, Stufflebeam's CIPP model of evaluation was reviewed by the researchers. Context, Input, Process, Product and Constraints (CIPPC) model which is a modified form of Stufflebeams (1971) Context, Input, Process and Product (CIPP) model was used in this study. This model according to Achebe (2004) is used to evaluate a programme about the context in which it operates the input of the programme process through which students go and the product of the programme as well as the problems militating against the implementation of the programme. This theory is relevant to the current study because it gave insight on the process/steps of evaluation. Context evaluation was being employed to diagnose the programme problems about the determination of the aims and objectives of the programme in the State.

Different research works have been conducted on Nomadic Education, most of which reviewed by the researchers have been found conducted in Nigeria. Among are those conducted and reviewed by the researcher are; Saidu, Abudu, Odebode and Oyeyemi (2017), studied on historical analysis of NEP in Kwara State, Nigeria: 1988-2011, Abubakar (2015) carried out research to determine the impact of the Nomadic Education Programme on the Nomads Employment Opportunity and Cattle production Output in the North-West zone of Nigeria, also Yaguya (2014) assessed the impact of the nomadic education curriculum on the educational development of nomads in Nigeria among others. This present study assessed the Instructional materials and Teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The study was guided by the following specific objectives, which are to:

1. determine the efficacy of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;
2. Examine the efficacy of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The followings are research questions:

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1. What is the impact of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?
2. What is the impact of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level:

1. There is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;
2. There is no significant difference between Choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design following the recommendation of Dada (2016) who stated that descriptive survey research is a detailed study, which strives to explain or determine and report the way things are. It is the type of research that specifies the true nature of a given problem or event. The descriptive survey research further involves assessing situations through the administration of instruments that are specifically prepared for such a purpose. The choice of descriptive survey design for this research was based on the fact that the entire population cannot be covered, and so a sampling procedure would be done. The population of this study comprised of all 102 Nomadic primary schools in all 14 Local Government Areas (LGAs) of three (3) senatorial districts in Zamfara State. The population comprised of one hundred and two (102) Head teachers, five hundred and eighty-eight (588) Teachers and forty-seven (47) Quality Assurance officials, totaling seven hundred and thirty-seven (737) (ZMSANE, 2020).

A sample size of 248 participated in the study. This is based on the recommendation by the Research Advisors (2006), which recommends that for a population of 700-799 a sample size of 248 is sufficient for generalization at 95% confidential level and 5% margin of error. A multi-stage sampling procedure to select the respondents. In the first stage, a proportionate sampling procedure was used to distribute the sample among the elements of the population (Head teachers, Teachers and Quality Assurance Officials) where Sulaiman (2015), explained that proportionate sampling is used when the elements of population vary considerably in size because it assures that those in larger size have the same probability of getting into the sample as those in the smaller size, and vice versa.

At the second stage, the LGAs and Nomadic primary schools were purposively selected based on recommendation by Dada (2016) who said in purposive sampling, researcher uses own judgment in selection of members of the population. It is used to obtain a representative sample by using a sound judgment, which will result in the collection of reliable data, saving time and money. At the third stage, convenient sampling technique was used by the researcher to select the Head teachers, Teachers and Quality Assurance Officers which Agbe (2003) opined is also known as grab sampling or opportunity sampling is the type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. The research instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire that was adopted by the researchers. The questionnaire was made in two parts, A and B. Part A contained the respondents' general information while Part B consist of 20 item or statements about the objectives of the study using four (4) points modified Likert scale of 4- SA (Strongly Agree), 3- A (Agree), 2- D (Disagree) and 1- SD (Strongly Disagree). The data collected was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Bar chart were used to present responses of the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using nonparametric statistics of Kruskal-Wallis H test which deals with the three independent sample groups in the study. This test is used to determine if there are statistically significance differences among three or more groups of independent variable on continuous or ordinal dependent variable by researcher (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952).

Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Figure 1: Responses of the respondents on the impact of Instructional Materials in Nomadic Primary Schools in Zamfara State (Field work, 2021)

Figure 1 shows the result of the opinion of impact of instructional materials on implementation of NEP in Zamfara State. The finding presented indicated that most of the respondents are not in agreement with the majority of the items and this revealed that instructional materials were not adequately provided in Nomadic Schools for the implementation of NEP in Zamfara State.

Research Question 2:

What is the impact of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Figure 2: Responses of the respondents on the Instructional Methods used by Nomadic Primary Schools Teachers in Zamfara State (Field work, 2021)

The result presented above in Figure 2 shows the responses of the respondents on the instructional methods used by Nomadic school teachers for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. The result presented indicated that most of respondents did not agree with the items. This shows that the majority of Nomadic school teachers are using inappropriate teaching methods for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;

Table 1: Kruskal-Wallis (*H*) test on the responses of the respondents on the Provision of Instructional Materials in Nomadic Primary Schools in Zamfara State

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	$H(X^2)$	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
Teachers	205	124.40	25.48	2	0.05	0.21	Retained
Headteachers	27	112.30					
Quality Assurance	16	146.23					

Source: Field work, (2021)

Table 1 presents the Kruskal-Wallis (*H*) test to determine the provision of instructional materials for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. The result of the Kruskal-Wallis (*H*) test shows that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State; was retained. This is because the Mean Rank of 124.40, 112.30 and 146.23 for the three groups of respondents, $H(X^2)$ of 25.48 and p-value $0.21 > \alpha=0.05$ level of significance was obtained. Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State.

Table 2: Kruskal-Wallis (*H*) test on the responses of the respondents on the Instructional Methods used by Nomadic Primary Schools Teachers in Zamfara State

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	$H(X^2)$	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
Teachers	205	105.14	117.80	2	0.05	0.00	Rejected
Headteachers	27	227.83					
Quality Assurance	16	198.18					

Source: Field work, (2021)

Table 2 shows the result of a test of hypothesis four, which says there is no significant difference among the responses of the respondents in the instructional methods used by Nomadic Education teachers for implementing the NEP curriculum in Nomadic primary schools of Zamfara. The result of the Kruskal-Wallis (*H*) test as shown above shows that a significant difference exists among the opinion of respondents in the instructional methods used by Nomadic teachers for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. It shows that the Mean rank of 105.14, 227.83 and 198.18 for the three (3) groups of respondents, $H(X^2)$ of 117.80 and p-value $0.00 < \alpha=0.05$ level of significance was obtained. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the findings of the study, alongside the findings of other researchers, also the discussion is based on the variables contained in the study which were guided by the research questions and research hypotheses tested. Firstly, finding number one reveals the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State was retained. The study also concluded that instructional materials were not adequately provided for the implementation of the Nomadic NEP in Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Ada (2014) whose finding in the study on the impact of communal crises on nomadic education in Plateau State revealed that there is a poor state of educational resources for nomadic education in Plateau State. This finding is also in line with Duze (2011) who found that educational resources were lacking in implementing nomadic education curriculum in Nigeria.

The second finding revealed that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State was rejected. Also, the study concludes that conventional methods are mostly used by Nomadic teachers in the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State,

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Nigeria. This finding is in line with Ogbondah (2008) in a study on Appraisal of instructional materials used to educate the Fishermen Children in Rivers State that most of the teachers are not qualified and cannot effectively utilize the available instructional materials for the effective implementation of migrant fishermen's children education programme.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that both the objectives and goals of the Nomadic education programme have not been achieved and therefore, the implementation of Nomadic Education Programme in Zamfara state was generally low.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

- 2 Governments at all levels should ensure that Nomadic schools are provided with adequate and relevant instructional materials;
- 3 Head Teachers and quality assurance officers should encourage Nomadic teachers to apply the appropriate teaching method when and where necessary

Acknowledgements

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Assessment of Online Facilitation for Teaching and Learning Processes among Facilitators in National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to assess the online facilitation teaching and learning processes among facilitators in the National Open University of Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions were answered and one hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study comprised all the facilitators and learners across study centres of the National Open University of Nigeria across the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. 44 facilitators and 161 learners were purposively selected for participation in the study. Cronbach Alpha reliability test was used to determine the internal consistency of the two instruments (Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (OFAQ) for facilitators and then for learners) which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.929 and 0.846 respectively. Frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer the research questions, and t-test statistics to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that there is no significant difference between online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff. The conclusion from the study is that facilitators to a high extent possessed the technical, communication, and class management skills required for effective online facilitation exercise and the difference in skills possessed by both male and female facilitators is not statistically significant. It was therefore recommended that the NOUN approach of training, re-training and follow-up services by a team of experts and technical staff be replicated in other institutions.

Keyword: Assessment, Online Facilitation, Competencies, Gender, National Open University of Nigeria.

Introduction

The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) seeks to bring education closer to multitudes of Nigerians, who do not have the privilege of pursuing full-time university programmes. NOUN's unique principle is flexibility. Flexibility helps to accommodate students, irrespective of their workplace situation, location or circumstance. This principle of flexibility coupled with the Covid-19 pandemic that has necessitated a new normal makes online facilitation the only visible option for instructional delivery in NOUN. For efficiency, assessment of its processes and implementation, especially as it affects facilitators' capability is therefore desirable at this time.

Online facilitation (also referred to as online teaching and learning) can be described as a Computer-Mediated, Web-based learning environment. It therefore requires facilitators with appropriate skills to drive (Setlhako, 2014; Angeli, Valamedes & Bonk, 2003). According to Gustafon and Gibbs (2000) as well as Martin, Wang and Sandaf (2020), successful online facilitators need to learn strategies to make the process learner-friendly and also devise ways of engaging learners sufficiently in the learning process. Online facilitation therefore requires that the facilitator or instructor apply multiple strategies to facilitate the student's learning and critical thinking skills (Richardson et al, 2015; Schinder & Burkholder, 2014); improve the student's sense of community (Rovai, 2007); and promote students' connectedness and learning (Shea, Li & Pickett, 2006). The role of an online facilitator has therefore shifted from just being a subject expert that dishes out the content to the learners, to someone who facilitates learning. For a successful online facilitation process, the facilitator in addition to being a subject expert should be able to display some technical competencies (Haruna & Hassan, 2017).

Technical competencies require a facilitator to be able to operate a computer and some necessary tools such as the Internet, e-mails, zoom etc. (Setlhako, 2014). According to Gulbahar and Kalelioglu (2015, competent electronic instructors are key to successful online learning implementation. Alqahtani & Rajkhan (2020) in a study of critical success factors for e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic found technology management to be one of them. Campbell and Cameron (2016)

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also submit that digital teachers must be able to educate students in a virtual environment using emerging digital technologies. On the facilitation platform of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), some of the technical skills where competencies are required include recording virtual class conversations, creating and uploading interactive videos, initiating and coordinating interactive forums, setting up a virtual library on the course page etc. Therefore, for this study, the required competencies investigated include recording virtual class conversations, creating and uploading interactive videos, initiating and coordinating interactive forums, setting up the virtual library on the course page etc. It is expected and important that these tools are used to help learners become comfortable during the online course as they increase students' learning and engagement (Martin, Wang & Sadaf, 2018). Using synchronous tools such as audio, video, text, etc. provides opportunities for interaction between facilitators and learners, assists students to grasp the instructional content better and connects with their instructors (Martin and Parker, 2014; Borup et al, 2015).

According to Xie and Derakhshan (2021), learning is beyond mere exposure to information, it encompasses social, psychological and emotional interactions. Strachan (2020) therefore opines that effective instruction is usually actualised within the positive teacher-student relationship context. According to Frisby (2019), and Mercer and Dornyei (2020), teachers should be approachable, believe in all their students, be empathetic, be responsive to each student's individuality, support students' autonomy and be passionate about their profession. For this, according to Mercer and Dornyei (2020), teachers take different actions such as taking care of their talk, being careful about feedback to students, listening to learners, employing questions to engage students and rethinking classroom management as managing relationships. All the above can be summed up in one word "communication". Communication is one essential skill for classroom efficiency both in the face-to-face and online modes.

In online facilitation, the learner and the facilitator in most cases are far apart, therefore, securing and sustaining the attention of the learner requires effectiveness in communication (Haruna & Hassan, 2017). According to Halias, Ismail and Baharudin (2017), the facilitation process cannot be effectively done without effective communication. Christen, Kelly, Fall and Snyder (2015), submit that students appreciate online instructors who are responsive to their needs, engage in frequent communication strategies, use visibility strategies and share personal information. Asha (2020) conducted a study on students' perceptions towards online classes and their effectiveness in enhancing active participation and communication skills. Findings from the study revealed that students agreed unanimously that to a greater extent, online classes enhance speaking and listening skills. They also agreed that online classes enhance participation as well as communication. Cakiroglu (2014) also observed a highly satisfactory percentage in terms of assessing communication between teachers and students in online classes.

Observation and experience have shown that in the face-to-face mode of teaching, the need for classroom management is key as it determines how successful the class session will be. Classroom management has been a consistent concern to educators and researchers because it plays a critical role in facilitating effective learning. According to Gold, Pfirmann & Holodynski (2021), classroom management is an important skill for the academic, social-emotional and motivational development of students and the health of teachers. Adedigba and Sulaiman (2020) therefore submits that teachers must have classroom management skills to successfully build a secure and effective learning environment for pupils' quality education. Babadjanova (2020) defines classroom management as a wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to keep students organized, focused and academically predictive during a class. Decades back, the physical classroom setting dominated our educational system. However, after the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, the virtual classroom system became a phenomenon in our mode of educational delivery in Nigeria. In particular, the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) now operates a virtual classroom system for the facilitation of all her courses. Just as in the physical classroom setting virtual classrooms which also involve pedagogical interactions also require effective classroom management (Oparaji, Igbokwe & Ugwu, 2020).

According to Bigne, Badenes, Ruiz and Andreu (2018), if a teacher possesses technical and affective skills and is familiar with the tools and functionalities that a virtual classroom offers, learner engagement can be enhanced and this would minimize untoward behaviour among learners in a virtual classroom. Kavrayici (2021) carried out a study on the relationship between classroom management and a sense of classroom community in a graduate virtual classroom. The findings of the study showed that various dimensions of classroom management considered (leadership, motivation, rules and behaviour management, communication, instructional planning and implementation and organisational dimensions) were positively correlated with connectedness and learning dimensions of the classroom community. Milliken (2019) found that when leaders implement an instructional approach in managing learner behaviour in a virtual classroom, the learners' pro-social behaviour is enhanced and academic engagement across all learning areas is increased. Sibanda (2021) carried out a study on private school teachers' classroom management in a virtual classroom. The result of the study revealed that private high school teachers adopted diverse strategies to manage learners' behaviour in a virtual classroom. The result also indicated that teachers use

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strategies such as collaborative learning, they also prepare all the materials required according to the set scheme of work, plan the learning activities which are exciting and use interactive learner-centred approaches which engage learners all the time. Teachers who manage learners' behaviour must actively engage them in meaningful and challenging educational experiences (Moore & Hansen, 2012).

The National Open University of Nigeria is the leading ODL University, providing online facilitation in Nigeria. To play this role well, the institution's Online Facilitation System must be efficient. The efficiencies expected cannot be, unless the facilitators are competent in their roles. The roles are numerous and cannot be covered extensively in a single research work. At the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) currently; three aspects of the skills needed by facilitators are prominent and call for immediate investigation. These are; facilitators' skills in the use of technological tools for facilitation (such as recording virtual class conversation, creating interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation, creating announcements on the course page, setting up Zoom online classes etc etc.), communication during online classes and class management in the online class. It is on this note, that this research work assessed the online facilitation process of the National Open University of Nigeria, with a focus on facilitators' competencies in online technology use for various functions, effective communication and class management in online classes.

Gender generally is always an issue in educational research. Shea (2007) in a study explored instructors' motivations to teach online and found that female faculty members were more attracted to online teaching than their male counterparts. Ganji and Sejjehie (2022) found a significant effect of gender on the scores of participants in classroom management behaviour. Men and women were found to be using different classroom management strategies. Martin, Yin and Mayall (2006) found a significant difference between males and females with regards to the instruction management subscale on the inventory. Female teachers were seen to favour interventionist behaviour more than their male counterparts. Nejati, Hassani and Sahrapour (2014) however found that gender is not significantly related to classroom management among a sample of Iranian EFL teachers of a private English institute. Since the gender of facilitators as discovered from research and experience can play an important role in their online facilitation, having a clear picture of how it affects facilitators' technical competencies is essential. Therefore, in this study, one hypothesis was tested to investigate the differences in the competencies of male and female participants.

Many of the studies reviewed attempted to investigate technical competencies, communication and classroom management skills possessed by online facilitators using quantitative measures through interview schedules with the facilitators themselves. This study however attempted to get the learners that were taught to rate their facilitators on their communication and classroom management skills. Studies that used this approach are very rare in literature. It is on this note that this study sought to investigate the technical competencies in handling virtual learning technological tools, communication and classroom management skills possessed by male and female facilitators in the National Open University of Nigeria online facilitation system, to make informed recommendations for improved performance by facilitators in NOUN and by extension in various universities that look up to the university for mentorship in the virtual classroom facilitation system in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

3. Assess the level of competence of online facilitators to carry out teaching and learning activities required for effective online facilitation in NOUN.
4. Assess the level of communication skills explored by facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.
5. Examine the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN.

Research Questions

- 4- What is the level of competency displayed by online facilitators during teaching and learning activities in NOUN?
- 5- How effective are the facilitators in their communication skills during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN?
- 6- What is the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN?

Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant difference in the online facilitation skills displayed by male and female facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.

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Methodology

A survey research design was adopted for the study. Academic staff at the university headquarter in Abuja and students from the various centres within the Abuja metropolis formed the sample for the study. The facilitators at the headquarters were used for the study because they have access to the technical staff at the Learner Content Management System (LCMS) directorate, and the various facilities such as studio room, whiteboard and other sophisticated tools. Therefore, they have all that is required to respond to the items in the questionnaire. For a similar reason, learners at the various centres within the Abuja metropolis were used as respondents for the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents from both facilitators and learners. Owing to the nature of the institution (Open and Distance Learning) both facilitators and learners are not always available at the same time. Sometimes staff have official duties outside the headquarters and deliver lectures, and attend meetings from where they are through virtual means. For learners, owing to the flexibility of the programme; they do not have to come to the centre most times before they do what they need to do. In view of this, staff and students that were available at the time of study were used. Since it is not ethical to force people to participate in a study like this, among those available, only those who were willing eventually participated in the study. In all 205 people participated in the study (44 facilitators and 161 learners).

The research instrument used was titled Facilitators Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (FOFAQ) for facilitators and then for learners. Learners Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (LOFAQ) for learners required that they rate their facilitators' communication skills and class management in Online Facilitation on a Four-Points scale instrument labelled Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The facilitators self-assessed their level of competency in accessing and navigating through the online facilitation environment in order to help students learn. Their responses were to be made on a five-point likert scale instrument using; Extremely Competent (EC), Moderately Competent (MC), Somewhat Competent (SC), Slightly Competent (SLC), Not Competent (NC). The research instrument was validated by experts. Corrections made were effected before the instruments were administered to the sampled respondents. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The reliability index of the instrument for facilitators and learners were found to be 0.846 and 0.929 respectively; thus portraying a high level of internal consistency and as such the instruments were found usable for the study. The data gathered was analysed using frequency, percentages, means, standard deviation for the three research questions, while independent sample t-test analysis was used to test the only hypothesis that guided the study.

Results

Frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent sample t-test was used for testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1

What is the level of competency displayed by online facilitators during teaching and learning activities in NOUN?

Table 1: Level of Facilitators' Competency for Online Facilitation in NOUN

Level of competency of facilitators	NC	SLC	SC	MC	EC	Mean	St. Dev.
Facilitate and record the virtual class conversation.	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (6.8)	20 (45.5)	21 (47.7)	4.41	0.622
Create interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation.	2(4.5)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	22 (50.0)	16 (36.4)	4.14	0.930
Lead forum discussions.	1(2.3)	2 (4.5)	6 (13.6)	19 (43.2)	16 (36.4)	4.07	0.950
Lead chat forums.	1(2.3)	2 (4.5)	8 (18.2)	20 (45.5)	13 (29.5)	3.95	0.939
Set-up 'meet your facilitator page' on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	20 (45.5)	23 (52.3)	4.45	0.730
Create announcement on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	15 (34.1)	24(54.5)	4.39	0.841

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Prepare a lesson plan for online facilitation on the course page.	1(2.3)	1 (2.3)	1 (2.3)	20 (45.5)	21 (47.7)	4.34	0.834
Set up a virtual library on the course page.	2(4.5)	1 (2.3)	5 (11.4)	17 (38.6)	19 (43.2)	4.14	1.025
Create introductory videos on the course page.	1(2.3)	1 (2.3)	2 (4.5)	17 (38.6)	23(52.3)	4.36	0.865
Set up zoom online class on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	14 (31.8)	25(56.8)	4.41	0.844
Use whiteboard in the zoom class.	3(6.8)	8 (18.2)	5 (11.4)	20 (45.5)	8(18.2)	3.50	1.191
Create a discussion forum on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	6 (13.6)	12 (27.3)	25(56.8)	4.36	0.892

Percentages in parenthesis

KEY: NC – Not Competent; SLC – Slightly Competent; SC – Somewhat Competent; MC – Moderately Competent; EC – Extremely Competent

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 1 above shows the level of competency of facilitators in the identified skills required for online facilitation in the teaching and learning process in NOUN. More than half of the respondents accepted all twelve (12) items as true. Those who agreed and strongly agreed with each of the twelve (12) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the twelve (12) items are each above the 3.00 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement on a five-Likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequency and percentage analyses. Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; who are academic staff on the level of competency of facilitators in the identified online facilitation skills in NOUN, they agree that they are competent in the following identified technical skills required for online facilitation processes; Facilitation and recording of the virtual class conversation, creating interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation, leading forum discussions, leading chat forums, setting up ‘meet your facilitator page’ on the course page, creating announcement on the course page, preparing a lesson plan for online facilitation on the course page, setting up a virtual library on the course page, creating introductory videos on the course page, setting up zoom online class on the course page, using a whiteboard in the zoom class and creating a discussion forum on the course page.

Research Question 2

How effective are the facilitators in their communication skills during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN?

Table 2: Facilitators’ Communication Skills During Online Teaching and Learning Activities in NOUN

Level of agreement that facilitators possess the listed skills	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
The facilitator uses language appropriate for the students.	0(0.0)	2 (1.2)	95 (59.0)	64 (39.8)	3.39	0.513
The facilitator’s introduction of lesson is always interesting.	1(0.6)	8 (5.0)	102 (63.4)	50 (31.1)	3.25	0.570
The facilitator asks appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the students.	0(0.0)	56 (34.8)	71 (44.1)	34 (21.1)	2.86	0.737
The facilitator asks appropriate follow up questions to sustain student’s engagement in the course.	0(0.0)	10 (6.2)	106 (65.8)	45 (28.0)	3.22	0.544
Facilitator delivers instructions that are accurate, clear and concise.	0(0.0)	11 (6.8)	47 (29.2)	103 (64.0)	3.57	0.620
Facilitator summarises the lesson to enhance retention of the content learnt.	0(0.0)	9 (5.6)	98 (60.9)	54 (33.5)	3.28	0.561

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Percentages in parenthesis

KEY: SD – Strongly Disagree; D– Disagree; A – Agree; SA – Strongly Agree

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 2 above revealed the effectiveness of the facilitators in communicating with their learners during the online class as opined by their students. More than half of the respondents agreed with all the six (6) items. Those that agreed and strongly agreed with each of the six (6) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the six (6) items are each above the 2.50 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement on a four-Likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequencies and percentages analysis.

Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; the following statements on the performance of the facilitators in communicating with their students during the online class are acceptable; the facilitator uses language appropriate for the students, the facilitator’s introduction of lesson is always interesting, the facilitator asks appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the students, the facilitator asks appropriate follow up questions to sustain student’s engagement in the course, facilitator delivers instructions that are accurate, clear and concise, facilitator summarises the lesson to enhance retention of the content learnt.

Research Question 3

What is the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN?

Table 3: The Level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN

ITEM	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
The facilitator ensures sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions.	0(0.0)	15 (9.3)	73 (45.3)	73 (45.3)	3.36	0.648
The facilitator promotes confidence in their students.	1(0.6)	14 (8.7)	105 (65.2)	41 (25.5)	3.16	0.587
Facilitator collaborates with their students to ensure efficiency.	0(0.0)	17 (10.6)	106 (65.8)	38 (23.6)	3.13	0.572
The facilitator understands and consistently applies best techniques for starting the session.	0(0.0)	10 (6.2)	104 (64.6)	47 (29.2)	3.23	0.551
The facilitator understands and consistently applies best techniques for sustenance of student’s interest.	0(0.0)	12 (7.5)	109 (67.7)	40 (24.8)	3.17	0.543

Percentages in parenthesis

KEY: SD – Strongly Disagree; D– Disagree; A – Agree; SA – Strongly Agree

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 3 above showed the skills displayed by facilitators in NOUN. More than half of the respondents agreed with all five (5) items. Those that agreed and strongly agreed with each of the five (5) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the five (5) items are each above the 2.50 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement in a four-likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequency and percentages analysis.

Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; the following statements on the classroom management displayed by facilitators in NOUN are true; the facilitators ensure sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions, the facilitators promote confidence in their students, facilitators collaborate with their students to ensure efficiency, the facilitators understand and consistently apply best techniques for starting the session, the facilitators understand and consistently apply best techniques for sustenance of students’ interest.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the online facilitation skills displayed by male and female facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.

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Table 4: T-Test Analysis of Difference in Online Facilitation Skills Across Gender

GROUP	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Male	26	49.77	10.041	-0.689	42	0.495	NS
Female	18	51.61	6.289				

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 4 above presents the t-test comparison of online facilitation skills possessed by male and female facilitators. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in the online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed value that is more than the 0.05 benchmark. Since the sig-value of t-test comparison of means of two groups which is more than the 0.05 benchmark signifies a no significant difference in online facilitation skills possessed by male and female facilitators, it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff is accepted. The values of the mean online facilitation skills possessed by female academic staff is higher than that of their male counterparts. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it can therefore not be generalized. The difference observed might have occurred due to sampling error.

Discussion of Findings

The sampled facilitators are competent in using the twelve (12) identified tools for online facilitation. Some of these include; setting up a zoom class, recording, initiating and coordinating discussion forum, chat etc. This is encouraging. The high competency might be because of the regular trainings and accessible for online facilitation. At the beginning of every semester, facilitators are usually given refresher training. Technical staff are also allocated to faculties for consultations during the facilitation period. In addition, modern computers equipped with all the software needed, studio for recording, as well as internet access are accessible to facilitators at the headquarters. The training and follow up opportunities as well as the enabling facilities and resources must have contributed to the high rating of facilitators' competency in handling facilitation tools.

The areas the respondents displayed competencies include setting up a zoom class, recording, initiating and coordinating discussion forum, leading chat forum, creating announcement page, setting up zoom class for online lesson etc. All these contribute immensely to making the learning process learner-friendly and engaging. Findings from this study therefore agrees with the submission of Gustafon and Gibbs (2000) and Martin, Wang and Sandaf (2020) who emphasised the need for successful online facilitators to learn strategies to make the process learner-friendly and also devise ways of engaging learners sufficiently in the learning process. The findings of the study also agree with Richardson et al, (2015); Schinder & Burkholder, (2014) who opined that online facilitator or instructor must apply multiple strategies to facilitate learning and critical thinking skills. It also correlates with Rovai (2007) that online facilitation ought to improve student sense of community and Shea, Li & Pickett, (2006), that it should promote students' connectedness and learning. A number of scholars submitted that when facilitators are competent in the various identified skills required for online learning, students will be better engaged and it becomes easy for students to understand learning materials (Berge, 2008; Martin, Wang & Sadaf, 2014; Martin and Parker, 2014; Borup et al, 2015; Rose, 2009).

Learners while rating their facilitators both on communication and class management agreed that the facilitators did well in all the identified areas of both communication and class management. As it applies to competency in online facilitation skills, the same explanation of regular training, as well as availability and unrestricted accessibility to enabling facilities and resources is a possible explanation. Various scholars also agree that possession of these competencies by facilitators, will bring about satisfaction of students with the process and also encourage collaboration (Eskey and Schulte, 2010; Swan, 2001). However, the research showed that a particular item - "the facilitators ask appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the students", attracted a disagree of about 35.0%. The implication of this is that a sizeable number of the facilitators are weak in asking appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the learners.

The findings of this study agrees with the submission of Cakiroglu (2014) that there is a highly satisfactory percentage in terms of assessing communication between teachers and students in online classes. Mercer and Dornyei (2020), also corroborate this view that teachers ought to take different actions such as taking care of their talk, being careful about feedback to students, listening to learners, employing questions to engage students and rethinking classroom managements as managing relationships. Communication is one essential skill for classroom efficiency both in the face to face and online mode. Particularly in online facilitation, the learner and the facilitator in most cases are far apart, therefore, securing and sustaining the attention of the learner require effectiveness in communication. Halias, Ismail and Baharudin (2017) as well as Christen,

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Kelly, Fall and Snyder (2015) both summed it up that facilitation process cannot be effectively done without effective communication. And that students appreciate online instructors who are responsive to their needs, engage in frequent communication strategies, use visibility strategies and share personal information.

The areas of classroom management studied included; facilitators ensuring sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions, promoting confidence in their learners, collaborating with their students to ensure efficiency, understanding and consistently applying best techniques for starting the session and understanding and consistently applying best techniques for sustenance of learners' interest. The facilitators' high rating in classroom management as evident from the result can also be attributed to regular trainings and retraining as well as follow up monitoring from technical staff and experts. Findings from this study agrees with Sibanda (2021) in a study on private school teachers' classroom management in a virtual classroom. The result revealed that private high school teachers adopted diverse strategies to manage learners' behaviour in a virtual classroom. The result also indicated that teachers use strategies such as collaborative learning, they also prepare all the materials required according to the set scheme of work, plan the learning activities which are exciting and use interactive learner-centred approaches which engage learners all the time. Teachers who would manage learners' behaviour must actively engage them in meaningful and challenging educational experiences (Moore and Hansen, 2012).

Gender differences in the possession of identified online facilitation skills showed a difference that is not statistically significant. In this study however female participants had higher score. A closer look showed that the male's standard deviation was higher, meaning that their mean score in identified online facilitation skill may not be the true representation. Some men might have scored very high while some scored very low. The difference however is not significant and so not generalisable. The findings of this study however disagree with findings of some scholars (Shea, 2007; Ganji & Seizeihe, 2022; Martin, Yin & Mayall, 2006 and Seaman, 2009).

Conclusion

This study sought to assess the online facilitation teaching and learning processes among facilitators at the National Open University of Nigeria. Specifically, the level of competence, communication and online classroom management skills of online facilitators to carry out teaching and learning activities in NOUN were explored. Findings showed that the participants of the study displayed a high level of competence, communication and efficient classroom management skills were displayed by them during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN. Also, the difference in competence displayed by male and female facilitators was not statistically significant. Findings from this study showed that NOUN facilitators at the headquarters were highly competent in the identified skills; they were also rated by their learners to be highly effective in communication and classroom management. This suggests that, with enough and regular training and retraining, along with the availability of support staff as well as accessibility to enabling facilities and resources obtainable in NOUN and as enjoyed by the respondents; efficiency in online facilitation is attainable. However, many students particularly disagreed that "the facilitators ask appropriate starting questions that help to engage the students".

Recommendations

In view of the above, it is therefore recommended that:

1. The model of operation in NOUN be studied by other Universities for implementation in their institutions.
2. Provision of and accessibility to enabling facilities and resources and services of support personnel should be extended to staff outside the headquarters.
3. The Nigerian University Commission (NUC) should also collaborate with NOUN to ensure that pieces of training given to NOUN staff are passed down to other Universities.
4. Subsequent training of facilitators in NOUN should lay more emphasis on asking appropriate starting questions that help to engage the students.
5. All the recommendations above should be effected equally on both male and female facilitators since there is no difference in competencies manifested across genders.

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Assessment of Supports and Challenges of Rural-Urban Migration among Irrigation Farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State

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Abstract

This study investigated assessment on supports and challenges of rural-urban migration among irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State. Two research questions were formulated for the study. The design for this study was descriptive survey research. The population of the study was six thousand two hundred and eighty-seven (6,287) irrigation farmers in the study area, simple random sampling techniques were used to select the sample size of 361 respondents. Researcher developed questionnaire titled: Questionnaire on irrigation farming and reduction of rural-urban migration (QIFRRUM). The instrument for data collection was a 10 items questionnaire which was validated by research experts and tested with a reliability estimate of 0.68 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) (PPMC). The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The findings indicated among others that the support received by the irrigation farmers include water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, soil conditioners, and loan schemes; the challenges facing the irrigation farmers indicate inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, inability to access loan schemes, and inefficient extension services. It was concluded therefore that supports received by irrigation farmers improved socio-economic condition, thereby providing a means of their livelihood generally in the areas of the study to determine rural-urban migration. It is recommended among others things that: government at all levels federal, state, and local non-governmental organizations and other philanthropist should be providing continuous support to irrigation farmers to mitigate rural-urban migration. Support in the area of water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, and loan schemes.

Keyword: Support, Challenges, Rural-Urban Migration

Introduction

The practice of rural development has been a global phenomenon as well as an age-long intervention effort by governments, non-governmental organizations and philanthropic foundations. Rural development generally denotes the processes leading to sustainable improvement in the quality of life of rural people especially the poor (Singh, 2002). In most developing countries of the world, rural areas occupy more geographical space than urban centers. This is why most rural locations are predominantly agriculture-based. In other words, majority of the people living in the rural areas of most developing nations are practicing subsistence agriculture (farming) as a way of sustaining their livelihood (Abbas, 2016).

In many developing nations, there had been a rapid growth of urban populations more than that of rural population (Andersen, 2013). In Africa, for instance, it has been estimated that between 1990 and 2020 there had been added at least 500 million people to the existing urban population compared to the less than 200 million people in North America and Europe (USAID, 2002). Such rapid urban growth in these African countries, including Nigeria, started even before independence. Nigeria is a typical example of this rapid urban growth, where there had been a tremendous expansion of urban areas, resulting in rapid urbanization at the expense of rural location and leading to rural-urban migration (Ledant, 2023).

However, the phenomenon of people migrating to other areas in search of a better life is not a novel one because the nexus of migration either rural-urban or urban-urban with development or otherwise is a subject of debate (Getso & Haruna, 2021). Therefore, rural-urban migration results from the search for perceived or recalled opportunities as a result of rural urban inequality in wealth. This inequality is as a result of the imbalance in the provision of social amenities for communities. Research findings, over the years, show an overwhelming concentration of wealth, assets, purchasing capacity, economic activities and a variety of services in urban centers as well as the continued neglect and degradation of rural areas (Chukwuedozie, Ajaero and Onokala, 2013). This assumption can be buttressed based on the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2014) report, which shows that the internal disparity between rural and urban areas was still very high in Nigeria. It is interesting to note that rural-urban migration in post-colonial Nigeria was equally practiced because Erringe (2012) reported that the record from 1963 indicated that 80.7% of the National population resided in rural areas. But the proportion dropped to 70.13% in 1985, and 69% in 1990, as noted by Moughalu (1992). The number of people residing in rural areas continued to decline; like in 2006 53% resided in rural areas and 51.6% in 2022.

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Rural development is an interdisciplinary area of practice which aims at the improvement of the living conditions of rural dwellers. Rural development programmes are aimed at reducing poverty, providing jobs, improving income, imparting useful knowledge, attitude and skills and facilitating ultimate change among rural people. The phenomenon of rural-urban migration is an important feature of rural life that exposes rural youth to various hazards, inculcates dependency, breeds crimes and renders migrant families vulnerable to diseases, rape, hunger and insecurity.

The introduction of irrigation rural development programmes in the Kano North Senatorial District is intended to improve the livelihood and wellbeing of rural communities as well as serve as a means of reducing the trend of rural-urban migration prevailing in the area. In some Local Government Areas of the Kano North Senatorial District, such as Bagwai, Bichi, Danbatta, Dawakin Tofa, Gwarzo, Gabasawa, Kabo, Kunchi, Makoda, Rimin-Gado, Shanono, Tofa and Tsanyawa, irrigation agricultural activities are taking place and youth in the area are being employed in irrigation sites as laborers, marketers, transporters, seed multipliers, and so on. This seems to prevent them from migrating out because they have employment and business opportunities at home. However, these programmes and strategies implemented over the years impacted greatly on the reduction of rural-urban migration. Despite the significant research on a particular irrigation rural development there are may be a lack of understanding mechanism of irrigation rural development in reduction of rural-urban migration in Kano North, although much research has been done on irrigation rural development programmes, the exact mechanism that lead to the rural-urban migration are not yet fully understood and affects farmers to increased dependences on hired labour by rural households whose most productive members are lost to urban areas and courses labour shortage on large scale. This study therefore, intended to find out the supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration as well as challenges facing them in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of this study were to examine;

1. The supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State;
2. The challenges facing irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State;

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?
2. What are the challenges facing irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for the study. It is a design in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group (Akuezuilo, 2002). The population for this study comprised the entire Irrigation Farmers from the 13 Local Governments areas in Kano North Senatorial District. According to available statistics there are six thousand two hundred and eighty seven 6,287 (KNARDA 2020 Records). The totals of 361 Irrigation Farmers were selected as respondents for the study out of the total of 6,287 that include irrigation farmers and executive members. The selection was based on the suggestions of the Krejcie and Morgan (2006) table for determining the sample size from a given population. A simple random sampling technique was adopted to select the relevant sample of 361 for the study. In applying the procedure, the researcher utilized two different sampling approaches to select the samples for the study in two phases; purposive sampling procedure and proportionate sampling procedure.

The instruments of data collection were self-developed instruments titled Questionnaire on irrigation farming and reduction of rural-urban migration (QIFRRUM) by the researcher. The instrument has two sections A and B. Section A has respondent's demographic information while section B had 10 items on the research questions, in the form of modified 4-point likert scale. The answering pattern provided multiple options for the respondents to choose, as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), the questionnaires were scored on the scale of SA= 4, A= 3, D= 2 and SD= 1. Therefore, the decision rule is based on the scale that a mean of 2.50 and above is considered as Agreed and a mean of below 2.50 as Disagreed was designed to elicit information from the respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with the items. The instrument was validated by experts. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the test-retest

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method was used. The results obtained were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) (PPMC) and the reliability co-efficient of 0.68 obtained showed the instrument is reliable for use in this study.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

This research question was answered using frequency and percentages (%). Also, the average mean and standard deviation is presented in the following Table where N=361:

Table 1 Supports Received by Irrigation Farmers in Kano North Senatorial District.

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)			
Water pump machines and pipe connector fitting	164 (45.4%)	183 (50.7%)	14 (3.9%)	-	3.42 +3	0.566	Agree
Fertilizers	23 (6.4%)	225 (62.3%)	113 (31.3%)	-	3.25	0.561	Agree
Agro-chemicals; liming, acidifying agent and soil conditioners	108 (29.9%)	251 (69.5%)	2 (0.6%)	-	3.29	0.468	Agree
Provision of canal by government	121 (33.5%)	217 (60.1%)	23 (6.4%)	-	3.27	0.571	Agree
Provision of tractors for harrowing on free charge	-	-	198 (54.8%)	163 (45.2%)	1.55	0.498	Disagree
Seminars on strategies of irrigation farming systems	208 (57.6%)	153 (42.4%)	-	-	3.42	0.495	Agree
Providing of adequate water to irrigation farmers associations	140 (38.8%)	185 (51.2%)	36 (10%)	-	3.29	0.637	Agree
Provisions of store or aggregation centers to irrigation farmers Associations	126 (34.9%)	181 (50.1%)	44 (12.2%)	10 (2.8%)	3.17	0.744	Agree
Provisions of loan scheme to irrigation farmers	180 (49.9%)	179 (49.6%)	2 (0.6%)	-	3.49	0.512	Agree
Provisions of efficient management to irrigation farmers	145 (40.2%)	207 (57.3%)	9 (2.5%)	-	3.38	0.534	Agree

Field Survey, 2023

The results presented in Table 4.5 indicate ten variables as the support received by irrigation farmers towards the reduction of rural-urban migration in Kano North Senatorial District. All the ten (10) supports received by irrigation farmers presented to the respondents were responded to by the 361 samples. Thus, nine out of the ten items were agreed as the support received by irrigation farmers. An individual assessment of the supports received by the irrigation farmers shows that in Item 1, the highest frequency of 183 (50.7%) agreed that water pump machines and pipe connector fittings are some of the support with a mean score of 3.42 (SD=0.566). In Item 2, the highest frequency of 225(62.3%) agreed that fertilizers are some of the supports with a mean of 3.25(SD=0.561). In Item 3, the highest frequency of 251(69.5%) agreed that agro-chemicals, liming, acidifying agents and soil conditioners with a mean of 3.29 (SD=0.468). In Item 4, the highest frequency of 217(60.1%) agreed with the provision of canal by government with a mean of 3.27(SD=0.571). in Item 5, the highest frequency of 198 (54.8%) disagreed that the provision of tractors for harrowing on free charge. However, in Item 6, the highest frequency of 208 (57.6%) strongly

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agreed on the seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems (Mean=3.42, SD=0.495). In Item 7, the highest frequency of 185 (51.2%) agreed on providing adequate water to irrigation farmer associations with a mean of 3.29 (SD=0.637). In Item 8, the highest frequency of 181 (50.1%) agreed on the provisions of stores or aggregation centers to irrigation farmer Associations with a mean of 3.17(SD=0.744). In Item 9, the highest frequency of 180 (49.9%) strongly agreed on the provisions of loan scheme to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.49(SD=0.512). In Item 10, the highest frequency of 207 (57.3%) agreed on the provisions of efficient management to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.38(SD=0.534). Overall, the participants agreed that nine out of the ten (10) statements were the supports received by irrigation farmers for the reduction of rural-urban migration because all the nine-item mean scores are above the decision rule of 2.5.

Research Question 2

What are the challenges facing irrigation farmer's in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

This research question was answered using frequency and percentages (%). Also, the average mean and standard deviation is presented in the following Table where N=361:

Table 2: Challenges Facing Irrigation Farmers

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)			
Inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines	104 (28.8%)	243 (67.3%)	14 (3.9%)	-	3.25	0.515	Agree
Access to loan scheme to irrigation farmers	120 (33.2%)	223 (61.8%)	18 (5%)	-	3.28	0.551	Agree
Inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers	108 (29.9%)	245 (67.9%)	8 (2.2%)	-	3.28	0.495	Agree
Inefficient extension services	129 (35.7%)	202 (56%)	30 (8.3%)	-	3.27	0.605	Agree
Communication and adequate capacity building	153 (42.4%)	193 (53.5%)	13 (3.6%)	2 (0.6%)	3.38	0.584	Agree
Startup capital and irregular fuel supply	147 (40.7%)	208 (57.6%)	-	6 (1.7%)	3.37	0.579	Agree
Poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown	135 (37.4%)	187 (51.8%)	39 (10.8%)	-	3.27	0.642	Agree
Poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming	136 (37.7%)	175 (48.5%)	40 (11.1%)	10 (2.8%)	3.21	0.745	Agree
Poor effective monitoring of irrigation activities	183 (50.7%)	178 (49.3%)	-	-	3.51	0.501	Agree
High costs of inputs	146 (40.4%)	206 (57.1%)	9 (2.5%)	-	3.38	0.535	Agree

Field Survey, 2023

The results presented in Table 4.7 indicate ten variables as the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State. All the ten (10) challenges presented to the respondents were responded to by the 361 samples. Thus, all the ten items were agreed as the challenges facing the irrigation farmers. An individual assessment of the challenges indicated that in Item 1, the highest frequency of 243 (67.3%) agree that inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines is one of the challenges with a mean of 3.25 (SD=0.515). In Item 2, the highest frequency of 223 (61.8%) agreed about the inability to access loan schemes to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.28 (SD=0.551). In Item 3, the highest frequency of 245(67.9%) agreed on inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.28 (SD=0.495). In Item 4, the highest frequency of 202 (56%) agreed on inefficient extension services with a mean of 3.27 (SD=0.605). In Item 5, the highest frequency of 193 (53.5%) agreed on communication and adequate capacity building with a mean of 3.38 (SD=0.584). In Item 6, the highest frequency of 208 (57.6%) agreed on startup capital and irregular fuel supply with a mean of 3.37 (SD=0.579). In Item 7, the highest frequency of 187 (51.8%) agreed on poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown with a mean of 3.27 (SD=0.642). In Item 8, the highest frequency of 175 (48.5%) agreed on poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming with a mean of 3.21 (SD=0.745). In Item 9, the highest frequency of 183 (50.7%) strongly agreed on poor effective monitoring of irrigation

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activities with a mean of 3.51(SD=0.501). Lastly, in Item 10, the highest frequency of 206 (57.1%) agreed on high costs of inputs with a mean of 3.38 (SD=0.535). Overall, the participants agreed that all the ten (10) statements were the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District because all the mean score were above the decision rule of 2.5.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding revealed that the supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State are water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals, liming and acidifying agent and soil conditioners, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems and the provisions of stores, and of loan schemes. Accordingly, this finding is also inline and complements the respondents responses with the various irrigation farmers' leaders from others areas, towards improving irrigation rural development among community members as well as encouragement with a view to determine rural-urban migration among the rural communities in the study areas. The farmers highlighted the various supports received from Kano state government from 2016 to date as part of its effort under the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACS), disbursed N1 billion interest-free loans to over 4,000 members of 517 associations of irrigation farmers in the state to revitalize agriculture, empower farmers and ensure food security in the state and the country at large, (Premium Times, 2016).

The state government also supported various irrigation farmer associations with water pump machines and pipe connector fitting, the provision of canals, fertilizers, agro-chemical, tractors for harrowing on free loan, seminars on the strategies of irrigation system, providing aggregation centers, loan schemes to irrigation farmers and also of experiences to efficient management of irrigation farmers in order improve productivity towards irrigational rural development programmes. This is said to be an initiative out of the need to re-invent agriculture in the state, which is the key solution to the current economic recession and an opportunity for farmers to boost their productivity, income and standard of living. Awe (2013) examined the mobilization of domestic financial resources for agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Some of the financial resources the study identified included credit facilities from the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industries (NBCI) and credit provided by commercial and merchant banks. The results revealed that these facilities have a positive relationship with agricultural productivity.

Anyebe & Ikani (2015) who assessed agricultural credit on rural farmers in Nigeria through the administration of questionnaires found that credits to agriculture had sufficiently boosted productivity in the sector. The work is related to this research in the sense that the former explains how locally generated sources of finance affects productivity positively. However, Bhattacharya and Narayan (2015) showed the impact of formal credit in India, which is usually provided at subsidized interest rates. They found that formal credit increased income and agric-productivity and calculated that benefits exceeded the cost by at least 13 percent, using district level panel data. The work investigated how increased farmer income and productivity are subjected to subsidized-rate credits. Meaning, when loan is subsidized, there is every tendency for it to improve income and output. Therefore, if this is held as a trend, the marginal propensity of income and output will be much higher when the rate is declared zero or free. This is what this research intends to explore. Diagne and Zeller (2001) found in Malawi that rural banks, savings and cooperative society's priority in issuing loans to households with diversified asset portfolios and diversified incomes. Households do not consider interest rates an important factor while deciding to choose financial institution. Non-price attributes such as types of loan provided and restriction on their use as well as the non-financial services provided play an important role. The work discusses factors that qualify individuals for loan, which is very essential while designing a repayment mechanism. The irrigation farmers leaders revealed that in terms of loan many things attributed to a long delay in disbursement to irrigation farmers in the rural areas. Since most of the banks are located in cities, in some cases where a loan is approved, it arrives too late for it to fulfill the purpose for which it was intended.

Moreover, this is also supported with by the work of Akinleye, Akanni Oladoja (2005), who wrote on the appraisal of the agricultural credit guarantee scheme in Nigeria. They also found that the scheme failed in bringing about the desired productivity of the agricultural sector. Ike (2007) conducted his study on institutional loan recovery in Nigeria. He classified the problems of loan recovery into three: farmer related problems; structural problems and bank related problems. It was found out that even though there was a positive relationship between agricultural support and output, yet a significant percentage of farmers was illiterate, ignorant and misinterpret the objectives of the government in granting agricultural loans. Hence, loans were diverted to non-agricultural purposes and sometimes used for traditional ceremonies. This is also indicated that some farmers could not manage their projects due to over expansion, natural hazards and loan mismanagement. Structural problems relate to security, like supply and demand for funds and the interest rate structure. Loans are usually made against security for agricultural production. Most farmers do not have tangible security. They may have guarantors but the main disadvantage of pledging them as security is that in case of non-repayment; they may disappear, thereby failing to fulfill their loan obligations.

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The farmers highlighted some of the bank related problems to include: lending policies and procedures as well as the personnel capacity of the banks; some bank managers do not apply the principles of good lending while giving loans to farmers and, lastly, the problem of skilled and an adequate number of bank staff to formalize loans as well as the follow up process. The work has a relationship with this work, because it investigated the problems of loan recovery in Nigeria, which is also one of these research objectives. However, this research extended or further investigated the negative role interest rate play to the detriment of loan repayment in the study area. Moreover, issues relating to farmers' illiteracy vis-à-vis loan mismanagement will all be given special priority in order to expose them to the Islamic agricultural source of finance. This is consistent with the finding of Kareem (2013) who revealed that foreign direct investment: commercial bank loan, interest rate and food import value, had a positive relationship with agricultural output. This finding is inconsistent with Adetiloye (2012) on agricultural financing in Nigeria in that credit to the agricultural sector is significant but noted that credit supply had not been growing in relation to the economy. The finding also agreed with that of Tasie Offor (2013) about government providing support to rural farmers as credit supply in River state, Nigeria and that the credit programme had contributed significantly to farm output and income.

In the same vein, Chisasa Makina (2015) opined that although credit was not well provided to rural farmers, credit supply had a positive and significant impact on agricultural output in the long run. This finding further confirms the recent development by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) that introduced Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP). The Program which was launched by President Muhammad Buhari (GCFR) on November 17, 2015 was intended to create a linkage between anchor companies involved in the processing and small holder farmers (SHFs) of the required key agricultural commodities. The program thrust of the ABP is the provision of farm inputs in kind and cash (for farm labor) to small holder farmers to boost the production of these commodities, stabilize inputs supply to agro-processors and address the country's negative balance of payments on food. At harvest, the SHF supplies his/her produce to the Agro-processor (Anchor) who pays the cash equivalent to the farmer's account. The loan shall be targeted at smallholder farmers engaged in the production of identified commodities across the country.

The second finding of this study indicates that, the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State and shows that the inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, in-ability to access loan scheme to irrigation farmers, inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers, inefficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building, startup capital and irregular fuel supply, poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown, poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming, poor effective monitoring of irrigation activities and high costs of inputs were the challenges. The implication of this is that through appropriate rural development programme by government, rural-urban migration can be curtailed, thereby making rural inhabitants economically self-reliant through irrigation rural development infrastructures. The findings also revealed that Government needs to do more to stem rural-urban migration. Government must intensify rural development in Nigeria as expected by majority of the rural populace. People in rural areas have no need to migrate to urban centers if basic social amenities and other variables to make them comfortable are provided. This finding is consistent with that of Oravee (2015), who reported that the challenges of inadequate funding of the river basins could be traced back to 1989, which was instrumental to discontinuing of direct involvement in farming activities by some of the River Basins and Rural Development Authorities consequently leading to the in-effectiveness of the scheme.

The attitudes and interests of the participating farmers have a larger role to play when it comes to Nigeria's irrigation farming. The government and its agencies in charge of irrigation systems need to be proactive in discharging their duties and correspondingly provide a platform to encourage and sensitize farmers on the need to engage in irrigation farming rather than on only the rain-fed. In addition, farmers are not interested in the operation and maintenance of the large-scale irrigation facilities. Furthermore, the irrigation farmers leaders revealed that the major constraints in utilizing irrigation potential through large-scale schemes include: Unwieldy functions of the RBDAs resulting in dilution of their functions relating to efficient management of irrigation projects, Scarcity of experienced, dedicated, motivated and technically sound manpower ready to implement the project on a sustainable basis, results in sub-optimal managed projects, Lack of direction and clear strategy on the development of irrigation by the government, Shortage, and at times the delayed release of finances by the government, Unwillingness of small farmers (less-powerfulness) to participate in the scheme as they continue to doubt the reliability and timeliness of irrigation water to them at their tail-end plots, lack of enough fertilizers, engines and agro-chemicals, Inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers, lack of direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming, canal erosion and land degradation in the field, lack of adequate startup capital and irregular fuel supply, lack of effective monitoring and improper maintenance. These farmers are expected to constitute the bulk of the beneficiaries.

Similarly, Adekunle (2015) found out that poor knowledge of irrigation techniques among farmers was one of the factors affecting their participation enlarge-scale irrigation scheme. Those that manage to participate are not equipped with the

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requisite knowledge for the operations and maintenance of facilities. This problem is one of the current challenges being faced by the large-scale irrigation scheme in Nigeria. Population in cities and sub-urban areas in developing countries, including Nigeria, is expected to increase from 1.9 billion in 2000 to 3.9 billion in 2030. This is principally attributed to rural to urban migration, which is consequent upon dichotomous planning and development many developing countries adopted. This subsequently results in the rural deprived and the urban endowed that translates into improved amenities and economic opportunities in urban centres than rural areas (Abdullahi, Shaibu-Imodagbe, Mohammed, Sa'id & Idris, 2015).

Conclusion

The study revealed the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State are water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals, liming and acidifying agent and soil conditioners, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems and the provisions of stores, and of loan schemes. Therefore, the supports received by irrigation farmers improved socio-economic condition, thereby providing a means of their livelihood generally in the areas of the study to determine rural-urban migration that is already present and includes access to increased employment opportunity of rural dwellers, boosting income levels, irrigation farming reduces the level of poverty among the rural dwellers, improves their food security of the rural dwellers, improves their general living conditions and also promotes self-reliance and independence among the community members. The result also from the data analyses revealed that irrigation rural development has immensely contributed to the reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District.

Similarly, the findings on the challenges revealed that, inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, inability to access loan schemes, inadequate technical advice, inefficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building and high cost of inputs. Thus, it can be concluded that despite the above challenges, irrigational rural development programmes enhance communities members to improve their skills, socio-economic status and employment opportunities thereby reduction rural-urban migration in order to stay in their communities.

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Recommendations

1. Government at all levels (Federal, State, and Local) Non-governmental organizations and other philanthropist should be providing continuous support to irrigation farmers to mitigate rural-urban migration. Support in the area of water pump machines and pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals; liming, acidifying agents and soil conditioners, the provision of canal by government, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems, providing adequate water, store or aggregation centers, loan schemes, efficient management, is needed by irrigation farmers for the reduction of rural-urban migration.
2. Kano State Government should intensify efforts in the provision of adequate fertilizers and water pump machines, access to loan schemes to irrigation farmers, adequate technical advice and the provision of efficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building in order to determine the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State Nigeria.

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Business Educators' Awareness of Technology Enhanced Resources for Teaching and Learning in Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research study aims to investigate the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in colleges of education in Delta State, Nigeria. To accomplish this, three research questions were formulated and answered, while three corresponding hypotheses guided the study were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, and the target population was 75 business educators in Delta State Colleges of Education. All 75 Business educators constitute the sample size since the total population is of manageable size. An instrument titled "Awareness of Technology-Enhanced Resources among Business Educators (ATERBEQ), validated by a business education expert was employed for data gathering. The correlation coefficient of the instrument was 0.80. The results showed that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their academic activities. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing TERs among business education lecturers at Delta State College of Education. The study also found a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TERs among business educators. The study suggests, among other things, that colleges of education should encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between business educators in Delta State to enhance the effective use of technology-enhanced teaching methods collectively.

Keyword: Awareness, Business Educators, Technology Enhance Resources (TERs), Teaching, College of Education

Introduction

The integration of technology in education is a crucial element of modern-day learning. It enhances traditional teaching methods, making education more engaging, effective, and accessible, Smith, and Johnson, (2021). Therefore, it is fundamental to understand how aware and accepting educators are of technology-enhanced teaching resources. In business education, technological integration is crucial to prepare students for a constantly changing and technology-based workforce by providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge. However, many business educators are unsure of how to integrate technology into their instructional delivery. Liadi, Adedapo, and Ibrahim, (2022), and therefore, it is vital to investigate the extent to which they use technology-enhanced teaching resources.

Technology Enhanced Resources (TERs) are modern tools that support, enhance, and even transform teaching practices both inside and outside the classroom, Liadi, and Bolupe, (2021). They include digital technologies such as web-based applications, computer devices, and online teaching, among others. TERs facilitate and enhance student learning in the classroom. Technology-enhanced resources can have a significant impact on the work of business educators. They provide a wide range of benefits such as easy access to information, increased student interest in learning, better retention of information, and improved presentation of information. Additionally, TERs facilitate interactive teaching and make knowledge sharing easier. Before requiring the use of TERs, business educators need to be aware of their existence. Awareness leads to a shift in teaching behavior and helps develop positive attitudes toward instructional technologies. It is important to consider whether business educators are aware of its existence.

Awareness refers to the ability to perceive, feel, or be conscious of events, objects, thoughts, emotions, or sensory patterns. It also involves knowing specific information that can be demonstrated through particular behavior (Akpojotor, 2016).

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Similarly, Oni and Ahiauzu (2016) also indicated that 'Awareness' is knowledge about something that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at present based on information or experience. In the context of this paper, awareness of TERs by business educators means having knowledge of the existing TERs opportunities and utilizing them to enhance effective and efficient instructional delivery. Whereas experience plays a pivotal role in the adoption of technology, Experience is the amount of time an individual spends being involved in something. According to a study by Kehinde, Aderibigbe, and Evans (2019) on the adoption of health information technology among healthcare workers in Thailand, experience has a moderating effect on the behavioral intention to use the technology, which implies that Business educators may intend to use TERs in their teaching if they have prior knowledge of technology adoption (Sadi & Haruna, 2020).

Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the level of awareness of TERs among business educators in Colleges of Education. Colleges of Education play an essential role in providing a strong foundation for teacher training and professional development. Business educators within these colleges have a significant impact on shaping the future of education in Nigeria. However, their effectiveness is dependent on their ability to embrace and leverage technology. Understanding the current level of awareness and adoption of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State is essential to inform educational policies and practices.

Business educators play a critical role in shaping the knowledge and skills of future professionals and leaders. While there is a growing trend towards digital learning environments and the potential for technology to enhance pedagogy, many academic institutions in Nigeria lack the necessary resources to incorporate ICT into their teaching practices Liadi (2015). As a result, the Federal Ministry of Education launched an ICT-driven project called "School Net" (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013) to provide computers to all schools in Nigeria to help them become more proficient in communication. However, many academic institutions in the country lack the requirements to use ICT in their teaching practices, Liadi (2015). As a result, they are unable to make an impact on teaching methods across the nation, and there remains a significant gap in the utilization of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in the Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria. Onasanya (2010). The limited awareness and utilization of technology tools and resources for teaching may hinder the effective integration of innovative teaching methodologies, potentially hindering the enhancement of student's learning experience and the development of essential digital competencies (Sadi & Haruna, 2020). However, research has shown that business educators' preparedness to harness technology-enhanced resources in the teaching and learning process effectively remains underexplored (Egbri, 2010). There seem to be disparities in access to technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State. The level of awareness can inform the development of targeted professional development programs that cater to the specific needs and gaps in business educators' technological competencies. Therefore, it is empirically essential to investigate business educators' awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching in Delta State Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate business educators' awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching in Delta State Colleges of Education. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. the level of awareness of business educators about technology-enhance teaching resources and teaching experience in the College of Education in Delta State.
2. the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among business educators in Delta State
3. the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business educators in the College of Education in Delta State?
2. What is the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State?
3. What is the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of technology-enhanced teaching resources.

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2. There is no significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.
3. There is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State Colleges of Education,

Methodology

This study investigates the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in Delta State, a descriptive survey research design adopted for the study. The sample of the study was taken from a census of lecturers in two colleges of education that offer business education programs, resulting in a total of 75 lecturers from Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) Asaba, and College of Education, Agbor. To collect data, a structured questionnaire called "Awareness of Technology-Enhanced Resources among Business Educators (ATERBEQ)" was used. It consisted of two sections: Section A gathered demographic variables of the respondents, such as institution/colleges and working experience, while Section B contained 21 statements related to applying technology-enhanced resources (TERs) that were structured on a 5-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of Business Education and one expert in Educational Foundations (Evaluation and Measurement unit). The instrument was administered to 20 business educators of the Department of Business Education, Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, who were not part of the final study but had the same parameters as the colleges of study. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha statistic, which yielded a value of $r=0.80$.

The researcher personally administered copies of the questionnaire to the respondents, with the help of two research assistants. Out of 85 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 75 were retrieved and used for data analysis. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, and the t-test and correlation analysis were used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. If the p-value was less than the alpha value of 0.05, the hypothesis was rejected, but if it was greater or equal to the alpha value, the hypothesis was accepted.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business educators in the College of Education in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean, and Standard Deviation on the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching Resources and teaching experience. (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	I am aware that there are numerous technology-enhanced teaching resources accessible to educators.	3.43	.72	Agreed
2.	I keep up to date with recent technological tools to enhance my teaching.	3.29	.59	Agreed
3.	I am well-versed in the advantages of using technology in the classroom.	3.11	.76	Agreed
4.	I make a conscious effort to pursue training and professional development opportunities that are relevant to the utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources.	3.43	.72	Agreed
5.	I am confident in my ability to incorporate technology into teaching.	3.40	.66	Agreed
6.	I use technology-enhanced teaching resources, such as e-learning platforms and multimedia, in my teaching.	3.11	.76	Agreed
7.	I believe that technology-enhanced teaching resources can enhance the educational experience for students.	3.40	.66	Agreed
Aggregate		3.31	0.70	Agreed

Note. SD = standard deviation

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The data presented in Table 1 depicts the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) for teaching among business educators in colleges of education located in Delta State. The responses indicate that the mean level of awareness of TERs varied from 3.11 to 3.43 with standard deviation values varying from 0.66 to 0.76. The overall mean and standard deviation were calculated to be 3.31 and 0.70, respectively. All measures had a standard deviation below one, which indicates that the awareness level of TERs exceeds the set criterion aggregate mean score of 3.00 for high extents. Thus, it can be concluded that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their teaching experience.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent of TERs utilization by business educators in their instructional practices (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
8.	How frequently do you integrate technology-enhanced teaching resources, such as multimedia presentations or online platforms, into your lessons?	3.43	.72	VF
9.	How often do you use e-learning platforms or digital resources for assignments, quizzes, or assessments in your courses?	3.36	.63	VF
10.	How frequently do you incorporate interactive technologies, such as educational apps or online simulations, in your teaching to enhance student engagement?	2.92	.71	VF
11.	How often do you encourage your students to use online research and resources as part of their assignments or projects?	3.01	.76	VF
12.	How frequently do you conduct virtual discussions or online forums to facilitate peer interaction and collaborative learning?	3.40	.66	VF
13.	How often do you employ technology-enhanced teaching resources to provide personalized feedback to your students, such as through online grading and feedback systems?	2.92	.75	VF
14.	How often do you participate in online professional communities, webinars, or conferences to stay updated on innovative teaching resources and methods?	2.88	.73	VF
Aggregate		3.13	0.71	VF

Note. SD = standard deviation VF = Very Frequent

Table 2 revealed data on the extent to which business educators in Delta States utilize technology-enhanced teaching resources in their instructional practices. The mean responses on the frequency of utilizing TERs varied from 2.88 to 3.43, with standard deviation values varying from .66 to .76. The aggregate mean and standard deviation were 3.13 and .71, separately. All measures had a standard deviation below one (1), indicating that business educators frequently utilized TERs in their instructional practices. This suggests that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice.

Research Question 3

What is the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the differences in awareness and utilization of TERs for teaching (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
15.	I believe that business educators in Delta State possess the same level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	3.43	.72	Agreed

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S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
16.	I believe that business educators at Delta State are more proactive in utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources in their teaching.	3.40	.66	Agreed
17.	There is no significant difference in the level of technological infrastructure and support available to educators in Delta State.	3.11	.76	Agreed
18.	Educational policies and initiatives in Delta State are more conducive to the adoption of technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	3.43	.72	Agreed
19.	The perceived level of institutional leadership support for technology integration in Delta State is the same.	3.37	.67	Agreed
20.	Business educators in Delta State have similar access to training and professional development opportunities related to technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	2.93	.70	Agreed
21.	A significant difference exists in the cultural or socio-economic factors that may impact the utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources between Delta State.	3.03	.73	Agreed
Aggregate		3.24	0.71	Agreed

Note. SD = standard deviation

Table 3 presents data on the differences in awareness and utilization of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) among business educators in Delta States. The mean responses on the awareness and utilization of TERs varied from 2.93 to 3.43, with standard deviation values varying from 0.66 to 0.73. The aggregate mean and standard deviation were 3.24 and 0.71, respectively. All measures had a standard deviation below 1, indicating no significant differences in the responses on awareness and utilization of TERs for teaching. Therefore, it can be inferred that there is no distinction in awareness and adoption of TERs between business educators in Delta State.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of technology-enhanced teaching resources.

Table 4: Correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of TERs for teaching.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	R	P
Working Experience	75	1.5200	.50296	.313**	.006
TERs Utilization	75	22.6933	2.74587		

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

		Correlations	
		Teaching Experience	TERs Utilization
Teaching Experience	Pearson Correlation	1	.313**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006
TERs Utilization	Pearson Correlation	.313**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	
		N	75
		75	75

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 demonstrates the result of the Pearson product-moment correlation analysis between the teaching experience of business educators and their usage of TERs for teaching. The analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation that was statistically significant. Specifically, the correlation table indicated that there was a Moderate positive and statistically

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significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TER among business educators at a 0.05 level of significance ($r = 313^{**}$, $p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Table 5: The t-test difference in the level of awareness of TERs and Teaching Experience

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p	Decision
Level of Awareness	75	23.1600	2.80463	74	70.610	.000	Significant
Teaching Experience	75	1.5200	.50296				

Note. SD = standard deviation.

In Table 5, the mean responses of Delta business educators were compared between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources (TERs) and the Teaching Experience. The results showed that the Level of awareness had a higher mean response ($M = 23.16$) than the Teaching experience ($M = 1.52$), with a mean difference of 21.64. However, since both mean scores were significantly different from the aggregate mean, the responses indicated differences in the level of awareness of TERs for teaching and teaching experience. The table also revealed that there was no notable distinction ($t = 70.610$, $df = 74$, $p > .05$) between the level of awareness of TERs for teaching, and Teaching Experience since the p-value less the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State College of Education,

Table 6: The t-test difference in the frequency of utilization of TERs for Teaching among business education Lecturers in in Delta State Colleges of Education

Variable	Colleges	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p	Decision
Frequency of Utilization of TERs for Teaching	Asaba	45	21.8000	2.85721	73	.486	.628	Not Significant
	Agbor	30	22.1000	2.20266				

Note. SD = standard deviation.

In Table 6, the mean responses for Asaba and Agbor business educators were compared regarding differences in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources (TERs). The results showed that Agbor Business educators had a slightly higher mean response ($M = 22.10$) than Asaba Business educators ($M = 21.80$), with a mean difference of 0.30. However, since both mean scores were not significantly different from the aggregate mean, the responses indicated only slight differences in the frequency of TER utilization for teaching. The table also revealed that there was no notable distinction ($t = .486$, $df = 73$, $p > .05$) between Asaba and Agbor Business educators regarding the utilization of TERs for teaching, as the p-value exceeded the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State College of Education,

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of the study was to examine the awareness of Business Educators in Delta State Colleges of Education regarding technology-enhanced resources for teaching. The first research question shows that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their academic activities. All seven items on the TERs questionnaire revealed a mean score above the benchmark average, indicating that Business educators have a high level of

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awareness of TERs for teaching in Delta State. This study is consistent with that of Ementa and Ile (2016), who reported that business educators in tertiary institutions in Southeast Nigeria were aware of Web 2.0 to a high extent. Similarly, this study is in agreement with that of Ubulom and Ogwunte (2017) who opined that business education lecturers in Rivers State tertiary institutions are aware of web-based instructional technology and that they have knowledge of various aspects of web base technology

The results of the second research question indicate that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice. This finding is in contrast to the report by Liadi, Adedapo, and Ibrahim (2022), which suggests that business educators in tertiary institutions in Edo and Delta States do not use TBIR for their instructional delivery. Furthermore, the study's findings differ from those of Fakomogbon, Olanrewaju, and Soetan (2015), who reported that lecturers use instructional media less frequently.

The findings of the third research question indicate that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice. However, there is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education lecturers in Delta State College of Education supported by the result of the third hypothesis as shown in Table 6. Similarly, there was a Moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TER among business educators. Finally, the result of the second hypothesis also revealed that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Conclusion

The study aimed to investigate the level of awareness and utilization of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) for teaching among Business Educators in Delta State Colleges of Education. The findings revealed that these educators are highly aware of TERs and use them frequently in their instructional practice. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing TERs among business education lecturers at Delta State College of Education. The study also found a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TERs among business educators. Thus, it can be inferred that there is no distinction in awareness and adoption of TERs between business educators in Delta State. The study concluded that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of TERs and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding information and the results of this study, the following recommendations deemed necessary were proffered:

1. Institutional management should allocate resources, provide training, and establish clear expectations of technology integration. This can be achieved by offering targeted professional development through workshops and mentorship programs that can help boost educators' confidence in using technology.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of technology-enhanced teaching, institutional management should establish an ongoing feedback mechanism. This can be accomplished by conducting regular surveys and focus groups with business educators to collect feedback on their experiences.
3. To promote the effective use of technology-enhanced teaching methods, colleges of education should encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between business educators in Delta States
4. Finally, it is recommended that a digital platform or network be established for ongoing communication and resource sharing between educators. This will further facilitate knowledge sharing and help Business educators stay up to date with the latest technology-enhanced teaching methods.

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Comparative Analysis between Marital Counselling and Family Planning among Married Women in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State

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Abstract

This study analysis comparatively, the relationships between marital counselling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, hence, a survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research hypotheses were formulated and the results of the study showed that there was positive relationship between acceptance of family planning $r = .155$, $P < .005$ and family planning $t(8) = 1.502$, < 0.05). Family planning methods would include every measure that can be taken so as to give a couple their required freedom to determine when they want to have their children and what the time gap should be if planning more than one child. It was concluded that marriage counselling is appropriate for all married women as this allows for appropriate family planning. It was recommended that family counselling should be made compulsory for intending couple in Nigeria as this will help reduce the incidence of unplanned pregnancy and premature death among children.

Keyword: Counselling, Family planning, Marriage, Married women

Introduction

The institution of marriage allows a man and a woman to join a family. It is a committed partnership when a man and a woman are accepted as parents by society. Hindu marriage is considered the sacred fulfilment of religious obligations (Naylor, 2014). Marriage is viewed less as a relationship between two young people and more as a union between two joint families. According to the psychological framework, getting married opens the door to having a close, personal relationship with someone who is the other sex. The marital life quality of couples is determined by their interactions and marital relationship. To lessen marital discord, marriage counselling offers a wide range of technical solutions (Siji & Rekha, 2018). Marriage counselling typically focuses on solving the current issues that are presenting, offers emotional support to the spouses, and increases their optimism and sense of self-worth. One form of psychotherapy that married couples or long-term partners can use to address issues in their relationship is marriage counselling. Usually, two persons meet for therapy to talk about particular concerns (Siji & Rekha, 2018).

Based on psychotherapy and family systems, marriage counselling aims to comprehend the symptoms of its clients and how their interactions lead to marital issues. Problems in the relationship can usually be resolved in a few sessions of short-term therapy (Haruna & Gurjiya, 2022). Counsellors for marriages typically inquire about the roles, norms, objectives, and beliefs of the couple (Siji & Rekha, 2018). Therapy frequently starts with the couple discussing the positive and negative elements of their relationship. Following that, the marriage counsellor works with the couple to assist them see that, most of

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the time, both parties are responsible for relationship issues. Once this is realised, the two can work together to modify their interactions in order to resolve issues. It could be suggested that the partners draft a contract in which each one outlines the conduct they plan to uphold. It is not necessary for two people to be married in order for them to seek marriage counselling. Help with behavioural challenges, relationship problems, or mental or emotional disorders is available to anyone looking to enhance their relationship. Premarital therapy is a service provided by marriage counsellors to help couples identify possible trouble areas before they get married. In this study, "marriage counselling" refers exclusively to counselling after marriage.

Young adults have exceptional physical functioning, vitality, and health. Young adults have not yet experienced the physical degeneration that comes with ageing, such as wrinkles, weakening body systems, and diminished heart and lung function. They are at their peak in terms of strength, coordination, reaction time, senses (taste, smell, touch, hearing, etc.), fine motor skills, and sexual response. Furthermore, young men and women alike reap the rewards of society's emphasis on youth. Generally speaking, they have an alluring appearance, sensual appeal, and allure. All or most of the hair, well-defined muscles, and good skin can be found in young men. A tiny waist, toned legs, thighs, and buttocks, and soft, supple skin are common characteristics of young women. The idea that older women are *passé* while older men are respected has been the fundamental cause of the double standard of ageing that neither gender has really experienced until recently. With their youthful beauty, excellent health, and boundless vitality, young adults fantasise and plan. Many adults in their 20s and 30s have a long list of goals they hope to achieve, ranging from becoming a billionaire before the age of 30 to completing graduate school and starting a family. Nothing appears difficult when you're a young adult; everything is achievable if you have the correct mindset, enough perseverance, and energy. Early in life, a person's main concerns are learning how to share intimacy, forming connections, and discovering intimate love (Camba, 2015).

Marital Satisfaction: The Impact of Premarital and Couples Counselling was the subject of a 2017 study by Mrozek & Mitchell. This study looked at the relationship between premarital and marital counselling and couples' marital satisfaction. The results revealed a pattern indicating that those who participated in premarital counselling reported higher levels of marital satisfaction than those who did not. In a research on the impact of a psycho-communicative-educational intervention on marriage, Teal (2018) evaluated the couples who were transitioning to motherhood one year after the intervention. In comparison to a control group, the results indicated that the psycho-communicative-educational preventive intervention was generally more successful for wife and husband marital quality, postpartum depression, and for the husband and wife's antagonistic behaviour as seen on the marriage dispute videotapes.

Mature psychological equilibrium and maturity are necessary for marriage, a lifelong institution, to handle the myriad obstacles that may arise (Adzovie Dabone, 2021). There are various procedures that must be followed when a man and a woman decide to start a family; these procedures vary depending on the tribe and culture. Pre-marital counselling, on the other hand, is thought to be one of the greatest practices since it helps prospective couples better comprehend the school they are going to be admitted to. In the past, premarital counselling gained popularity in the 20th century and has continued to grow in popularity among elites. According to Naylor (2014), premarital counselling refers to the services that licensed professionals provide to those who are considering or have expressed a desire to enter into a marriage. This means that premarital counselling has a significant role in influencing marriage success.

An estimated 536,000 women and girls worldwide pass away from pregnancy-related causes each year; that is one death per minute (World Health Organization, 2013). If nothing had been done, there's a chance the number would have skyrocketed. More than 99 percent of maternal deaths happen in underdeveloped nations, with Sub-Saharan Africa accounting for over half of these deaths. Sub-Saharan African women actually have a higher chance of dying during childbirth than women in any other part of the world. This is particularly true for African women between the ages of 15 and 19, for whom giving birth is the primary cause of death. Moreover, up to 20 million girls and women are thought to die each year in the world. Endure chronic illness while managing to survive childbirth, a condition known as maternal morbidities.

Maternal deaths during pregnancy, childbirth, or the postpartum period are caused by a variety of reasons. The majority of these issues arise from the pregnancy itself, and some happen when an underlying illness has gotten worse during pregnancy. Infections (also primarily soon after birth), hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (eclampsia), severe bleeding (mostly postpartum), and obstructed labour are the four main deaths (United Nations Children's Fund (2007). 15 Maternal deaths from complications following an unsafe abortion account for 13% of cases. Approximately 80% of maternal fatalities worldwide are caused by these direct factors. Thus, it can be argued categorically that illnesses like malaria, anaemia, and HIV that worsen or complicate pregnancy are among the indirect causes of maternal death (20%). Inadequate prenatal care and poor health at conception are some reasons why women die during pregnancy rather than having a healthy pregnancy and healthy offspring.

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The majority of women in Nigeria do not have complete access to maternal healthcare, despite several developed and developing nations having made progress in this area. This is because, among other reasons, there is insufficient information about health care availability, personnel shortages, or lack of availability. Because most traditional forms of delivery have long been valued in Southwest Nigeria, most women, particularly those living in rural areas, are reluctant to use health care facilities, despite the significant risks associated with doing so. Inadequate data hinders government organizations in charge of providing significant health care from carrying out projects in the most efficient manner, and barriers to access and affordability keep women from taking advantage of the resources that are available. It is undeniable that in recent years, women's access to prenatal, postpartum, and post-delivery health care has improved, despite the fact that cost was a contributing factor in this lack of access in the past. This was created to guarantee that women's and children's mortality rates are as low as possible.

It is possible to view family planning as a way to prevent maternal illnesses and mortality. When a couple plans their family, they talk about when and how many kids they can have in order to provide the best possible care for the child—financially, mentally, and socially. Although birth control and contraception are frequently associated with family planning, family planning is potentially much more than that. Every step that may be done to grant a couple the necessary flexibility to choose when they want to have children and how long to wait between them, if they are planning more than one, is included in family planning strategies. Deciding how many children to have and when to have them is the goal of family planning. This probably has to do with when pregnancies occur and how far apart babies are born. The World Health Organization (2013) states that in order to lower the dangers to the mother and child, a minimum of 24 months should elapse before attempting another pregnancy. If a woman engages in sexual activity after giving birth and does not nurse exclusively, she may become pregnant a few weeks later. For this reason, it is important to talk about this with a counsellor or healthcare professional who can provide expert direction towards appropriate spacing and a happy family.

In Akure South Local Government, there are not enough comprehensive marital counselling programmes designed to meet the unique requirements and difficulties married women encounter. This divide could impede couples' ability to resolve conflicts, communicate effectively, and enjoy a happy marriage. Access to reliable information and high-quality family planning services may be impeded for married women residing in the area. Low use of family planning techniques may be caused by a number of factors, including cultural attitudes, ignorance, and a lack of access to quality healthcare. Misconceptions about contraceptive methods and the social stigma associated with family planning may prevent married women from making educated decisions regarding their reproductive health. It is essential to address these myths by implementing focused education and awareness initiatives. The impact of married women's decisions about family planning in Akure on approval from their spouses The South Local Government presents a major obstacle. A spouse's lack of support or participation in family planning conversations may restrict a woman's ability to make decisions about her reproductive health. Investigating the region's teenage population's knowledge and use of contraception is necessary. Adolescent reproductive health outcomes may be impacted by elements like parental supervision, educational initiatives, and availability to contraceptive services. Through focused interventions, policy modifications, and community involvement, stakeholders can improve married women's reproductive health outcomes and general well-being in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The study aims to compare and analyze the relationship between marital counseling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study worked on the following objectives:

1. Investigate the relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria;
2. Examine the implications of marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria and
3. Investigate family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study therefore raised three (3) research questions for the purpose of achieving this work

1. What is the relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Ondo Stat?
2. What are the families planning methods mostly adopted by married women in Ondo State?
3. What are the discrepancies between women exposed to family planning and those that are not exposed to in Ondo State?

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Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria
2. There will be no significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria
3. Investigate family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design of the correlational type. This method was used to gather the opinions of respondents on the influence of marital counselling on the acceptance of family planning by married women. The population used for this study comprised all married women in the Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size for this study was one hundred (100) married women, drawn randomly from the public. A simple random sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. The age range of the samples used for the study was between twenty and sixty years of age. The adapted version of the Couple Therapy Questionnaire was used in the study. This instrument was developed by Shull (2000). The original version of the instrument was used to elicit information from clients who are still in the process of getting married. The instrument has a 0.087 alpha beta coefficient and, as such, was considered reliable for the purpose of the study. Hence, the adapted version was used to elicit information from married individuals. The researcher met each of the participants. The purpose of the research was adequately explained to the participants, and each participant was assured of the utmost confidentiality of the information supplied. Therefore, the questionnaires were administered to the participants, and at the end of the exercise, the questionnaires were retrieved for data analysis. The collected data were analysed using Pearson product-movement correlation and multiple regression analysis.

Results

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Table 1 reveals that there is a significant positive relationship between acceptability of family planning and marital counselling among women. Marital counselling correlates ($r = 0.155, p < .001$), and family planning ($r = 0.155, p < .001$). This implies that the level of family planning acceptability can be traced to the level of marital counselling provided by counsellors.

Table 1: shows Zero Order Correlation Showing the Relationship between marital counselling and acceptability of family planning among women

Variable	N	Mean	St-Dev	Df	r	P
Acceptability of family planning	100	54.9103	8.01718	183		
Marital counselling	100	1.4421	0.49751	194	0.155	<.001

Source: Author’s Survey, 2024

Sig. at 0.05 level

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria Table heading.

The table 2 shows that $t_{(8)} = -1.502, P > 0.05$. This indicates that there is significant relationship in the marital counselling provided by counsellors and the choice of married men towards different method of family planning. In essence, this result shows that the different methods used by married women in family were due to the counselling services received from competent counsellors.

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Table 2: Relationship between marital counselling and method of family planning among women

Relationship	N	x	SD	df	T	Sig.	Remark
Methods of family planning	89	45.00	8.00	858.5	1.502	1.001	Sig.
Marital Counselling	11	52.67	13.715				
Total	100						

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Research Hypothesis 3

States that family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

The table above shows that there is a significant difference in the influence of married women who received counselling on family planning and those who did not receive any counselling ($F_{(3,249)} = 35.213, P < 0.05$) which is statistically significant.

Table 3 shows the difference between exposed and not exposed women to family planning

Level of acceptance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Counseled	121.000	123	211.120	35.213	.000*
Not counseled	023.589	3	.621		

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Discussion of Findings

The result from research hypothesis 1 indicated that prior counselling on family planning provided married women with the option to accept and make use of the available methods for planning their families. This implies that the level of family planning acceptability can be traced to the level of marital counseling provided by counselors. This study correlates with the findings of Larson & Olson (2019), who found that the competence and effectiveness of controlling birthrate are due to proper orientation about different types and mediums of family planning among women. There is no doubt, therefore, that providing counselling services in relation to family planning could boost the acceptability of different methods by women. Counselling is considered necessary when it comes to family setup. Invariably, planning the family in relation to childbirth is synonymous with the level of counselling services provided.

The result of research hypothesis 2 revealed that there is a significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women. Invariably, the method that individual women prefer could be attributed to the level of counselling provided by competent counsellors. There is no doubt that this finding negates the work of Johansson (2016), who found out that, especially in many parts of Africa, women must seek permission from their husband or family to visit a clinic for care. Even when permission is nominally given, women's lack of autonomy in their families can still prevent them from seeking care and birth control. However, the present study corroborates the findings by Fowers and Olson (2016) that family members may consider childbirth as a woman's concern and not that of the household. As a result, women may find it difficult to get the money to pay for services or to obtain transportation to get medical care.

The result of research hypothesis 3 states that the importance of counselling cannot be underemphasized in this study. It was established in this study that counselling is an integral part of day-to-day activities and, as such, cannot be considered less. This was obvious in the outcome of the study, as it was found that women who understand marital counselling should have a higher level of acceptance of family planning than those who are not counseled. There is a need to stress the fact that marital counselling gives married women the opportunity to adequately plan their family as regards birth control when counselling services are put in motion. This work is in line with the work of Cuervo-Arango et al. (2019), which reported a retrospective comparison of the efficiency of different assisted reproductive techniques in horses, emphasizing the impact of maternal age.

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Conclusion

The study examines the role of marital counseling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government. It highlights the importance of both services in addressing conflicts, improving communication, and fostering healthy relationships. Family planning is crucial for reproductive health and well-being, enabling informed decisions about pregnancy timing and spacing. However, utilization patterns vary due to cultural norms, religious beliefs, socioeconomic status, and awareness levels. The study suggests that policymakers need to consider comprehensive strategies to address these challenges, such as expanding counseling services, increasing awareness about family planning options, and addressing socio-cultural barriers. Further research is needed to explore the long-term effects of these interventions on marital stability, reproductive health outcomes, and family dynamics.

Recommendations

From the foregoing, the following recommendations were made.

1. Encourage the integration of marital counseling and family planning services within existing healthcare facilities should be made compulsory. This approach ensures that married women have access to comprehensive reproductive health services that address both relational and contraceptive needs.
2. Launch targeted awareness campaigns should be organized to educate married women and their families about the benefits of marital counseling and family planning. Engage community leaders, religious institutions, and local organizations to disseminate accurate information and dispel myths or misconceptions.
3. Tailor counseling and family planning programs to align with the cultural and religious beliefs prevalent should be embedded in Akure South Local Government for married women. Provide culturally sensitive counseling services and incorporate religious perspectives into family planning education to increase acceptability and uptake.

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Comparative Analysis of Psychometric Properties of Multiple-Choice Test Items Question in Economics Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study examined the comparative analysis of psychometric properties of multiple-choice test items in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations in Economics, Kwara State. Reliability coefficient, difficulty levels, discriminating power and effectiveness of distracter of West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) Senior School Certificate Examinations SSCE in Economics multiple choice items were examined and compared. The study employed descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, which was carried out in 20 randomly selected public senior secondary schools in Kwara State. Three hundred and seventy-six (Male 180 and Female 180) senior secondary school class three (SSIII) Economics students during the 2022/2023 academic session were sampled using multi-stage sampling techniques. 2022 Multiple-choice Economics items were administered to students in their classes to collect data. Item analysis was done using Excel and SPSS software packages while the results were analysed using frequency count, mean rating and analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Among the findings, NECO items were found to be more reliable than those of WAEC and NABTEB, while WAEC items exhibited higher discrimination levels. NABTEB items were noted to be more difficult. It is concluded that all three examination bodies are equally valid and reliable, urging stakeholders to view them as partners in the nation's educational development rather than as superior or inferior entities. Recommendations include promoting collaboration among the examination bodies to enhance the overall quality of assessments.

Keyword: Analysis, Comparative, Co-efficient, Discriminating power & Reliability

Introduction

In Nigeria, educational assessment is being conducted at schools and at national level and it is based on prescribed curriculum of the school system. At the school level, the teacher gets information on pupils' performance and such information is being interpreted and used for improving both teaching and learning activities (Haruna, 2019). Educational assessments at the national level are tested for selection and certification in Nigeria. At this national level, educational assessment is in the form of public examination such as West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). Thus, the qualification for admission into any higher educational institution is the school certificate issued by the West African School Certificate Examinations Council (WAEC), the National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) are the three examining bodies charged with the responsibilities of conducting final examination and evaluating final year students in Senior Secondary Schools and Technical Colleges in Nigeria respectively.

In the light of the above, Evaluation agencies are examining bodies which are tasked with maintaining a common standard in the development and administration of public examinations. A study by Nworgu (2006), reported that evaluation agencies were set up to promote education, co-ordinate educational programmes, and to control and monitor the quality of education in the institutions of learning, with the essence of organizing public examinations in order to provide uniform standards to all examinees, irrespective of the type or method of instruction they have received. The main examination bodies in Nigeria include the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), the National Examination Council (NECO) and the National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). A critical observation of the operations of these boards reveals that they perform similar functions. For instance, all conduct secondary school graduate certification, although in the case of NABTEB, the examination is reserved for final year students of Nigerian Technical and Vocational Colleges.

Therefore, the assemblage of subject examinations conducted by these examining bodies is known as the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) and serves as an end-of-course evaluation for all secondary school

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graduates. The purpose of this examination is to ascertain to what extent students have achieved educational objectives in a particular course (Offor, 2001). In view of the economic and social importance attached to senior secondary school certificates and the opportunities to proceed to higher institutions for those who possess such certificates, the awarding of this certificate is one of the most important events in the Nigerian academic calendar. It thus goes without saying that much is expected from the certificate examining and awarding bodies, in ensuring that the spirit and focus of the examinations are not misplaced.

West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) conduct standardized tests and standardized tests are known to possess psychometric properties before it could be judged worthwhile. These tests could be in essay or objective form. Essay tests are test items where the testees candidates are allowed to answer the questions with sentences composed and organized by them (Nkwocha, 2004). On the other hand, objective tests are tests in which every question is set in such a way as to have only one correct answer. The opinion of the examiner is not required to judge the correctness of the answer. One example of an objective test is multiple-choice tests which contain items that are usually with four to five plausible answer options from which testees candidates are expected to recognize the correct answer.

Nevertheless, multiple choice testing is one of the most commonly used assessment formats particularly in public examinations; it consists of a stem and a set of plausible options. The stem presents the item as a problem to be solved, a question or an incomplete statement to be completed and the options are the possible answers that the examinee can choose from, with only one correct answer called the key and the incorrect answers called the distracters (Morrison & Free, 2001). Therefore, in order to be sure of the true performance of the testees candidates in any examination, there is a need to ascertain the quality of the examination (test) which indicates the psychometric properties of the test items. Psychometric properties of the test items cannot be over-emphasis because the considerations of validity and reliability typically are viewed as essential elements for determining the quality of any test. However, professional and practitioner associations frequently have placed these concerns within broader contexts when developing standards and making overall judgments about the quality of any test as a whole within a given context.

The field of psychometrics is primarily concerned with the construction and validation of measurement instruments such as test, questionnaires and personality inventories. Also, one of the theoretical approaches in psychometrics is Classical test theory, which involves the validity and reliability of an item. In classical test theory, the psychometric properties of objective items are determined through item analysis and test analysis, Item analysis is a general term used to describe a set of statistical techniques employed to evaluate test items (Cohen, Swerdlik & Sturman, 2013). According to Anastasi and Urbina (2014); Anikweze (2012) and Denga (2003) items could be analysed qualitatively, in terms of their content and form, and quantitatively, in terms of their statistical properties. Thus, psychometric properties are those aspects of a test that explain how good a test is, they deal with things like the reliability and validity of a test.

The psychometric properties that every measuring instrument such as a test should possess are validity and reliability. Robson (2011) defined validity as a measure of the extent to which the test (or an instrument) measures what it intends to measure. Enyi (2002) further observed that if a test possesses other qualities but lacks validity, the test will be considered as not being useful. Validity is the watchword or foundational stone over which the entire superstructure of testing is based (Sidhu, 2005). Onah (2014) therefore, stated that tests are required to be valid if results based on them are going to be utilized for value judgment. If an item is valid, such an item is said to be reliable to a greater extent. On the other hand, reliability of a test refers to the degree to which a test measures accurately and consistently yielding comparable results when administered a number of times (Akuezuilo & Agu, 2003) cited in Juliet (2018). A test validity and reliability can be ascertained through item analysis among others.

In view of this, Nwaobia (1990) cited in Bandele and Adewale (2013) stated that item analysis is concerned with ascertaining the worth of test items. Item analysis involves quantitative computation used to verify how each test item measures effectively the construct it is designed to measure. Item analysis helps to improve a test by revising or discarding ineffective items, provide diagnostic information on what examinees know and what they do not know. Item analysis usually calls for the computation of some indices such as difficulty index, discrimination index, and distracter effectiveness (Okoye, 1996) cited in (Ugama, 2017).

These indices of item analysis will now be explained one after the other. Therefore, the difficulty of a test item is normally determined from the proportion of the total group selecting the correct answer to that item (Hotiu, 2006). Item difficulty is the percentage of students that correctly answered the item, also referred to as the P-value. The range is from 0% to 100%, the higher the value, the easier the item. P-values above 0.90 are very easy items and might be a concept not worth testing. P-values below 0.20 indicate difficult items and should be reviewed for possible confusing language or the contents

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needs re-instruction. Optimum difficulty level is 0.50 for maximum discrimination between high and low achievers. For example, an item answered correctly by 70% examinees has a difficulty index of 0.70. If 90% of a standard group pass an item, it is easy; if only 10% pass, the item is hard or too difficult. Generally, items of moderate difficulty are to be preferred to those which are much easier or much harder.

Secondly, Item discrimination is a measure of how well the item discriminates between examinees who are well knowledgeable in the content area and those who are not (Professional Testing, 2010). The extent to which a test item discriminates between those in the upper third and the lower third, respectively is its discrimination power (Ede, 2019). It also refers to the ability of an item to differentiate among students on the basis of how well they know the material being tested. This value ranges between 0.0 and 1.00, also referred to as the D-value. Higher the value, more discrimination of the item is. A highly discriminating item indicates that the students who had high tests scores got the item correct whereas students who had low test scores got the item incorrect. Lastly, Distracters are classified as the incorrect answer in a multiple-choice question. According to Instructional Assessment Resources (IAR, 2011), student performance in an exam item is very much influence by the quality of the given distracters. Analysis of distracters can function as a valuable indicator of item difficulty; a good quality distractor should be selected by those who perform poorly and should be ignored by those who perform well. If a distractor is chosen more often than the correct answer, this may indicate poor instructions or a misleading question.

Non- function distractors are those options that are selected by less than 5% of the examinees. These non-function distractors may have no connection or having some clues, which are not directly related to the correct answer. Distractors that are not chosen or are consistently chosen by only less than 5% of the examinee are obviously ineffective and should be omitted or replaced (Hamza et al, 2014). Hence, it is necessary to determine the effectiveness of each item provided distractor as an addition to the item difficulty analysis.

Items considered suitable and acceptable are stored in the database ready for use in any examination. Extraction of the items to be used can be done easily and can be passed on for typesetting in readiness for printing. Collation of items by many people as the case with manual method is eliminated. Incidence of paper leakage is reduced or eliminated at this stage. Test items for selection are evaluated. They are either considered as worthy or unworthy of inclusion in the item bank. The items considered worthy are either accepted for direct use without any revision or for further post editing before being put into use. Item can be considered as unworthy and discarded. Unworthy items are those that do not focus on the central concept or requiring too much revision and considered rejected. The items for further post editing may require minor, fair or major revision. The revision is minor if action needed is insertion of articles, correction of spellings and punctuation. It is fair if it requires re-ordering, removal of words and replacement of one distractor at most. The revision is a major one if it involves more substantial grammatical revision and replacement of two or more of the distracters (Borkinni, 2009).

However, the position of Economics as a subject in secondary school curriculum has been strengthened because it has been accepted that it has some civil values based on some topics such as "the element and determinants of national income, the structure and activities of labour unions, the working and influence of financial institution". These prepared one adequately for life in modern society (Obemeata1991) cited in (Idika, 2020). According to Adu (2002), the study of economics serves a useful purpose in modern life. It gives us facts and shows us what may be expected to be the outcome of certain lines of conduct; it helps us to decide which of several alternatives to choose. It charged its recipient to make wise choice that will satisfy their needs in the presence of unlimited wants and resources. Despite the relevance of Economics to everyday life in the area of commerce and industry, Adu and Ayeni (2004) demonstrated that achievement of candidates in Economics is not only poor generally but continues to fall over the years in a study on an "Appraisal of Trends in Achievement of Students in Economics at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination in Oyo State."

However, despite the fact that the certificate being awarded by these three examining bodies are said to be equivalent, yet, stakeholders in the education sector doubts the equivalence. The criticisms against these examining bodies gave the researcher a lot of concern. Based on these, the researcher therefore, examine and compare psychometric properties of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB economics achievement examinations so as to know whether there exists any relationship between their difficulty levels, discrimination power, distracter index, and reliability coefficient and finally to find out whether their economics multiple choice items are equivalent test items.

Statement of the Research Problem

This research addresses the issue of standard comparability across different tests used by various Nigerian examination bodies, focusing on the quality of multiple-choice questions. It advocates for the comparative analysis of these items based on psychometric properties such as reliability, item difficulty, item discrimination, and item distracters (Bandeled & Adewale, 2013).

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Previous studies have analyzed the psychometric properties of senior school certificate multiple choice test items, yet gaps remain. Bandele and Adewale's (2013) research compared WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB's mathematics exams, but did not consider item analysis or Economics Achievement Examinations. Similarly, Mahmud-Jamiu's (2012) analysis of the psychometric characteristics of Economics Objective Test Items did not involve a comparative analysis of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB. Olatunji's (2009) investigation on the effect of option number on psychometric properties also left out NABTEB when comparing Economics multiple choice papers.

These previous works, while representing significant contributions to the field, did not conduct a comparative analysis of the psychometric properties of the three major Nigerian examining bodies for Secondary Schools in Economics. Moreover, none of these studies investigated all four measures of item analysis. This research work aims to fill these gaps, providing a comprehensive and comparative analysis of the psychometric properties of multiple-choice questions across these examination bodies.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study were to juxtapose:

- 7- The reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items.
- 8- The item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items.
- 9- The item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Achievement Examinations.
- 10- The item functionality level of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items in terms of equivalence among secondary school students in kwara state?
2. What are the differences in the difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?
3. What are the differences in the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?
4. Do distracters of each item in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB function equally among secondary school students in kwara state?

Research Hypotheses

The study was anchored on the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.
2. There is no significant difference in the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population for this study consists all public senior secondary school students in Kwara State. There are 347 public Senior Secondary Schools and 5 Technical School in Kwara State which make the total number to be 352 public schools. However, the target population for this study consists all the 2014/2015 final year students in Public Senior Secondary Schools and Technical College in Kwara State. This target population consists all the 16,996 final year students. The proposed sample for this study made up of 376 students which were selected using multi-stage sampling technique (www.raosoft.com/samplesizecalculator). Multi-stage sampling technique was used for this study as follows:

At the first stage, stratified random sampling technique was adopted to stratify the four (4) local government areas with eighty-eight (88) public secondary schools within the Kwara Central Senatorial Districts in Kwara State as stated below;

1. Asa Local Government Area with fifteen (15) public senior secondary schools
2. Ilorin East Local Government Area with twenty-seven (27) public secondary schools
3. Ilorin South Local Government with twenty-one (22) public senior secondary schools
4. Ilorin West Local Government Area with twenty-four (24) public senior secondary schools

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The researcher selects five (5) public senior secondary schools from each stratum. Thus, a total of twenty (20) public senior secondary schools in Kwara Central Senatorial District were randomly selected. At the second stage, purposive sampling technique was used as the researcher purposively selects SS3 class from the chosen schools. This class was selected because the students are expected to have covered a major part of the school certificate Economics syllabus. They are in the best position to respond to the tests prepared for this research work because they are preparing for their WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics examinations.

At the third stage, simple random technique was used to select nineteen (19) students who offer Economics from the three (3) arms (Art, Commercial and Science class) in each school. The instruments that were used for data collection in this study are WAEC, NECO and NABTEB multiple Economics papers. These three Economics Multiple Choice Question paper were adopted in their original form, with NECO Question paper having 60 items and both the WAEC and NABTEB Question paper having 50 items each respectively. The instruments are standardized test which are presumed to be content valid. In computing the reliability of these research instruments, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instruments. In administering the instrument, the researcher collected an introductory letter from the head of department of Social Sciences Education which was presented to the principal of each of the selected schools to seek permission of the school authorities. Date and time slated for the administration of the test was fixed, and duration for the test administration was last for 1 hour in their various classes with the help of research assistant and Economics teachers in the school. The data collected were scored in dichotomous and polytomous form which were used to carry out item analysis (reliability coefficient, difficulty levels, discriminating power and effectiveness of distracter) using Excel and SPSS software packages. The results obtained from the item analysis were used to provide answers to the research questions using Descriptive statistics (frequency counts and mean rating) and inferential statistics (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses postulated at 0.05 level of significant while split-half method was used to determine the reliability co-efficient.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items in terms of equivalence among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 1: Reliability Levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Examination	NO	Reliability
WAEC	50	0.76
NECO	60	0.78
NABTEB	50	0.75

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 1 show the comparison of the reliability of 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the Table 1, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.76; NECO SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.78 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.75. The results show that these three (3) examinations are reliable, but there is difference in their reliability with NECO Economics Multiple Choice Test Items having more reliable test items than WAEC and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items with a reliability value of 0.78.

Research Question 2

What are the differences in the difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?

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Table 2: Results of Item Difficulty of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Ranges of Difficulty	WAEC Frequency	%	NECO Frequency	%	NABTEB Frequency	%	Description
0-14%	0	0	0	0	1	2	V. Difficult
15%-29%	16	32	31	52	12	24	Difficult
30%-69%	34	68	27	45	34	68	Moderately Difficult
70%-84%	0	0	0	0	1	2	Easy
85%-100%	0	0	2	3	2	4	V. Easy
Total	50	100	60	100	50	100	

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 2 show the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that for WAEC; no item 0 (0%) was very difficult, 16 (32%) of the items were difficult, 34 (68%) of the items were moderately difficult, no item 0 (0%) was easy and no item 0 (0%) was very easy. For NECO; no item 0 (0%) was very difficult, 31 (52%) of the items were difficult, 27 (45%) of the items were moderately difficult, no item 0 (0%) was easy and 2 (3%) of the items were very easy. On the other hand, for NABTEB 1 (2%) of the items was very difficult, 12 (24%) of the items were difficult, 34 (68%) of the items were moderately difficult, 1 (2%) of the items was easy and 2 (4%) of the items were very easy. However, results in Table 3 below compare the mean (x) of **item difficulty indices** of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Table 3: Results of Mean Difficulty Indices of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Examination	No of Item	Mean Difficulty
WAEC	50	0.34
NECO	60	0.32
NABTEB	50	0.40

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 3 show the comparison of item difficulty in 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the Table 3, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.34; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.32 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.40. This means that there is difference in their difficulty indices with NABTEB SSCE Economics items had the highest mean difficulty of 0.40 and the results also imply that NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice items have more difficulty items than WAEC and NECO Economics Multiple choice Test Items.

Research Question 3

What are the differences in the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 4: Results of Discrimination Power of 2014 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Ranges of Discrimination Index	WAEC Frequency	%	NECO Frequency	%	NABTEB Frequency	%	Description
-0.00-0.18	15	30	18	30	24	48	Poor
0.19-0.29	9	18	18	30	17	34	Moderate
0.30-0.39	10	20	14	23	5	10	Good
0.40-1.00	16	32	10	17	4	8	V. good
Total	50	100	60	100	50	100	

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 4 show the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that for WAEC; 15 (30%) of the items were poor, 9 (18%) of the items were moderate, 10 (20%) of the items were good and 16 (32%) of the items were very good. For NECO; 18 (30%) of the items were poor, 18 (30%) of the items were moderate, 14 (23%) of the items were good and 10 (17%) of the items were very good. Also, for NABTEB, 24

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(48%) of the items were poor, 17 (34%) of the items were moderate, 5 (10%) of the items were good and 4 (8%) of the items were very good. However, results in Table 5 below compare the mean (x) of item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Table 5: Results of Mean Discrimination Power of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Examination	NO	Mean Discrimination
WAEC	50	0.30
NECO	60	0.27
NABTEB	50	0.21

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 5 show the comparison of item discrimination power of the 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the table, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.30; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.27 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.21. This means that there is difference in their discrimination power with WAEC SSCE Economics items had the highest mean discriminating value of 0.30 and the results also imply that WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice items have more discrimination power than NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple choice Test Items.

Research Question 4

Do distracters of each item in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB function equally among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 6: Results of Functional and Non-functional Options of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Variable	WAEC Frequency	Percentage %	NECO Frequency	Percentage %	NABTEB Frequency	Percentage %
Functional Options	148	98.7	231	96	140	93
Non-functional Options	2	1.3	9	4	10	7
Total	150	100	240	100	150	100

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 6 show the item functionality level of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that there were 148 (98.7%) functional options and 2 (1.3%) non-functional options in 2014 WAEC SSCE Economics items, also there were 231 (96%) functional options and 9 (4%) non-functional options in 2014 NECO SSCE Economics items while there were 141 (93%) functional options and 10 (7%) non-functional options in 2014 NABTEB SSCE Economics items. The researcher compares functionality of options in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items by using 5% of the students that selected distractors as shown in Table 7 below. However, results in Table 7 below compare the mean (x) of results of the 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items according to number of functioning options.

Table 7: Comparison of Results of the 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items According to Number of Functioning Options

Variable	No of functional options	Percentage %
WAEC	148	98.7
NECO	231	96
NABTEB	141	94

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 7 show the comparative analysis of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items according to number of functioning options. The result shows that WAEC had 148 (98.7%) functional options;

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NECO had 231 (96%) functional options while NABTEB had 141 (94%) functional options. This means that distracters of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items do not function equally and the results also imply that WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items had more functional options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items because its options are all functional.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Table 8: Results of ANOVA Showing Item Difficulty Indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.	Decision
Among Groups	.160	2	.080	4.403	.014	
Within Groups	2.856	157	.018			Rejected
Total	3.016	159				

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 8 show that F-value yielded 4.403 which is significant at 0.05 alpha level ($P < 0.05$). Since the calculated level of significant (0.014) is less than the critical level of significant (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, this implies that there is a significant difference among item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Items. In order to determine the direction of this significant difference, Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) was employed.

Table 9: Results Showing Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) on Item Difficulty Indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Variable	No of Items	Post Hoc Mean Score
WAEC	50	34.24
NECO	60	32.22
NABTEB	50	39.72

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) analysis revealed that the mean score for NABTEB SSCE Economics items is 39.72, significantly higher than the mean scores of WAEC and NECO SSCE Economics items, which are 34.24 and 32.22, respectively. This ranking indicates that NABTEB SSCE Economics items had the highest mean score, followed by WAEC SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 34.24, and NECO SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 32.22. Consequently, the hypothesis was rejected due to the significant difference observed among the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Table 10: Results of ANOVA Showing Item Discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.	Decision
Among Groups	.230	2	.115	6.497	.002	
Within Groups	2.776	157	.018			Rejected
Total	3.006	159				

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 8 show that F-value yielded 6.497 which is significant at 0.05 alpha level ($P < 0.05$). Since the calculated level of significant (0.002) is less than the critical level of significant (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, this suggests a significant difference across the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB Economics

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Multiple Choice Items. In order to determine the direction of this significant difference, Post Hoc Test (Duncan Test) was employed.

Table 9: Results Showing Duncan’s Post Hoc (DPH) on Item Discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Variable	No of Items	Post Hoc Mean Score
WAEC	50	30.06
NECO	60	26.80
NABTEB	50	20.64

Duncan’s Post Hoc (DPH) analysis reveals that the mean score for WAEC SSCE Economics items is 30.06, significantly higher than the mean scores of NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items, which are 26.80 and 20.64, respectively. This ranking indicates that WAEC SSCE Economics items had the highest mean score, followed by NECO SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 26.80, and NABTEB SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 20.64. Consequently, the hypothesis was rejected due to the significant difference observed among the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that NECO Economics Multiple Choice Test Items has the highest reliability coefficient of 0.78 compared with WAEC and NABTEB reliability coefficient of 0.76 and 0.75 respectively. It might be that the much criticism by stakeholders against the three examining bodies have geared the officials toward improving the standard of these examination bodies particularly NECO. This finding is supported by Bandele and Adewale (2013) who reported that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB mathematics achievement tests were highly reliable. It also showed that the examination bodies are comparable and equivalent. This clearly contradicted the finding of Adeniran (2000) that showed that NECO is inferior to WAEC in all standards. Of recent, NECO has been criticized of poor performance such that the national assembly had to intervene on the crisis between stakeholders and officials of NECO.

Most interesting of the findings in this study is that NABTEB SSCE Economics items have more difficulty items than WAEC and NECO SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Objective test. NABTEB has of recent been rejected by some National Universities for admission purpose. It is quite often the case that criticism against examination bodies in Nigeria is centered on emotion and people that have no knowledge of the psychometric properties of examination are the loudest in the criticism. It is revealed that NABTEB outperformed WAEC and NECO in terms of difficulty of items.

On the basis of this finding, it is quite advisable that criticism against examination bodies would be based on knowledge of facts rather than perceptions. Examinations especially Multiple-Choice tests have their procedure, processes and functions. Therefore, anybody criticizing the examination must have adequate knowledge of the psychometric properties of test. Even though, the findings contradicted the work of Aborisade and Fajobi (2020) who found that no significant difference between the difficulty index of the examination items constructed by WAEC and NECO. This finding is also similar with the work of Moyinoluwa (2015) which revealed same average difficulty on four Mathematics examinations administered to SSS by NABTEB, NECO, JAMB and WAEC.

The findings of this study have further revealed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had more discriminating items than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items. WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.30; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.27 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.21. This finding should not be surprising because WAEC has a long history of existence; WAEC has wide area of operation and possibly more technical know-how and qualified personnel that are learned in examination psychometric properties. This finding is in line with the result of Olatunji (2009) that 4 option formats of WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice tests have better discriminating indices than NECO SSCE Economics Multiple Choice tests. The result corroborates with the findings of Ogunbamowo, Adediwura and Diyan (2019) who showed that the discrimination indices of NECO and WAEC Economics test items were different from one another significantly.

It was further discovered that WAEC SSCE Economics items have more functional options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items. The result showed that WAEC had 148 (98.7%) functional options; NECO had 231 (96%) functional options while NABTEB had 141 (94%) functional options. This reinforces the claim that WAEC has better facilities, personnel

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and excellent past records than NECO and NABTEB. This finding concurs with that of Olatunji (2009) and Abiri (2006) which revealed that 4 alternatives has the best functional options in WAEC than NECO multiple choice test item in Economics.

Similarly, findings of this study showed that there is significant difference among the difficulty and discrimination indices of WAEC; NECO and NABTEB multiple choice economics test items. This implies that the difficulty and discrimination levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics items are not the same. However, the Duncan post-hoc analysis shows that the significant difference noted above was accounted for by NABTEB and WAEC with higher mean difficulty and discrimination indices respectively. Finally, the findings support the claim that the three examining bodies have credibility that could be adjudged as functional and worthy of their establishment. Therefore, we should not be tied down to narrow minded critics who have no adequate knowledge of standardized examination or psychometric properties of examination.

Conclusion

It can also be concluded that there is a significant difference among difficulty and discrimination indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice items with NABTEB and WAEC having the highest mean difficulty and discrimination indices respectively. The findings of this study also revealed that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items do not function equally, with WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items having better plausible options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Finally, it could be concluded here that furthermore, multiple choice test items of the three Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations in Economics do not have the same psychometric properties in terms of reliability, item difficulty, item discrimination and effectiveness of distracters.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Examinations are highly valid and reliable and none of these examination bodies should be seen by stakeholders as being inferior or superior to the others in terms of reliability or standard, rather they should be seen as partners in progress of the nation's educational development whereas the examining bodies should improve more on the item analysis of their test items.
2. Moderately difficult items should be given to the students so as to boost the performance of the students in various examinations and as much as possible all forms of ambiguity and bias should be avoided in the development of items.
3. Test development procedure should be strictly followed by examining body so as to arrive at item that will function effectively in differentiating between brilliant and not brilliant students. The discrimination power of the item should be ascertain to avoid redundant item.
4. The examining bodies should continue to engage the services of experts and professional in cross checking the plausibility or functionality options in a test. The key and distracters should be written in such a way that they will be equally attractive and appealing to the examinees.
5. Examination bodies should ensure that reliability level, difficulty index and discrimination power of items as well as functionality of options fall within the acceptable limits for certification at the school certification level.

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Correlation Between Private School Teachers' Participatory Role In Decision Making And Productivity In North Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined teacher participatory decision making and productivity in North Central private basic schools, Nigeria. The research design employed for the study was a descriptive survey research method design. The population of the study comprised of 31,566 teachers during the 2022/2023 academic session in all private junior secondary schools in North Central geo-political zone of Nigeria were considered as a suitable population for this study. A multistage sampling technique of stratified, proportionate and convenience sampling were used to select 284 teachers in private schools from 3 States (FCT, Kwara and Niger States) in the zone as participants for this study from the target population. One main and four operational hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The Teacher Participatory Decision Making and Productivity Questionnaire (TPDMPQ) was tested for reliability using test-retest method while Spearman rank correlation coefficient statistics was used to analyze the data and test for hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. From the findings obtained in this study, it was revealed that positive relationship exists between participatory decision making and teachers' productivity, teachers' participation in curriculum management had the highest mean. However, teachers' participation in decisions on school finance had the lowest mean and there is also no significance relationship between school plant maintenance and teachers' productivity. This reveals that, less attention was given to teachers' involvement and effective participation in decisions on maintenance of school plants and school finance. The study concludes that teachers' participation in school policy implementation, maintenance of school plants, curriculum management and school finance all have important roles in improving teachers' productivity. It was recommended that teachers should be actively involved in school policy planning and its implementation including formulation of rules and regulation, late arrival of students and disciplinary policies to improve teachers' productivity and learning outcomes for students.

Keyword: Policy plan, school plant, curriculum management, school finance, teacher productivity

Introduction

The school system is a complex institution with various ways and approaches that can lead to the performance of a distinct task, the success or failure of any school is largely dependent upon the groups that make it up and make decision, effective utilization of the intellectual abilities of these group or human resources helps the development of such school. Teachers are one of the important inputs in the school system (Kaikai & Haruna, 2022). Although other stakeholders like parents, non-teachers, school administrators and the community also take part in the decision making but teachers are actively involved in school activities and programs, their impact in decision making in school cannot be over emphasized unlike other stakeholders. Abdulrahman (2016) affirmed that the stakeholders of any institution are all the people, who have a legitimate interest in the continuing effectiveness and success of that institution. It is pertinent to state that teacher is a central figure in the school operations. They are the closest to students, always in touch with them, more aware of their needs of the students and in a better position to anticipate the effects of decision implementation. In addition, teacher participation in decision making has been shown to be one of the key characteristics of their performance and schools' effectiveness (Wadesango, 2016; Daramola, Ogunsanwo, & Adebayo, 2021).

Teacher productivity on the other hand is the hall mark of school growth and development. Teachers' productivity may be measure in terms of teacher's performance. Afolabi & Aragbaye (2022). Wainaina, Iravo and Waitutu (2014) suggest

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that teachers' productivity may be evaluated in terms of what the teacher control and actually do in class room such as teaching effectiveness and class room performance. Productivity of staff depends on the extent to which the teacher efficiently utilizes the education input to maximize output. Education input in this regard are resources used in the process of educating a child such as pre-student expenditures, student-teacher ratios, teacher education, experience, salary, school facilities, and administrative factors. This is the more reason why the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) captures that no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers. Without efficient and effective teachers, the education system will be crippled. Productivity of teachers at work is the most pivotal factor among educational factors as a requirement for teachers to plan, execute and monitor each single educational activity for the sake of school goal.

However, it is important to review the contributions of other authors, researchers and experts in this area of study with a view of drawing from their opinions, observations and recommendations as it affects teacher participatory decision making and their productivity at work. Within the framework of Theory Y, McGregor (1960) emphasized the importance of participative management as a means to tap into the potential and capabilities of employees. It is believed that involving employees in decision making and giving them autonomy and responsibility can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction, productivity, and organizational performance. This theory assumes that employees are self-motivated, enjoy work, and are capable of self-direction and self-control. McGregor suggests that management should create a work environment that nurtures employee potential and allows for greater employee involvement in decision-making processes. Participative decision making aligns with Theory Y, as it encourages employees to contribute their innovative ideas, expertise, and perspectives when making decisions that affect their work. Participative decision making fosters a sense of ownership, responsibility, and empowerment in teachers, as they are directly involved in shaping the decisions that affect their work and the school as a whole. This approach not only increases teachers' satisfaction and motivation but also tap into the diverse knowledge and experiences of the workforce, leading to better decision outcomes and improved educational performance.

Meanwhile, decision making has been observed by Adham (2011) to be the heart of administrative process and leadership in schools needed for the growth and survival of any school. It is a conscious and deliberate resolve that binds the individual or group to take action in a specific way in the effort towards having better result. In schools, Olorunsola and Olayemi (2011) submit that participatory decision making permits the teachers to lend their voice in school matters for the purpose of enhancing their job performance and achieving educational set goals. From their submission therefore, it could be said that teacher participation in decisions were geared towards solving immediate school problems and in the long run aimed at achieving education goals and objectives. These decisions could bother on school instructional programs, transportation systems, personnel administration, staff welfare, student discipline, school plant maintenance, health facilities, admission policy, school finance, extracurricular activities and many others.

Researches have shown over the years that participatory decision making often lead to more efficiency and high staff morale (Wadesango, 2010; [Sarafidou & Chatziioannidis, 2013](#)). In spite of this, there has been a lot of controversy as to whether teachers should participate in the decision making or not. In the past, only the school heads engage in decision making, teachers seemed to be neglected by their school heads who managed the schools authoritatively and became unapproachable to the class teachers. They have always been left out when it comes to restructuring the context within which teaching occurs especially on issues related to pedagogy, administration and governance (Abdulai & Shafiwu, 2014). Teachers seemed inefficient and less effective on the job which could be as a result of the fact that they no longer take their job seriously due to non-participation in the management of their schools. Such teachers appeared to shed their responsibilities and did not do much teaching in the schools which seemed to have adverse effect on their students academically. Many students were observed to be poor academically and morally. Students' inadequacies appeared to result from their teachers' poor attitude to work and low level of productivity. Participation of teachers in decision making is one of the pillars of work performance in schools. However, in spite of this, studies (Macha & Mhagama, 2022; Ngussa & Gabriel, 2017) reveal little or no teacher participation in decision making, as school head do not have good relationship with their teachers in the management of various education matters. This condition has dampened teacher morale and work performance and in turn results to poor academic performance on part of the students. Therefore, this study investigates teachers' participation in decision making process for optimal productivity in North Central Secondary Schools.

Objectives of the study:

The study examined the various ways teachers can take part in the decision-making process in the school and how it influences their job productivity. Specifically, this study

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3. Determine the correlation between teachers' participation in school policy implementation and teachers' productivity in Private Basic Schools in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
4. Investigate the relationship between teachers' participation in maintenance of school plant and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
5. Determine the relationship between teachers' participation in curriculum management management and their productivity in North Central basic schools, Nigeria.
6. Examine the relationship between teachers' participation in school finance management and their productivity in North Central basic schools, Nigeria.

Hypotheses:

The following hypothesis were postulated and tested in this study:

Main:

There is no significant relationship between teacher role in decision making and productivity in North Central Basic schools, Nigeria.

Operational Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in school policy implementation and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in maintenance of school plant and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship teachers' role in curriculum management and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in school finance management and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive research of the survey method. This design is appropriate for this study because it allowed the researcher from a sample of the population, analyze the data and make reasonable recommendation about the whole population. Furthermore, the quantitative study was considered a correlation between participatory decisions making with regards to teachers' productivity in North Central basic schools. A total number of 31,566 teachers in all private junior secondary schools in North Central geo-political zone of Nigeria were considered as a suitable population for this study (FGN, 2018). A multistage sampling technique of stratified, proportionate and convenience sampling were used to select 284 teachers in private schools from 3 States (FCT, Kwara and Niger States) in the zone as participants for this study.

Following the sample of 284 participants, teachers were selected based on the percentage proportion of the population in each stratum as 25% of the sample teachers were from FCT, 34% from Kwara and 41% from Niger State constitute the sample. This makes up a total of 284 participants. The method then required that teachers be selected using convenient sampling of schools. The instrument developed for this study was in two parts, a structured questionnaire tagged, "Participatory Decision Making and Teachers' Productivity questionnaire (PDMTPQ)". The Part A contains 16 items on a four-point Likert like rating scale of Always (4points), Often (3points), Sometimes (2 points) and Never (1point) respectively to elicit information on participatory decision making and the Part B consist of 10 items for teachers' productivity questionnaire. The instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin. Their comments and corrections were incorporated and used to finalize the instrument for data collection. For the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha value of 0.76 obtained adjudged the instrument reliable for use in this study. The final instrument was administered to participants and the rate of return was 88% after retrieved ones were checked to ensure the completeness and correctness of data without missing values. This was considered appropriate for analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between teacher role in decision making and productivity in North Central Basic schools, Nigeria.

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Table 1: Teacher Participation in Decision Making and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
Participatory Decision Making	250	2.71	0.89	0.125	0.043	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

Table 1 represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.125, p -value = 0.043 and sample size = 250. Although the Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.125 indicated that there exists a weak positive relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. However, the p -value indicated that there is a significant relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. As the teacher participation in decision making increases, their productivity increases by just 13%. P -value = 0.043 is less than level of significance of 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there exists a significant relationship ($p = 0.125 < 0.05$ for a two-tailed test).

Operational Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 2: Teacher Participation in School Policy Implementation and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Policy Implementation	250	2.45	1.12	0.513	0.002	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.513, p -value = 0.002 and sample size = 250. Although the Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.513 indicated that there exists a positive relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria, however, the p -value indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between student teacher participation in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. As the teacher participation in policy implementation increases, their teacher productivity increases by 51%. P -value = 0.002 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

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Table 3: Teacher Participation in School Plant Maintenance and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Plant Maintenance	250	2.02	.733	0.008	0.077	Accept Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.008, p -value = 0.077 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.008 indicated that there exists a weak positive relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Therefore, the result implies that as teacher participation in school plant maintenance increases, their productivity increases by 8%. P -value = 0.077 is greater than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is accepted while the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the results indicated that there is no significant relationship between teacher participation in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

H_{03} : There is no significant relationship between teacher role in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 4: Teacher Participation in Curriculum Management And Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
Curriculum Management	250	2.32	.820	0.520	0.018	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 with p -value of 0.018 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 indicated that there exists a strong positive relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Since the correlation obtained with a p -value less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the result reveals that as teacher participation in curriculum management increases, teacher productivity increases by 52%. P -value = 0.018 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the results indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

H_{04} : There is no significant relationship between teacher participation in school finance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 5: Teacher Participation in School Finances and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Finances	250	2.23	1.008	0.520	0.018	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). (Field Work, 2023)

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The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school finances and productivity. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 with p-value of 0.018 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 indicated that there exists a positive relationship between teacher participation in teachers' role in school finances and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Since the correlation obtained with a p-value less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the result reveals that as teacher participation in school finances increases, teacher productivity increases by 52%. P-value = 0.000 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the results indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' role in school finances and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigates the relationship between teachers' role in decision making and teachers' productivity, the raised objectives in the study were analyzed using the correlation table, the findings suggest areas of teachers' participation in school decision which include, school policy implementation, school plants maintenance, Curriculum management and school finance play a vital role in improving teachers' productivity. There exist a significant positive correlation exists between Participatory Decision-Making and Teachers' Productivity. The findings in line with Mashambo, (2022) and Tijani, (2022) that participatory decision making can have a significant positive impact on teachers' productivity, in terms of both their job performance and their engagement with their work. When the teachers are given a voice in decision making and the opportunity to participate in school governance, they are more likely to feel a sense of ownership and engagement with their work. In, participatory decision making can improve communication and collaboration among teachers which can lead to better working relationships and improved teamwork. As a result, teachers may be more productive and may be more likely to stay in their jobs for longer periods of time.

The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between school policy implementation and teachers' productivity. However, it is important to understand this relationship in context, when teachers are given the opportunity to participate in policy implementation, they are more likely to feel like they are part of the decision-making process and that their voices are being heard. This, in turn, leads to increased job satisfaction and commitment to the school. Giving teachers a voice in policy implementation is not only beneficial for the school, but also for the teachers themselves. Teacher participation in policy implementation can have a positive impact on student achievement. This finding is in line with that of Derrington and Anderson (2020) whose study focused on the roles of teacher participation in school policy implementation.

The study revealed that there is no significant relationship between maintenance of school plants and teachers' productivity. This implies that, less attention was given to teachers' contribution in school plant maintenance for efficient and effective of teachers' productivity and performance, this affects the overall activities of the school in general and teaching-learning process in particular. The findings underscore the importance of school plants and its maintenance. The findings of this study is in agreement with the Jacob and Gupta (2013) studied the influence of physical facilities on teacher performance in secondary schools in urban and rural areas. The study found that teacher satisfaction with physical facilities was significantly related to teacher perceptions of productivity and effectiveness. The findings of this study suggest that teachers should be actively involved in the maintenance of physical facilities of schools such as the school buildings, equipment, textbooks, hostels, laboratory, furniture and school offices, so as to improve teachers' job satisfaction and their productivity.

It was also revealed that there is a significant relationship between curriculum management. Curriculum management includes developing of teaching methodologies, setting learning goals, deciding on the type of instructional material to be used for each topic, evaluating student performance and extra curriculum activities. Teachers have two distinct role to play. One is their role in instruction and their other role is in participating in school management and decision-making. The study revealed a significant relationship between school finance and teachers' productivity, when teachers are given the opportunity to participate in school decision making, it gives them a sense of ownership over the policies and procedures that affect their job. This can lead to increased job satisfaction, as teachers feel that their input is valued and that they have a voice in the decision-making process. It can lead to increased motivation and engagement, as teachers are more likely to feel invested in the success of the school if they have been involved in shaping its policies. It also creates a culture of collaboration and trust among teachers, which can facilitate the sharing of ideas and resources.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, these findings indicate that teachers' participation in school policy implementation, Maintenance of school plants curriculum management and instruction and school finance all have important roles in improving teachers' productivity. School heads/ principals should ensure teachers are actively engaged in the decision-making processes of the school for a greater output by the teachers and quality students' performance. From the findings obtained in this study, it was found that positive relationship between participatory decision making and teachers' productivity, teachers' participation in curriculum management and instruction had the highest mean. However, teachers' participation in decisions on school finance had the lowest mean and there is also no significance relationship between school plant maintenance and teachers' productivity. This reveals that, less attention was given to teachers' involvement and effective participation in decisions on maintenance of school plants and school finance. This can affect teaching and learning process in general and the overall activities of the school. Teachers have two distinct roles to carry out. One of their roles is instruction and the other is their involvement in school administration and decision-making processes. The study indicated that teachers participated mostly in decisions regarding curriculum management and instruction. 58 However, from this finding obtained, it can be concluded that there might be a misconception in identifying and understanding teachers' duties and functions by both the teachers, school heads, PTA and educational officials, they might consider teachers duties and functions as teaching and learning activities alone and other activities as the duties and responsibilities of administrators of school. Teachers must have a voice in the decision-making processes of the school and school heads should ensure full participation of teachers in school decision making, so as to enhance their productivity and to provide a quality learning outcome.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Teachers should be actively involved in school policy planning and its implementation including formulation of rules and regulation, late arrival of students and disciplinary policies to improve teachers' productivity and learning outcomes for students.
2. School heads/Principals should ensure that teachers are fully involved in ensuring that school facilities such as library, school buildings, equipment, hostels, laboratories, furniture and so on are well maintained and managed so as to secure school resources and maintain a safe and functional school environment.
3. School Principals should give room for teachers to take part in decision making on deciding teaching methodologies, setting learning goals and objectives, instructional materials, content and forms of lesson plans and extra-curricular activities, for easy implement school curriculum and to meet the needs of all categories of students.
4. Teachers should be given the opportunities to participate in determining school financial process through committees or other structures

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Correlation between Teachers' Capacity Building Programmes and Effective Service Delivery among Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study focuses on correlation between teachers' capacity building programmes and effective service delivery among senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey. One research question and three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consist of 1999 teachers in 57 schools in Abuja, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting 323 teachers in accordance to sample size determination table. A researcher self-designed questionnaire tagged "Teachers' Capacity Building Programmes and Effective Service Delivery Questionnaire (TCBPESQ)" was used to collect data for the study. The instrument gave a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Descriptive statistics of percentage and mean score were used to answer research questions and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings among others revealed that is significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Abuja. Based on the findings, the study concludes that teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes is a means of promoting school effectiveness. It therefore, recommended among other things that an evidence of capacity building programme should be considered as a major priority for promotion of teachers in public senior secondary schools.

Key words: Capacity building programme, school service delivery, instructional methods and classroom management

Introduction

Secondary education is known to be the link-bridge between foundation level of education (pre-primary and primary) and higher-level of education. It is a level of education that prepares students for higher institution of learning. The secondary education, as the name implies, is the second or next level of education in Nigeria system of education after the successful completion of basic or primary education. It is the programme of education the children receive between the ages of 12 and 18 years. It is the spring board from where all the students of higher education take of and all primary school leavers should undergo to be useful to themselves and society (Kaikai, Haruna, 2022). The value of secondary education in any nation of the world cannot be underrated. This is due to the fact that training for specific professional development is specifically and uniquely begins at secondary schools.

It is obvious that formalization of education programmes in Nigeria was introduced, practice and managed by missionaries as far back as 1882 before the government intervention in 1887. Ever since then, secondary education is not left out. This is an indication that among other levels of education, secondary education plays significant roles in human capacity development and nation building. The broad aims of secondary education as identify by Alabi (2022) are:

- a) preparation for useful living within the society, and
- b) preparation for higher education.

The National Policy of Education (2013) sees senior secondary education as post-basic level of education and career development whose objective is to:

- a) provide holders of the basic education certificate with opportunity for education of higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background;
- b) offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles;
- c) provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grade; and

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d) provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development, among others.

From the objectives set for secondary education in Nigeria and as laudable as those objectives are; the attainment of the set objectives could be a mirage if the teachers who are to interpret the contents of the curriculum and implement to have desired changes on students are lacking basic skills to withstand the dynamic nature of educational programme. Teachers are opening door for desired development in any nation but the teachers hold the key.

Teachers are important factor to be considered in ascertaining the goals of secondary education as far as senior secondary school is concerned. Teachers' roles towards ensuring the effectiveness of the school system cannot be over stressed. Therefore, their Job Performance such in areas like: record keeping, administration of discipline, school community relation, students' assessment among others are crucial to the effectiveness of secondary education. Teachers' job performance involves demonstration of competence and commitment to the process of performing the tasks given to them (Alabi, 2022). Teachers' activities are not hidden but are seen as factors that dictate the quality of the products as well as the quality of the schools.

Teaching as a profession is challenging in nature and this is as a result of diversified nature of the programme of education. The intricacies of the teaching job coupled with the demanding needs of the time have posed challenges to teachers. The premise that unless teachers provide effective instruction and create a conducive classroom environment to learning, students will not achieve at high levels, even when essential material inputs are available and the curriculum is relevant (Alabi, 2022). Teachers determine the happenings in the school. Most especially, the learning opportunity for the students is hinged on the quality of knowledge been possessed by the teachers.

Researchers over the years have noticed that there is declining performance of students in secondary schools in Nigeria in terms of reading, writing, and practical skills (Omopariola, 2017). This is especially noticed among students in public schools. Some of the reasons accounted for this include the declining competence and commitment of teachers, inadequate provision of facilities, non-maintenance of available facilities, outdated and largely irrelevant curricula coupled with poor implementation. The aspect of teachers' incompetencies has been identified as inability of teachers to withstand the current dimension of educational system. That is, the global changes of teaching and learning (Ahmed, 2017). Teachers Without Borders (2006) as reported by Alabi (2022) stated that educational standard is measured from the products of schools. The cognitive and affective development of the students depend on the quality of the instructional delivery. Teachers controls classroom activities. Teachers create the love of continues learning for the students and they provide guide for future development of the students. For the teachers to be able to achieve all of these, such teachers must be updated in learning to be able to cope with new trend of relating with students.

However, building capacity of teachers should constitute school challenges of educational managers; bearing in mind that the manpower of any organization is its greatest asset. In the educational sector, teachers' capacity building has to do with updating teacher competencies for efficiency on the job. The process is made up of the sum total of learning experiences throughout teachers' career from initial training to retirement. These learning experiences ensure that the performance of teachers is high and contributes significantly in the accomplishment of educational goals. Researchers, such as Alabi (2023) and Ahmed (2017) see capacity building as a means of increasing teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies for effective job performance. Capacity building relates to human resource management in an organization, ensures that organizational members possess the new but relevant knowledge and skills needed to deliver effectively in their jobs, as well as take up new challenges, and adapt to changing environments.

Capacity is the ability to understand and do something while building is an increase in the amount of something over a period of time (Cambell, 2015). Hence, building capacity of teachers, for instance, is the conscious attempt at promoting, rebuilding, and gathering skills, abilities and strategies that must be promoted at regular interval to encourage teachers to contribute adequately to academic dynamics, as well as acquire professional training, effective teaching strategy and materials, effective skills for teaching, serve as effective role model, effectively enforce discipline and control of the students, enhanced condition of services, and the ability to ascertain the readiness of the students in the learning process. It is a process where teachers seize opportunity to gather new skills, ideas, attitudes or learning to promote the achievement of designed goals.

The purpose of capacity building programme is to improve an individual's skills or effectiveness in carrying out certain functions, solving problems, defining and achieving objectives. Thus, capacity building in education can be seen as a set of programmes designed to train or retrain teachers and other staff so that the learners would be able to benefit from the training. Capacity building programmes can be planned at two levels which include personal development and institutional development. A well-organized capacity building programme for teachers is believed to have influence on the quality of teaching and learning and in the long term, on students' learning outcomes. The focus of most capacity building programmes

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is on understanding the obstacles that frustrate or hinder people and organizations from achieving set goals and enhancing the abilities to achieve such goals.

World Bank (2011) describes capability building as the process of empowering the actors the society through learning, training, knowledge acquisition, information sharing and innovation to promote transformational and sustainable change in the organisation, which in turn promotes the achievement of the set developmental goals. Training is the act of transferring and taking information for the purpose of solving identified problems. This means that training is conducted to solve a particular problem. In the opinion of Agbatutu (2013) training is involving the development of abilities, skills and knowledge of the employee to carry out particular assignment to enhance productivity. Adeniji (2002) contended that training and retraining in educational system is geared towards work situation of an institution. This is because there may be situations where an institution has the required quality and quantity of workforce, yet experience low productivity; hence the need for more training and development in the institution. Effective training can have significant impact on the whole life of the worker in an organization and enhance productivity in the organization.

According to Stewart and Hart (2002), capacity building programmes classify approaches to teacher development under three general categories; thus: traditional, informal and intermediate approaches. The traditional approach refers to provisions made by the institution or the school system for improving the performances of school personnel from initial employment to retirement. Although, staff development generally recognizes that it is possible for teachers to improve their effective discussion activities. This approach is well suited to gathering routine information, updating teaching techniques and ideas relating to one's work.

Informal approaches involve the most innovative and provocative orientation to staff development in that they rely on exploration and discovery by teachers. Ferg (2005), in support of this, observed that informal approaches involve intense teacher's commitment, and the activities are initiated by teachers. Informal approaches are predicted upon the assumption that by providing teachers with an encouraging environment equipped with relevant teaching materials, media books and devices coupled with the generous encouragement of the employers, teachers will interact with this encouraging environment and with one another through research and findings. This approach encourages teachers to plan and work together. Teachers seek for help and new ideas from each other, thus strengthening their self-confidence and integrity. Intermediate approaches are essentially supervisory systems of staff development that result into cordial relationship without formal intervention. Teachers are exposed to logically structured programmes or activities through lectures, demonstration and observation to enhance their job efficiency and thereby leads to school effectiveness.

However, it is important at this juncture, to ask a very important question that how often is the attendance of secondary school teachers in capacity building programme? In an attempt to find answers to this question and other related to it makes this study to examine the relationship between teachers' capacity building programme attendance and effective service delivery in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The focus of this study is to examine the correlation between teachers' capacity building programmes and effective service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify how often teachers attend capacity building programmes among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;
2. Examine the influence of teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on the use of instructional method among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;
3. Determine the influence of teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria; and
4. Investigate the influence teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on teacher-student relations among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Question

One research question was raised to guide this study as follow.

How often does public senior secondary school teachers attend capacity building programmes?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;

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2. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building programme and use of instructional methods among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria; and
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building programme and classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is descriptive survey design. This is considered appropriate for the study because it gives account of the true picture of the observed variables without any manipulation. The population for the study covers all the public senior secondary schools in the six Local Government Area in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. As at the time of conducting this study, there were 57 senior secondary schools in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. There were 1999 senior secondary school teachers in all the 57 schools available in Abuja. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting 323 teachers. The selection of 323 (175 females and 148 males) teachers. The selection of 323 teachers was guided by sample size calculator and Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. Hence, total respondents chosen for the study 323. The research instrument used to collect data from the respondents was a research self-designed questionnaire titled “Teachers’ Attendance of Capacity Building Programme and School Effectiveness Questionnaire (TACBPSEQ)” and its content and construct validation were observed before been subjected for reliability test. A 0.83 score obtained for reliability study and this shows that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics of percentage and mean score were used to answer research question and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The mean score is used to take decision as follows:

Table 1: Decision Making for Descriptive Analysis

Mean Score	Decision
3.00 - 4.00	Very Good
2.00 – 2.99	Fair
1.99 - 0.00	Poor

Results

Research Question

How often does public senior secondary school teachers attend capacity building programmes?

Table 2: Analysis of Teachers’ Attendance in Capacity Building Programmes in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria between year 2021 and 2023

S/No	Items	No & (%) of time attended				Mean Score	Decision
		None	One time	Two times	Three times		
1	2021	250 (77)	73 (23)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.45	Poor
2	2022	211(65)	70 (22)	42 (13)	0 (0)	2.11	Fair
3	2023	237 (73)	80 (25)	6 (2)	0 (0)	2.21	Fair
Composite Mean						1.92	Poor

Source: Field report, 2023

Table 2 presents the analysis of teachers’ attendance in capacity building programmes among teachers in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria between year 2021 and 2023. The mean scores teachers’ attendance in the capacity building programmes were rated 1.45, 2.11 and 2.11 respectively and composite mean score was 1.92 and this is rated poor. The implication of this result is that majority of the teachers in the study area are not privilege to attend any of the capacity building programmes within the year frame. The implication of this is that teachers in the study schools were eroded to be updated on the new trends for their professional development. It is on this account, Alabi (2023) and Otu (2020) argued that capacity building programmes for teachers are means of increasing teachers’ knowledge, skills and competencies for effective job performance. Teaching as a profession is a dynamic job which is characterized by frequent changes. And, for teachers to move along with changing nature of teaching profession; there is need for update skills and knowledge through training and

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retraining. Modern system of education demands high quality teaching and learning from teachers that possess a great deal of knowledge and skills with regard to both teaching and assessment practices in order to meet those demands and standards of quality education. Twenty-first century education is about skills –sets of processes. Our students need to be able to adapt to contexts, meet challenges, and solve problems that are as yet unknown. Training is teaching, or developing in oneself or other's any skills and knowledge that relate to specific useful competencies. Training has specific goals of improving one's capability, capacity, productivity and performance. Training constitutes a basic concept in human resource development. It is concerned with developing a particular skill to a desired standard by instruction and practice. Training is a highly useful tool that can bring an individual into a position where they can do their job correctly, effectively, and conscientiously.

Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria

Table 3: Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and School Effectiveness in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	3.45	2.01	321	0.01	0.73	Rejected
School Effectiveness	323	3.11	1.78				

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance.

Source: Field report, 2023

The testing of the relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and school effectiveness in Abuja public senior secondary school, Nigeria is presented in Table 3. The calculated r-value is 0.73 and p-value is 0.01. Thus, the significance level is 0.05. Hence, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that the null hypothesis saying there is no significant relationship is hereby rejected. It means that positive and strong (0.73) significant relationship is found between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and school effectiveness in Abuja public senior secondary school (cal. $r = 0.73$; p-value of $0.01 < 0.05$ significance).

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and use of instructional methods among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria

Table 4: Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and Use of Instructional Methods in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	2.63	0.98				
Use of Instructional Methods	323	2.13	0.52	321	0.01	0.68	Rejected

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance.

Source: Field report, 2023

As shown in Table 4, the test for relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional method in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria. The calculated r-value is 0.68, the p-value is 0.01

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and the level of significance is 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis saying that there is no significant relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional methods is hereby rejected. This implies that positive significant relationship is existing between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional methods.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria

Table 5: Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and Classroom Management in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	3.05	1.07	321	0.00	0.64	Rejected
	323	2.01	1.12				
Classroom Management							

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance. (Field report, 2023)

As indicated in Table 5, the calculated r-value is 0.64 and p-value is 0.00 while the level of significance is 0.05. This shows that the null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and classroom management in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria is hereby rejected. This means that positive and significant relationship is existing between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and classroom management in the study area (cal. $r = 0.64$; $p\text{-value of } 0.01 < 0.05$ significance).

Discussion of Findings

The roles of teachers are undeniable when it comes to goal achievement of education programmes in any nation of the world. As previously observed that if education is an opening door for national development as anticipated in the National Policy on Education (2013), then teachers hold the key. This is why it is imperative to always keep teachers on the tones or ensure that they work in right direction by doing the right things regardless of the dynamic nature of the programme of education. In this study, effort is made to identify capacity building programmes as one of the key factors for improving the quality of teachers for professional competencies. Although, and as presented in Table 2 of this study, poor attendance of teachers in capacity building programmes is recorded in the study area with composite mean score of 1.92. This is why public senior secondary is identified with old style of professional discharge. In the sample schools, the sitting arrangement of students in classroom is not learned centred. Mostly, teachers are used to lecturing method of teaching and many more old teaching acts that cannot withstand the 21st century system of education. There is need to keep teachers updated in terms of new knowledge, principles and skills. Students stand to gain more from teachers' updated knowledge. According to Omopariola (2017), teachers stand to do their best in their professional discharge if only they possess new skills and knowledge. This what the teacher stands to benefit in their attendance in capacity building programme.

Meanwhile, positive significant relation existed between teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes and teachers' job performance in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria. This implies that the best of teachers can do has to with learning opportunities received in their attendance in conferences, workshops and seminars. Training and retraining of teachers as described by Ayodimeji (2015) as vital and sensitive education activities to rebrand teachers and other key players of educational industry. Teachers should approach capacity' building workshops with much interest hoping to benefit from it. With the knowledge gained teachers, they will be in a better position to impact knowledge, positive attitudes, skills to the students' and the community at large. Often when new scheme are launched in our education system, teacher development is an important aspect of a practicing teacher, it involves the teacher's participation in short period refreshers course, in-service training, seminars, workshops, part-time evening programme, the development programme is needed in order to keep the practicing teacher abreast with new knowledge, ideas, concepts, values and needs of the society, more also rapid trend in the wave of technological changes, is an added impetus to the need to retrain our teachers who are supposed to import these new values to the younger generation.

The results of the operational hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance revealed that there is positive relationship or influence between teacher attendance in capacity building programmes and use of instructional methods and classroom

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management as p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance (p-value of $0.01 < 0.05$ sig. and p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$ sig). These results indicated that teachers' ability and efforts towards the use of instructional methods and classroom management will not just improve but will be blended to cope with the contemporary trends of educational system. Ayodimeji (2015) observed that curriculum of education can only be best translated and use to benefit students only when teachers are in vogue with current circumstances of impacting knowledge in the 21st century.

Conclusion

The art and science of teaching profession is guided by the established principles and ethics. These principles and ethics are subject to change as changes reflect in the life of man and the society to which the programme of education tend to serve. It is a must for teachers to understanding the circumstances that surrounded the changing nature of their profession and seek knowledge and skills to cope with the challenges change might cost. Teaching among other profession of man is complex and dynamic. This is the reason why researching to seek for new knowledge by teachers becomes mandatory. Teachers are known for discovery in their respective areas of specialization. Capacity building programmes is an immediate solution to the current poor or unsatisfied teachers' performance in school and as well as keeping teachers abreast of social and educational changes. Hence, teachers' attendance in programmes like workshop, induction training, seminars and conferences should be encouraged by all education stakeholder to revive the lost glory of secondary education in public schools.

Recommendations

On the accounts of the findings in this study and the conclusion drawn, the followings are here by recommended:

1. The government and other stakeholders that are in-charge of managing public secondary schools should as matter of need attach importance to teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes so as to better the performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools;
2. Government and dedicated regulated body overseeing the affairs of public secondary schools should as matter of concern sponsor teachers to attend various capacity building programmes as regular interval;
3. As part of promotion requirements for teachers in public senior secondary schools; evidence of capacity building programme attendance should be considered as priority; and
4. Corporate and non-governmental organizations should be partner with in sponsoring teachers to attend capacity building programmes.

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Effect of Problem-Based Strategy on Performance in Concept Ecosystem Among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This paper investigated the effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Problem based instructional strategy is relatively new hence the need to ascertain to what extent it would assist at improving the performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in geography. A lot of concerns have hitherto before now been raised by stakeholders on how instructional strategy have been a major challenge to high performance by students in geography. This has necessitated the call for a paradigm change from the traditional method to the one being investigated in this work. It was on this note that its effect is being investigated before long. A total number of three (3) research objectives, research questions and hypotheses each were formulated in this study. The research design used in this study was quasi experimental research, using researcher designed Geography Achievement test. The target population for this study was comprised of five thousand, five hundred and forty - eight (5,548) SS II students from Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of three hundred and fifty - seven (357) respondents was therefore selected at random using simple sampling technique for the study. It thus represented two (2) study schools with two (2) classes of students from SS II involved in this study, one was the controlled group (conventional method) and the other, is the experimental group (problem - based strategy). Sole instrument used in this study was validated and adjudged reliable via Cronbach alpha (α) reliability, reliability co - efficient scores obtained for the instrument was 0.882. Data analyses were undertaken through the use of inferential statistics. Kruskal Wallis, Independent t - test and one way analysis of variance statistics were used in the testing of hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that there is significant effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. In addition, the study revealed that significant gender difference exists in the effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. In conclusion, significant effect of problem - based strategy resulted to increase in performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem. The study therefore recommended that the use of problem - based strategy should be encouraged among geography teachers through constant supervision. That Geography teacher should be motivated to using these modern methods of teaching through sponsorship to workshops and in - house trainings.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Effects, Geography, Problem - Based Learning

Introduction

The important role of teachers in the teaching - learning process in and around the schools cannot be underestimated. Teachers are noted to play a lot of influences in their classroom practices. They therefore need to apply specific abilities and skills without which their influence may not reflect in students' performance in their subject. Consequently, the need to use appropriate and effective instructional strategy to make students easily transfer what is taught in schools and apply such to solve problems in real life situation has become imperative. The teaching of concept ecosystem has featured in Geography before now was popular with the traditional approach that is gradually fading out (Getso & Haruna, 2021). This perhaps could be due to poor performance of students in Geography generally as attested to, by various external reports of West African

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Examinations Council and other bodies. Bearing this in mind, the need to explore other instructional method such as problem - based learning which is relatively new has become essential. Problem - based learning (PBL) is a well - established learner centred and inquiry - oriented instructional strategy. Rosing in Hirca cited by Idris (2023) explained that students in a PBL classroom try to look for information, access learning material and share ideas among themselves while working in small groups. PBL is new from the known traditional method of teaching. Perhaps, since there is an alarming outcry that teachers tend to dominate the whole classroom activities, making the learners passive listeners, inactive and dull. Also, making the teaching process un lively, uninteresting, unproductive, unreal and less permanent in the learners' mind in most cases.

Therefore, an alarming call for a shift from the common, olden days traditional teacher - centred method of teaching to a more productive learner centred, activity centred, child centred or experienced centred approach for improved performance by the students. According to Adedokun & Jamu cited by Idris (2015), Geography is an old discipline from the basis of human knowledge about his environment, the world and his relationship with the element of environment. In view of this, Geography can be viewed as a subject that focuses on disciplinary change and paradigm shift which makes the use of appropriate teaching method important for its teaching and learning. The need for the use of problem - based strategy (PBS) in concept ecosystem in Geography stems from the belief that it is an abstract subject that needs to be centralized for students to appreciate as a school subject. Geography as a school subject is very important and useful to students and everyone who seeks to cope with the ever - emerging realities of the present time. This is because the earth which is the focus of geography study is the theater where virtually all human activities are carried out. And it is only reasonable that man knows about the nature and character of the earth, as well as the consequences of interactions between man and his environment. The above concept had further lend itself to varied meanings by different scholars, among which are Akintade (2011); Abidoye & Ogunniyi (2012) and Idris (2015).

Academic performance on the other hand represents learning outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. As observed by the researchers, every individual is born with certain potentialities and peculiarities, but it is the teacher that helps bring out such potentialities in the learners. Ability of the teacher to dominate the class activities makes the learners idle, the lesson bored and the environment dull. For improved performance in learners' academics, the teachers' roles have to embrace learning by doing, making the lesson lively and interactive too. Learner's participation is encouraged such that all will be carried along in the entire teaching process. By so doing, students' performance tends to improve and more investments can be committed to it by the different stakeholders. The sad scenario however is, most geography teachers don't display such skills in their teaching. This calls for research such as the present one being conceived.

Academic performance is determined by many factors and it thus means the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals. It is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average of a student (Talib & Sansgiry, 2012). Some of these factors include teachers' subject mastery, textbooks availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratory and many other factors (Chinyoka & Naidu, 2013). Performance could also mean "achievement" in a course taught by the teacher reflecting the quality and quantity of a student's work during a given period". Academic performance thus represents learning outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, or university. The field of academic achievement which can be used interchangeably is wide-ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes.

Academic performance of learners has in recent times attracted the attention of scholars, parents, policy-makers and planners. This was because the amount of investment by governments and parents on schools and learners are far what is obtainable now. Quality education, manpower and infrastructural facilities that do not justify what is on ground. Suneetha & Mayuri (2001) in their contributions opine that the major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic excellence by students. According to them, the school may have other peripheral objectives; emphasis is thus always placed on the performance of students in and outside the school settings. Besides, virtually everybody concerned with education places much premium on academic performance; excellent academic performance by children is often the expectation of parents..

Problem Based Learning (PBL) is an instructional (and curricular) learner - centered approach that empowers learners to conduct research, integrate theory and practice, and apply knowledge and skills to develop a viable solution to a definite problem. PBL is further described as an educational strategy where learning is driven by a problem. The problem could be a challenge or a description of a difficulty, a curious outcome, or an unexpected happening. It could also be an incident where there are interesting elements or an episode or occurrence that requires either a solution or some explanation. PBL as an educational strategy assists the students to take up responsibility for their own learning. In the teaching profession, the ability to direct and regulate one's own learning experience is crucial to its success.

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PBL facilitates not only the acquisition and organization of knowledge, but also the development of several other desirable attributes, such as communication skills, teamwork, problem-solving skills, self-directed learning, sharing of information and identification of personal strengths and weaknesses (Neville, 1999 in Williams, 2001).

Geography is one of the activity - based school subject offered at the senior secondary school levels. It has however, been observed that many Geography teachers still use old instructional strategy that are ineffective and cannot meet the needs of the twenty - first century learners. This is contrary to what is expected or could deliver better results and responses from students in terms of their interest and performance in geography. Bearing this in mind, there is a need to employ a better and more suitable method of teaching as anticipated in problem - based learning (PBL). In the past, teaching used to be teacher - centred, where the teacher takes the lead and is at the centre of classroom activities. It is important to stress that there is thus a paradigm shift in the twenty first century classroom from teacher - centred to learner- centered approach. Although, efforts put in place by teachers to effectively teach geography in Nigerian secondary schools is not satisfactory when compared with students' performance in the subject. To further buttress this point, the report of external examiners of West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO) for May 2016 and thereafter indicated that the students performed poorly in geography (Mohenty, 2016). Studies have further shown a decline in students' performance in science and geography in particular and this has been attributed to the fact that strategies of teaching used in classrooms are not very effective (Bichi in Kawu, Arabi and Murtala, 2023). Obviously, students' performance is being used as one of the predictors of overall quality of education system. To this end, Usman (2018) stated that the quality of education that teachers provide to students is dependent upon what the teachers do in the classroom. Sanlera (2016) pointed out that despite the existence of learning theories (detailing how people learn), most teacher still dispense information using traditional methods without regard to students learning activities. It was on account of all this, that study on effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State has become imperative.

Objectives of the Study

The study assessed effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.
2. Determine the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.
3. Determine the interactive effect of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone?
2. What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?
3. What is the interactive effects of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Hypotheses

The following null - hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

- HO₁** There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.
- HO₂** There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.
- HO₃** There is no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

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Methodology

This study adopted quasi - experimental research design. It thus connotes that two (2) groups exists namely experimental and controlled groups. Students were taught using different instructional strategies (lecture and problem-based) under the different groups with a view to ascertain what their performances would be. The controlled group (lecture method) is for SS II students of GSS K/Kuyanbana while the experimental group (problem - based learning) covered SS II students of Government Commercial College, Zaria. Treatment was given to the experimental group alone since it is the focal point for this study. The choice of the two (2) selected schools was supported by this type of research design been undertaken. It does not allow for the selection of many schools since it is experimental in nature. The target population of this study was comprised of eight hundred and eleven (811) Geography students from the selected senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. A sample size of three hundred and fifty - seven (357) respondents was selected at random from the targeted population. In view of this, only SS II students offering Geography as a school subject were involved in this study. The study employed the use of achievement test as sole instrument for data collection. A pilot study was carried out in Government Secondary School, Muchia using forty (40) geography students of equal proportion of both sexes. The reliability test scores for the instrument was 0.882 for the achievement test. Permission was sought from the Inspectorate Division Data collection was undertaken within ten (10) weeks. Research assistants were identified, trained and motivated on how to assist in the administration of instrument. The data analysis was carried out on the formulated hypotheses using inferential statistics such as t - test statistics, one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and descriptive means statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance for acceptance or rejection.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics effect of problem - based instructional strategy on concept ecosystem on students' performance in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	Remarks
Performance	Experimental	202	50.83	10.23	6.370	Problem based learning has positive effect on students' performance
	Control	156	44.46	7.77		

Source: Field Work (2023)

The descriptive statistics above showed that Problem based strategy has positive effect on performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in the Zone. Their computed mean performance scores are 50.8292 and 44.4583 by experimental and control group respectively in favour of the experimental group who were exposed to the problem- based strategy implying a positive effect on performance in the concept ecosystem as one of the topics in geography.

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 2: Descriptive mean statistics on mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone in Kaduna State

Variable	Gender groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	Remarks
Exp	(Male)	132	56.1061	9.91741		The mean performance scores of experimental male and female groups are far higher than those of
	(Female)	69	57.3623	10.47963		

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Academic Performance	Control (Male)	107	45.5047	10.35718	male and female mean score of control group
	Control (Female)	49	40.5306	8.41403	

Source: Field Work (2023)

The results of above descriptive statistics showed that there is positive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in the Zone. The experimental male and experimental female performance mean scores are 56.1061 and 57.3623, while control male and control female performance scores are 45.5047 and 40.5306 respectively. This shows that both experimental male and experimental female have remarkable higher mean scores than their counterparts in the control group.

Research Question 3

What is the interactive effects of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on interactive effects of Problem-based strategy on mean performance of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem in Zaria Educational Zone in Kaduna State

Groups	Gender	N	Mean	STD
Experimental	Male	132	50.4545	9.96644
	Female	69	51.8623	10.47963
	Total	201	50.9378	10.14149
Control	Male	107	45.6075	7.50347
	Female	49	41.9490	7.87880
	Total	156	44.4583	7.78646
Total	Male	239	48.2845	9.25109
	Female	118	47.7458	10.64717
	Total	357	48.1064	9.72298

Source: Field Work (2023)

Results in table 3 above showed that there was interactive effect of problem - based strategy on male and female geography students using ecosystem in the Zone where the study was conducted. The computed mean statistics showed that at the experimental group the computed mean performance scores are 50.454 and 51.862 for male and female geography students respectively, while at the control group the computed mean performance score are 45.807 and 41.949 for male and female geography students also. Invariably, this shows that there was an interactive effect of the problem - based strategy on male and female geography taught ecosystem in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 4: Independent t - test statistics on effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	df	T-Cal	T-Crit	P-value
Performance	Expr	202	50.8292	10.233	6.37087	356	6.463	1.96	0.000
	Cntrl	156	44.4583	7.786					

Source: Field Work (2023)

p value < 0.05, t cal> 1.96 at df 356

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Outcome of the independent t - test statistics revealed that there was significant difference on the effect of problem - based strategy and performance of students in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna state. The calculated p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and their t calculated value of 6.370 is higher than the 1.96 t critical value at df 356. Their computed mean performance scores are 50.8292 and 44.4583 for experimental and controlled groups respectively in favour of experimental group who were exposed to the problem-based strategy implying a positive effect on performance in concept ecosystem in geography. Therefore, null hypothesis which says there is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone is hereby rejected.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics on significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Gender groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	df	f-cal	f-crit	PValue
Academic Performance	Exp (Male)	132	56.1061	9.917		3	49.705	2.60	0.000
	Exp (Female)	69	57.3623	10.480					
	Control (Male)	107	45.5047	10.357					
	Control (Female)	49	40.5306	8.414					

Source: Field Work (2023)

P calculated < 0.05, f calculated > f critical at df 3

The results of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics showed that there was significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna state. Reasons being that the calculated p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. The experimental male and experimental female performance scores are 56.1061 and 57.3623, while controlled male and controlled female performance scores are 45.5047 and 40.5306 respectively. This shows that both experimental male and female groups have significantly higher mean scores than their counterparts in the controlled group. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State, is hereby *rejected*.

HO₃ There is no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 6: Descriptive mean statistics on interactive effect of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Groups	Gender	Mean	STD	N
Experimental	Male	50.4545	9.96644	132
	Female	51.8623	10.47963	69
	Total	50.9378	10.14149	201
Control	Male	45.6075	7.50347	107
	Female	41.9490	7.87880	49
	Total	44.4583	7.78646	156
Total	Male	48.2845	9.25109	239
	Female	47.7458	10.64717	118
	Total	48.1064	9.72298	357

Source: Field Work (2023)

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Results of the above table 6 showed that there was significant interactive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. This was on account that at the groups versus gender levels, the calculated p-value of 0.015 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the t calculated value of 5.941 is greater than the 3.00 F critical value at df 1. The computed mean statistics showed that at the experimental group the computed mean performance scores are 50.454 and 51.862 for male and female geography students respectively, while at the controlled group the computed mean performance scores are 45.807 and 41.949 for male and female geography students also. This was an evident that there was an interactive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. Therefore, the null hypothesis which showed that there is no no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State is hereby rejected.

Discussions of Findings

This study assessed the effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. A total of three (3) null hypotheses were tested in line with the specific objectives and research questions of the study. In hypothesis I, significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone was tested. The result of the test conducted using t - test statistics revealed that the respondents were of the opinion that problem - based strategy was of significant effect on performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in geography in the study area. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected on account of this. The finding here concurred with Wright, Horn & Sanders (1997) that the most important factor influencing student learning is the teacher.

Teachers stand in the interface of the transmission of knowledge, values and skills in the learning process. If the teacher is ineffective, students under the teacher's tutelage will achieve inadequate progress academically. This is regardless of how similar or different the students are in terms of individual potential in academic achievement. Since PBL was found to have positive effect on students' academic achievement and that the teacher plays a vital role in actualizing that, geography teachers need to be conversant with this learning strategy so that they should employ it in their instructional process for effectiveness and efficiency, as well as ensuring high academic performance. It is one thing to know the strategy, another thing is to have the technical know - how on when and where to apply it having improved this on the teachers. It is assumed that students' concentration and achievement in class performance, end of term examination, promotion examination and final year examination with improve to the positive. This position concurs with that of research question I with PBL having a positive effect on students' achievement.

Null hypothesis II tested the significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. The result of the test revealed that there was significant difference in performances of male and female geography students taught concept ecosystem in geography in Kaduna State. The null hypothesis formulated in this regard was therefore accepted and rejected. The findings here agreed with Adeyemi (2010) and Yala & Wanjohi (2011) who found out that teachers' experience and educational qualifications are the prime predictors of students' academic achievement irrespective of their gender affiliations. In science education, attitude toward science is an important factor affecting both male and female students' science achievement as well as students' alternative conceptions and misconceptions.

It is a clear indication from the analysis that PBL is gender friendly. Meaning that both male and female students liked the approach that is, why it doesn't indicate any change or difference in their academic attitudes. Geography teachers being just and sincere need to embrace this approach so that equal treatment and attention can be given to the students. Despite the extroertic nature of male and introbatric nature of female, the PBL seemed highly appropriate and suitable to diagnose, handle, guide, direct, assist and counsel students' attitudes to the positive for better and stable behavior and conducive learning environment. As teachers' experience and qualification form an integral part of moulding students' behavior, they should be up and doing in serving as parents, friends as well as role model who inspires his students for better interest and positive attitudes. Besides, research question IV concurred that positive effect exists between gender and students' attitude to Geography as far as the use of PBL is concerned in the classrooms.

In null hypothesis III, significant interactive effect between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

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was tested. The result revealed that the two variables were significantly correlated against one another viz - a - viz the significant interactive effect of male and female secondary school geography students taught concept ecosystem in the study area. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. The finding here is a reflection of statement credited to Zhou, Huang & Tian (2013) who concluded that task-based learning improves student's analytical skills and ability to personalize learning. Students are able to evaluate and infer into contents learnt while making reasonable conclusion. In their own contributions, Sungur & Tekkaya (2006) asserted that the use of PBL is found to enhance self - regulatory skills in students thereby improving academic performance. The students are able to explore other ways of learning through the use of PBL.

Students' interactivity with learning and learning materials is the demand of learner centeredness. Observations from this study equally revealed that when students are exposed to identifying problems by themselves and solving that problem according to their peculiarities and differences, such interaction makes learning meaningful, interacting, real and permanent in them. What they have done will stay permanent and can easily be recalled at anytime the need arises. The same approach can make them think critically and have diversified approaches to handling similar problems on their own without teacher's guide. Geography teachers should take that as a challenge for them to study and master this approach thoroughly when applied to their lessons for effective and efficient instructional process, as well as improvement on student's academic achievement.

Conclusion

It can be deduced from the analysis of data and hypotheses tested for this study that problem-based strategy no doubt has improved the performances of students taught concept ecosystem in geography. This may not be limited to schools used for this study alone but across to other secondary schools if same instructional strategy is adopted. Also, there was significant difference between performances of male and female geography students taught concept ecosystem in secondary schools of the study Zone. Absolutely, problem-based strategy stands as a better method of teaching when compared with the lecture method. It is therefore essential that its use be encouraged across all school subjects by teachers for which higher performances are targeted.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations put forward as a result of the outcome of this study:

1. The use of problem-based learning strategy should be encouraged among geography teachers through constant supervision of the geography teachers.
2. The attitude of the students can be further enhanced in geography lesson by proper monitoring of the students by involving the students in the lesson.
3. Geography teachers should be provided all the necessary teaching facilities and infrastructures such as teaching aids and conducive learning environment.

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Effective School Health Hygiene: A Tool for Sustainable Public Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examines the effective school health hygiene: a tool for sustainable public health education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Relevant literature were reviewed such as concept of health education, health education programme, components of health education programme, school health, health aspect of school, public health, school health as a strategy to improve public health education, problems associated with the school health. Therefore, the study recommends that student involvement should be encourage in the health initiatives such as forming health clubs or peer education programs, parent engagement in health education by offering workshops and resources to support healthy habit at home, to encourage regular assessments and screening for student to identify and address health issues earlier, Community partnerships in collaboration with local health care providers, public health agencies and community organizations to expand health education resources.

Keywords: School health, Public Health Education.

Introduction

Schools are essential for young people to acquire knowledge, socio emotional skills including self regulation, resilience and critical thinking skills that provide the foundation for a healthy future. Access to education, safe and supportive school environments have been linked to better health outcomes (Muhammad & Haruna, 2021). Furthermore, good health is linked to reduced drop-out rates and greater educational attainment, educational performance, employment and productivity. World Health Organisation has long recognized the link between health and education and the potential for schools to play a crucial role in safeguarding student health and well being. In 1995, WHO launched the Global School Health Initiative which aimed to strengthen approaches to health promotion in schools, among those approaches include pairing children with health services occupies an important place (World Health Organisation, 2006).

Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education

Health education refers to consciously constructed opportunities for learning involving some form of communication designed to improve health literacy including improving knowledge and developing life skills which are conducive to individual and community health (WHO, 2006). [School Health Encyclopedia](#), (2019) sees Health education as education that consists of a planned, sequential curriculum that addresses physical, mental, emotional and social dimensions of health. Health services are provided to students to appraise, protect, and promote health. These services include the provision of emergency and primary care access and referral to community health services and management of chronic health conditions. A healthy school

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environment attends to the physical and aesthetic surroundings and to a psychosocial climate and culture that maximizes the health of students and staff. Health education is a profession of educating people about health. Areas within this profession encompass environmental health, physical health, social health, emotional health, intellectual health and spiritual health as well as sexual and [reproductive health education](#) (Donatelle, 2009). Health education can be defined as the principle by which individuals and groups of people learn to behave in a manner conducive to the promotion, maintenance, or restoration of [health](#) (UNESCO, 2018).

According to United State Joint Committee on Health Education and Promotion Terminology, (2001), Health education is any combination of planned learning experiences based on sound theories that provide individuals, groups and communities the opportunity to acquire information and the skills needed to make quality health decisions. Health education is systematic process of imparting knowledge, skills, attitude and behavior toward anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of communicable and non-communicable diseases, sanitation, pollution and all other forms of threat that may hinder well-being of individual and community.

Health Education Programme at Secondary School Level of Education

Health education programme is any planned activity or set of activities aimed at increasing health literacy and developing life skills conducive to health e.g. decision making, problem solving, critical thinking, interpersonal skills and stress management coping with emotions. Health education programmes are designed to promote awareness and knowledge regarding various aspects of human health. The programme is aim to educate individuals on disease prevention, healthy lifestyles and the importance of regular health screenings, these programmes play a vital role in public health by empowering individuals to take responsibility for their own health and well being (WHO, 1998).

Components of School Health Programme at Secondary School Level of Education

Number of factors influences the physical and mental health of school children and their learning process. These factors include health conditions of the children themselves, physical and social environment in their school, quality of life of their parents, their own knowledge about health promoting practices and availability of health services around them. These factors according to UNESCO, (2010) can be achieved through the following components:

4. **School Health Environment:** School environment plays a pivotal role in the retention and learning outcomes of students. Availability of proper facilities is a pre-requisite for creating a healthy environment in a school. Provision of following facilities contributes in creating a conducive environment for the children in the school such as Safe clean drinking water (with regular water quality monitoring), Gender and culturally appropriate sanitation/toilet facilities, adequately spacious class rooms with comfortable seating arrangements and Play grounds etc. and child friendly environment access for disabled and physically challenged.
5. **School Health Education:** Children are at a greater risk of various infections and diseases. Schools have the responsibility to educate their students and foster among them healthy and hygienic behaviour. They need to warn their students about various health risks and guide them how to protect themselves and others against diseases and other forms of ill-health by adopting health and hygiene promoting habits and practices.
6. **School Health Services:** Young children are prone to many diseases. In the developing countries, where health services for the general public are poor and overall knowledge about health care is low, parents and teachers are unable to detect health problem of children which impede their learning. Provision of health services to the children and young students in following forms fall under this category; Health screening (medical checkup) of students on regular basis, Referral of students with health problems to medical centres for treatment or rehabilitation, De-worming campaigns among others.
7. **School Nutrition Programmes:** Nutritional level affects overall health and consequently the pace of learning among the children. Nutritional inputs can increase both attendance and quality of education. Provision of following inputs to schools can be grouped under nutrition component of school health programme such as. Good supplements for malnourished children, Food as incentive to enhance enrolment and attendance, Promotion of use of iodized salt School feeding or school lunch programme for all students in schools.

School Health Hygiene at Secondary School Level of Education

School health is the comprehensive efforts of developing, implementing and evaluating services both within the school and the community that provide each and every student with the resources needed to thrive within a healthful environment,

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(American school health association, 2023). School Health can also be describe as a process of enhancing the health attitude and practices in school which may be applicable to maintain physical, mental and social well being in the community.

Health Aspect at Secondary School Level of Education

It is widely recognized that schools can play an important role in promoting society's health. Much effort has been invested over recent years in health education techniques for schools in low income communities including child to child methods, curriculum development and the productions of locally appropriate education materials. However, the impact of the actual fabric and management of school premises on child health has been relatively neglected. Many schools fail to provide healthy environments for their pupils. Poorly designed and maintained schools can be a source of disease and ill health. Sick children also make poor learners. It is therefore, the concept tempting to suggest that all these problems are the products of poverty and that the answer is to improved socio economic status of one's nation (Abraham, et al, 2005).

Public Health at Secondary School Level of Education

Is the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts and informed choices of society, organizations, public, private, communities and individuals (Gatseva & Argirova, 2011). To Abraham, et al, (2005) Public health also refers to the aggregate at which health is been maintain in the community that include sanitation, structural safety, nuisance prevention, water supply and quality, pollution, pest and insect control, open defecation management, waste management and improve indoor air quality among others.

School Health for Sustainable Public Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education

It must be stressed that, there is no simple technical strategy for achieving and improving a healthy school community or environment; hence there is need to synchronize or practice the following strategy in Nigeria as mentioned by Abraham et al, (2005).

- 4 **Commitment and Motivation:** There is no doubt that, the single and most important factor in achieving a healthy school environment is the presence of committed and informed people. The emphasis should be on the commitment as there are plenty of evidence that shows the information is not enough, People are often well aware of the health risks and the theories of contamination but do not act on that knowledge. People who are not committed will always find reasons for not acting while a committed person will seek ways around apparently insuperable problems, if necessary committed people will also seek out information. There is no simple formula for making people committed. However, recognizing and valuing people's efforts and ensuring that there is sufficient scope for their own decision making and creativity can go a long way towards encouraging sustained commitment. The essence of commitment is a person's belief that his or her efforts can make a difference.
- 5 **Free Environment:** Evidently, faeces on the ground will be a threat to health. The point to be made though is that of staff, pupils, parents and governing bodies of schools should consider the whole school environment not just classrooms but ideally concern should extend to the streets and fields between home and school include the school compound. Success in eliminating material from a school compound is dependent on informed and responsible pupils, supervision of young children that may defecate around, compound fence, and vigilance to stop animals and outsiders from defecating in the compound rather going toilets which are conveniently located, reliable, clean, reasonably odour free and reasonably private.
- 6 **Safe Drinking Water:** The condition required for clean water is well known but often they are unachievable. Recommendations to boil all water are of little value in a society where fuel is expensive and scarce. Advice about deep boreholes is of no use to a resource starved school. Rather than concentrating on the source of the water, achievable measures are often those concerned with the handling of available water. Frequently, water from a tap or pump is reasonably clean, but has become contaminated by the time it reaches someone's mouth. For example, if people are dipping their hands into a water container to scoop up water in a cup, it may likely contaminating it with germs from their hands. Similarly, in some circumstances covering the water container with a lid may be an important step.
- 7 **Convenient Hand Washing Arrangements:** In many countries awareness is widespread of the importance of washing one's hands after defecation. It is reasonable to suppose that it is one of the central planks of all school health education programmes. However, it is equally clear that hand washing is a practice that is widely ignored. Spreading the message of the importance of hand washing is not enough and it must also be an easy and convenient thing to do. People will not

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normally go out of their way to wash their hands if the tap or water source is distant from the toilet, people are unlikely to use it if water is stored in a relatively high sided tank and it may be difficult for younger children to use. Similarly, wells with high sides may discourage people from drawing water. Taps or water tanks which are constantly surrounded by mud may be discouraging. Hand pumps may be too stiff for a small child to use or it may be difficult to pump and wash one's hands at the same time.

- 8 **Structural Safety:** It is obvious that, the health of children will not be enhanced if the school building falls down. This is more the concern of engineers and builders, but teaching staff should check their school rooms on occasional basis for cracks in the main structure of more immediate importance are small scale structural issues or problems like doors falling off their hinges, rotten floor boards, broken glass, exposed nails and broken paving stones. While large scale structural problems are likely to require significant amounts of money to solve, a simple but systematic safety audit can reveal hazards which have simple remedies in many societies, communal work sessions are traditional. If parents can be persuaded to work together even just for one day once a year then such a labour force will inevitably include people with specialist skills can tackle much of the heavier structural repair work. Working together, parents can accomplish tasks such as clearing away broken concrete, rebuilding eroded steps, replacing rotten fence posts, relaying roofing sheets and repairing furniture and play equipment etc.
- 9 **Adequate Cleaning and Maintenance:** Problems of structural safety can often be avoided through careful routine maintenance. Dealing with broken roof tiles or undermined foundations straightaway as soon as they occur, minimizes the need for expensive structural repairs later. Often, where a capital budget is available for construction but resources for routine upkeep inadequate, the result is dilapidated buildings which need to be replaced far earlier than should be necessary. The key to good maintenance is not letting the situation deteriorate too far before taking action. Broken, clogged or soiled toilets in particular will deteriorate rapidly if action is not taken immediately.

Problems Associated with School Health at Secondary School Level of Education

There are many problems associated with the school health and these problems can hinder well being of school children, staffers and parent as well as individuals members in the community as cited by Abraham et al, (2005) and include the following;

4. **Location of the School:** In many cases the most dangerous aspect of a school is its location, when informal urban settlements grow up, the best land is generally taken at the outset for residential houses. Schools are often built on the least desirable land for example, on the site of an old waste dump or in areas prone to flooding or subsidence. Schools are also often located on busy roads increasing the risk of accidents or at some distance from the community they are intended to serve.
5. **Indoor Air Quality:** There is a wide range of potential indoor air pollutants which may influence the health of school children. Pollution from heating stoves can lead to chronic respiratory diseases and carcinomas. In a crowded environment, airborne bacteria and viruses can cause cross infection. Other threats include rotten matter produced by moulds and fungal growths, fine dust, gaseous and particulate compounds from building materials and radon gas. Many health problems are associated with these pollutants including acute respiratory infections and asthma.
6. **Noise:** High levels of noise can cause irritation, encourage aggressiveness, reduce physical and mental performance, and cause discomfort and headaches. Exceedingly loud and continual noise can lead to more serious problems. Children with hearing problems, visually impaired children, and children with learning difficulties are particularly dependent on a good acoustic environment.
7. **Sanitation:** Without sufficient clean and functioning toilets children will defecate in and around the school compound. In such situations the school and its surroundings are likely to become infested with parasite. Neglected school compounds tend to accumulate waste both from within the school itself and dumped by people from outside. When waste builds up because of a municipal strike for example, school grounds are likely to become a natural dumping site since they probably represent one of the few accessible open spaces. If the case was left unquiet, school buildings adjacent to health buildings, medical waste including items such as used syringes can frequently be found on the ground which may be very harmful and of a greater risk to health.
8. **Water Supply:** Many of the oral infections can also spread via contaminated drinking water, Children dipping or putting their unwashed hands into a shared drinking water supply is a typical route of contamination. But problems can also arise from water which is not used for drinking, if rain water or flood water is allowed to stand in puddles or drainages the

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breeding of mosquitoes and other insects may be encouraged and leading to transmission of diseases such as malaria, dengue fever and schistosomiasis. Similar problems can arise from accumulated waste which additionally may attract flies, rodents and dogs.

Conclusion

School health and public health education is not only limited to the dissemination of health related information but rather also fostering the motivation, skills and confidence (self-efficacy) necessary to take action to improve health as well as the communication of information concerning the underlying social, economic and environmental conditions impacting on health as well as individual risk factors and risk behaviors and use of the health care system. The main purpose of school health and public health education therefore is not only to increase knowledge about personal health behaviors but also to develop skills that demonstrate the political feasibility and organizational possibilities of various forms of action to address social, economic and environmental determinants of health.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations outline by the writers;

1. Students involvement should be encourage in the health initiatives such as forming health clubs or peer education programs.
2. Parent's engagement in health education by offering workshops and resources to support healthy habit at home.
3. To encourage regular assessments and screening for student to identify and address health issues earlier.
4. Community partnerships in collaboration with local health care providers, public health agencies and community organizations to expand health education resources.
5. Public health advocacy toward maintaining a healthy community.

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Effects of 7Es Model and Problem-Based Strategy on Performance in Wave Motion among Secondary School Students in Bauchi Metropolis

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Abstract

This study examined the effects of 7Es model and problem-based strategy on performance in wave motion among secondary school students in Bauchi Metropolis. Three research questions were answered while three corresponding null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study employed pre-test post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental research design involving two treatment groups. Population for study comprised 3579 (71 Male and 57 Female) Senior Secondary class Two (SS II) students offering Physics during the 2022/2023 Academic session among government secondary schools in Bauchi Metropolis. Sample comprised 128 SS II physics students consisting of 71 males and 57 females obtained using simple random sampling technique by balloting technique. Wave Motion Performance Test (WMPT) with reliability coefficient of 0.80 obtained using Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (K-R 21) was used to collect data. Trained research assistants taught in the sampled schools use lesson plans prepared following tenets of 7Es model and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) strategy. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. Findings revealed: no statistical significant difference in performance of students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those taught using PBL strategy [$F(1,125)=1.756, P=0.188 > 0.05$]. It was concluded that the use of 7Es learning model and PBL strategy enhanced students' academic performance in wave motion. It was recommended among others that, Physics teachers should use 7Es model but PBL should be used with care in attempt to improve male and female students' performance in wave motion.

Keyword: 7Es Learning Model, PBL Strategy, Performance, Wave Motion

Introduction

Physics plays an important role in all the natural sciences, Achor (2020) views Physics as a branch of natural science which deals with matter, its motion and behaviour through space and time and the related entities of energy and force. The ultimate aim of Physics is to explain unified set of laws governing matter, motion, and energy at small (microscopic) subatomic distances and human (macroscopic) scale of everyday life. It could also extend to the largest distances like those on the extragalactic scale (Haruna, 2019). Physics knowledge and skills are applied in other branches of sciences such as Biology and Chemistry. However, Physics is reputed to contain concepts that are more abstract compared to other sciences (Achor, 2020) of which one of such concepts is wave motion.

Several researches on the issue of academic performance of secondary school students offering Physics show that there is decline in academic performance of students in Physics (Adeyemo, Babajide & Iwuji, 2014; Omebe & Akani, 2015; Josiah & Mankilik, 2021; Offordile, Umeano, Adene, Obi, Ugwuanyi, Okeke, & Adimora, 2021). Evidence from West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) chief examiners report also attest to the fact that performance of students in Physics has dwindled over the years (WAEC, 2015-2021).

Year	Total Number of Registered candidates	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation
2015	658,393	19.00	9.90
2016	666,992	19.00	8.83
2017	704,504	15.00	8.43
2018	728,924	26.00	9.80

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2019	762,340	26.00	9.95
2020	749,752	34.00	9.33
2021	759,232	22.00	8.37

Source: WAEC Chief Examiners Report (2015-2021).

The teaching and learning of Physics particularly wave motion is faced with some challenges leading to students' poor performance in Physics. The major challenges according to Assem, Nartey, Appiah and Aidoo (2023), are poor quality of Physics teachers and teaching methods employed by these teachers to teach Physics. Especially in abstract Physics concepts like mechanics, electromagnetism, gravitation and wave motion. The use of defective methods of teaching limit students' active involvement in learning of Physics. Hence, this poses serious danger not only as obstacles to students' academic performance but as hindrance in the nations efforts to produce Physics specialists for national scientific and economic development. Students' poor academic performance in Physics at the senior secondary school level means that the number of students opting to study Physics and Physics related courses in higher institutions will decline resulting in low manpower, infrastructural and economic development. As Bunkure (2019) observed, Physics is a pre-requisite for courses like Medicine, Geology, Agricultural Science and Pharmacy. Other are Engineering, Architecture, Astronomy and Physics Education.

The issue of poor performance in Physics is a source of concern as the underperformance of students in Physics has attracted attention of government, researchers, and professional organisations like the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), curriculum planners, Physics teachers, parents and students. Attempts have been made by different stakeholders to emphasize that teaching of science be more student-oriented. Professional organisations like STAN has consistently organize workshops to upgrade teachers on current trends in teaching and learning of science.

Over the years, researchers globally have also conducted studies aimed at improving academic performance of students in Physics. These studies focus on innovative teaching strategies that could enhance students' performance in Physics concepts particularly wave motion. Some of these innovative teaching strategies include the 5Es and 7Es learning model (Onyilo, Tine, Kpiranyam & Wirba, 2022). Others include Problem-Based Learning Strategy, Think-Pair-Share Strategy, Student Team Achievement Division Strategy and Project-Based Learning Strategy among others (Omega, 2017; Kpiranyam, Agbidye & Ukor, 2022; Strobel Education, 2023). For the purpose of this study, the researchers considered the use of 7Es learning model and Problem-Based learning strategy to enhance students' performance in wave motion.

Wave motion is one of the topics taught in Senior Secondary Two (SS II) Physics curriculum. It is a topic considered by students to be difficult because it involves the use of formulas and drawings with lots of related concepts in it such as reflection, refraction, diffraction, interference. Students sometimes have difficulties differentiating between these concepts which could be some of the reasons responsible for poor academic performance. Students' poor performance in wave motion could also be traceable to many other factors among which are the teaching methodologies employed by the teachers (Josiah & Mankilik, 2021). There is therefore the need to use a learner centered approach in the teaching and learning of physics. It is against this backdrop that the researchers sort to see if the use of innovative teaching strategies such as 7Es learning model and Problem-Based learning strategy could enhance students' performance in wave motion.

The 5Es learning model was developed initially by Robert Bybee based on the works of German Philosopher Freidrich Herbert (Bybee, 1997) and was modified by Sadeq (2003) to generate 7Es learning model. The 7Es learning model has seven stages which include Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate and Extend. It aims at enabling students to build their scientific knowledge acquisition by themselves. The 7Es learning model enable learners acquire concepts and apply them in new contexts and real situations thereby developing students' skills of applying scientific method, problem solving ability, engaging in dialogue and team work which may improve their performance in Physics. In addition, it could help students view abstract concepts differently (Khataibeh, 2005; Adesoji & Idika, 2015; Cakir, 2017; Abuh, 2021). Thus, 7Es learning model has the potential and could improve students' academic performance as it enables them construct active knowledge through mind-on and hands-on activities. Cherono, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) posits that this strategy gives learners opportunity to collaborate with peers through interactions, thus learners are able to learn effectively and develop critical thinking skills. The strategy can enhance students' performance in Physics in Benue State (Onyilo, Agernor, Kpiranyam & Wirba, 2022).

Another learning strategy that could help foster students' performance in wave motion is the Problem-Based learning strategy. Problem-Based Learning Strategy (PBL) is a student centred pedagogy. With this strategy, students learn about physics concepts such as wave motion through the experience of problem solving. PBL strategy is the process of acquiring new knowledge based on the recognition of a need to learn. The role of the teacher in a PBL classroom is to facilitate learning by supporting, guiding and monitoring the learning process. The PBL strategy is activity based, promotes interaction among

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learners, encourages active learning and the acquisition of problem solving proficiency among learners. According to Hun School of Princeton (2020), some of the benefits of PBL strategy include promotion of self-learning, high engagement in learning and developing transferable skills. Others are; it improves team work among learners and encourages intrinsic rewards. Researches indicate that PBL strategy can enhance students' performance (Ajai & Imoko, 2015; Omaga, 2017).

Physics classrooms in Nigeria contain male and female students distinguished as such based on biological characteristics. Gender issue permeate science classrooms, Physics inclusive. As regards the use of 7Es learning model, Al-Eid (2014), Balta and Sarac (2016) in their separate studies found no significant difference in the academic performance of students exposed to 7Es learning model based on gender of students. Corroborating the assertion, Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) aptly stated that intrinsically, there is practically no significant difference in the intelligence quotient of males and females that can be traceable to gender difference. Shalini and Anurag, (2018) also reported that 7Es learning model is gender friendly. Similarly, Ibrahim, Lakpini, Abdulkarim and Falau (2022) stated that 7Es learning model can improve students' performance irrespective of their gender. Studies by Mergendollar, Maxwell and Bellisimo (2002), Anyafulude (2014), Ajai and Imoko (2015), Omaga (2017) in other locations showed that PBL does not discriminate in terms of enhancing male and female students' performance. By implication, with PBL strategy, as male and female students collaborate and solve problems, they gain during the learning process which could improve their performance. However, in most secondary schools across the study area of this research, the use of defective methods has resulted in low performance of students in Physics (Usman & Yakubu, 2020; Ogonna & Joseph, 2023). This has necessitated the to explore other ways of salvaging the situation. Thus, this study sought to find out if the use of 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy will enhance students' performance in wave motion.

Evidences abound of underperformance in Physics especially in wave motion among male and female students in senior secondary schools with most students unable to obtain a credit pass (WAEC, Chief Examiners' Report, 2015 -2022). The dwindling performance of male and female students in Physics particularly in wave motion continue to attract considerable attention from government, researchers, curriculum planners, concerned teachers, parents and students.

The fear is that performing poorly in Physics concepts like wave motion may affect male and female students desire to acquire high education in Physics and Physics related areas, thereby, limiting manpower production, scientific and technological development of the nation. Research evidences indicate that the major reasons for persistent low performance in Physics are students' perception of the subject as being abstract. Others are teachers use of defective instructional strategies which produces students with poor problem solving ability, inability to reason critically and lack of curiosity about science especially Physics concepts like wave motion.

It is therefore imperative that innovative instructional strategies of improving students' performance be applied. Consequently, this study aimed to find out the efficacy of 7Es and problem-based learning strategies. The problem of the study posed in questions form is: Will the use of 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy enhance students' performance in wave motion?

Objectives of the Study: The study sought to:

1. determined the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.
2. determined the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.
3. determined the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Research Questions: The following research questions were asked to guide the study.

1. What is the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?
2. What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis?
3. What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Hypotheses: The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

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1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Methodology

The study employed pre-test post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental research design involving two treatment groups. The design was considered appropriate for the study because it is more reliable to use natural intact classes than forming a group through randomization of subjects which makes the subjects suspicious of an unusual activity taking place which may influence the outcome of the study. The subjects used for the study were assigned to two experimental groups. One group was taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model while the second group was taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy. Population consisted of 3,579 Senior Secondary Two (SS II) students in 22 public secondary schools located within Bauchi Town offering Physics in the 2022/2023 academic session (Bauchi State Ministry of Education, 2023). Sample comprised 128 students consisting of 71 male and 57 female SS II students offering physics which was obtained using simple random sampling technique through balloting. Of the two schools sampled, wave motion was taught in one using the 7Es learning model and in the second using Problem-Based Learning Strategy.

The instrument used for data collection was Wave Motion Performance Test (WMPT), the WMPT comprised 20 multiple choice questions with options A-D. The questions were adopted from past WAEC and NECO examination questions. This was done to ensure that the questions used for the study were valid and reliable. Reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson Formula-21 (K-R₂₁) to determine the internal consistency of the instrument.

Before commencement of treatment, the students were pre-tested. After administering the pre-test, students were exposed to treatment using 7Es learning model and Problem-Based Learning Strategy. The treatment lasted for three weeks after which a post-test was administered to them. In answering the research questions, mean and standard deviation was used while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of data analysis and interpretation are presented according to the research questions asked and hypotheses formulated for the study.

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 1: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT Mean and Standard Deviation of 7Es Learning Model and Problem-Based Learning Strategy

Instructional Strategy		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
7E Learning	N	62	62	
	Mean	22.37	30.27	7.90
	Std. Dev	4.42	7.07	
Problem Based Learning	N	66	66	
	Mean	20.97	31.27	10.30
	Std. Dev	5.82	6.13	
	Mean diff.			2.40

Result in Table 1 shows that students taught wave motion using 7Es model had a mean score of 22.37 in pre-WMPT with standard deviation of 4.42 and mean score of 30.27 and standard deviation of 7.07 in the post-WMPT. Students taught wave motion using PBL strategy had a mean score of 20.97 and standard deviation of 5.82 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 31.27 with a standard deviation of 6.13 in the post-WMPT. The result in the table further shows that mean gain in

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performance of students taught wave motion using 7Es model is 7.90 while that of PBL is 10.30. The difference in the mean scores of students taught wave motion using 7Es model those taught wave motion using PBL is 2.40.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 2: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT mean and Standard Deviation showing Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es learning model.

Students' Gender		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
Male	N	35	35	
	Mean	22.86	31.20	8.34
	Std. Dev.	4.03	8.26	
Female	N	27	27	
	Mean	21.74	29.07	7.33
	Std. Dev.	4.90	5.00	
Mean diff.				1.01

Result in Table 2 shows that the mean scores for male students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model is 22.86 with standard deviation of 4.03 in the pre-WMPT and a mean score of 31.20 with standard deviation of 8.26 in the post-WMPT. Female students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model had a mean score of 21.74 with standard deviation of 4.90 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 29.07 with standard deviation of 5.00 in the post-WMPT. The mean gain in performance of male students is 8.34 while for female students, it is 7.33. The mean difference in performance of male and female students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model is 1.01.

Research Question 3

What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 3: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using PBL Strategy

Students' Gender		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
Male	N	36	36	
	Mean	20.97	32.97	12.00
	Std. Deviation	5.42	4.99	
Female	N	30	30	
	Mean	20.97	29.23	8.26
	Std. Deviation	6.35	6.80	
Mean Diff.				3.74

Result in Table 3 shows that the mean scores for male students taught wave motion using PBL strategy is 20.97 with standard deviation of 5.42 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 32.97 with standard deviation of 4.99 in the post-WMPT. Female students taught wave motion using PBL strategy had mean score of 20.97 with standard deviation of 6.35 in the pre-WMPT and a mean score of 29.23 and standard deviation of 6.80 in the post-WMPT. The mean gain in performance of male students is 12.00 while for female students, it is 8.26. The mean difference in performance of male and female students taught wave motion using PBL strategy is 3.74.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

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Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es Learning Model and PBL Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	472.433 ^a	2	236.216	5.848	.004
Intercept	3611.347	1	3611.347	89.410	.000
Pre-Test	440.558	1	440.558	10.907	.001
Strategy	70.927	1	70.927	1.756	.188
Error	5048.872	125	40.391		
Total	126861.000	128			
Corrected Total	5521.305	127			

R Squared = .086 (Adjusted R Squared = .071)

Result in Table 4 reveals that $F(1, 125) = 1.756$ at $P = 0.188 > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.188 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. By implication, there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.

Table 5: ANCOVA Results of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es Learning Model

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	387.518 ^a	2	193.759	4.303	.018
Intercept	783.284	1	783.284	17.394	.000
Pre-Test	318.631	1	318.631	7.076	.010
Gender	35.813	1	35.813	.795	.376
Error	2656.821	59	45.031		
Total	59869.000	62			
Corrected Total	3044.339	61			

R Squared = .127 (Adjusted R Squared = .098)

Result in Table 5 reveals that $F(1, 59) = 0.795$ at $P = 0.376 > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.376 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. By implication, there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Table 6: ANCOVA Results of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using PBL Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	378.625 ^a	2	189.313	5.772	.005
Intercept	3053.026	1	3053.026	93.077	.000
Pre-Test	149.873	1	149.873	4.569	.036
Gender	228.575	1	228.575	6.969	.010
Error	2066.466	63	32.801		
Total	66992.000	66			

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Corrected Total 2445.091 65
R Squared = .155 (Adjusted R Squared = .128)

Result in table 6 shows that $F(1, 63) = 6.969$ at $P = 0.010 < 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.010 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

Results from hypothesis one shows that no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis. The outcome in this study however, does not confirm with that of Cheron, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) whose result showed statistical significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using 7Es learning cycle and those taught using the conventional instructional method. However, Cheron, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) compared 7Es learning cycle with a conventional instructional method and used t-test without determining group homogeneity. These reasons may account for the inconsistency in findings. The finding in this study means that adopting effective instructional strategies like 7Es learning cycle and PBL will enhance meaningful learning and improve performance in Physics concepts like wave motion.

The finding of hypothesis two reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis. This means that the use of 7Es learning model can enhance students' academic performance irrespective of gender. This is in agreement with research findings by Ibrahim, Lakpini, Abdulkarim and Falau (2022) and Shalini and Anurag, (2018) who said that 7Es learning model can improve students' academic performance irrespective of their gender. This implies that 7Es learning model is gender friendly.

Finding from hypothesis three reveals that a significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis. This implies that male students performed better than their female counterparts when taught wave motion using PBL strategy. This contradicts research findings by Omega (2017), [Ajai and Imoko \(2015\)](#), [Anyafulude \(2014\)](#) who found that PBL strategy is non-discriminatory as regards gender, that is, it enhances the academic performance of both male and female students.

Conclusion

The use of innovative learning strategies such as 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy helped enhanced students' academic performance particularly in wave motion. However, as regards gender, the use of 7Es was found to enhance students' academic performance irrespective of gender but with PBL male students performed better than their female counterparts in wave motion.

Recommendations

It is therefore recommended that:

1. Physics teachers should endeavour to use innovative learning strategies such as the 7Es learning model to improve students' performance in wave motion.
2. Workshops, seminars and conferences could be organized to enlighten Physics teachers on the use of innovative strategies such as 7Es model to help improve male and female students' academic performance in Physics.
3. The PBL strategy should be used with care in attempt to improve male and female students' performance in wave motion.

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Effects of Cashless Policy on Business Activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State

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Abstract

This study investigates the Effects of cashless policy on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State. Three research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of seven hundred and twenty-three (723) shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local government, Kano State. Sample size of 248 Shoe Sellers were selected using research advisor's table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is cashless policy and business activities (CAPABA) Questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, the reliability correlation coefficient of 0.728 was obtained using Cronbach alpha method. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that internet banking, point of Sales and Automated Teller Machine had significant effect on business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Kano State. Base on the findings it was concluded that cashless policy affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon gari market. It was further recommended that association of shoe Sellers in the market should collaborate with internet service providers to improve internet connectivity within the market, workshops and seminars to educate sellers on cashless transactions and digital financial services to be conducted at regular intervals.

Keywords: *cashless policy, business activities, shoe sellers and Market*

Introduction

The emergence of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has led to great revolutionary developments in finance, economics, and operations, which included the development of electronic payment instruments as well. Electronic payment instruments have come to the attention and attracted the attention of researchers for the importance of their vital role in the current era of electronic commerce (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019). As a result, it leads to different perspectives on the definitions of cashless, among others, from different perspectives, ranging from finance, business technology, to information

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systems. Ajayi (2014) defines cashless as a form of financial instrument, where buyers and sellers are facilitated by electronic communication. More specifically, cashless payments as electronic value payments, transacted from payer to recipient through a comprehensive electronic payment channel, which allows payers to freely access and manage their transactions through electronic networks. Cashless policy is an economy where transaction can be done without necessarily carrying physical cash as a means of exchange of transaction but rather with the use of credit or debit card payment for goods and services. The cashless economy policy initiative of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is a move to improve the financial terrain but in the long run sustainability of the policy will be a function of endorsement and compliance by end-users. The CBN cash policy stipulates a daily cumulative limit of N150, 000 and N1, 000,000 on free cash withdrawals and lodgments by individual and corporate customers respectively in the Kano, State with effect from March 30, 2012. Individuals and corporate organizations that make cash transactions above the limits will be charged a service fee for amounts above the cumulative limits (Daniel 2020).

The introduction of electronic banking, online transactions and mobile banking in Nigeria has paved way for a new era of development where the use and demand for physical cash is gradually declining. These recent evolution of technology in the Nigerian financial institutions possess interesting questions for economist, financial institutions, business analyst and the government regarding the current economic status, logistics, and availability of instruments to guarantee economic growth and stability, efficiency and effectiveness of the cashless policy (Humphrey, 2021). The CBN and Pro cashless policy activists have asserted reduction in crime rates, minimized risk associated with carrying huge sums of money, reduction in political corruption, reduction in banking cost, improvement on monetary policy in management of inflation and the overall growth and development of the economy of Nigeria as advantages associated with the implementation of the cashless policy (Humphrey, 2017). The recent evolution of technology for financial transactions poses interesting questions for policy makers and financial institutions regarding the suitability of current institutional arrangements and availability of instruments to guarantee financial stability, efficiency and effectiveness of monetary policy. Over the course of history, different forms of payment systems have been in existence. Initially, 'trade by barter' was common; however, the problems of barter such as the double coincidence of wants necessitated the introduction of various forms of money. Nevertheless, analysts have been predicting the complete demise of study instruments and the emergence of potentially superior substitute for cash or monetary exchanges, that is, 'cashless society'.

According to Sabi (2014) the advent of internet technology has revolutionized the way business and services are provided by companies and businesses all over the world. It provided innumerable service innovations for the consumer. They started using the internet technology to deliver banking and financial services. The technological change has brought the rapid transmission of information, the easy way for marketing banking products and enhanced the customer's access and awareness. Banks can use the opportunities offered by the internet as strategic tools and revolutionized the way they operate. Point of Sale (POS) terminals are deployed to merchant locations where users swipe their electronic cards through them in order to make payment for purchases or services instead of using raw cash. As the POS terminals are online real-time, the customers bank account is debited immediately for value of purchases made or services enjoyed. The POS terminal is also known as a POP terminal and is used for instant payment of goods and services, as it is user-friendly, easy to operate, and has multi-functional capabilities (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Muritala, 2022). POS terminals allow customers to access their linked bank accounts in real-time through debit or credit cards (Iwedi, 2017). They are considered by Awoniyi (2022) as a virtual replacement for cash transactions.

Osang (2017) view POS terminal as a device deployed in a merchant location that allows users to swipe their electronic cards to make payments instead of using physical cash (Williams et al 2018). The adoption of POS terminals has significantly reduced the volume of cash-based transactions, as such adoption of POS technology allows cardholders to make payments at sales or purchase outlets without the need for physical cash. Automated Teller Machines will be used much frequently for making variety of online payments such as utility bills, T.V subscriptions, GSM recharges, customers are advised to keep their ATM cards (Debit and Credit) safe and never to divulge their PINs in Sabon Gari market in Fagge Local Government Area of Kano State.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has implemented a cashless policy to encourage electronic transactions and reduce reliance on cash. While the policy aims to improve financial inclusion and economic growth, its effects on small businesses like shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State, remains unclear.

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This study investigates the effects of the cashless policy on the business activities of shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market. Specifically, the research will explore the challenges faced by shoe sellers in adopting the cashless policy, such as lack of access to technology, customer resistance to cashless payments, and limited financial literacy.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the effects of cashless policy on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State. Specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the extent degree at which internet banking transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
2. To examine the effects of points of sales (POS) transactions on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
3. To examine the effects of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Research Questions

This Study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent does internet banking transactions business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?
2. To what extent does points of sales (POS) transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?
3. To what extent does ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Internet banking transactions has no significant effects on business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
2. Points of sales (POS) has no significant impact on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
3. Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions has no significant impact on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of seven hundred and twenty-three (723) shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local government, Kano State. Sample size of 248 Shoe Sellers were selected using research advisor's table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is cashless policy and business activities (CAPABA) Questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, the reliability correlation coefficient of 0.728 was obtained using Cronbach alpha method. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance. The questionnaire was divided into sections according to the two specific purposes and research questions. Responses to items in the questionnaire were based on a four-point Likert-type rating scale, ranging from strongly agree (SA) (4 points), to agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points), and strongly disagree (SD) (1 point).

The questionnaire was administered by the researchers to the shoe Sellers with an explanation on how to fill it. The researchers used descriptive and correlation statistics in analysis of the data. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Mean rating below 2.5 was rejected while any rating of 2.5 and above was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does internet banking transactions affects business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

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Table 1 Mean rating of responses on the impact of internet banking transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1	Convenient and efficient way to manage finances.	3.21	0.54	Agreed
2	Allows you to pay bills online.	3.21	0.54	Agreed
3	Allows you to make online purchases.	3.23	0.58	Agreed
4	Allows you to manage your bank accounts online.	3.24	0.56	Agreed
5	Allows you to apply for loans online.	3.22	0.58	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.22	0.56	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 1-5 used to answer research question one was presented in table 1 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.22>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.56. The analysis therefore indicated that internet banking transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fegge local government area, Kano State.

Research Question 2

To what extent does Points of Sales (POS) transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

Table 2 Mean rating of responses on the impact of POS transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
6	Allows me to process payments.	3.23	0.55	Agreed
7	Used to track inventory levels	3.18	0.56	Agreed
8	Used to manage my customers data	3.21	0.53	Agreed
9	Used to generate my purchases reports	3.19	0.57	Agreed
10	Used to generate my sales reports	3.25	0.56	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.21	0.55	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 6-10 used to answer research question two was presented in table 2 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.21>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.55. The analysis therefore indicated that POS transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fegge local government area, Kano State.

Research Question 3

To what extent does ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fegge local government area, Kano State.

Table 3 Mean rating of responses on the impact of ATM transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
11	Impacted my business transactions	3.27	0.56	Agreed
12	Easier for you to conduct business	3.29	0.57	Agreed
13	Saved time and money	3.32	0.54	Agreed
14	Made you more likely to do shoe business.	3.32	0.54	Agreed
15	Safer and secured	3.32	0.54	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.30	0.55	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 11-15 used to answer research question three was presented in table 3 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean

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value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.30>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.55. The analysis therefore indicated that ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fegge local government area, Kano State.

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested as follows:

Hypothesis 1

Internet banking transactions has no significant effects on business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Table 4 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Internet banking transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.829	0.174	10.535	0.484	.234	0.231	0.000
Internet banking	0.461	0.053	8.675				

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 4 revealed a computed significant value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (internet banking) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (internet banking) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 0.234% (R²=0.234). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 0.053% (Standard error of estimate = 0.053). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of internet banking, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.461 (B=0.461). This implies that internet banking has significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.829 + 0.461 (internet banking).

Hypothesis 2

Points of sales (POS) has no significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Table 5 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Points of sales (POS) transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.654	0.171	9.673	0.532	.283	0.280	0.000
Points of sales	0.516	0.052	9.843				

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 5 revealed a computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (Points of sales) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (Points of sales) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 28.3% (R²=0.283). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 5.2% (Standard error of estimate = 0.052). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of point of sales, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.516 (B=0.516). This implies that point of sales had significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.654 + 0.516 (point of sales).

Hypothesis 3

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has no significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State

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Table 6 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1(Constant)	1.000	0.151	6.615	0.703	.494	0.492	0.000
Automated Teller Machine	0.700	0.045	15.500				

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 6 revealed a computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (automated teller machine) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (automated teller machine) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 49.4% ($R^2=0.494$). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 4.5% (Standard error of estimate = 0.045). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of automated teller machine, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.700 ($B=0.700$). This implies that automated teller machine had significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.000 + 0.700 (automated teller machine).

Discussion of Findings

The finding in Table 4 related to null hypothesis one revealed that, internet banking had a variance at 23.4% ($R^2=0.234 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of internet banking, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that internet banking had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This finding is in line with study of Dedi SS, Agil FI, Putri A. (2019) showed that internet banking can have a real influence on e-commerce development if properly administered.

The finding in Table 5 related to null hypothesis two revealed that, point of sales (POS) had a variance at 28.3% ($R^2=0.283 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of POS, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that POS had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This finding is in line with study of Mbah S, Obiezekwem J. (2019) opined that there is positive relationship between POS transactions and performance of SMEs.

The finding in Table 6 related to null hypothesis three revealed that, Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had a variance at 28.3% ($R^2=0.283 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of ATM, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that ATM had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This finding is in line with study of Saudah W. & Kosala C. K. (2017) opined that ATM transactions had a significant effect to the customer's satisfaction.

Conclusion

This study concluded that Internet banking, points of sales (POS) and Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had significant effects on business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, fagge Local Government Area, Kano State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were given from the findings of the study:

1. The Shoe Sellers Association should encourage sellers to utilize online marketplaces to reach a wider customer base and accept online payments.
2. The Association of shoe Sellers in the market should collaborate with internet service providers to improve internet connectivity within the market.
3. The Sabon Gari Market Authority should be conducting workshops and seminars to educate sellers on cashless transactions and digital financial services.
4. There should be a collaboration with market traders, banks and financial institutions to develop tailor-made financial products and services.

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5. The shoe sellers should promote the use of mobile wallets such as MTN MoMo and Airtel Money for convenient and secured transactions.

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Effects of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation on Achievement and Retention in Physics among College of Education Students in Niger State

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Abstract

The study investigated effects of computer-laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics, specifically in the latent heat of fusion of ice, among colleges of education students in Niger state. The design for the study was quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, post-test non-randomized, non-equivalent control group design. Four research questions and corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study consists of all Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) level one Physics students in Colleges of Education during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger state. The sample of the study consists of 57 (30 male and 27 Female) level one physics students in Niger state, two intact classes were used. The instrument used in this study was Physics Practical Achievement Test (PPAT) as a test instrument. The PPAT comprised of 25-item multiple-choice type questions, validated by experts and its reliability coefficient was calculated to be 0.82, using Kuder-Richardson (KR₂₀). Data gathered were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Independent t-test statistics. The study revealed that experimental group achieved more than the control, and the difference in the achievements was statistically significant $t(67) = 3.21, p=0.002, (P<0.05)$. The difference in the achievement of male and female students in the experimental group was not statistically significant, $t(25) = .19, p=0.85, (P>0.05)$. It was therefore concluded that the students' achievement and retention are better attained when simulation method is used in teaching. It was recommended that science teachers should be trained to produce indigenous Simulation Software.

Keywords: Physics, Latent Heat, Computer Simulation, Achievement, Retention

Introduction

One motive of integrating technology especially computer software technology such as computer simulation models in education is to improve teaching strategies and consequently improve students' academic achievement and retention. Computer Simulation Strategy in this study refers to the method of teaching Physics practical through the use of computer. Simulation, according to Apau (2020) is a specially designed animated model that looks like a live environment in which learners can experience different real-life situations. Computer Simulation Strategy was also defined in Emmanuel, Maxwell and Shuaibu (2016) as the process of using a computer to imitate the operation of a real world process or facility according to appropriately developed assumptions taking the form of logical, statistical or mathematical relationships which are developed into a model. A simulation program can be based on hypothetical situations to study how a system works (Haruna, 2019). These kinds of programs allow the learners to modify the variables in the provided virtual scenario in order to study the effect of the variables on the processes. Basically, Computer Simulation Strategy allows the learners to master their skills or tasks without facing any risks, (Apau, 2020).

Computer simulation, especially in Physics practical brings about great academic achievements to the students through an open learning environment, which gives students opportunities to develop an understanding of physical phenomena and laws by developing hypotheses and testing ideas, to develop an understanding of the relations between physical concepts, variables and phenomena by isolating and manipulating parameters, to utilize a variety of representations, including pictures, animations, graphs, vectors and numerical data displays, which help them understand the underlying concepts, relationships and processes in physics. It also gives them opportunities to demonstrate their portrayal and mental models of the physical world and to employ an investigative approach about phenomena that are difficult to experience in a classroom or laboratory

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environments, due to their complexity, technical difficulty, money or time consumption, or because they occur too fast to be understood by just observing them in real-life settings, example in nuclear fission or fusion experiments, (Abdullahi, 2021).

A lot of similar studies have been carried out by different scholars in different places at different times. Some studies significant to the current one are reviewed. On academic achievement, using the computer simulation strategy to teach Physics, the study of Gambari and Yusuf (2015) indicated that a significant difference, $F(1, 81) = 5.092$, $p = .027$ in students' achievement in favor of those in the experimental group (those exposed to Computer-Assisted Strategy, STAD). The result also indicated no significant difference, $F(1, 43) = 0.852$, $p = 0.361$, in the achievement of male and female students taught physics using computer-assisted STAD cooperative setting. Lastly the study indicates that there was significant difference, $F(1, 81) = 3.870$, $p = 0.053$ in the retention test of students taught physics using computer-assisted STAD and those exposed to traditional method.

The study of Igweh (2012) revealed that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 114) = 4.057$, $p = 0.046$ between the mean scores of students taught basic electronics with computer tutorial drill and those taught using conventional teaching methods in the achievement test. The result also indicated no significant difference, F -value (3.774), significance of F (.055) and confidence level of 0.05, in the achievement of male and female students taught physics using computer simulation. Similarly the study revealed that the students taught basic electronics with computer tutorial and drill retained their learning better than those taught with the conventional teaching methods. Analysis of covariance showed F -value (157.009), significance of F (.000) and confidence level of .05. Similar results in the study of Gambari and Yusuf (2015).

Another significant study to the current one is that of Olorukooba, Sani and Kazeem (2016). The study revealed that there was significant difference, $t(98) = 3.51$, $p=0.001$, ($P<0.05$) on the achievement of students taught Qualitative Analysis Concept of Chemistry using Computer Simulations performed better than those taught with traditional method alone. The result showed that there was no significant difference, $t(48) = 0.33$, $p=0.75$, ($P>0.05$) in the average performance of male and female students taught Qualitative Analysis Concepts of Chemistry using Computer Simulations. The study also revealed that there was significant difference, $t(98) = 4.51$, $p=0.001$, ($P<0.05$) in the academic retention between students taught Qualitative Analysis Concept of Chemistry using Computer Simulations and those exposed to traditional method alone. The findings in Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) agreed with those of Gambari and Yusuf (2015) and Igweh (2012). In the study of Adam, Mamuda, Adedoh. and Isaiah (2021), it was revealed that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 331) = 20.230$, $p = .000$, in the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Educational Technology, EDT, using computer simulation and those exposed to conventional method. And also, that gender has no significant effect on students' achievement in EDT when exposed to computer simulation, $F(1, 329) = .50$, $p = .48$.

Findings on academic retention based on gender according to Nkok (2021) showed no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught sexual reproduction in plant with computer simulation strategy, $F(1, 15.7) = 0.921$, $p=.340$. But Egara and Mosimege's (2023) study did not support earlier Nkok's (2021) finding on gender retention. It was revealed in Egara and Mosimege (2023) that there was a significant gender difference, $F(1, 110) = 6.947$ and $p=.010$, in the mean retention scores of students taught algebra using a computer simulation approach, with the female students faring better.

Some research studies including those of Ewansiha and Omorogbe (2013) and Benson (2017) on the use of laboratory to teach Physics practical in Nigerian schools have been carried out. Such studies have revealed some problems such as decline rather than improvement in the teaching of Physics practical to students; in addition, there is inadequacy of facilities in many of our schools' laboratories. While the studies of Danjuma and Adeleye (2015) and Abdullahi (2021) showed that a big problem to the effective teaching of Physics in some colleges is not lack of the necessary laboratory or equipment but rather lack of their usage, probably due to problem of lack of knowledge of using the equipment by the teachers. In the absence of laboratories and laboratory equipment, teaching and learning of Physics concepts face great problems and poor achievement and retention may result.

One such concept that suffers misconception according to Chavan (2013) and Madu and Orji (2015), is Heat and Thermodynamics. The concepts of heat and thermodynamics in Physics pose many problems to students as a result of misconception resulting to low achievement. Therefore, the problem of this research is to determine the effects of computer-

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laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics, specifically in the concept of latent heat of fusion of ice, among colleges of education students in Niger state.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to determine the effects of computer-laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics (latent heat of fusion of ice) among colleges of education students in Niger state. The specific objectives were to:

1. To determine the difference between the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught Specific Latent Heat of Fusion (SLHF) of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies.
2. To find the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught Specific Latent Heat of Fusion, SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy.
3. To determine the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
4. To determine the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?
2. Is there any difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy?
3. What are the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?
4. Is there any difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of all Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) one Physics students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Colleges of Education in Niger state. The sample used for the study consisted of 57 (38 males and 19 females) NCE I Physics students. The study was carried out in two Colleges of Education in Niger state, Federal College of Education (FCE) Kontagora and College of Education (COE) Minna. NCE I Physics students of FCE Kontagora were purposively assigned as the Experimental Group, EG. While the NCE I Physics students of COE Minna, being the Control group, CG.

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Table 1. Research design layout

Groups	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest	Retention
Experimental Group	O ₁	X ₁	O ₂	O ₃
Control Group	O ₁	X ₀	O ₂	O ₃

Where: O₁, O₁ = Observation of pre-test for the experimental and control groups
O₂, O₂ = Observation of post-test for the experimental and control groups
O₃, O₃ = Observation of retention for the experimental and control groups
X₁ = Treatment for Experimental Group
X₀ = No Treatment

A Physics Practical Achievement Test (PPAT), was developed to test students' achievement and retention in the concepts of heat, calorimetry. Thus, The (PPAT) was based on NCE I syllabus on concepts of Heat. It consisted of 25 objective test questions which were developed for use at pre-test, post-test and retention (Achievement tests). Each correct answer attracted a score of one mark, total marks were converted to percentage to arrive at the total scores. Computer simulation software used as the treatment instrument in the study was SIMLAB Physics Laboratory Simulation Model, developed and uploaded on the web as a freeware by Tarara (2011). The PPAT was validated by two experts, a senior lecturer and a chief lecturer in the Department of Physics, FCE Kontagora. The experts' observations / recommendations were taken into consideration and corrections effected.

To determine the reliability coefficient of the treatment instrument (PPAT), pilot tests were conducted at FCE, Zuba. FCE Zuba is not part of the population but it shares similar characteristics with the sampled Colleges of Education. A total of 30 students were used for the pilot study, the trial test. The results obtained from the trial tests conducted were used for reliability test of the instrument. Kuder-Richardson (KR₂₀) formula was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the (PPAT) to be 0.82

Cooperation of the Physics heads of department of the two institutions, laboratory technicians and the students were sought. In order not to disrupt the academic activities of the schools, the research work was scheduled to lecture-free periods of the students. Before the treatment, pretests were administered to both experimental and control groups using the instrument described above. Variables of teacher's qualities were controlled by the researchers themselves to introduce the Physics practical lessons to the participating students. The control group received instructions on the practical Conventional strategy on SLHF of ice experiment, while experimental group was given the treatment on the same SLHF of ice through computer simulation strategy, using the simulation model. The treatment lasted for two weeks. Immediately after the treatment, posttest was administered to the two groups. The administration of delayed test was after two weeks so as to test students' retention. Reports of experiments performed based on the given instruments were used to collect data.

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. The independent sample t-test analysis was used to test all the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Computer software Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0 was used for the data analysis.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Physics Achievement Scores for Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation and those Exposed to Conventional Laboratory Strategies.

Group	N	Pre-test Mean, \bar{x}	SD	Post-test Mean, \bar{x}_g	SD _g	Mean Gain	Gain Diff.
Experimental	27	30.19	7.50	58.80	13.22	28.61	10.91
Control	30	31.50	7.01	49.20	11.60	17.70	
Total	57						

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Results in Table 2 showed that the mean gain of achievement of the experimental group ($\bar{x}_g = 28.61$, $SD_g = 13.22$, $n = 27$) was higher than that of the control group ($\bar{x}_g = 17.70$, $SD_g = 11.60$, $n = 30$). This indicates that the intervention (i.e. the use of the simulation strategy) have higher effect in improving physics students' academic achievement in SLHF of ice experiments than the use of the conventional teaching strategy. The mean gain difference was 10.91.

Research Question 2

Is there any difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy?

To answer this research question, mean and standard deviation were used and the result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Results of Male and Female Taught SLHF of ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation.

Instructional Mode	Gender	N	Pre-test Mean \bar{x}	SD	Post-test Mean \bar{x}_g	SD_g	Mean Gain	Gain Diff.
Simulation	Males	17	41.10	7.69	65.88	11.31	24.78	
	Females	10	39.22	6.28	66.72	10.01	27.50	2.72
	Total	27						

Table 3 showed that male students taught SLHF using the Simulation approach had ($\bar{x} = 41.10$, $SD = 7.69$) in the pretest and ($\bar{x}_g = 65.88$, $SD_g = 11.31$) in the posttest, giving a pretest-posttest achievement mean gain of ($\bar{x}_g = 24.78$). While, the female students treated equally achieved ($\bar{x} = 39.22$, $SD = 6.28$) in the pretest and ($\bar{x}_g = 66.72$, $SD_g = 10.01$.) in the posttest, giving a pretest-posttest achievement mean gain of ($\bar{x}_g = 27.50$). The findings indicated a difference between the mean gain of the males and females (2.72) in favour of the female students. Inferential statistics was used to find the significance of this difference.

Research Question 3

What are the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategy?

Table 4. Mean Retention and Standard Deviation of Retention Scores of Experimental Group and the Control Group

Group	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	Mean Diff.
Experimental	27	45.60	13.08	13.57
Control	30	32.03	24.42	
Total	57			

Table 4 shows the mean retention and standard deviation of achievement scores of experimental and control groups at posttest. From Table 4, it can be deduced that the mean and standard deviation scores at posttest for Experimental Group were ($\bar{x} = 45.60$, $SD = 13.08$), while those of the control group were ($\bar{x} = 32.03$, $SD = 24.42$). These give a mean difference of 13.57.

Research Question 4:

What is the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation?

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation of Retention Test Scores of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice Using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Gender	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	Mean Diff.
Males	17	52.67	13.78	3.49
Females	10	49.18	9.33	
Total	27			

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Table 5 reveals the mean retention and standard deviation of achievement scores of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy. From the Table, it is observed that there is a difference between the mean retention scores of the two groups at post-test where male students had mean achievement and standard deviation of ($\bar{x} = 52.67, SD = 13.78$), while their female counterparts had mean achievement and standard deviation of ($\bar{x} = 49.18, SD = 9.33$). Independent t-test was used to determine whether the mean difference of 3.49 is statistically significant.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.

Table 6. Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Achievement of Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Simulation and those Exposed to Conventional Strategies.

Method	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Simulation strategy	27	58.80	13.22	55	2.92	.005	Rejected
Conventional strategy	30	49.20	11.60				
Total	57						

Table 6 showed $t(55) = 2.92, p=0.005, (P<0.05)$. The null hypothesis was thus rejected because there was a significant difference in achievement between students' taught physics practical with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy. Hence, it was established that students that were taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy had a higher score and significantly performed better than their counterparts that were exposed to Conventional Strategy.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy

Table 7: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Achievement of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Simulation Strategy

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	17	65.88	11.31	25	.19	.85	Accepted
Female	10	66.72	10.01				
Total	27						

Table 7 showed no significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy. The table showed $t(25) = .19, p=0.85, (P>0.05)$. The null-hypothesis was thus accepted because there was no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students taught physics practical with Computer Simulation Strategy. Hence, it was established that the achievement of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation approach did not differ.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.

Table 8: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Retention Test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Experimental	27	45.60	13.08	55	2.57	0.01	Rejected
Control	30	32.03	24.42				
Total	57						

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Table 8 revealed the independent t-test comparison of retention test scores of the Experimental and Control groups. An examination of the table shows that there was significant difference in the retention scores of the two groups, $t(55) = 2.57$, $p = .01$, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, H_0_3 was rejected. This implies that there was actually a significant difference in the retention of students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to SLHF of ice with Conventional Strategy.

HO₄: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy

Table 9: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Retention Test Scores of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice Using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Gender	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Males	17	52.67	13.78	25	0.71	.49	Accepted
Females	10	49.18	9.33				
Total	27						

Table 9 shows the independent t-test result of the comparison of retention scores of experimental group based on gender. An examination of the table shows $t(25) = 0.71$, $p = .49$, ($P > 0.05$). On the basis of this, hypothesis four was retained. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in research question one which deals with the students' academic achievement mean scores in SLHF of ice when taught with the Simulation Strategy and when exposed to Conventional laboratory method, revealed that there was a mean gain difference of 10.91 in favor of the experimental group. Also, the t-test analysis in hypothesis one revealed that the difference in the mean achievement scores was statistically significant, showed $t(55) = 2.92$, $p = 0.005$, ($P < 0.05$). This is an indication that the use of the Simulation Strategy has higher effect on students' academic achievement in teaching SLHF of ice. The study affirms the study of Adam, *et al.* (2021) that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 331) = 20.230$, $p = .000$, in the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Educational Technology, EDT, using computer simulation and those exposed to conventional method. The finding in this study is also in tandem with earlier studies of Igweh (2012), Gambari and Yusuf (2015) and Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016), that students taught using computer simulation achieved significantly more than those exposed to traditional strategy.

Findings in research question two showed that the mean achievement scores of female participants was 66.72 which was higher but not statistically significant than that of their male counterparts which had a mean achievement of 65.88. The result showed that $t(25) = .19$, $p = 0.85$, ($P > 0.05$). This means that the observed higher achievement of female students over their male counterparts was not statistically significant. This result again supports the earlier findings of Gambari and Yusuf (2015), Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) and Adam, *et al.* (2021). These indicated that there was no significant differences in the achievement of male and female students taught using computer simulation.

Findings in research question three on the mean retention scores of students taught SLHF of ice using the Computer Simulation and Conventional Laboratory Strategies indicates a mean difference of 13.57. The t-test analysis showed that the difference is statistically significant. An examination of table 8 shows that there was a significant difference in the mean retention scores of the two groups, $t(55) = 2.57$, $p = .01$, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis three was rejected. This study also agrees with the earlier studies of Igweh (2012) and Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) that teaching sciences using Simulation Strategy significantly enhances students' retention.

Findings on the influence of gender on the retention scores of students exposed to Computer Simulation Strategy revealed a mean retention difference of 3.49 in favor of the males. However, this difference was not statistically significant, $t(25) = 0.71$, $p = .49$, ($P > 0.05$). As such there was no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy. The finding agrees with the earlier finding of Nkok (2021) but disagreed

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with that of Egara and Mosimege (2023) which revealed that there was a significant gender difference, $F(1, 110) = 6.947$ and $p = .010$, in the mean retention scores of students taught using computer simulation.

Conclusion

The study investigated effects of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation on achievement and retention in the concept of latent heat among colleges of education students in Niger state. It was revealed that the students that were taught SLHF of ice with the computer simulation strategy have achieved more than those exposed to the same topic with Conventional Laboratory Strategy. The difference in the achievement was statistically significant. The difference in the mean achievement scores of male students over that of their female counterparts was not statistically significant. Results of the study also revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Simulation and those expose to Conventional Strategies.

Recommendations

Based on findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Computer Simulation Strategy should be used to supplement Conventional Laboratory method of teaching to improve students' achievement and retention in physics.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to teach Physics using Computer Simulation Strategy in the absence of laboratory equipment.
3. The use of Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy should be encouraged where it is found that students have low retention in the course of learning. Computer Simulation Strategy builds academic retention in students as revealed here.

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Effects of Peer Tutoring Strategy on Performance in Basic Science among Upper Basic Secondary School Students in Makurdi Metropolis

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of peer tutoring on academic performance of upper basic science students in Makurdi metropolis. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to sample 65 (30 Male and 35 Female) students in two intact classes from the population of 1726 (828 Male and 898 Female) upper basic II students during 2023/2024 academic session in 25 government approved public secondary schools under Benue State Universal Basic Education Board, Makurdi. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), with reliability coefficient of 0.86 was determined using Kuder Richardson (KR-21) formula was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation, mean gain scores and mean gain difference to answer research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using two-way analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings of the study showed that there is significant difference in performance mean scores of upper basic science students taught basic science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among others. Based on the findings, it was concluded that peer tutoring strategy enhance upper basic science students performance without gender disparity. Therefore, it was recommended that peer tutoring strategy should be encouraged at basic education level.

Keywords: Peer tutoring, Performance, Basic science and Gender

Introduction

The inclusiveness of Basic science as a core subject to be offered at lower, middle and upper basic level of education as enshrine in the national policy on education is to exposure the young learners to the world of science and technology so as to prepare them to meet up contemporary issues they may be facing in their daily activities. Basic science (BS) is not a term that cannot be pinned down to a precise definition, Okworo (2002) as cited in Agogo and Ode (2017) sees BS as a course study which presents science discipline in all ramifications or diversity, in a unit whole so as to appreciate the interdependence of all science disciplines. According to the authors, the knowledge gained is relevant for man's comfortable living in his environment. Agogo and Ode (2011) referred to it as a subject in which concepts and principles of science are presented so as to express the fundamental unity of scientific thought and to avoid premature or undue stress on distinctions among the science fields.

The importance of Basic science and technology to national development in the life of any country cannot be overemphasized as the revised Curriculum of Basic Science and Technology (2012) has spelt out its importance as it is expected to enable the learners: develop interest in science and technology; acquire basic knowledge in science and technology; apply scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet contemporary societal needs, take advantage of the numerous career opportunities provided by science and technology; become prepared for further studies in science and technology, avoid drug abuse and related vices; and be safety and security conscious. In spite of the importance of Basic Science, the performance of students is reported to poor in recent years. An analysis of students' performance in Basic Science from 2019 to 2022 at Basic

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Certificate Education Examination (BECE) shows a steady increase in failure rate from 3.72% in 2019, 8.97% in 2020 to 10.18% in 2021 and 8.46% in 2022 (Benue State Examination Board, 2023).

Several reasons have been advanced by researchers on the persistent poor performance in Basic Science reported by Ozaji as cited in Peni, (2016) identified factors responsible for the poor performance of learners in Basic science to (among others) include the followings: learner's inability to interact directly with learning materials; wrong perception of science by the learners and, fundamentally, the instructional strategy employed by teachers; all of which could be addressed by the use of peer-tutoring instructional strategy. In most educational organizations however, the instructional method consistently employed by science teachers is the lecture method (Obiekwe, 2008). This method of teaching places emphasis on memorization of facts which would only appeal to learners with well-developed reasoning abilities and intelligence. According to Marvel, Magnolia, Brillante and Laureano (2018) true learning means that the information that is presented and the skills that are acquired can be used throughout life, he believes that teachers should insist on learning activities linked to the real world.

Effective and appropriate implementation of students centred instructional methods such peer tutoring, fish born, thinking maps, and role play among others strategies could help improve Basic Science students' academic performance. Peer-tutoring otherwise known as peer mentoring or peer assisted learning strategy is an effective and affordable way of providing students with academic and personal support from other students (Jibrin, Ibrahim & Zayum, 2016). In peer-tutoring technique, a higher performing student is paired with a lower one to review critical academic or behavioural concepts. Peer mentoring improves the learning experiences of both the tutors and tutees. When peer tutors participate in these schemes, they not only improve their own understanding of the subject areas, they also develop important communication and teamwork skills (Adamu & Kusa, 2018). Consequently, it has been argued that peer-tutoring learning strategy improves the academic achievement of students. In a quest to improve the general performance of students, Wael (2014) suggested the used of peer-tutoring strategy. According to Tran (2014) peer-tutoring method does not only increase the performance of students, but also promotes their communication abilities and interpersonal relationships. Usually shy children learn effectively through tutoring by sharing their thoughts with classmates (Bombardelli, 2016). Peer-tutoring is an active teaching methodology that fosters student inclusion while enabling students to learn from each other (Cockerill, Craig & Thurston, 2018). These interactions between tutors and tutees promote active learning and foster student inclusion, as all students participate in the process (Fung, Tan & Chen, 2018). Empirically, Ovie (2022) investigated the effect of peer tutoring instructional strategy on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry. The findings revealed a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught using conventional strategy, in favor of those taught using peer tutoring strategy. In a similar vein, Azeez, Omananyi, Kwasi, and Abuh (2022) examined the effect of Jigsaw and Peer-tutoring instructional strategies on students' achievement and interest in periodic table of elements. Findings of the study revealed that jigsaw and peer-tutoring instructional strategies have significant effect on students' academic achievement and interest in periodic Table of elements concept of chemistry. Also, gender and interest have no influence on the academic achievement of students exposed to Jigsaw and peer tutoring instructional strategies. More so, Samuel and Sambo (2019) examined the effect of peer tutoring and reversed jigsaw instructional strategies on senior secondary school science students' interest and achievement. Findings from the study revealed a significant difference between the achievement of Science students in Peer-Tutoring, Reversed Jigsaw instructional strategies and conventional Demonstration method in favour of the two innovative strategies. These results indicates that students centred strategies such as peer tutoring instructional strategies are more effective in enhancing Science students' performance than the conventional lecture or demonstration methods.

According to Emaikwu (2012), there is a drastic and constant reduction in the level of performance by science students especially, basic science in Nigeria. This is evident in the students' low learning outcomes in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and other examination bodies. Academic performance has been defined and explained by several authors. For instance, Ayua and Tartenger, 2020 defined Academic Performance as the level of students scholarly accomplishment in Basic science where high and low scores indicate good and poor achievement respectively. Toryem, (2021) sees academic performance as a measure of change in behavior of learners over a given period of instruction. The measure of student's cognitive and psychomotor domains of behavioral objectivities in the learning process is determined through performance test. Persistent low academic performance in general has been an issue of concern and discussion among researchers in the past decade (Samba 2019). This could be attributed to ineffective teaching methods adopted which according to Ode and Tartenger (2021) has negative implication on students' academic abilities. According to Tatli and Ayas (2013), effective teaching and learning will foster students' performance in the following ways:

1. Models positive influences on students' performance;
2. Improves the utilisation of psychomotor kills;

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3. Enhances students' self-confidence in tackling scientific problems;
4. Increases students' engagement and participation in the learning;
5. Visualises macro, micro, and symbolical level presentations of the experiment; and
6. Provides a strategy that follows the procedural steps.

This study intended to use peer tutoring strategy to determine whether these performance attributes could be achieved in Basic Science classroom.

Another factor that plays an important role in learner's performance is gender. Gender is defined by Ugwu and Nwagbo (2019) as the socially or culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in any society. Review of literature has shown inconsistency in the results of male and female students' academic performance in Basic Science and science at large (Tofi, Usman & Lakpini, 2021). For instance, Ovie (2022) investigated the effect of peer tutoring instructional plan on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry. The study found that Male had less achievement than female student taught chemistry using of peer tutoring teaching approach. Alamri (2018) also found that female students performed better than the male students; conversely Tartenger, Omega and Enemariae (2023) study revealed that boys performed better than their female counterparts. While Ode and Tartenger (2021) found no significant difference between male and female students' performance scores, Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed students centred strategies.

Students' low performance in Basic Science irrespective of gender is indications of the likelihood of a deficiency in instructional strategies used in Basic Science instruction and this shows all is not well with the way the subject is been taught/learnt. To motivate and enhance students' performance, the teachers needs to make science real and relevant by using teaching strategies that will enable students learn easily and effectively. It is against this backdrop that it is imperative to investigate the effect of peer tutoring strategy on Basic Science students' academic performance in Makurdi metropolis.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to find out the effectiveness of peer tutoring instructional strategy on Basic Science Students' Academic Performance in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine if there is a difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method
2. compare the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring instructional strategy.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method?
2. What is the mean score difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.
2. There is no significant mean scores difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy

Methodology

The study adopted pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group, quasi experimental research design. The population of the study consisted of the 1726 (828 male and 898 female) Upper basic II students out of the 25 Government approved public secondary schools during the 2023/2024 academic session in Makurdi, Benue State under Benue State Universal Basic Education Board Makurdi. A sample of 65 (30 Male and 35 Female) upper-Basic II Students in two schools was drawn from the population using purposive and random sampling. The instruments used for data collection was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT). The instrument had 30 objective questions with 4 options (A, B, C and D). Each question had one correct answer and three distracters. The BSPT was used for pre-test and post-test on both control and experimental groups. The research instrument was validated by two experts in Department of Science and Mathematics Education of Benue State University, Makurdi, their inputs helped in improving the quality of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of BSPT was determined

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using Kuder Richardson (KR-21) on 30 students which were part of the population but not part of the sample for the study which yielded a reliability index of 0.86. The Data was collected with the help of two research assistants from the sampled schools. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation Whereas, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Results are presented according to order of research questions and hypotheses:

Research Question 1

What is the mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of students taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method.

S/No	Method	N	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
			Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Peer tutoring	34	7.55	2.273	13.92	5.310	6.37	In favour of peer tutoring strategy
2	Lecture	31	7.61	2.530	11.94	4.174	4.33	
Mean difference							2.04	

(Source: Field work, 2024)

The data in Table 1 shows the difference in the mean academic performance scores students taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method. Data in the table also reveals that the mean gain of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy is 6.37 and those taught using lecture method is 4.33. The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of the students' taught is 2.04. in favour of students taught using peer tutoring strategy.

Research Question 2

What is the mean score difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy (PTS)?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students' taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy (PTS).

S/NO	GenderPTS	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Male	7.00	2.828	14.27	3.495	7.27	In favour of female students
2	Female	7.50	2.542	15.74	4.929	8.24	
Mean difference						0.97	

(Source: Field work, 2024)

The data in Table 2 shows the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students' taught Basic Science using peer tutoring. Data in the table further reveals the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy as 7.27 and those of female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy as 8.24, The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students' taught Basic Science using peer tutoring is 0.97 in favour of female students.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.

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Table 3: ANCOVA of Academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	291.371 ^a	2	145.686	6.502	.003	.173
Intercept	663.766	1	663.766	29.623	.000	.323
Pretest	57.244	1	57.244	2.555	.115	.040
Method	239.601	1	239.601	10.693	.002	.147
Error	1389.244	62	22.407			
Total	14281.000	65				
Corrected Total	1680.615	64				

a. R Squared = .173 (Adjusted R Squared = .147)

(Source: field work 2024)

The data in Table 3 reveals that $F(1,62) = 10.693$; $p = 0.002 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method is not retained. This implies that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students' exposed to Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught exposed to lecture method. The partial Eta square of 0.147 was obtained for method meaning that only 14.7% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of instructional strategy/ method in Basic Science class when taught using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean scores difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy

Table 4: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	35.739 ^a	2	17.869	.619	.545	.038
Intercept	608.216	1	608.216	21.070	.000	.405
Pretest	.955	1	.955	.033	.857	.001
Gender	32.218	1	32.218	1.116	.299	.035
Error	894.879	31	28.867			
Total	9349.000	34				
Corrected Total	930.618	33				

a. R Squared = .038 (Adjusted R Squared = -.024)

(Source: field work 2024)

The data in Table 4 reveals that $F(1,31) = 1.116$; $p = 0.299 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.035 was obtained for gender meaning that only 3.5% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using peer tutoring.

Discussion of Findings

Finding from hypothesis one showed that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students' taught using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture. The students exposed to peer tutoring strategy outperformed their counterparts exposed to lecture method. This finding agrees with Ovie (2022) whom investigated the effect of peer tutoring

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instructional strategy on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry and found a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught using conventional strategy, more so Azeez, Omananyi, Kwasi, and Abuh (2022) also found a significant difference in students' achievement and interest in periodic table of elements when taught using peer tutoring and conventional method. The finding is also in line with that of Samuel and Sambo (2019) whom examined the effect of peer tutoring and reversed jigsaw instructional strategies on senior secondary school science students' interest and achievement and found a significant difference among the strategies when compared with conventional methods. This finding may be possible because peer tutoring strategy provide equal opportunities to both fast and slow learners students as it has been reported to be a useful tool for helping students with the process of building conceptual understanding of disciplinary content and consequently, promoting their performance which made it possible for the students in peer tutoring strategy to attained high performance.

The finding from hypothesis two indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy. This implies that the performance of both male and female students exposed to peer tutoring strategy is enhanced. This agrees with Ode and Tartenger (2021) who found no significant difference between male and female students' performance scores. Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed to students-centred strategies. This high and gender free performance could be a result of the involvement of students' active participation in the class as every student's is given an opportunity to make their contribution during group discussions, the intelligent and even the slow learners. Conversely however, this finding disagreed with the findings of Alamri (2018) who found that female students performed better than the male students and Tartenger, Omega and Enemariae (2023) study revealed that boys performed better than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained in the study, the researchers concluded that, the use of peer tutoring strategy enhance students' academic performance in basic science than the conventional lecture method. Peer tutoring strategy of teaching is also gender friendly.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study it was recommended that;

1. Basic science students should be encouraged to serve as tutors to teach their colleagues various concepts in basic science especially during tutorial classes.
2. Peer tutoring strategy should be use by basic science teachers at basic education level to enhance Basic Science students' academic performance since the strategy is gender friendly.

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Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was on Effects of Print Media on Reading habits in Social Studies concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria. Two objectives, two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Quasi experimental research design specifically, pre test-post test, control group design was adopted. The population of the study consists of 11,281 (Male, 4,680 and Female,6,601) upper basic two students of 2022/2023 academic session in Kano State. A sample size of 276 (Male, 108 and Female,168) were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. An instrument titled Social Studies Reading Habit Test (SSRT) was developed and used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, and t-test was used to test the two-null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that print media has significant effect on social studies students' reading habit and positively affects their performance. It was concluded that print media significantly improved students' reading habits in social studies. The study recommended that social studies teachers should employ different kind of print media to teach their students and students should be frequently engaged with reading tasks within and outside the classroom.

Keyword: Print media, Readership & Social Studies Students.

Introduction

Print media is one of the oldest and basic forms of mass communication. Teaching and learning can be conducted through print media. Print media includes textbooks, charts, pictures, graphics, bulleting, newspapers, magazines and journals. It plays a vital role in providing information and transfer knowledge (Diso & Haruna, 2020). Even after the advent of electronic media; the print media has not lost its charm or relevance. It has the advantage of making a longer impact on the minds of the reader, with more in-depth reporting and analysis. Print media such as books, journals, newspapers and magazines influence social, emotional and intellectual development of individuals. The most common medium encountered in school learning is still the books, which happens to be a channel used to send messages to the receiver (learners). Publications help individuals in research. Through illustrations and cartoons, people can find learning easier and more interesting (Maley, 2017).

Students may develop reading skills through the influence of print materials available for their study. Bala, (2017) is of the view that print media helps to enhance students' interest to read which broaden their perspectives towards global activities. Thus, reading newspaper and magazines not only teach social studies better but give current knowledge of the world happenings. Furthermore, if at higher secondary level, there is an adequate and appropriate use of print media, learners familiarize themselves with the world surrounding them (Mujittaba, 2022). When a piece of news is presented in the newspaper and magazines this will enhance students' knowledge. The task accompanying each text from the print media used in social studies classrooms would give the learners adequate confidence to read and view news items in social studies through print media outside the classroom. Print media is a tool that we use to pass information from sender to the receiver in this case, this research intends to assess the influence of print media in reading habits among social studies students in secondary school. This is to say that print media influence the interest of social studies students to engage or develop readership habit. Therefore, reading is the foundation of all formal and informal learning. Future success is dependent on the learners' reading ability. It is the gateway to success and the number of time students spends in reading is the indicator of successful academic life in future (Wigfield, Guthrie, Perencevich & Taboada, 2008).

Authors publish audio format of their manuscript and textbooks to assist students in Upper basic schools but even this also become ineffective. Students with a poor reading habit in Upper basic schools face a lot of challenges if they make it to the tertiary institution, mostly because they are compelled to read huge volumes of academic books. They may find it even more challenging because they required to do their research at the library or online to fully understand and succeed in their course work. The extent to which secondary school' students neglect the value attached to print media is what motivate the researcher to assess the effect of print media on reading habits of social studies students in Upper basic schools in Kano State.

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This is with the view of facilitating healthy discourse amongst stakeholders in education on how to reverse and enforce readership and interest in social studies students.

Print media are very essential in teaching and learning situation, especially in secondary and tertiary levels of education, as it stands as an instrument in which knowledge and information are directed to the learner. Considering the fact that, in most cases, the mode of assessment (examinations) in Nigerian Upper basic schools mostly is based on written form. Students in this regard, have to read notes and textbooks in order to confront any examination. Apart from that, teaching and learning social studies requires the use of print media such as textbooks, magazines, charts and journals among others. The use of different types of print media is inevitable due to the broadening nature of the social studies curriculum.

As multi-disciplinary subject, social studies depend heavily on the content of social sciences and humanities to realize its objectives of preparing people to become good and effective citizens in a democratic society with links to other societies, social studies incorporate the personal and social experiences of students and their cultural heritage. It links factors outside the individual, particularly the development and use of reflective thinking, problem-solving, rational decision-making skills, to create involvement in social action. Therefore, social studies have been defined by different scholars based on their point of viewed. Ikwumelu, (2012) in Godebe, (2016) perceived social studies as a program of study that focuses on man, his environments and the interrelationship between man and his environments. In other words, social studies have three dimensions, first, the study of man; second, the study of man's environments (social, economic, physical, cultural); and third, the study of how man affects his various environments, and how these environments affect man. There is reciprocal relationship between man and his environment as social studies explored it to the students how to handle their environmental issues. The definition explained the three dimensions of social studies in which are all vested on man's both physical and social environment.

Social studies in Nigeria has to do with the development of socio-civic and personal behavior. Considering this, Nigerian policy recognizes the importance of social studies, making it a core subject in Nigerian primary and upper basic schools and assigns it the responsibility to develop the essential knowledge, values, and skills associated with citizenship. Therefore, social studies at all levels of the education system are tailored towards the realization of Nigerian educational goals. Print media is a revolutionary evolution that has buried the gap of communication with the aid of tangible printed assets such as books, newspapers, magazines, letters. among various targeted groups of people so that the hierarchy of information would never get broken down due to slacking conversation. Print media has several sources to destine its significant role among which newspapers and magazines are the gigantic dominants for intermediating information till the date today while business letters, brochures, billboards, pamphlets, signboards, postcards and advertisements play a secondary role in catapulting a large audience in one go (Okeeffe, 2012).

Print Media in education is a worldwide programme whereby all types of print media are used to promote education in school classrooms. Print media such as books, journals, newspapers and magazines influence social, emotional and intellectual development of individuals. The most common medium encountered in school learning is still the book, which happens to be a channel used to send messages to the receiver. Publications help individuals in research. Print media provide a rich learning experience in the classroom. Media in the classroom engage students in learning and provide a richer experience (Bala 2016).

Printed media help a lot in transmitting the culture and history of the society without a writing text many facts regarding to world history would have been missed. Knowledge can be a permanent on students' mind if they can open books to read and illustrated the information written on it. In Nigerian classes, textbook is the most commonly used to deliver information. In each curriculum there is available textbooks that will guide both teachers and students in getting the information and the successful implementation.

A textbook is a type of print media that is transmitting information to all students. Print media can help the intellectual and professional person to transmission their knowledge and experience to readers. Newspapers have provided the practice section for primary and secondary school students to do their assignments more especially social studies students that deal with global phenomena. Print media such as newspaper and magazines have a contributing factor to the development of reading habits. As they serve as a channel through which messages, information, ideas, and knowledge are disseminated more easily. Reading is one of the major skills in present-day literary society. Books are the storehouse of knowledge and this knowledge is usually translated through reading. Reading involves the ability to identify ink marking on paper by way of formal elements of the language i.e. identifying these inks marking either as alphabets or words and then knowing the meaning of the words so identified (Olanrewaju, 2016). People read to be able to interpret information into meaning. The extraction of meaning from a

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written piece of work either of a line, paragraph or more is referred to as comprehension. Students can generate the information only when they read and understand the instruction delivered to them is either from the classroom or outside the classroom.

Reading is defined as a cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. Reading is an active process of constructing meanings of words. Reading with a purpose helps the reader to direct information towards a goal and focuses their attention. Although the reasons for reading may vary, the primary purpose of reading is to understand the text. Reading is a thinking process. It allows the reader to use what he or she have already known, also called prior knowledge. During this processing of information, the reader uses strategies to understand what they are reading, uses themes to organize ideas, and uses textual clues to find the meanings of new words (Gabriel 2008). Reading is an essential tool for knowledge transfer and the habit of reading is an academic activity that increases skills in reading strategies. To know about the world and its environment, a child helps himself through reading books, newspapers and other magazines. Once the child has been taught to read and has developed a love for books, he can explore for himself the wealth of human experiences and knowledge through reading. Children, who miss the opportunity of getting in touch with books in their early stages of life, find it hard to acquire good reading habits in their later years (Hassan, 2010). Teachers and students tap information through a reading which came in a different form of print media. It also one of the basic skills which children learnt from school how to read and understand the message that came to them in a text mode.

Different research works have been conducted on reading and print media, some of these studies were conducted outside the country, but majority that were reviewed by the researcher have been found conducted in Nigeria. Among are those conducted and reviewed by the researcher are; Jude and Udosen, (2012) conducted a study on the influence of print media strategies (magazines and Novels) in determining the development of students' reading competence in AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. Abdulrasheed, Abdulkarim, Dogara, and Umar, (2015) conducted research titled "An assessment of reading habit among Upper basic schools in Kaduna metropolis. Njeze (2013), conducted research on use of Newspapers and Magazines in the academic pursuits of university students: Case Study of Covenant University. This present study examined the Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

Despite the value and importance attached to print media in teaching and learning, students nowadays neglect to take its advantage and embrace it as a reliable tool of sourcing information, rather they use various electronic media to watch motion pictures or listen to audio (Mujittaba 2022). What becomes an order of the day is that students turn their attention to books when their examination is around the corner without consulting print media even during their leisure time.

The researcher observed that the unavailability of print media in Upper basic schools and the poor functioning of school libraries are among the root causes of poor reading habits among social studies students in Upper basic schools. Many students come to school regularly but most of them have no textbooks. Even teachers do not encourage and motivate students in any form of reading activities. Also, inappropriate teaching methods by the teachers might be the contributing factor for the students to develop an undesirable habit in reading. Students are poorly motivated to read. Apart from the teacher's failure to motivate students to read, the parent does not find it worthy to equip their children with reading materials.

The emergence of availability of electronic media further contributes immensely in fading away from the value of print media in the eyes of both students and parent (Mujittaba, 2022). Some students using their smart phones to browse, and chat with their friends, sometimes they watch movies and play music. This poor attitude serves as problems that make it difficult when it comes to reading. It has been itching deeply into the mind of many Nigerians that, lack of interest to read and poor reading habits among students of Upper basic schools is attributed to poor performance in their examinations. Many parents and teachers complain about students of our generation who have not developed reading habits among themselves. Officials of the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and teachers of English complain of the kind of written English by today's generation of students (Olowolagba, 2018). The net result is the poor performance of many students in final examinations. One of the many issues confronting students nowadays is perhaps, not their inability to read but their lack of interest.

As a result of this poor reading habit, they failed woefully in their examinations. This leads to poor grades for students and difficulty in trying to find or advance to a good job in adulthood. Given the above, the researcher finds it interested to investigate the influence of print media on reading habits among social studies students in upper basic school in Kano State.

Objectives of the study

The following specific objectives guided the study:

1. Determine reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

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2. Determine reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using textbooks and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Research Questions:

1. What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?
2. What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbook and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.
2. There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbooks and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi experimental design to assess the Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts Among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria. The design pretest- posttest, Experiment- Control group method requires that pretest be administered on students, after which treatment be giving to the experimental group. While the control group receive no treatment. And thereafter both the Experimental and Control groups receive post-test. The population comprises of eleven thousand two hundred and eighty-one (11,281) upper basic 2 students (male 4,680 and female 6,601) of 2022/2023 academic session. Therefore, the population of this study are located in twenty-five (25) public Upper Basic 2 School students in Dala Education zone which covers Dala and Gwale Local Government Councils of Kano State, Nigeria. **For the purpose of this study, four intact classes from four schools comprise 276 (Male 108 and Female 168) students who were sampled using multistage sampling techniques.**

The instrument for data collection was Social Studies Reading Habit Test (SSRT) which was developed by researcher. The SSRT consist of six short passages in social studies topics for the purpose of the treatment. The topics are family system, our culture, marriage system, transportation, national economy and social and health issues. At the end of each passage five items were drawn to make a total of 30 items. The instruments were subjected to construct and content validity. A pilot study aimed to determine the reliability coefficient of the designed instrument. Therefore, the researcher conducted a pilot study at one Secondary School from Dala Education zone which is Government Junior Secondary School Masaka. The school is part of the population, but not in the sample size. Thirty questionnaires were distributed for conducting the pilot testing. The reliability of the research instruments was determined by the outcome of the pilot study. After the pilot study, the data collected from the Pilot study was statistically analyzed for reliability index using Spearman-Brown (r) for measuring reading habit, the result obtained was 0.770. This result showed that the instrument was reliable for the study at hand.

The data collected on the effects of print media on reading habits in Social Studies concepts among secondary school students in Kano State, Nigeria was analyzed using statistical tools. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used in the analysis of the data. At descriptive level, the researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze responses of the research questions, while at inferential level, the researcher tested the hypotheses using inferential statistics of independent sample t-test to test the two hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Table 1: Description of Post-test Performance of Students Taught Social Studies Using Print Media and those exposed to lecture method.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	151	61.56	15.68	17.64
Control	125	43.92	11.14	

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Source: Field work 2023

Table 1 reveals the post-test performance of students taught social studies, in Upper basic schools using print media and those exposed to lecture method in Kano State. The mean scores as presented above shows that students taught Social Studies using print media at post-test (61.56) performed better as against those who were exposed to lecture method performance of (43.92), which yielded a mean difference of 17.64. Yet, the corresponding standard deviation of 15.68 and 11.14 were obtained respectively. This implies that students performed better if they were taught social studies with different kind of print media.

Research Question 2:

What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbook and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Table 2: Computation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ performance of Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	151	61.55	15.68	7.67
Control	125	53.88	12.75	

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 2 revealed the post-test students’ performance of both control and experimental group taught social studies, in Upper basic schools using printed short passages. The mean scores as presented above shows that students taught social studies concepts using printed short passages at post-test (61.56) performed better as their performance exceeds the control group performance of (53.88), with corresponding standard deviation of 15.58 and 12.75 respectively which yielded a mean difference of 7.67. This implies that students’ performance at post-test using short passages varied widely from that of control group who received no treatment.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Table 3: Paired t-test showing differences in post-test scores of students taught some Social Studies concepts using print media and those taught using lecture method in Upper basic II in Kano State.

Groups	N	M	SD	t cal.	Df	α	P- value	Decision
Experimental	151	61.56	15.68	150	10.98	0.05	0.01	Rejected
Control	151	43.92	11.14					

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 3 reveals the post-test performance of students taught social studies, using print media and those taught using lecture method. The Table shows that there is significant effect on print media on student’s reading habit comparing their performance with control group in post-test. The control group mean score is (43.92) against the experimental group mean score of (61.56), with standard deviation of 15.68 and 11.14 respectively. The t-test calculated of 10.98 is less than the p-value 0.01 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbooks and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State

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Table 4: Independent sample t-test showing differences in post-test scores of students taught some social studies concepts using short passages for experimental group and control group without any treatment in secondary school in Kano State.

Groups	N	M	SD	t. cal.	Df	α	P- value	Decision
Experimental	151	61.55	15.68	4.39	274	0.05	0.00	Rejected
Control	125	53.89	12.75					

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 4 reveals the performance of Students taught using short passages for experimental group and control group that received no treatment. The table shows that there is significant difference between the performance of experimental and control groups. After administering the post-test experimental group performance is higher than the control group performance with the mean score of (61.55) against the mean score of control group (53.89) with standard deviation of 15.68 and 12.75 respectively. The t-test calculated was 4.39 which is less than the p-value 0.01 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in post-test performance of students taught Social Studies using printed short passages and those without printed short passages in Upper basic schools in Kano State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the findings of the study, alongside the findings of other researchers. Firstly, finding number one reveals that there is significance deference between experimental group who taught social studies concept using different kind print media and control group who were expose with lecture method. This can be deduced from the results of both descriptive and inferential analysis. For instance, the descriptive analysis revealed that the mean score of control group is 43.92, while the experimental group mean scores is reading 61.56. For inferential analysis the result indicated that the calculated P-value of (0.01) is less than the critical value of (0.05) therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Jude and Udosen, (2012) in their study on the influence of print media strategies (magazines and Novels) in determining the development of students' reading competence in Akwalbom State, Nigeria, Jude and Udosen (2012), established that when students are exposed to print media, their higher reading competencies is developed and their performance would rise much higher.

The second finding revealed that experimental group who were taught some topics in social studies using short passages performed better against. Thus, the descriptive analysis revealed that the mean scores of experimental groups after post-test was 61.56 with standard deviation of 15.58 was quite different with those of control group that taught without short passages with mean scores of 53.88 with standard deviation of 12.75 which yielded the margin of 7.67. This implies that students' performance at post-test using short passages for the experimental group varied from that of the control group which received no treatment because there is a wide gap between the performance of experimental and that control groups. Equally, the inferential analysis revealed that the calculated P-value of (0.00) is less than the critical value (0.05) therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding established that, there was a significant difference in their performance. This finding is in contrary to that of Gulzar (2014), in his study effects of print media: A study of reading skills among University EFL Students. Gulzar (2014), revealed that a fixed and limited reading material of prescribed textbooks is one of the main causes of students' limitations of reading competence. Also, students were not exposed to the English language apart from the textbook materials in the classrooms at large and reading activities were also limited for the proper exposure to the reading skills. In view of this finding teachers should be encourages to make good use of textbook in the process of teaching. The use of textbook brings positive difference in students' performance.

Conclusion

Print Media significantly improved students' performance in Social Studies and facilitated their reading habits.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Social studies teachers should be encouraged to be using different kinds of print media in teaching social studies. This enables the students' performance to be improved and their readership attitudes will be developed. This can be done by the school Quality Assurance Officer and at workshops.

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2. Students should be frequently engaged with reading tasks within and outside the classroom. This is in line with developing students' reading interests and good reading habits so that their academic performance can be improved to a significant level.

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Efficacy of Social Studies Curriculum in Promoting Entrepreneurial Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the efficacy of Social Studies curriculum in promoting entrepreneurial skills among students in colleges of education in North-Central Nigeria. The study was guided by one research objective, one corresponding research question and one hypothesis. Descriptive survey method research design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 6,836 students during the 2022/2023 academic session in the colleges of education. A sample of 400 students was drawn from the population using multi-stage sampling technique, that is, purposive sampling was adopted in selecting the colleges, proportionate sampling was adopted to determine samples from the selected colleges and simple random sampling was used to select the respondents from each sampled college. The sample size was determined by Research Advisors (2010) table of determining sample size. The data used in the study was collected through researcher-made questionnaire vetted by a team of experts in Statistics and Language departments. Data collected was analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square test of independence. The hypothesis was retained because no significant relationship was found. The findings thus indicate that specific aspects of the curriculum, such as exposure to innovative ideas and economic activities, significantly influence students' interest in entrepreneurship. While the study supports the hypothesis of no significant difference in students' opinions on the curriculum's impact, recommendations are made to enhance the curriculum by incorporating practical experiences and expanding entrepreneurship education components.

Keywords: Social Studies, Teaching methods, Employment and Entrepreneur

Introduction

Functional educational development is apparently the most important ingredient that guarantees every country's development in all ramifications, because education is the key for sustainable development. This aphorism "education is not an end, itself, but, a means to an end" further buttresses the undeniable role of education towards the development of every nation. However, Social Studies as a distinctive Subject which plays a balancing role in solving the problems of every society, Nigeria inclusive, it is of paramount importance to canvass for a qualitative education. In view of the above, Udoh, Nsit and Ukpong (2014) reaffirmed that education has often been described as a powerful instrument of liberation from disease, ignorance and poverty. It is presumably established fact that, Social Studies curriculum is a well sought out from the needs, desires and aspirations of the society.

This is owing to the fact that the subject is dynamic in nature which fits in to the dynamism of the ever-changing world we live. According to Sofadekan (2012), before the introduction of western education in Nigeria, there had been a traditional form of education which was not rigidly structured. The purpose of traditional education was clear because functionalism was the main guiding principle that is, the curriculum was relevant to the needs of the

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society. Traditional education was generally a means for immediate induction into society and a preparation for adulthood. Abdul-Kabir (2014) observed that Social Studies education is a subject that develops in learners the right type of values and attitudes that are needed to create a peaceful and sustainable society. Social Studies education teaches values that would enable peaceful social Integration in Students. Values like maintenance of discipline, respect for law and order, recognition of the principles of cultural relativity and the effect of cultural ethnocentrism, respect for other people's rights, formation of social competency, and citizenship education (Adesina & Odedeji, 2011).

However, Nwaoga and Omeke (2012) established that, skills shortage, as earlier mentioned, remains a serious constraint in Nigeria. Over 80% of graduates in Nigeria are unemployed, yet they have the qualifications, Unemployment in Nigeria appears to be a labour market paradox, and can be attributed to prevailing skills deficit and skills mismatch. Most of the employers, therefore, select fresh graduates who studied in the relevant fields for their jobs as trainees for a number of years before decision is taken either to hire them on full-time basis or as casual workers (Kareem, Ademoyewa, Jolaosho, Ojenike & Sodiq, 2015). In this regard, Akiri, Onoja and Kunanzang (2016) buttressed that, the prosperity and progress of a nation depends on the quality of its people. If they are enterprising, ambitious and courageous enough to bear the risk, the community/society will develop quickly. Such people are identified as entrepreneurs and their character reflects entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is no monopoly of any religion or community. Akiri, Onoja and Kunanzang (2016) further opined that, entrepreneurial potential can be found and developed anywhere irrespective of age, qualification, experience or socio-economic background, only efforts are required in the right direction. Social Studies NCE curriculum contents is designed to include aspect that deals with man and his economic activities which exposes the students to activities that will ignites their zeal of becoming conscious of their inherited socioeconomic activities (Haruna & Hassan, 2019). As part of effort to impact entrepreneurship education students in all the colleges of education in Nigeria must undergo a course “entrepreneurship education” as a general course. In order to tackle the problem of unemployment various administrations had expedited the formation of laudable programmes or policies to condense the risk of the scourge such as N-POWER which started in 2016 by President Muhammadu Buhari administration in Batches and has six categories; N-Teach, N-Health, N-Agro, N-Build, N-Creative, and N-Tech respectively. It is against this backdrop this research was conducted.

Meanwhile, no society can grow above the quality of its education. Education has no specific definition in the field of humanity. Let's examine some scholarly definitions of education. Etymologically, the word “education” is a derivative of the Latin verb “*educare*” meaning ‘to bring up’, ‘to lead out’, ‘to raise up’, ‘to inform’, ‘to teach’ and ‘to train’. In its original sense, to educate means acting in order to lead out fully all the potentialities of an individual. Education is therefore a process of learning, acquiring and transferring knowledge, training, skills, and ideas. Fafunwa, defines it as the “aggregate of all the process by which a child or adult develops the abilities, attitudes and other forms of behavior which are of positive value to the society in which he lives, that is to say, it is a process of disseminating knowledge either to ensure social control or to guarantee rational direction of the society or both” (Nnaemeka, 2011, p.2). Adeel (2010) defines education as a means of transmitting worthwhile ideas that are considered necessary for an individual to conveniently adjust to his total environment. Education is a process that helps an individual to develop his/her whole being, physically. It is a process of transmitting culture in terms of continuity and growth and for disseminating knowledge to ensure social control of individuals (Mvendaga, Ifeanyichukwu & Apine 2014). This has a great implication for Social Studies.

Thus, Zakari (2014) posited that Social Studies is an organized, integrated study of man and his environment. Social Studies as the booster rocket of the human's development of all the faculties of a child. That will make him an effective citizen. Social Studies aims at offering a comprehensive study which takes care of the Child's cognitive effective and psychomotor domains. Similarly, Adeyemi (2013) Defined Social Studies as a course of discipline gained it is entrance in Nigeria school curriculum shortly after its independence precisely 1963 is at its infancy. Mores so, because of the nature of the subject (Social Studies) its definitions are countless that is why Ediyang, Ubi and Adelikwu (2012) asserted that Social Studies is aimed at inculcating the necessary skills, competences, and intellectual

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capabilities the learners will use for a healthy living in the society. To further, buttress the importance attached to Social Studies Basiru (2013) posited that, Social Studies presents the dynamics of values, interest and attitudes. Such that will help the learners in decision making on matters affecting them. Thus, Social Studies is a discipline that equips the learners with the tools necessary for their survival in the society. In view of this, Social Studies has been presumed as a problem-solving discipline that is capable of fixing socio-political worlds inflicted on the country by number of factors then, and now. In other words, Akinlola (2014) defined Social Studies as the planned and unplanned process by which individuals acquires values, skills and knowledge which will make them useful to themselves and the society at large. The goals of Social Studies are so beautifully designed to be in line with those of the national goals. Olawumi, Adu, and Adu (2021) reported that, one of the main functions of Social Studies is that it aims to educate learners to live a responsible life now and in the future in their communities. The essence and purpose of establishing the subject varies from one society to another. However, Social Studies curriculum addresses economic, political, psychological, physical and technological relevance of cultural and moral way of life of a people to national development. Its content is organized around social and environmental issues affecting man's existence, ability to perform and conserve the environment for sustainable development (Akpan, 2020). The fundamental focus of Social Studies is man and his complex relationships in the world around and beyond him. The NCE Social Studies curriculum attempts to instill in its products the basic knowledge, desirable values and skills for investigating, analyzing and explaining these interrelationships (NCCE, 2021).

Consequently, the economic entrepreneurship theory was adopted for this study. According to Simpeh (2011), the economic entrepreneurship theory has deep roots in the classical and neoclassical theories of economics, and the Austrian market process (AMP). These theories explore the economic factors that enhance entrepreneurial behavior. Classical Theory; the classical theory extolled the virtues of free trade, specialization, and competition. Neo-classical Theory; the neo-classical model emerged from the criticisms of the classical model and indicated that economic phenomena could be relegated to instances of pure exchange, reflect an optimal ratio, and transpire in an economic system that was basically closed. Austrian Market Process (AMP); these unanswered questions of the neo-classical movement led to a new movement which became known as the Austrian Market process (AMP).

Objective of the Study

Assess the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

Research Question

To what extent does Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

Methodology

The descriptive survey method was used for this study. The study covered 12 colleges of education offering Social Studies as a standalone course in North-Central, Nigeria. The population comprises of NCE III students from the colleges of education. The total number of Social Studies Students is 6,836. Research Advisors' (2010) table for determining sample size was the adopted blueprint for selecting number of respondents for the survey. Consequently, a sample size of 400 was adopted for use. The researcher therefore used a structured questionnaire for data collection in the study. The questionnaire was prepared based on four points modified Likert scale in which participants responded to each item with options ranging from Strongly Agreed (S.A) 4, Agreed (A) 3, Disagreed (D) 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) 1. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained from a pilot test which was conducted on thirty (30) Social Studies students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano State and the Cronbach's

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alpha reliability co-efficient index of .827 was obtained. Both descriptive and inferential statistics, such as, mean, standard deviation and Chi-square were used for the data analysis.

Results

Research Question

To what extent does Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected was subjected to descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Table 1 presents summary of the result.

Table 1: Summary of Means and Standard Deviations on views of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	Skills acquired for Entrepreneurship developments are embedded in NCE curriculum where Man's economic activities are taught as compulsory course.	3.0800	.85465
2	The study of Social Studies at NCE level stimulates self-employment intention where the traditions way of surviving is taught to students.	2.8300	.94251
3	Social Studies curriculum content exposes students to innovative ideas, which does not develop in the students a high level of autonomy.	2.0300	1.13239
4	Social Studies curriculum content does not enhance students' ability of critical and creative thinking.	2.2300	1.13150
5	Social Studies curriculum contents enlightens students on economic activities that existed generations before us, therefore, ignites the zeal to revive them.	2.8775	1.00749
6	Social Studies curriculum does not promote hardworking disposition among students to able to fend for themselves.	2.6300	1.02993
7	Social Studies curriculum does not promote self-awareness and self-confidence among students who use their talents to survive.	2.6500	.98992
8	Social Studies curriculum teaches the students about production system by exploring raw materials within their local community	2.5825	1.13861
9	Entrepreneurship skills taught in Social Studies NCE programme are not practical experiences required for self-employment	2.3900	1.08897
10	Social Studies curriculum contents which target students' manipulative skills such as craft making, drawing, discussion about mineral resources among others stimulate production	2.9525	1.02365
Aggregate Mean		2.62	1.033

Table 1 presents a summary of the means and standard deviations of students' views on the extent to which the Social Studies curriculum for the NCE program promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central Nigeria. This table serves as a crucial component of the study, offering valuable insights into the perceptions of students regarding the integration of entrepreneurship skills within the curriculum. The aggregate mean of 2.62, with a standard deviation of 1.033, indicates that, on average, students held a moderately positive perception of the relationship between the Social Studies curriculum and entrepreneurial skills. This suggests that there is a general inclination among students to view the curriculum positively in terms of fostering entrepreneurial

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abilities. The standard deviation of 1.033 reflects a moderate level of dispersion in responses, indicating some variability in how students perceive the curriculum's effectiveness in promoting entrepreneurial skills.

Among the individual items listed in Table 1, the highest mean response of 3.08 signifies a strong agreement among students with a particular statement related to the promotion of entrepreneurial skills. This high mean suggests that students are particularly supportive of certain aspects of the curriculum that are perceived to enhance entrepreneurial abilities. Conversely, the lowest mean of 2.03 indicates less agreement with a statement regarding the enhancement of critical and creative thinking skills through the curriculum. This disparity in mean values highlights the varying degrees of support for different aspects of the curriculum in relation to entrepreneurial skills development. The acceptance of positive response statements and rejection of negative statements by the respondents further underscore the general positive perception of the Social Studies curriculum in fostering entrepreneurial skills. This trend indicates that students are more inclined to acknowledge and appreciate the beneficial aspects of the curriculum that contribute to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria.

The data collected from students were summarized using tally system based. The summarized data was tested using non-parametric statistical tool of chi-square (χ^2) at 0.05% level of significance. The summary of the hypothesis tested is presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Summary of Chi-square (χ^2) statistics on the opinions of students regarding the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria.

N	χ^2 cal.	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
400	83.069 ^a	9	0.05	0.620	Retained

Source: Field Work

Table 2 shows that the calculated p-value of 0.620 was greater than 0.05 level of significance, while the χ^2 calculated value of 83.069 at df (9). Consequently, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The study yielded significant findings that contribute to our understanding of the role of education in fostering entrepreneurship. The analysis of mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square statistics provided valuable insights into students' perceptions and experiences regarding entrepreneurship education. One key finding of the study was the positive perception among students towards Social Studies curriculum's impact on entrepreneurial skills. Students acknowledged the relevance of the Social Studies curriculum in stimulating entrepreneurial thinking and preparing them for economic independence. This finding aligns with previous research (Chineze, Uche & Gabriel 2021) emphasizing the importance of integrating entrepreneurship education within the academic curriculum to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset. Furthermore, the study highlighted the value of practical experiences in enhancing students' entrepreneurial skills. Students emphasized the importance of hands-on opportunities, such as business idea development and engagement with local businesses, in enriching their understanding of entrepreneurial practices. This finding is consistent with existing literature (Secundo, Mele, Passiante & Albergo) that underscores the significance of experiential learning in entrepreneurship education.

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While the study found no significant difference in students' opinions on the promotion of entrepreneurial skills through the curriculum, it identified opportunities for curriculum enhancements to further support entrepreneurial development. Recommendations were made to broaden the curriculum to include entrepreneurship education and practical experiences that guarantee innovative skills among students. This recommendation is supported by previous studies (Lindberg, Bohman, Hulten & Wilson, 2017) advocating for the integration of entrepreneurship modules in educational curricula to foster entrepreneurial competencies. Also, the findings of the study underscore the importance of equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary for entrepreneurial success. By enhancing the Social Studies curriculum to incorporate entrepreneurship education and practical experiences, colleges of education in North-Central Nigeria can better prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the evolving business landscape. This aligns with the broader goal of education in promoting self-reliance, economic empowerment, and sustainable development.

This study equally found out that Social Studies NCE programme content areas are relevant in promoting determination to focus on innovative skills among students in Colleges of Education, North-Central, Nigeria. This implies that the students perceived that content areas of Social Studies NCE programme acquainted them with determination to focus on innovative skills such as Man's economic activities are taught as compulsory course, Social Studies at NCE level stimulates self-employment intention where the traditions way of surviving are taught to students and Social Studies curriculum content exposes students to innovative ideas, which does not develop in the students a high level of autonomy among others. This means that the content areas of Social Studies NCE programme which include: Man's economic activities, entrepreneurship education in general studies course and cultural identity and others are capable of making them determined to focus on innovative skills for their survival. This finding was supported by Nuhu, Abdullaheem, Abubakar, Abdurauf and Idiagbo (2021) where they conducted research on "Entrepreneur Skills as Determinants to Job Opportunities among LIS Postgraduate Students in University of Ilorin". They concluded that Entrepreneurial skills equip students with abilities that increase their employment potential and include: the abilities to solve problems, to develop social interaction, abilities to find information and to handle it for decision making, planning, and communication and presentation skills.

Conclusion

The study revealed a generally positive perception among students towards the curriculum's role in fostering entrepreneurial abilities. With an aggregate mean of 2.62 and consistent agreement on key aspects of the curriculum, students demonstrated a recognition of the curriculum's relevance in stimulating self-employment intentions and innovative skills. The findings support the hypothesis of no significant difference in students' opinions on the promotion of entrepreneurial skills through the curriculum, indicating a cohesive viewpoint among students. These results emphasize the importance of the Social Studies curriculum in equipping students with the necessary competencies for entrepreneurial endeavors and self-reliance, suggesting opportunities for curriculum enhancements to further support entrepreneurial development and economic empowerment in the region.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Colleges of education should consider enhancing the Social Studies curriculum by incorporating practical experiences and real-world applications of entrepreneurial skills. Institutions can better prepare students for self-employment and financial independence by giving them practical opportunity to participate in entrepreneurial activities, such as developing and implementing business ideas. Furthermore, working with nearby companies and entrepreneurs will help students gain insightful knowledge and excellent mentorship, which will enhance their comprehension of entrepreneurial processes.
2. Policymakers in the education sector should prioritize the integration of entrepreneurship education within the broader curriculum framework, emphasizing the development of critical and creative thinking skills essential for

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entrepreneurial success. Advocates for the inclusion of experiential learning opportunities and entrepreneurship modules in the curriculum can help students gain real-world experience and information that is applicable to today's corporate environment. Incentives for collaborations between academic institutions and business partners can also help students receive resources and entrepreneurial know-how.

3. Industry leaders and successful entrepreneurs play a crucial role in nurturing the next generation of entrepreneurial talent. Through active participation in mentorship programmes, guest lectures, and internship opportunities, industry leaders can offer invaluable insights and support to students who aspire to pursue entrepreneurial endeavours through active engagement with schools of education. Fostering an innovative, risk-taking, and resilient culture among students can aid in establishing the entrepreneurial attitude required to successfully navigate the obstacles of the corporate world. Furthermore, encouraging programmes that advance entrepreneurship education and skill development will help North-Central Nigeria's entrepreneurial environment become more dynamic and long-lasting.

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Evaluation of Software Design Tools on Enhancing Security Measures in Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Concern over security measures has grown in recent years as a result of tertiary institutions' rising reliance on technology. Academic institutions, especially universities and colleges of education, manage and retain a large volume of sensitive data, including student and faculty members' personal information and academic records. As a result, there is very little standardization in the administration and execution of security measures. Because of this variation, developing customized solutions necessitates an understanding of the unique security requirements of various organizations. The research seeks to address these multifaceted challenges by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of software design tools in the context of higher education. The objective is to assess the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures, considering the unique needs and constraints of educational institutions. The research strategy for this study was a mixed-methods approach. This population consist of a variety of stakeholders, in Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto such as students, faculty, administrative staff, and IT personnel. The results show that majority of the participants have significance experience and take measures in using software design tools to enhance security measures.

Keyword: Software Design Tools, Tools, Software, Security, Gidan Madi

Introduction

Concern over security measures has grown in recent years as a result of tertiary institutions' rising reliance on technology. Academic institutions, especially universities and colleges of education, manage and retain a large volume of sensitive data, including student and faculty members' personal information and academic records. Because of this data's great value and attractiveness to potential attackers, institutions must put strong security measures in place to safeguard their networks and systems. There are many different types of higher education institutions, and each has unique security requirements and limitations. The size, funding, and technological infrastructure of universities, colleges, and other educational institutions differ. As a result, there is very little standardization in the administration and execution of security measures (Rumez et al., 2020). Because of this variation, developing customized solutions necessitates an understanding of the unique security requirements of various organizations. In addition, the Cyber security threat landscape is ever-changing. Cybercriminals and hackers use more advanced techniques to get past security measures (Dillon et al., 2021). Higher education institutions now worry about ransomware attacks, data breaches, and other security events on a daily basis. These occurrences have the potential to impair educational pursuits, jeopardize confidential data, and cause large financial losses.

Higher education is changing and adapting to the digital age, and as a result, security is becoming more and more important to institutional governance rather than just being an IT issue (Alenezi, 2023). The findings of this study will be an invaluable tool for academic institutions as they work to improve security protocols, choose wisely which software

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development tools to use, and uphold their obligation to protect the data and digital infrastructure that are essential to their operations. A thorough summary of secure software development techniques was given by Humayun et al. (2022), who also handled project budgets and schedules. Based on the discovered practices, they put forth a secure SDLC framework that incorporates the best security practices throughout the SDLC stages. An analytical model is employed to verify the suggested structure. The suggested approach helps integrate security best practices into the whole SDLC, leading to more secure applications, as demonstrated via a case study and conclusions. Fuzzy analytic hierarchy process-technique for order preference by similarity ideal solution (AHP-TOPSIS) method was the hybrid multi-criteria decision-making strategy used by Alenezi et al. (2021) for the selection and evaluation of multi-criteria judgments. The suggested methodology combines the fuzzy TOPSIS order preference by similarity ideal solution with the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (fuzzy AHP). The results are obtained after the evaluation has been tried on fifteen various web application projects (online quiz competition, entrance test, and others) of Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow, India, in order to establish the efficacy of this technique. The tabulated results show how successful the Multi-Level Fuzzy Hybrid system's methodology is in accurately estimating how to make web applications more secure. In order to improve accuracy and increase security, the suggested study will assist developers and experts in creating and managing security from any stage of the web application design process.

The hybrid Fuzzy AHPTOPSIS technique was employed by Attaallah et al. (2021) to assess the risks associated with enhancing the security durability of various institutional web applications. Furthermore, software durability is used to measure the e-component of security risk, and vice versa. The paper's conclusions will be helpful in improving the security resilience of various online applications. In order to improve information security assurance in healthcare, Yeng et al. (2020) conducted a survey on current software development processes and evaluated their adequacy for gathering and analyzing security needs. Software security engineering standards and guidelines were used to gather information for security requirement activities. The extent to which the security activities were included into the current software development methodologies toward secure software development in the healthcare industry was then evaluated. The findings of this review indicate that traditional software development methods, such as the Waterfall Model, integrate security requirement capture activities more thoroughly than agile methods. By examining and contrasting various approaches and standards, Ramirez et al. (2020) concentrated on secure software development and identified the stages of the software development life cycle (SDLC) where one or more of these stages could be used to enhance the security of a software application while it is being developed.

Prior research has shed light on the variety of always changing security issues that higher education institutions must deal with. These difficulties cover a broad spectrum of topics, including sensitive information protection, regulatory compliance, data breaches, and cyber threats. Scholars have recorded cases of security breaches and incidents that have affected organizations' operations and reputation (Smith et al., 2019). Brown and Wilson (2019) conducted a thorough review of software design tools for security in tertiary institutions. The review focuses on analyzing software design tools specifically toured for security. Another study by Anderson and Parker (2018) examined the characteristics, weaknesses, and practical implementation elements of selected software design tools that are frequently used for security enhancement in tertiary institutions. Smith et al. (2018) and Johnson et al., (2019), carried out another investigation. With a focus on evaluating static code analysis tools, these tools help developers spot unsafe coding practices and enforce safe coding practices as security precautions. Using a threat modeling technique, one can detect possible risks and weaknesses in software systems. Developers can use these tools to prioritize security countermeasures, analyze the system architecture, and find probable attack vectors.

The research seeks to address these multifaceted challenges by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of software design tools in the context of higher education. This study to assess the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures, considering the unique needs and constraints of educational institutions. By doing so, this study aims to contribute to the development of tailored security strategies that can safeguard the digital infrastructure of higher education institutions while promoting a safe and secure learning environment.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assesses the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures,
2. To consider unique needs and constraints of educational institutions

Research Questions:

1. What personally experienced of any improvements in information security do stakeholders have as a result of using software design tools?
2. What are the challenges or concerns have encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in the institution
3. What are the specific security incidents or breaches in the institution that could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?

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11- What are the frequency of update its security policies and procedures and adhere to them?

Research Methodology

The research strategy for this study was a mixed-methods approach, chosen for its capacity to yield a comprehensive and multidimensional understanding of the subject themes. It is necessary to employ both quantitative and qualitative research methods in order to examine the many aspects of software design tools' contribution to enhancing security measures in higher education. The foundation of the quantitative portion of the study design is structured surveys. These surveys will be distributed to a representative and diverse sample of participants from Federal College of Education Gidan Madi. The quantitative part of the study aims to gauge users' perceptions of and usage of software design tools. By collecting data via surveys, we can identify statistical relationships, patterns, and trends that are pertinent to the goals of the study. The qualitative component, on the other hand, delves deeply into user experiences and institutional actions. Case studies and semi-structured interviews conducted at the selected institution make up this format. These qualitative methods seek to provide rich contextual information, engrossing narratives, and profound insights. On an interview platform, participants will be able to talk about their opinions, challenges, and experiences with software design tools.

The study's population is typified by those connected to Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, the primary case study institution. This population consists of stakeholders in Federal College of Education, GidanMadi. However, the primary emphasis of this study throughout its initial scope was the institution's internal community. The study's sample consists of one hundred stakeholders chosen from the Federal College of Education, GidanMadi during the 2023/2024 academic session. The quantitative part of the study, adopts a survey and a stratified random sampling method was used to divide the population into multiple strata based on the different stakeholder groups (administration staff, instructors, students, and IT personnel). From each stratum, a random sample was selected. This ensures that the survey responses are representative of the different demographic groups and enables meaningful comparisons to be made across different subsets.

The qualitative portion of the study, which comprises of case studies and interviews, adopts purposeful sampling. Experiences with software design tools and information security. Academic professionals, administrative staff, and IT staff with extensive expertise with these tools and their use was the focus of case studies and interviews. This tactic ensures that the qualitative portion carefully considers the perspectives of significant stakeholders. This study aims to capture a comprehensive view of the population's experiences, perceptions, and practices related to software design tools and information security within the context of Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi. It does this by combining stratified random sampling for the quantitative component and purposive sampling for the qualitative component. These sampling strategies are chosen to preserve the sample's representativeness while enabling a thorough examination of the experiences of individuals with particular knowledge and duties in this field.

The primary instrument for collecting quantitative data in this study was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire's goal is to compile user views, habits, and firsthand knowledge regarding software design tools and their impact on security procedures within the selected institution. Using a combination of closed-ended and Likert-scale questions in the questionnaire, respondents communicate their thoughts and experiences in a standardized manner. The questionnaire was sent to the selected sample of participants, and response tested. Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders was conducted. These stakeholders include academic staff, administrative staff, students and IT specialists who are knowledgeable in software design tools and information security. The interview guide contains open-ended questions to encourage participants to share their opinions, experiences, and thoughts. A further in-depth analysis of the research questions was made possible by extensive qualitative data collected from these interviews.

The case study component adopts case study methodology. These protocols outline the methodology and procedures for conducting in-depth case studies at the selected institution. The standards that govern data collection address information security protocols, the institutional environment, and the use of software design tools in depth. Case studies facilitate a comprehensive analysis of the study objectives and offer a complete viewpoint on the specific contexts in which these methodologies are used.

To obtain user viewpoints and experiences about software design tools and their impact on security measures, a methodical questionnaire was developed. The participants in the sample were selected from Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, using stratified random selection techniques. To facilitate the gathering of data, case study protocols and semi-structured interview guides were created. Using purposive sample techniques, key stakeholders—faculty, administrative staff, and IT professionals with knowledge of software design tools and information security—were chosen for interviews and case studies. Each question from the questionnaire was represented in a table in order to provide a flexible and easy interpretation

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of result. The table covers five valid sections which includes; Frequency, Percent, Valid percent, Cumulative percent and a bar chart to aid a pictorial representation of the collected data.

Results

To allow for flexible and simple result interpretation, each questionnaire question was expressed as a table. The table contains five useful sections: Cumulative percent, valid percent, Frequency, Percent, and a bar chart to help visualize the data that was gathered.

Q1: Sex Categories

Table 1: Sex Categories

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	60	60.0	60.0	60.0
Female	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

As seen in figure 1, the above table indicates that 60% of respondents were men and 40% were women. As seen in figure 1, the above table indicates that 60% of respondents were men and 40% were women.

Figure 1: Sex Categories

Q2: Years

Table 2: Years

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-30 Years	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
31-40 Years	40	40.0	40.0	50.0
41-50 Years	35	35.0	35.0	85.0
51 Years and Above	15	15.0	15.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

As can be seen in figure 2, 9.8% of the respondents were between the ages of 18 and 30, 39.2% were between the ages of 31 and 40, 8% were between the ages of 41 and 50, and 4% were over the age of 50.

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Figure 2: Years

Q3: Marital Status

Table 3: Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
Married	75	75.0	75.0	95.0
Divorce	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

It is evident from the preceding table that 20% of respondents were single, 75% were married, and 5% were divorced. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Marital Status

Q4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi?

Table 4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, GidanMadi?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Student	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
Faculty Member	29	29.0	29.0	49.0
Administrative Staff	20	20.0	20.0	69.0
IT Personnel	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Based on the statistics provided, the responsibilities at Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi are distributed as follows: Students make up 20% of the sample, followed by faculty members (29%), administrators (20%), and IT staff (31%). This is illustrated in Figure 4.

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Figure 4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi?

Table 5: Have you personally experienced any improvements in information security as a result of using software design tools?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	89	89.0	89.0	89.0
No	10	10.0	10.0	99.0
Undecided	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Examining personal experiences with information security improvements due to the use of software design tools, a significant majority of respondents (89%) affirm positive changes, while a minority of 10% report no discernible improvements. One respondent (1%) remains undecided on the matter. This can be shown in figure 5.

Have you personally experienced any improvements in information security as a result of using software design tools?

Figure 5: Have you personally experienced any improvements in information security as a result of using software design tools?

Table 6: What challenges or concerns have you encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in your institution?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Technical compatibility issues	42	42.0	42.0	42.0

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Lack of user training	30	30.0	30.0	72.0
Budget constraints	12	12.0	12.0	84.0
Resistance to change	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Identifying challenges or concerns encountered in using software design tools for security enhancement within the institution, respondents noted the following: 42% faced technical compatibility issues, 30% cited a lack of user training, 12% dealt with budget constraints, and 16% encountered resistance to change. This can be shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: What challenges or concerns have you encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in your institution?

Table 7: Are there specific security incidents or breaches in your institution that you think could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	15	15.0	15.0	15.0
No	80	80.0	80.0	95.0
Undecided	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

In considering the potential impact of software design tools on security incidents or breaches within the institution, 15% of respondents believe that such tools could have prevented or mitigated incidents. Meanwhile, 80% express the view that these tools may not have made a significant difference, and 5% remain undecided on the matter. This can be shown in figure 7.

Evaluation of Software... (Abdulkadir, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11474724>

Figure 7: Are there specific security incidents or breaches in your institution that you think could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?

Table 8: Do you believe that the utilization of software design tools for security enhances the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders (e.g., students, parents, faculty, etc.)?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	95	95.0	95.0	95.0
Undecided	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Examining perceptions on the impact of utilizing software design tools for security on the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders, an overwhelming 95% of respondents believe that such utilization enhances the institution's standing. Meanwhile, 5% remain undecided on this matter. This can be shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Do you believe that the utilization of software design tools for security enhances the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders (e.g., students, parents, faculty, etc.)?

Table 9: How frequently does your institution update its security policies and procedures?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very frequently	80	80.0	80.0	80.0

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Frequently	9	9.0	9.0	89.0
Occasionally	7	7.0	7.0	96.0
Rarely	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Regarding the frequency of updating security policies and procedures within the institution, a substantial 80% of respondents indicate that updates are made very frequently. In contrast, 9% report updates occurring frequently, 7% occasionally, and a minor 4% rarely. This can be shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: How frequently does your institution update its security policies and procedures?

Table 10: Does your institution need to adhere to any of the following regulations or compliance standards regarding data security and privacy?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act)	41	41.0	41.0	73.0
FERPA (Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act)	17	17.0	17.0	90.0
PCI DSS (Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard)	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Concerning adherence to data security and privacy regulations or compliance standards within the institution, the respondent ticked as follows: GDPR: 32%, HIPAA: 41% FERPA: 17% PCI DSS: 10%. This can be shown in figure 10.

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Figure 10: Does your institution need to adhere to any of the following regulations or compliance standards regarding data security and privacy?

Discussion of Findings

Staff and students at Federal College of Education Gidan Madi were asked how much they knew about the use of software design tools. Table 1 revealed that men make up roughly 60% of the participants, which suggests that women also participate to a considerable extent. The bulk of participants, as seen by Table 2, are between the ages of 31 and 40. The data presented in Table 3 indicates that the majority of participants are married. The bulk of participants are IT professionals, as Table 4 illustrates. Also, Table 5 shown that majority of the respondent (89%) affirm positive changes in examining personal experiences with information security improvements due to the use of software design tools, table 6 shown that majority of the respondent (42%) faced technical compatibility issues in respect of challenges or concerns encountered in using software design tools for security enhancement within the institution, table 7 shown that majority of the respondent (80%) express the view that these tools may not have made a significant difference in considering the potential impact of software design tools on security incidents or breaches within the institution, table 8 shown that majority of the respondent (95%) of respondents believe that such utilization enhances the institution's standing on the impact of utilizing software design tools for security on the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders.

Furthermore, table 9 shown that majority of the respondent (80%) of indicate that updates are made very frequently regarding the frequency of updating security policies and procedures within the institution and table 10 shown that majority of the respondent (41%) follow Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act data security and privacy regulation.

Conclusion

To sum up, the careful assessment of software design tools for improving security measures at Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, reveals a complex environment in which technical solutions are essential to strengthening the security posture of the school as a whole. A good step towards a robust cybersecurity framework is indicated by the overwhelmingly positive reaction from respondents, with 65% expressing confidence in the major advances brought about by these technologies. The prioritizing of data encryption and enhanced network monitoring technologies, which are in line with contemporary best practices, indicate a proactive response to the ever-evolving threat landscape. Crucially, the collaborative and cooperative spirit within the institution, as evidenced by the IT Department's central role and the excellent level of cooperation and communication between departments (76%), underscores a collective commitment to a robust security infrastructure. This collaborative ethos is foundational in fostering a holistic understanding of security needs and ensures that all stakeholders, including students, faculty, and administrative staff, feel adequately supported.

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However, it's crucial to acknowledge the identified challenges, particularly technical compatibility issues (42%) and the need for user training (30%). Addressing these challenges should be approached not merely as technical hurdles but as opportunities for continuous improvement. Furthermore, the institution's commitment to very frequent security policy updates (80%) positions it at the forefront of adapting to emerging threats and adhering to the ever-evolving cybersecurity landscape. In navigating the future, Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, stands poised to leverage technology and collaboration as cornerstones in fortifying its security measures. As the institution continues to evolve, sustaining a proactive and adaptive approach will be pivotal in maintaining not only the current positive momentum but also in proactively addressing emerging challenges in the realm of cybersecurity.

Maintain the institution's commitment to very frequent security policy updates (80%) to ensure that security measures align with emerging threats and industry best practices. Establish a framework for continuous evaluation of security measures, regularly soliciting feedback from stakeholders to adapt strategies based on evolving needs and technological advancements.

Recommendations

In light of these findings, we suggested:

1. Ongoing training programs.
2. Handling of technical compatibility concerns and guarantee that all users are adept in utilizing software design tools to their fullest potential,
3. Implementation of regular and customized training initiatives.

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Impact of Addressing Education in North-East Nigeria (AENN) Programme on Literacy Education among Children and Youths in Yobe State

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Abstract

Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria (AENN) programme seeks to respond to the immediate educational needs of youth and children in Yobe state through safe non-formal and formal literacy education in the area of foundational skills (functional, critical and traditional Literacy skills) which is the target area of (AENN) programme. This paper was guided by four research questions which include: to assess the impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills provided among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state, and last to determine the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study population was (13123) Children and Youth who registered with AENN literacy education programme. The sample size of 390 was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan Table. Stratified Random sample was used for selecting samples from three programme education zones. The closed questionnaire with liker-type scale was used for data collection. The validation of the instrument was done through content and face validity, by three experts from research unit in Yobe state University. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of test and retest method, the first week and after two weeks later. The analysis was done using PPMC and result showed a measure of stability at 0.870. The descriptive statistic of simple percentage was used to analyze data collected. The findings of the present study have revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill on social and livelihood among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state. It is recommended Based on findings the AENN literacy education programme should continue to satisfy educational need of teaming population in the State.

Keywords: AENN Project, needs of Literacy Education and programme learner-beneficiaries

Introduction

Literacy education is a continuum of learning opportunity provided to learners through non-formal and formal education at various Centers and Institutions by Governments, Individuals, cooperate bodies and Organizations with aim to extensively, address the public illiteracy and promote literate society (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019). In the year (2020) Therefore, the AENN programme in Northeast Nigeria has sought to respond to the immediate educational needs of 302,500 project beneficiaries between youth school dropout and the out of school children in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education. The project was concerned to ensure that youth school dropout and the out of school children have equitable access to literacy education programme that would focus and foster the skills of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills and provide opportunities through non-formal and formal education programme, in Yobe states as reported in United States Agency for International Development {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020).

The critical concern of AENN Project} (2020) is to improve on the social and economic transformation in the life of people in their communities through Literacy skills of functional, critical and traditional literacy skills for the programme learner-beneficiaries around: ability and skill to read, write, spell, listen and speak. Hence the ability and skill of literacy incorporated to the social and economic activities involving the life in the community; reading and writing skills that are adequate to manage daily earns livelihood and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level; central thinking skills as it is done in both tertiary and secondary education to develop in students.

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The literacy skill is also incorporated to health and disease prevention, psychosocial support to prepare youth and children to positive behavior skills, ability and competence for improving social and economic life by providing the learning needs of beneficiaries in a consistent manner; maximizing positive gender norms and minimizing negative gender norms in providing equal education opportunities which learner-beneficiaries would have availed themselves under The Literacy education programme for Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria (AENN) {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020). In spite of the predetermined goals of literacy education programme of (AENN) The recent gradual transformation in public policy, economic policy which have affected community life, social system as well as proliferation in science and technology greatly also affected community way of life in term of security, social, economic and political lives of people in our entire society {USAID and AENN Project Manual} (2020). These circumstances therefore, affect mind-set of many youth school dropout and out of school children to view the impact of literacy education skills to their contemporary life in society and now begin to recognize the needs of literacy skills in order to help them improve and cope with prevailing living gaps in our society. The question to ask here is that, does the Literacy education provided by the AENN programme satisfy the needs of programme beneficiaries in terms of functional, critical, and traditional literacy skills in Yobe state?

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the impact of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
2. To assess the impact of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
3. To assess the impact of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state.
4. To determine the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state.

Research Questions

1. What are the impact of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
2. What are the impact of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
3. What are the impact of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state?
4. What are the challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state?

Review of Related Literatures

Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria (AENN) seeks to respond to the immediate Educational needs of 302,500 project beneficiaries between youth school dropout and the out of school children in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education. While laying a foundation for the sustainable improvement of education systems at the community and government levels. AENN in particular has worked with community and government partners to provide safe and certified education opportunities, to revitalize/establish non-formal learning centers and support formal schools in 225 communities. The activity ensured that the safety and well-being of students were prioritized in target locations by engaging communities and school personnel in developing safety plans and codes of conduct for teachers. A minimum package of learning materials was provided to enrolled learners that will improve upon existing curricula to emphasize age-appropriate foundational skills (literacy, numeracy, social-emotional learning, and vocational skills) reported in {USAID and AENN Project} (2020).

AENN project in (2023-2024) identified and established 300 new NFLCs (Non-Formal Learning Center) as revealed {USAID and AENN Project} (2023) in Borno and Yobe States; enrolls 46,385 learners: AENN worked with the CBO (Community-Based Organization) sub-grantees and CCs (Community Coalition). AENN has supported 900 NFLCs and 79 formal schools in intervention communities across Borno and Yobe States. As a result of collective mobilization efforts coordinated by the activity, enrollment figures during the quarter shot up in both States and reached a high of 46,3852 (19,599 males; 26,786 females), 29% above the activity's targets of 36,000 basic literacy learners.

In Yobe State AENN Mainstreams 8,445 Basic Literacy completers to formal schools in Yobe States: The activity completed the mainstreaming of all learners from the Year One cohort to either formal school - for learners below the age of 12 or to post- basic literacy programme for adolescent learners. The Yobe States Agency for Mass Education took the lead in the assessment, moderation and certification of learners. AENN also provided testimonials to all learners to certify their

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participation in the cohort 1 learning activities. After the end of programme examination, the activity collaborated with State Agency for Mass Education (SAME) to compile and send the list of successful learners to SUBEB and LGEAs for placement. In all 8,445 learners (4,529 males, 3,916 females) were successfully mainstreamed during the reporting period, {USAID and AENN Project} (2020).

Table 1: Number of learners mainstreamed into formal schools and those transitioning into the post-basic literacy program to continue their basic education pursuit along formal and non-formal education streams respectively.

States	Post Literacy			Mainstreamed Into formal Schools		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Yobe	2,759	1,413	4,172	1,770	2,503	4,273

AENN Year Two Quarter Two Report January 1 to March 31, 2024

Activity Implementation Progress

In Yobe State AENN started the quarter with preparations for the mainstreaming of cohort one learners into formal schools and Post-basic literacy programme, and the enrollment of new learners into cohort 2 Basic-literacy course. The activity worked with relevant government partners to revise and adapt the mainstreaming guidelines first produced by the USAID-Education Crisis Response project in 2017. The new guideline clearly spelt out the pathways for completers of the basic literacy program depending on their age and education experience {USAID and AENN Project} (2024). As at March 2024, in Yobe State AENN mainstreamed 8,445 cohort one learners (4,529 males, 3,916 females) into formal schools in Yobe States (more learners will be mainstreamed into formal schools as soon as schools reopen). Also among the cohort 1 learners, 8,640 (4,384 males, 4,256 females) adolescent learners transitioned into the Post-literacy program offered by the activity (this number will also increase as more learners transition into the post-literacy course when schools reopen).

Following the Back to Learning campaign conducted in all AENN communities in Yobe States, AENN exceeded its enrollment target for Y2 by 29 per cent. The activity collaborated with the CBOs and CCs for pre- enrollment of the second cohort of learners into the NFLCs in Yobe States.

Table 2: Number of learners enrolled to Basic and Post Basic literacy program in Yobe States

Learners enrolled into Basic Literacy (cohort 2)			Learners transitioned into Post Basic		
Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
6,070	6,929	12,999	2,759	1,413	4,172

AENN Year Two Quarter Two Report January 1 to March 31, 2024

Concept of Literacy Education

Literacy is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy involves a continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society (UNESCO, 2017) as cited in (Kosioma Eli, 2019). Indabawa (1995) referred to it as the ability to acquire the skills of reading, writing and numeracy in local or foreign language for effective and efficient functioning of individuals in the activities they involve themselves in the society. Thus, literacy is seen as a human right, a tool for personal empowerment and social development as cited in (Christian and Gloria, 2016). They have further pointed out that the importance of literacy as it was captured by Kaufman and Kraay (2008) that it is the heart of basic Education for All (EFA) and essential for eradicating poverty, reducing child mortality, curbing population growth, achieving gender equality and ensuring sustainable development, peace and democracy.

The Centre for Literacy (2014) put literacy to be a complex set of abilities needed to understand and use the dominant symbol systems of a culture—alphabets, numbers, visual icons—for personal and community development. It touches every aspect of individual and community life. It is an essential foundation for learning through life, and must be valued as a human right. Canadian Council of Learning (2007) further emphasized literacy to be an essential part of the fabric of modern societies, a thread that links all aspects of life and living in our contemporary world. Its reach is extensive and complex, influencing how fully and effectively a person is able to engage in the social and economic life of his or her community.

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To buttress the above definitions of literacy The National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE, 2008) has summarized what literacy should achieve in today's knowledge economy. According to the Organization's report, active, successful participants in this 21st century global society must be able to; Develop proficiency and fluency with the tools of technology, Build intentional cross-cultural connections and relationships with others so to pose and solve problems collaboratively and strengthen independent thought, Design and share information for global communities to meet a variety of purposes, Manage, analyze, and synthesize multiple streams of simultaneous information, Create, critique, analyze, and evaluate multimedia texts, Attend to the ethical responsibilities required by these complex environments.

Giving credence to this statement, UNESCO (2014) posited the usefulness and benefits of literacy as helping learner to get knowledge and skills that are useful in everyday life activities, helping learners to communicate to people especially in writing, giving the learner a feeling of self-confidence, personal security and freedom from being cheated or exploited. It further helps the individual to actively participate in politics, increases one's economic, political and social gains, and helps the individual to operate new machines (such as the ATM). No wonder, Omoruyi and Omage (2013) noted that the purpose of literacy is the liberation of man from the restraints and limitations of ignorance and dependence. A cursory look at these benefits shows that literacy education programme is capable of raising the consciousness of individual to be more aware of the fundamental problems in their locality and lives, and the extent they are motivated to improve their conditions.

Albert Education also defines literacy as the ability, confidence and willingness to engage with language to acquire, construct and communicate meaning in all aspects of daily living. Literacy is also the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy is also seen a process by which one expands one's knowledge of reading and writing in order to develop one's thinking and learning for the purpose of understanding oneself and the world. This process is fundamental to achieving competence in every educational system and is required for drop out youth and children survival in a new environment. Basic literacy is an important tool for people to be able to comprehend the world around them and make informed decisions. Literacy is not only a human right but also an enabling tool that will unlocks the door to the enjoyment of many other human rights, including the right to freedom of expression, the right to participate in public affairs, the right to work, and the right to participate in cultural life. All these are needed by drop out youth and children to maintain their dignity as human beings. This is cited in (Kosioma Eli, O. 2019). Literacy is the cornerstone of development. Literacy lifts individuals out of poverty and lacking in basic reading and writing skills is a tremendous disadvantage. Literacy not only enriches an individual's life, but it creates opportunities for people to develop skills that will help them provide for themselves and their family.

From a collective perspective, a literate society is a dynamic society that exchanges ideas, engages in dialogue, innovative and productive. Literacy and English language proficiency are tools that help people move out of poverty and get better-paying jobs to support their families. Limited health literacy is associated with lower health outcomes, increased rates of hospitalization, decreased use of preventative services, poor health management, and higher costs. It is essential for social and human development and provides individual the skills and empowers them to transform their lives with an improved standard of health and ability to earn a higher income. Adhikari and Joshi (2008) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014). In 1991, the US National Literacy Act defined literacy as an individual's ability to read, write and speak in English to solve problems at a level of proficiency necessary to function in society, to achieve one's goals and to develop one's knowledge and potential reported in Eno E. Uduak G. Mbaba, Alice U. and E. Patricia I. (2010) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014). Street (2003) defined literacy as conceptions of reading, writing and all types of social practices and many theorists favor such a broad definition in which social contexts of literacy practice are also considered cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014). Warschauer, (2010) asserting that what is considered skillful reading and writing differs with the historical, political and sociocultural contexts as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) Gee, (1996) stated that when the context is considered, literacy becomes 'having mastery over the process by means of which culturally significant information is coded.

De Castell and Luke, (1988) as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) opined the concept of literacy as a continuum that includes the ability to reproduce letter combinations at one extreme and the ability to engage in logical thinking, higher-order cognitive skills and reasoning on the other as cited in Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) Clifford, (1984). Lank, shear and Knobel (2004) argued that literacy has many different definitions under varying social conditions and that the nature of the concept changes within the conditions of textual work. Similarly, Leu et al. (2007) argued that achieving a precise definition of literacy is not possible because it's meaning changes regularly. Much of the literacy-related literature of the last decade focuses on what it means to be literate in contemporary society, referring to a spectrum of abilities that relate to digital technologies, particularly the Internet. These definitions often attempt to extend the traditional notion of literacy beyond its application to the medium of writing

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Forms of literacy Education: Traditional, Functional and Critical Literacy Skills

As the AENN seeks to respond to the immediate educational needs of children and youth in Borno and Yobe states through safe non-formal and formal education which are incorporated to traditional, functional and critical literacy skills programmes focusing on (literacy; reading, writing, speaking, numeracy, social-emotional learning, and vocational skills) for the sustainable improvement of education systems at the community and government levels.

Traditional literacy skills

In the traditional sense, literacy is the ability of reading and writing. Traditional literacy learning involves learning rules and conventions such as spelling or grammar rules Wilder and Dressman, (2006) as cited in Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014). They have further stated that besides, students read texts seen to be of “literary value” and try to comprehend “meanings” that were thought by the author. Successful acquisition of literacy is manifested by giving the right answers in multiple choice comprehension tests or writing “correctly”, which shows that one has comprehended the “correct” meanings written in texts. Students passively accept the knowledge which is presented to them as “correct”. This approach to literacy, which is called “transmission pedagogy”, produces compliant learners who will be willing to follow directives of received authority at work. In other words, they lack creativity or critical thinking which the modern society requires. Schrock (2021) opined that traditional literacy skillset contains the traditional literacies of reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) also opined that traditional literacy is the ability to read, write and understand text and is a primary source of information and communication. There is some evidence that one’s capacity to use the Internet remains contingent on his or her level of traditional literacy (Wilder and Dressman, 2006) as cited in van (Deursen and van Dijk 2014).

However, empirical studies focusing on the relationship between traditional literacy and Internet skills among populations at large are, to our knowledge, non-existent. One reason for this lack of empirical investigations might be the overabundance of Internet skills-related concepts and definitions that often remain abstract. Traditionally, literacy has been defined as the ability to use written language actively and passively or the ability to read, write, spell, listen and speak Moats, (2000) and Bawden (2008) states that the simplest form of literacy involves the ability to use language in its written form: ‘A literate person is able to read, write and understand his or her native language and express a simple thought in writing’ this is as cited in van (Deursen and van Dijk 2014)

Functional literacy skills

Functional literacy is seen as the broader concept of literacy however as cited in Oduola (2015) that Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (1997) defines functional literacy as the ability to understand and employ printed information in daily activities at home, at work, and in the community to achieve one’s goals and to develop one’s knowledge and potential. Similarly, Canadian Council of Learning Report (2007) has the following to say about functional literacy a true literacy encompasses much more than just these basic skills. It includes the ability to analyze things, understand general ideas or terms, use symbols in complex ways, apply theories, and perform other necessary life skills including the ability to engage in the social and economic life of the community.

Functional literacy deals with how people actually use such skills to live and work in society. Furthermore, Schlechty (2014) defined functional illiteracy to be ‘reading and writing skills that are inadequate to manage daily living and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level’. In other words, functional literacy could be seen as the ability of individuals to possess the reading and writing skills that are adequate to manage daily living and employment tasks that require reading skills beyond a basic level. Functional literacy refers to the practical skill set needed to read, write, and do math for real-life purposes, so people can function effectively in their community UNESCO (2000) as cited in Cocchiarella (2018). Functional approaches to literacy focus on reading and composing the texts that enable students to succeed at school and in society. These approaches aim to help learners understand why real-world texts exist and how this affects texts. Functional approaches start with the question “What is the purpose of this text?” and the next question is “How is the text structured to meet this communicative purpose” This was reported in (Van Deursen and van Dijk 2014).

Critical literacy

Critical literacy is a timeless needed skill that means you are able to analyze and evaluate forms of text by critiquing the author/source and considering the bias that the source has, (Peterson2018). Critical literacy means to be detailed in your thoughts while interpreting a text. It is, “the ability to analyze, evaluate and critically reflect on the media a person encounters and creates” (Buckingham, 2010). Critical literacy as cited in the Oxford Research Encyclopedias that individuals must be

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critically literate not only in school, but we need to take these skills with us through our entire lives and Critical literacy should not be a topic to be covered or a unit to be studied. Instead, it should be looked on as a lens, frame, or perspective for teaching throughout the day, across the curriculum, and perhaps beyond” (Vasquez, 2018). This is a skill that is as necessary as being able to be culturally aware. Just like how you need maps to navigate through winding roads and confusing cities, you need critical literacy to be able to effectively navigate through various texts, in traditional print or in forms of media. He further opined that Critical literacy is a central thinking skill that a tertiary education seeks to develop in students. It involves the questioning and examination of ideas, and requires you to synthesize analyses, interpret, evaluate and respond to the texts you read or listen to.

Batchelor, (2019) has asserted that Critical literacy encourages students to use language to question their everyday world experiences, and in particular, the relationship dynamic between language and power. She further explained that in most cases, these dynamics are rarely obvious. More often, they are part of many nuanced and interconnected factors that underlie the plots and perspectives of the narratives we consume. And unless viewed through a critical lens, the inherent biases that are often present can go unnoticed and unquestioned. “For example,” Batchelor explains, “if you're reading *Little House on the Prairie*, asking students to consider the indigenous voices, and who was there on the Prairie besides the family.” So critical literacy not only encourages multiple perspectives, it also helps us step back and get a clearer look at a bigger cultural picture. And since she works primarily with education majors studying to become English teachers, Batchelor exposes students to a variety of texts by helping them to re-see the world in numerous ways. Some of the most commonly used practices that support critical literacy included: reading supplementary texts; reading multiple texts; reading from a resistant perspective; producing counter-texts; having students conduct research about topics of personal interest; and challenging students to take social action. Reading from a critical perspective requires thinking beyond the text to understand issues such as why the author wrote about a particular topic, wrote from a particular perspective, or chose to include some ideas about the topic and exclude others. Teachers who facilitate the development of critical literacy encourage students to interrogate societal issues and institutions like family, poverty, education, equity, and equality in order to critique the structures that serve as norms, and to demonstrate how these norms are not experienced by all members of society.

By matching our teaching with the specific talents and needs of our students, and by considering our students' points of views in early childhood literary teaching, we are able to speak to children's identities and empower them. We must use texts in our classrooms with which students will identify, that reflect the lives and experiences of our students, as well validate them. The books we read with our students should address issues that affect the lives of our in important ways. We must also engage students in meaningful class discussions and conversations about these books, crossing lines of culture, gender, race, and class, as well as providing students with opportunities to critically examine the world around them. Critical literacy does not end in discussion, rather it leads to action. Critical literacy is a perspective and way of thinking about curriculum, literacies, and the lived experiences of our students. Critical literacy is the ability to read texts in an active, reflective manner in order to better understand power, inequality, and injustice in human relationships. Critical literacy views readers as active participants in the reading process and invites them to move beyond passively accepting the text's message to question, examine, or dispute the power relations that exist between readers and authors. It focuses on issues of power and promotes reflection, transformation, and action (Leo, 2018). He has also pointed out the important of critical literacy to life as We need critical literacy because it helps us; to establish equal status in the reader-author relationship, to understand the motivation the author had for writing the text and how the author uses the text to make us understand in a particular way, to understand that the author's perspective is not the only perspective, and to become active users of the information in texts to develop independent perspectives, as opposed to being passive reproducers of the ideas in texts.

In addition Critical literacy helps us to read texts in deeper, more meaningful ways, by encouraging readers of all ages to become more actively engaged and use their power to construct understanding and not be used by the text to fulfill the intentions of the author. Critical literacy helps us to move beyond passive acceptance to take an active role in the reader-author relationship by questioning issues such as who wrote the text, what the author wanted us to believe, and what information the author chose to include or exclude in the text. The development of critical literacy skills enables students to look at the world through a critical lens and challenge the power relations within the messages being communicated. Critical teaching allows students to actively work out their learning and problem solving, by providing an outlet, a source of action or social justice. Critical teaching allows students to better connect classroom practice with the social realms they engage in outside of school, providing a connection between the home, school, and social realms. Critical literacies practice engages students and allowing them to use their previous experiences, providing classroom literacies more similar to literacies used outside of the classroom. Using critical literacy as a frame through which the teacher and students design curricula and use literacies in the classroom,

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helps students view literacy as connected to their personal experiences and as a tool to use effectively to explore and effect change in their lives. Critical literacy is the form of literacy capability in making contradiction and reflection of the information provided in texts. Critical literacy awareness emphasizes the fact that text can be constructed to understand the background and choices made by the author. By knowing the background, the students will have a comprehensible understanding of a certain text. In critical literacy, this kind of understanding can be received by reading as well as thinking critically which are closely related. This was reported in (Leo, 2018). She has further examined the relationship between critical literacy and critical reading and thinking can be found in the scheme below. There are sequential stages to create critical literacy skills. The scheme is based on the assumption that receiving information (in this case is reading) and putting them on the brain that involves thinking capability (the ability to think critically) are the basic things to respond the information. In addition, research showed that there was a significant positive relationship between reading and critical thinking; critical reading skills will help students to practice critical thinking.

In order to understand the whole information given, the students will think critically while analyzing and evaluating text in the process of reading. After successfully getting the information, they will take a side and make contradictions for testing the validity of the information, whether it is suitable for the current situation. This is called as critical literacy capability. Critical reading activity, its process focuses on understanding explicit and implicit information. That critical reading activity helps the students in deeply understanding certain text and criticizing new information. Critical reading techniques involve the ability to analyze, comparing, and assessing the content of the text. This technique requires students to think critically about which they should not only passively receive the information but also actively give responses. It then becomes the basic thing in creating students' critical literacy skills. Critical thinking is an ability to use complex thinking and reasoning skill. Critical thinking requires the students to be active in analyzing and evaluating the facts of information to obtain or make some conclusion. It can be developed since the early ages in accordance with cognitive development. Its activities are made based on the stages and portion of students' cognitive development through simple and sustainable activities.

Reviewing Impact of Literacy education Programmes of AENN Project in 2024, Yobe state

In March 2024 AENN conducted a Rapid Education and Risk Analysis (RERA) and Gender Equity and Social Inclusion (GESI) assessment to provide conflict, gender, and socially inclusive sensitive recommendations for the program design and operations. The first assessment was in 2018 and focused mostly on understanding the factors responsible for educational exclusion. In 2020 (AENN) project was introduced aiming to ensure that out of school children and dropout adolescents in Northeast Nigeria have equitable access to literacy education skills opportunities through non-formal and formal education programme. The Year Two Quarter Report (2024) Assessments shows improved learning performance among cohort one learners: The end-line Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) conducted by the activity showed statistically significant improvements in all reading subtasks (letter sound, syllables, oral reading fluency, and reading comprehension). It also showed statistically significant improvements in almost all Math subtasks (number identification, simple addition, and simple subtraction) girls have higher gains than boys In Yobe, average ORF scores increase by 11 CWPM for males and 14 CWPM for females. Across both states and genders, learners perform best in number identification, then addition, then subtraction.

Yobe States again assess progress made in implementation of the community action plans that were created. The participants were clustered into small groups according to their respective communities to assess and review progress made towards addressing education exclusion within communities. The review session revealed that CCs and community members have continued to make significant progress in the implementation of the community action plans developed and reviewed last quarter. The CCs made presentations showing that community action plan activities, such as community awareness sessions to increase education opportunities for girls and boys, have remained ongoing across the communities. The (AENN) project work to increase social cohesion by facilitating meaningful community dialogues to ensure that all vulnerable children are part of the non-formal learning communities. Social-emotional learning activities will help different children form positive relationships and peacefully resolve conflicts in NFLCs and formal schools.

The pre-enrollment figures presented earlier in this report shows that the AENN activity is succeeding in bridging the gap between male and female participation in literacy education. Currently, the activity's pre-enrollment figures show disparity between female learners at 58% and that of their male counterparts at 42% in the non-formal learning centers. AENN organized several town hall meetings and back to learning campaigns to encourage the enrollment of girls into either school or non-formal learning centers. The findings of the Gender Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) assessment conducted in 2018 and 2019 showed low level of female involvement in education activities in Yobe States. Based on this finding, AENN prioritized female participation in trainings, workshops and meetings during the reporting period. AENN also facilitated a training for 250 (142

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Male, 105 Female) parents/caregivers on ways of maximizing positive gender norms and minimizing negative gender norms in providing equal education opportunities for girls and boys. The training also enhanced the capacities of the parents/caregivers on ways of preventing, mitigating and responding to school related gender-based violence in a bid to promote violent-free home environment.

The messages of the literacy education was incorporated to provide guidance on simple literacy and numeracy activities that caregivers can conduct with their children at home, along with tips on health and disease prevention, psychosocial support, and caregiver wellbeing. Functional literacy provided increases business reading ability for learners. Functional literacy provided increases business communication ability for learners. Functional literacy provided increases business writing ability for learners. The training focused on how parents/caregivers can improve their relationship with their children in a continual manner using positive behavior that includes caring, teaching, leading and providing for the needs of a child in a consistent manner.

Challenges associated with literacy education Programme provided by AENN in 2024 Yobe state.

According to the participants highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme were lack of space in classrooms to accommodate new learners. The head teachers said their schools were already overcrowded and that teachers were overwhelmed with the number of learners in their classrooms. To address this challenge, the participants agreed that schools that are yet to start operating double shift systems should do so in order to admit more learners. One of the major challenges was the escalation of the insecurity situation in Northeast Nigeria and effectiveness of Basic Literacy and Post-Literacy Materials Packages. The materials were found to be user-friendly and effective in transmitting the intended contents. However, there is need for language simplification and further contextualization of SEL activities in the Hausa basic Literacy, Numeracy facilitator guide.

Material and Research Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study population was (13123) Children and Youth who registered with AENN literacy education programme. The sample size of 390 was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan Table. Stratified Random sample was used for selection samples from three programme education zones. The closed questionnaire with liker-type scale was used for data collection. The validation of the instrument was done through content and face validity by three experts from research unit in the department of education, Yobe state University. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of test and retest method, the first week and after two weeks later. The analysis was done using PPMC and result showed a measure of stability at 0.870. The descriptive statistic of simple percentage was used to analyze data collected. The findings of the present study have revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill activities on social and livelihood among children and youth under AENN programme in Yobe state. It is recommended Based on findings the AENN literacy education programme should continue to satisfy educational need of teaming population in the State.

Table 3: Impacts of functional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Functional literacy provided increases business reading ability for learners.	35	83	4	-	130	122	93.85%
2. Functional literacy provided increases business communication ability for learners.	31	87	7	3	130	128	98.5%
3. Functional literacy provided increases business writing ability for learners.	10	24	61	20	130	115	88.5%
Total	76	194	72	23	390	365	280.85%

Source: Field survey, 2024

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Impacts of Functional Literacy Skills

Increases business reading ability for learners as responded 35 (SA) 85 (A) 4 (D) - (SD) with 122 responses at (93.85%) increases business communication ability for learners as responded 31 (SA) 87 (A) 7 (D) 3 (SD) with 128 responses at (98.5%) increases business writing ability for learners as responded 10 (SA) 24 (A) 61 (D) 20 (SD) with 115 responses at (88.5%)

Table 4: Impacts of critical literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education.	30	71	15	9	130	125	96.15%
2. Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education.	26	79	11	6	130	122	93.85%
3. Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of Adult literacy learning.	21	69	19	2	130	111	85.38%
	77	246	45	17	390	358	275.38%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Impacts of critical literacy skills

Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education as responded 30 (SA) 71 (A) 15 (D) 9 (SD) with 125 responses at 96.15% Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education as responded 26 (SA) 79 (A) 11 (D) 6 (SD) with 122 responses at 93.85% Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of Adult literacy learning as responded 21 (SA) 69 (A) 19 (D) 2 (SD) with 111 responses at 85.38%

Table 5: Impacts of traditional literacy skills on addressing educational needs among children and youth provided by AENN programme in Yobe state

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage.	29	77	11	4	130	121	93.07%
2. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage.	12	57	49	6	130	124	95.4%
3. Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic.	14	61	25	23	130	123	94.6%
	55	195	85	33	390	368	283.7

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Impacts of traditional literacy skills

Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage as responded 29 (SA) 77 (A) 11 (D) 4 (SD) with 121 responses at 93.07% Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage as responded 12 (SA) 57 (A) 49 (D) 6 (SD) with 124 responses at 95.4% Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic as responded 14 (SA) 61 (A) 25 (D) 23 (SD) with 123 responses at 94.6%

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Table 6: Challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education under AENN programme in Yobe state

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	No. sampled	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
1. Language used for learning slow learners understanding.	12	46	40	15	130	113	86.92%
2. Method used for learning slow learners understanding.	10	29	56	20	130	115	88.46%
3. Location of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding.	8	17	67	16	130	108	83.07%
	30	92	163	51	390	336	258.45%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Challenges faced in the implementation of literacy education of AENN programme

Language used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 12 (SA) 46 (A) 40 (D) 15 (SD) with 113 responses at 86.92% Method used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 10 (SA) 29 (A) 56 (D) 20 (SD) with 115 responses at 88.46% Location of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding as responded 8 (SA) 17 (A) 67 (D) 16 (SD) with 108 responses at 83.07%

Discussion of Findings

The impact of literacy education programme to promotion of social and livelihood of people in the World and Nigeria in particular, is the critical area which is much concerned about by many researchers. Despite the challenges faced in the implementation of (AENN 2020 Project) of literacy education programme however there was significant impact in the social and livelihood of people in the Yobe state. The study shows that Functional literacy provided Increases business reading ability for learners 122 (93.85%) also increases business communication ability for learners 128 at (98.5%) similarly, increases business writing ability for learners 115 at (88.5%). This is in agreement with UNESCO (2000) as cited in Cocchiarella (2018) that Functional literacy refers to the practical skill set needed to read, write, and do math for real-life purposes, so people can function effectively in their community and enable students to succeed at school and in society. The study shows that Critical literacy provided enable learners to think over the need of girl child education with 125 at 96.15% also Critical literacy provided enable learners to distinguish the benefit of health education with 122 at 93.85% similarly, Critical literacy provided enable learners to estimate benefit of adult literacy learning with 111 at 85.38%. This is in agreement with Batchelor (2019) that critical literacy not only encourages multiple perspectives, it also helps us step back and get a clearer look at a bigger cultural picture exposes students to a variety of texts by helping them to re-see the world in numerous ways.

The study shows that Traditional literacy provided enable learners to read Hausa and English passage with 121 at 93.07% also Traditional literacy provided enable learners to write Hausa and English passage with 124 at 95.4 % similarly, Traditional literacy provided enable learners to use arithmetic with 123 at 94.6% It is in line with Deursen and van Dijk (2014) stated that the simplest form of literacy involves the ability to use language in its written form. A literate person is able to read, write and understand his or her native language and express a simple thought in writing. The study shows that Language used for learning slow learners understanding with 113 at 86.92% also Method used for learning slow learners understanding with 115 at 88.46% similarly, Location and space of learning centers and hours used for learning slow learners understanding with 108 at 83.07% . It is in line with report of (AENN 2020 Project) According to the participants highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme were lack of space in classrooms to accommodate new learners.

Conclusion

Empirical evidence from the (AENN 2020 Project) Addressing Education in Northeast Nigeria through literacy education programme has affirmed the endeavor of the (AENN 2020 Project) to meet up the literacy needs of many out of school children and dropout adolescents in Yobe state. This is to help them become critically and functionally literate by preparing them for skills abilities and competencies around social and economic or vocational life of the community or to live and work in society, to manage daily living, family, poverty, education, equity, and equality and employment tasks that require

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reading skills beyond a basic level. The ability to read texts in an active, reflective manner in order to better understand power, inequality, and injustice in human relationships.

Based on the data obtained from the (AENN 2020 Project) highlighted some of the challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme in Yobe state. These include the escalation of the insecurity situation, and effectiveness of Basic Literacy and Post-Literacy Materials Packages. The materials were found to be user-friendly and effective in transmitting the intended contents. However, some of the LFs have no prior reading experience in Kanuri and often find it difficult to read. Also, from a technical perspective, there seemed to be inconsistencies in the translations in terms of language usage and orthography. Despite, the challenges faced in the implementation of the literacy education programme of AENN 2020. The finding of the present study has revealed overall significant impact of functional, critical and traditional literacy skill on social and livelihood of service beneficiaries of the programme in Yobe state.

Recommendation

In response to the above outlined associated challenges affecting the implementation of literacy education programme in Yobe state, it is recommended that the AENN Project should take these steps; to review the SEL books, review of the Kanuri orthographic system relative to AENN Kanuri materials with the view of standardization of orthography and consistent use of common terms in the books through Kanuri Linguists from the University and college of Education, AENN must trains more Master Trainers Learning Facilitators on non-formal Basic Literacy and Post Literacy curriculum. However, there is need for language simplification and further contextualization of SEL activities in the Hausa basic Literacy, Numeracy facilitator guide. In Kanuri Basic Literacy, Numeracy and SEL, it has been observed that generally both the LFs and learners were enthusiastic to use the materials. In view of the overall significant impact of literacy education programme of the AENN 2020 on social and livelihood improvement. It is recommended the extension of programme to cover the wider communities in the Yobe state.

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Impact of Mind and Concept Mappings Strategies on Map Reading Skills Among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the Impact of Mind and Concept Mappings Strategies on Map Reading Skills Among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. Two research objectives, research questions and corresponding null hypotheses. The research design adopted for the study was pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consisted of 6623 (Male, 3765 and Female, 2858) Senior Secondary School class two SSII geography students from twenty-one schools in during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. Three co-educational public senior secondary schools were selected using Clustered sampling technique. A total number of 183 (Male, 78 and Female, 105) Senior Secondary School class two students formed the sample of the study. Using an intact class. Geography Skills Acquisition Scale (GSAS) were developed and used in data collection. The GSAS was validated by experts and reliability coefficient of 0.601 was obtained. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics, while the null hypothesis were tested using ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean scores of skills acquisitions of geography students taught map reading concept using Mind Mapping, Concept Mapping and those exposed to lecture method. It was concluded that the use Mind Mapping, Concept Mapping strategies is effective in enhancing students' skills acquisition in geography. Based on the research findings it was recommended, State Ministry of education should provide adequate seminars, workshops and training, re-training of teachers to adopt mind and concept mappings teaching strategies for effective teaching and learning of geography in secondary schools.

Keywords: Map Reading Skills, Mind Mapping Strategies, Concept Mapping Strategies and Students

Introduction

Geography as a school subject is one of the most important subjects in secondary school education. Geography is relevant for both the students who are likely to continue to tertiary level and those who will not proceed. It equips students with a body of knowledge to make them functional and socially relevant in the fast-changing world. Geography is a distinct and dynamic science and or social science discipline that deals with the study of man and his physical environment (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023). According to Ibrahim and Salisu (2023) It is the field that concerned with sharing the scientific content, process skills and developing efficient teaching methods affect achievement in science education. Teaching science may require special attention and efficacy of teachers in order to better attract students and teach the subjects through concrete and clear methods, through the use of individual problem-solving skills. The strategies adopted for teaching Geography include; field trip, discovery method, models, games and simulations, observation and practical work. Map reading is the process of looking at the map to determine what is depicted and how the cartographer depicted it. This involves identifying the features or phenomena depicted, the symbols and labels used, and information about the map that may not be evident on the map (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023).

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Mind mapping is defined as an interesting note-taking style that describes what you think (Ibrahim, 2023). Broadly speaking, mind mapping actively involves both of our brains and can help us to think creatively. In the other hand, concept mapping used as a learning and teaching technique visually illustrates the relationship between concepts and ideas, often represented in circles or boxes, concept are linked by words and phrases that explain the connection better the ideas, helping students organize and structure the thoughts to further understand information and discover new relationship (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023).

One of the problems of teaching Geography identified by Liman, Babajo and Hari (2022) is the persistent failure in senior secondary school's certificate examination (SSCE) among students. Ibrahim (2020) reported that factors identified as a bane of poor student's performance in geography is the use of faulty and inappropriate teaching method like lecture method. According to Salisu (2019) stated that due to its nature, common use of teacher-centered method to teaching leads to poor understanding, assimilation and application of learning, while the use of student-centered methods enhances students' achievement, thus, the need to find out whether Mind and concept mapping are learner-centered teaching/learning method, would enhance student's performance in geography. However, the use of different approaches and techniques in which the students' ability to utilizes their skills should be encouraged. Therefore, teachers must act as the catalysts of the students in teaching geographical concepts, such as map reading. This enables students to assume full responsibility about the organization of their work. Skills include: observation, interpretation of data, measurements, and classification of data (Ibrahim 2023). Skilled enough to use map, students show a greater motivation to learn within this environment and a greater predisposition to use maps. Teachers who adopt strategies of enhancing students' skills might be regarded as predictors of development, proper utilization of skills could help the students to provide feedback and also improves their performance throughout the teaching process (Ibrahim 2023).

The purpose of secondary science education is to equip young learners with scientific process skills, to enable them to define existing problems, observe events in their society, analyze and hypothesize possible solutions, conclude and generalize and apply gathered information for the betterment and advancement of his community (Ibrahim 2023). According to Mbewe, Chabalengula, and Mumba (2010) and Huppert, Lomask, and Lazarowitz (2002) cited in Derilo (2019) reiterated that the Science Process Skill acquisition is the main objective of science education because of the fact that science process skills is needed by every individual in whole citizenry, and not just the scientific community. Huppert and colleagues further pointed out that since Skills acquisition are applicable to all elements of the community, everyone should be knowledgeable on how it could be applied in everyday living. To overcome the problem, scholars advocate the use of innovative strategies like Mind-mapping. Ayca Kartal, Kaya Tuncer, Cennet and Ozlem Ozcakir (2015) has taking the views of teacher candidates on the implementation of the mind-mapping technique on Geography courses and at under-graduate level, is thought to be an important step to contribute to increase the applicability of the technique. Against this background the study is set to examine the Impact of Mind and Concept Mapping Techniques on Map Reading Skills Among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to:

investigate the effects of Mind and Concept Mappings on Map Reading skills among senior secondary school Students in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research question were formulated to guide the study:

What is the difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping strategies and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State?

Hypotheses

The following Null Hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State.

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Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test post-test control group design;

Table 1: Design

Group	Description
EG ₁	Experimental Group 1
EG ₂	Experimental Group 2
X ₁	Treatment (Teaching using Mind Mapping)
X ₂	Treatment (Teaching using Concept mapping)
X ₀	No Treatment (Teaching with lecture method)
O ₁	Pre-test
O ₂	Post-test

Pre-test (O₁) were administered to both experimental and control group to ensure careful selection of samples that are not significantly different in terms of skills acquisition and academic performance before treatment, in other word to establish equivalence of the groups before treatment. Subject were assigned to experimental and control prior to the administration of treatment. The three groups were taught Map Reading concept for a period of six weeks. Post-test (O₂) were then be administered after treatment to determine impact of instructional methods on students' skills acquisition, interest and academic performance.

The population of the study consist of all Government Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Geography students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State, Nigeria. The schools consisted of all of public schools that offer Geography within the metropolis. There are 25 public schools out of which 21 schools are offering geography with population of 6,623. The number of male students was 3,765 and female students 2,858 making a total population of 6,623.

The sample of the study covered a total number of 183 SS II geography students from three coeducational schools in the study area. The choice of 183 students as a sample is in line with the recommendation of Tucker (1973), Kerlinger (1989), Sambo (2008), Salisu (2022) and central limit theorem that recommend for a number of 30 participants as viable enough to form a study sample in experimental research. In order to ensure selection of subject with comparative abilities, the researcher analyzed the result of pre-test administered to 12 out of 21 secondary schools, using Analysis of variance. The outcome revealed significant difference, the researcher used Schiffer's Post-hoc test to determine the direction of disparity. As a result, six schools revealed no significance difference. In order to select the schools, Cluster sampling was used from which three schools were randomly selected from the number of schools in the area of this study through balloting. The researcher wrote the names of all the 21 public secondary schools on pieces of papers and randomly selected three schools.

Table 2. Sample Distribution of the Students

S/N	School	Status	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	Experimental (E1)	24	39	63
2	School B	Experimental (E2)	27	26	53
3	School C	Control	27	40	67
Total			78	105	183

In this study two research instruments namely Geography Skills Acquisition scale (GSAS) were used for data collection. It was an instrument adapted from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (2007), and were used in determining the skills acquisition of Geography students in Map Reading concepts. The original instrument contained more than five hundred items from different field of sciences such as Geography, Chemistry, Physics, Agricultural science, Biology and Mathematics using different scale such as Likert five points scale. The scale contained twenty (20) items in which the first five 5 items measure observation skills, the second 5 items measure classification skills, the third 5 items measure the measurement skills and the last 5 items measure inferring skills. The scale was selected because it has been used widely in the literature in order to assess skills acquisition characteristics.

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping strategies and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State?

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations of skills acquisition scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Grouping	N	Mean	SD	SE	M Diff
Mind Mapping	63	58.90	8.09	1.02	
Concept mapping	53	60.24	8.10	1.11	1.34
Lecture Method	67	38.41	11.10	1.35	21.83
Total	183	51.79	13.78	1.01	

Table 3 presents Mean and Standard Deviations of skills acquisition scores of Experimental and Control Groups. From the results, geography students taught map reading using mind mapping scored a mean of 58.90 and Standard Deviation of 8.09; students taught using concept mapping scored a mean of 60.24 and Standard Deviation of 8.10, while students taught using lecture method scored a mean of 38.41 and Standard Deviations of 11.10. From the result it is observed that students taught using concept mapping acquired skills higher than those taught using mind mapping followed by those taught using lecture method.

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method.

Table 4. ANOVA of skills acquisition of Experimental and control Groups

Source of Varia.	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value	Remark
Between Groups	18958.571	2	9479.285	109.254	0.01	
Within Groups	15617.538	180	86.764			*Sig
Total	34576.109	182				

Table 4 presents ANOVA of significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method. From the result, sum of squares between groups is 18958.571, sum of squares within groups is 15617.538. F-Value recorded is 109.254 and p-value obtained is 0.01. The P-Value is less than alpha value of 0.05, hence there is significant difference. Consequently, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method is rejected. To determine the direction of disparity, the researcher run post-Hoc test using sheffer and the result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Sheffer post-hoc test of Direction of Differences in skills acquisition scores of Experimental and control groups

(I) Grouping	(J) Grouping	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Remark
Mind Mapping	Concept mapping	-1.34052	1.73616	.743	No Sig.
	Lecture Method	20.48685*	1.63468	.01	*sig.
Concept mapping	Mind Mapping	1.34052	1.73616	.743	No Sig.
	Lecture Method	21.82737*	1.71232	.000	*sig.
Lecture Method	Mind Mapping	-20.48685*	1.63468	.000	*sig.
	Concept mapping	-21.82737*	1.71232	.000	*sig.

Table 5 presents Sheffer Post-Hoc test of Direction of Differences in skills acquisition scores of Experimental and control groups. From the results, p-value of 0.74 was recorded between mind mapping and concept mapping. This means that there is

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no significant difference between the two methods. However, p-value of 0.01 was recorded between mind mapping and lecture method. This means that there is significant difference in favour of mind mapping. From the same results, p-value of 0.74 was recorded between concept mapping and mind mapping. This means that there is no significant difference between the two methods. However, p-value of 0.01 was recorded between concept mapping and lecture method. This means that there is significant difference in favour of concept mapping. Similarly, the results revealed significant difference in favour of mind mapping and concept mapping as p-value of 0.01 was recorded in all the cases.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the Impact of Mind and Concept Mapping Techniques on Skills Acquisition Among Senior Secondary Geography Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. Finding number, one shows that there was significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading concept using mind mapping and concept mapping and those exposed to lecture method. This implies that subjects in the experimental group who were exposed to mind mapping and concept mapping developed more skills in map reading concept better than the subjects in the control group who were exposed to lecture method and can be used to improve the skills acquisition of students in map reading techniques of secondary schools' geography curriculum. This finding agrees with several other studies, such as that of Teresa and Carter (2018); Samuel, Libata and Sabitu (2018); Gunawan, Harjono, Hermansyah, and Herayanti (2019); Acarli and Dervisoglu (2021) who conclude that there was a statistically significant difference in the skills acquisition of students when exposed to innovative teaching strategies such as Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping compared to lecture method.

In Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping students form themselves as cooperative groups in which they perceive that they can reach their learning goals if and only other group members also reach their goal. So, it helps the students develop note by themselves and burst critical thinking to students as well as expanding the horizon of the brain hemisphere which are logical thinking and reasoning. The use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping removes the barriers associated with teacher centered instructional methods and offers a very unique learning situation in which learners are given opportunities to actively seek for information, analyzed it and construct knowledge by themselves.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be concluded that the use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping techniques is effective in enhancing students' skills acquisition and academic performance in geography, in other words employment of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping strategies have the potential of enhancing academic performance in geography.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping improved the map reading skills acquisition ability of students in the present study. As such therefore, teachers and students of geography should be encouraged to use the two strategies as alternative or innovative teaching strategy in order to improve teaching and learning of geography.
2. The government and STAN, ANG, NERDC should inculcate the habit of adopting new teaching strategies that will enable both teachers and students interact and actively involved in the lesson, however, publishers should learn the skills of adopting new strategies such as Mind Mapping into their textbooks. This will enable the students and the reader to develop interest and skills acquisition ability also will improve.
3. State Ministry of education among others at all levels should provide adequate seminars, workshops and training of teachers to adopt the new teaching strategies for effective classroom delivery.

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Impact of POGIL Instructional Strategy on Academic Confidence and Performance in Genetics Concept among Secondary School Students in Tarauni, Kano State

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non randomized control group design. The population of the study consists of 2493 (1,200 Male and 1,293 Female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students in Tarauni, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The Sample size of the study consists of 200 (100 male and 100 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students. This was arrived at using an intact class from four government secondary schools randomly selected in Tarauni, Kano State. Genetics Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were used to elicit information on performance and academic confidence, respectively. The reliability of the instruments was 0.79 and 0.97. The subjects in the experimental group were taught genetics concepts using POGIL instructional strategy, while the subjects in the control group were taught same concepts using Lecture Method. Two research questions were raised and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviations while null hypotheses were tested using t-test and Mann Whitney at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference between the performance mean scores of students taught genetics concept using POGIL instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method in favor of experimental group. Therefore, students taught genetic concept using POGIL instructional strategy exhibited high academic confidence and performance when compared with their counterparts taught same concepts using lecture method. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the use of POGIL instructional strategy should be emphasized and use in secondary schools across the state.

Keyword: POGIL instructional strategy, Academic confidence and Performance

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Introduction

Biology is the scientific study of living organisms and their interaction with each other and their environment. This field encompassed a wide range of topics, including genetics, evolution, ecology, physiology among others. The objectives of teaching Biology as a science subject are based on practical and experiment as contained in the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013) also included among others are to equip learners with meaningful and relevant knowledge of Biology, adequate laboratory, instructional material and field skills. It is expected that, through utilization of Biology laboratory equipment and other instructional materials that the biology students' academic performance could be and the above objectives and goals can be achieved (Haruna, 2019). Academic performance represents the outcome that indicates the extent to which a student has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in schools. In teaching and learning situations, academic performance is synonymous with academic achievement. They could be seen as the outcome of students' effort in examinations. Okoye, (2018) contended that a student's academic performance is dependent on several factors such as, learning environment, instructional methods and teaching strategy, teachers' attitude and enthusiasm, as well as students' attitude and background. When suitable teaching method is employed during instructional delivery particularly subsumption could improve performance.

Low performance in Biology among Nigerian secondary school students has been the major concern of parents, teachers and the public. This low performance in SSCE Biology examination at credit level may be due to poor methods of teaching and lack of instructional materials among others. Scholars such as Rilwani, Akahomen, and Gbakeji, (2014) have identified several factors influencing students' academic performance in Biology as a course of study including class size, laboratories, instructional strategies, textbooks, guidance and counseling services, academic and professional qualification of teachers, teachers' attributes, students' attributes, peer groups, parental and home background, and school environment among others. Warfa (2016) have shown that the teaching of science (including Biology) in Nigerian secondary schools have fallen short of the standard expected of it as a result of using inappropriate method of instruction. This assertion was supported in the work of science educators like Ali, Toriman and Gasim (2014) who have found that the persistent low academic performance in science education were attributed to teachers' instructional strategies such as lecture method in which the learner remained passive while the teacher is always active. They emphasized that lecture method does not promote meaningful learning of science because differences in students' ability are not considered and it cannot satisfy the individual learning mode. Thus, instructional strategies used by teachers in the teaching and learning process have significant influence on learners' academic performance. This is why Rabi, Toriman and Gasim, (2014) says that for decades, individual and other professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) have worked tirelessly to deal decisively with students' poor academic performance in science by developing/innovative teaching strategies that would improve learning of science. Therefore, for effective learning to take place, appropriate method of instruction such as POGIL can be utilized.

Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is a research-based, student-centered philosophy and science pedagogy in which students work in small groups to engage in guided inquiry using carefully designed materials that direct and guide students to build and rebuild their knowledge (Kim 2016; Roller & Zori 2017). In POGIL activities, students construct their understanding of the content and key process skills such as problem solving, critical thinking skills, application of information, and communication in science, deductive reasoning, self-assessment, teamwork, and time management (Conway, 2014).

A review of the literature shows that there are various studies relating to POGIL instructional strategy. The study by Roller (2015), however, analyzed the effects of POGIL on students' understanding of biological classification. The research found that POGIL was influential in uncovering students' alternative conceptions and in changing them. A review of other studies in the literature concerning POGIL, shows that students' achievement levels have generally risen, and more sustained and in-depth learning has occurred through POGIL (Barthlow, Watson 2014; Vanags, Pammer, & Brinker, 2014. It was also found that students have positive opinions regarding POGIL learning environments (Conway, 2014 and Soltis *et al.*, 2015). BeÂneÂteau *et al.* (2016) compared three different teaching methods in science education - problem-based learning (PBL), POGIL and peer-led team learning. The researchers showed that the POGIL method contributed more to the development of students' learning capabilities. Moog (2014), on the other hand, investigated the effects of POGIL method on changing alternative conceptions about the particulate nature of matter. Consequently, it was found that students taught through POGIL had fewer alternative conceptions than those taught using traditional teaching methods.

Various studies have been documented for the effectiveness of POGIL instructional strategy in enhancing students' academic confidence and performance. For example, Kwarteng (2014) and Canelas, Hill and Novicki A. (2017) reported that POGIL improved academic confidence and performance in the course, encouraged active engagement with the material in the

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class, provided immediate feedback to the instructor concerning student deficits and misunderstandings, and created a positive classroom environment where students enjoyed learning very difficult material. Moog (2014) reported positive gains in students' achievement as their test grades and overall test grades were positively affected by POGIL. Walker and Warfa (2017) have found statistically significant difference in students' academic confidence and performance between two groups, one of which experienced a traditional instructional approach while the other experienced POGIL activities. Therefore, this study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State.

Academic confidence according to Honicke & Broadbent (2016) refers to a student's belief in their capabilities to succeed academically. It involves having faith in one's own skills, knowledge, and capacity to learn, which leads to a positive attitude towards academic challenges and tasks. Samikwo (2014) maintained that confidence plays a significant role in students' learning, thus, students with higher level of academic confidence are proved to be high achievers than those with low academic confidence. Allchin (2015) found that the student who perceives himself confident has a high level of academic achievement and student who perceives himself as worthless is less confident and may not come up to the optimum level of attainment. Degale and Boisselle (2015) asserted that academic confidence is believed to affect performance through the influence on task perception. For example, research studies by Sedumedi (2014) and Stevens (2015) suggest that high academic confidence creates a feeling of calmness when approaching a difficult task and conversely, low academic confidence may result in an individual perceiving a task as more difficult than it really is, which leads to stress and a narrowness of ideas when tackling the solution of the problem. Ochoa and Sander (2014) opined that students with low academic confidence enter colleges with lower academic skills and are found to be less engaged and face more transition difficulties than those who enter college with confidence. Sanders, Putwain and Fuente (2015) believe that student academic confidence can change if the student enters into the academic environment where the form and processes of education itself are demystified. This involves giving learning opportunities to refine the students' academic skills. An understanding of students' confidence could be beneficial in helping teachers create more effective learning environments. It helps teachers to understand their students, which enhances the teaching process even if just through a psychometric profile. De Gale and Boisselle (2015) ascertained that academic confidence can develop from the mastery of skills, various experiences and social and emotional support. Students having confidence in academic setting have been found to perform better than students with low confidence in academic setting. Confidence level also affected retention of learned concept. In this study therefore, students' academic confidence was investigated. Therefore, this study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State.

In spite of the importance of Biology among Nigerian students, performance at SSCE level remained poor at credit level. This persistent failure in SSCE Biology examination at credit level may be due to poor methods of teaching and lack of instructional materials among others. Some research studies by Albaladejo and Lucas, (2014) shown that students do not fully understand chromosomes, genes, or alleles. Slack and Stewart, (2014) opined that many biology students cannot adequately interpret some concepts such as homozygous or heterozygous. Kindfield, (2016) says that many biology students have alternative views of some processes such as mitosis and meiosis and also they do not understand the meanings of probability in relation to genotype and phenotype frequencies in offspring. Rahamneh, (2017) opined that medium of instruction in teaching biology at post primary/higher education institutions is another factor contributing to poor academic performance in sciences. Low academic confidence has been found to bring about poor performance and it's affected by instructional method which creates stress and apprehension in students. This also affects retention of learned concepts and also affects performance. The use of POGIL instruction strategy has been found to have significant impact on improving student's academic confidence and performance.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the impact of POGIL instruction strategy on academic performance of students taught genetic concept.
2. determine the impact of POGIL instruction strategy on academic confidence of students taught genetic concept.

Research Questions

This study provided the following research questions:

1. What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

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2. What is the difference between mean academic confidence scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean academic confidence of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non randomized control group design. The population of the study consists of 2493 (1,200 Male and 1,293 Female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students in Tarauni, during the 2022/2023 academic session. Simple random sampling, involving balloting method was used to select four schools out of the twenty-one (21) in the population. This was done by written the name of all the schools that make up the population on a piece of paper and a child was asked to pick four (4) papers randomly. Four schools selected were assigned into control and experimental groups respectively. From the four (4) schools, one intact class of SSII was selected using balloting method of simple random sampling because they were found to be equivalent. This gave a total number of four (4) intact classes for the study, which were randomly assigned into control and experiment groups. Thus, the total sample for the study stood at 200.

Two instruments, Genetics Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were used for the study. GCPT was adapted from past questions papers of WAEC and NECO and Biology textbooks, which consisted of thirty-five (35) items with multiple choice of letters A-D. GCPT was used for pretest and posttest in order to measure the level of performance among SSII Biology students while the Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) was adapted from Sander and Sanders, (2005) and used to measure student's academic confidence. The SACI has 12 items of Likert 5-scale involving Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U) Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Each of the options carried weight in order of priority from 5 – 1 in positive confidence responses and from 1- 5 in negative confidence responses. Students were asked to freely indicate their confidence in genetic concept of biology by ticking one of the responses that suits their interest.

The instruments Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were validated by three experts. The instruments were revised and corrected in the light of responses of expert opinions, pilot testing, difficulty level and discriminating Index. The final version of tests consisted of thirty-five (35) questions. Then item difficulty level and Discrimination index was calculated for each item as a response of 100 students from different schools in the study area. The reliability of a research instrument concerns the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated trials. To determine the reliability coefficient of Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) a test-retest method was employed to a trial-testing group who were found to be equivalent in all aspects to the students in the study. After a two weeks interval the second test was administered to the same group of students in line with Tuckman's (1975) recommendation on the use of two-week interval for test-retest method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used for the analysis. From the result obtained, the reliability of the instruments was found to be 0.75 and 0.79 for both instruments. This signifies that there is strong positive relationship between the first and second administration of GCPT and SACI.

For effective data collection, the four groups (one experimental and one control group) were taught separately for the period of six weeks. Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) was administered to both groups at the beginning which serve as a pretest. The essence of pretest is to ensure that the selected schools were not significantly different in terms of abilities before actual treatment. The selected sampled schools were taught genetic concept for the period of six weeks. The posttest was administered to the four groups in order to determine the effect of the treatment. After two-week, Post posttest was administered to all groups in order to determine their retention level of the genetic concept. Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) was administered to both experimental and control groups, before and after the treatment in order to determine their academic confidence level. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were analyzed and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance using t-test and Mann Whitney.

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method? The detail of the results is presented in Table 1

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics on difference between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics Concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture Method

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std.Err	M D
Academic performance	Exp.	100	29.49	5.265	.526	16.77
	Control	100	12.72	3.452	.345	

Table 1 showed that difference existed between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics Concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method. The computed performance mean scores for the experimental and control groups are 29.49 and 12.72 respectively, and their mean difference was 16.71. This implies that students in the experimental group had higher mean scores compared to those in the control group.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 2: Independent t-test statistics on difference between performance mean scores of students taught Genetics concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	S.Dev	Std.Err	M D	Df	t-cal	P
Academic performance	Exp.	100	29.49	5.27	.526	16.77	198	26.63	0.00
	Control	100	12.72	3.45	345				

Calculated $p < 0.05$ computed $t > 1.96$ at $df 198$

Table 2 showed that significant differences existed between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method. Reasons being that the calculated p level of 0.00 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the computed t value of 26.63 is higher than the 1.96 t-critical values at df 198. Their computed performance mean scores are 29.49 and 12.72 of students taught Genetics Concept using Ausubel's Subsumption Instructional Strategy and those taught using the Lecture method in favour of the experimental groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis one rejected.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference between mean academic confidence scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method? The detail of the results is presented in Table 1.3

Table 3 Mean Ranking statistic of Academic confidence of the Experimental Group (EG) and Control Group (CG)

Academic confidence		N	Mean Rank	Sum of rank	Mean gain
Experimental group	(Pretest)	100	43.62	6151.00	
	(Posttest)		54.43	6243.00	10.81

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Control group	(Pretest)	100	40.88	5151.00	
	(Posttest)		33.42	4051.00	7.46
Total		200			

Table 3 shows the academic confidence mean rank of experimental group exposed to POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method. The experimental group has mean rank of 43.62 before the treatment and 54.43 after the treatment with mean gain of 10.81, while the control group (CG) has mean rank of 40.88 before the treatment and 33.42 with mean loss of 7.46. This indicates that the academic confidence of the experimental groups taught genetics concept using POGIL instruction strategy has improved after the treatment while those in the control group exposed to lecture method showed reduction in their academic confidence after the treatment.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between mean academic confidence of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method. The detail of the results is presented in Table 1.4

Table 4 Non Parametric test of Mann Whitney on academic confidence of Experimental Groups (EG) and Control Group (CG)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney	Z	P
Academic confidence	Experimental group	100	45.44	14543.50	300.50	11.400	0.002
	Control group	100	40.03	5157.50			
	Total	200					

Table 4 shows the results of Non Parametric test of Mann Whitney on academic confidence of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using lecture method. The mean rank of experimental group academic confidence is 45.44 while the control group has the mean rank of 40.03 respectively. The calculated p value of 0.002 of the experimental groups is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows clearly that students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy have higher academic confidence than students taught the same concept using lecture method. Therefore, null hypothesis 2 is hereby rejected. The result of finding is in favour of the experimental group because they have higher academic confidence.

Discussion of Findings

Table 3 shows that there was a significant different between performance mean score of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instructional strategy and those taught the same concept using lecture method. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Soltis, Verlinden, Kruger, Carroll and Trumbo (2015) who reported positive gains in students' performance using this method. Also Vishnumolakala, Southam, Treagust, Mocerino and Qureshi (2017) reported that students' test grades and overall test grades were positively affected by POGIL and they also stressed that POGIL improved performance in the course, encouraged active engagement with the material in the class, provided immediate feedback to the instructor concerning student deficits and misunderstandings, and created a positive classroom environment where students enjoyed learning very difficult material. The finding of this study contradict the finding of Warfa, (2016) who showed no significant differences between the performance of students who were in a POGIL-based section of a course compared with those who were in a traditionally taught section.

The result of Table 4 revealed that there was a significant difference between the academic confidence of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using lecture method in favour of the experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Salih and Ahmed (2015) who investigated the impact of academic confidence on EFL Sudanese tertiary level students Department of English language at El-Imam El-Mahdi University and White Nile College for Science and Technology in the White Nile State. The findings of their study revealed a positive, significant correlation between academic confidence, and academic performance. The finding of this study contradict the finding of Degale and Boisselle (2015) who found no statistically significant difference in students' confidence between two

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groups, one of which experienced a traditional instructional approach while the other used POGIL activities. Also, Sadiq and Mehwish (2014) studied “University Students’ academic confidence between Social Sciences and Natural Science students Pakistan. Their finding indicated that control group held significantly higher levels of academic confidence than experimental group.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that POGIL instructional strategy can improve academic performance of students taught genetics concept if properly implemented. This is evident in the finding of hypothesis one that students taught genetics concepts in the experimental group has significantly higher performance mean scores than their counterparts taught same concept using the Lecture Method. Also, POGIL instructional strategy can improve academic confidence of students in the experimental groups if properly implemented. This is evident in the finding of hypothesis two that students in the experimental group taught genetics concepts using the POGIL instruction strategy have significantly higher academic confidence mean rank scores when compared with students in the control group. This infers that POGIL instruction strategy can improve academic confidence.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the followings recommendations a made:

1. The use of POGIL instruction strategy should be emphasized and rigorously implemented in secondary schools across the state because students taught using tis instructional strategy exhibited remarkable academic confidence and performance when compared with their counterparts taught using the lecture method
2. Curriculum planners should examine the effectiveness of POGIL instruction strategy and consider it suitability for teaching science concepts since it has the potential of bringing about meaningful learning and improving academic confidence and performance.
3. Organizations such as the STAN, the NERDC should organize seminars, workshop and conferences on the use of POGIL instruction strategy for science teachers at the secondary school level for better implementation and utilization of the method.
4. The use of POGIL instruction strategy should be incorporated into the Biology teacher training curricula at NCE and BSc. Ed Bio program in order to produce teachers who are able to use POGIL instruction strategy in the teaching and learning process.

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Impact of Science Process - Based Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of the science process-based approach on performance in biology among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Two Research Questions and two Null Hypotheses guided the study and were tested at a $P \leq 0.05$ significance level. The pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. The study population consists of 3,929 (Male, 1,623 and Female, 2,306) senior secondary school class two (SS II) government secondary school biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 133 (Male, 63 and Female, 70) were selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. The experimental group was taught the concepts of living in biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.), while the control group was taught using the lecture method. A validated instrument called the Biology Performance Test (B.P.T.) was used for data collection. The reliability of B.P.T. was assessed utilizing a test-retest reliability method. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics was used for analysis, and the result produced a reliability coefficient of 0.86. Moreover, B.P.T. was validated by three (3) Senior Lecturers. Data collected were analyzed using mean rank and standard deviation for the research questions, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were used to analyze the Null hypotheses; the study revealed that Students taught using S.P.B.A. performed significantly better in their academic performance in favour of the high experimental group than those taught using lecture method; Male and Female Students taught using S.P.B.A. did not perform significantly different in their academic performance in all the varied ability groups from those taught using lecture method. In light of these findings, S.P.B.A. instructional strategies enhanced the academic performance in the concept taught in Biology. This study, amongst others, concludes that S.P.B.A. training should be organized for biology teachers through workshops to equip them with learning and integrate it into lessons in some biology concepts to enhance students' academic performance and varied abilities.

Keywords: Process-Based Approach, Performance, Biology, Varied Ability.

Introduction

The teaching and learning science subjects present challenges across educational systems globally, including Nigeria. Various factors contribute to these challenges, such as poor quality of students admitted, population explosion, inadequate teaching and learning facilities, and ineffective teaching strategies (Ahmed, 2014; Ahmed, 2014). Notably, teaching strategies, particularly in science education, have been a focus of concern among educators. Research indicates that hands-on science instruction and cooperative learning approaches significantly enhance students' science performance and attitudes towards the subject (Felita, 2018). Academic performance is often measured by the extent of knowledge acquisition and mastery of skills resulting from instruction or training (Usman, 2010). Understanding science concepts goes beyond mere recall; it involves actively manipulating and applying knowledge (Cavallo & Lauback, 2021; Ahmed, 2014).

Biology education, a critical component of science education in Nigeria, aims to equip students with knowledge and skills to understand the natural world and prepare them for the workforce (Haruna, 2019; N.E.R.D.C., 2013). However, challenges persist, with students' achievement in biology examinations declining due to inadequate teaching methods and emphasis on theoretical presentation over practical aspects (Nsofor & Dada, 2013; Maikano, 2016). A shift towards a process-based approach to teaching biology is recommended to address these challenges. This approach emphasizes acquiring science process skills alongside conceptual knowledge, enabling students to learn actively and retain information effectively (Danjuma, 2017). As proposed by Piaget, constructivist theory underpins this approach, viewing learning as an active process where students construct knowledge based on their experiences and existing understanding (Danjuma, 2017; Maikano, 2016). In light of these considerations, this study investigates the impact of the Science Process-Based Approach on the performance of secondary school biology students with varied abilities in Zaria, Nigeria. By adopting a constructivist perspective and

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integrating science process skills into teaching, the study aims to enhance students' learning experiences and academic achievement in biology.

Despite biology's significance and popularity among Nigerian students, performance at the senior secondary school level could be consistently better (Ahmed, 2014). This trend raises concerns about potential workforce shortages in science and technology-related fields. Inadequate teaching methods employed by teachers in Nigeria's senior secondary schools significantly contribute to this poor performance (Ahmed & Abimbola, 2011; Umar, 2011). Rote learning is prevalent, where students memorize information without gaining a deep understanding of the subject matter. Biology students' performance in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (S.S.S.C.E.) in Kaduna state, Nigeria, reflects this issue. The statistical table of Biology results in the May/June West African Examination S.S.C.E. in Kaduna State, Nigeria, shows students' performance.

Table 1 Students' Performances in Biology in Kaduna State W.A.E.C. May/June 2016-2022

Year	Total Sat	No with A1-C6	% with A1-C6	No with D7-F9	% with D7-F9
2016	126,821	59657	47.04	67161	52.96
2017	134,852	56570	41.95	78282	58.05
2018	130,653	56155	42.98	74498	57.02
2019	150,925	72204	47.85	78722	52.17
2020	143,936	62008	43.08	81928	56.92
2021	149,162	61028	40.90	88134	59.10
2022	136,916	58284	42.60	78632	57.40

Source: West African Examination Office, Kaduna Office (2022).

Over the past seven years (2016-2022), the percentage of students passing biology at credit level (A1-C6) in the examination conducted by the West African Examination Council (W.A.E.C., 2022) consistently remained below 50% (West African Examination Council, 2022). This decline underscores the need for interventions that promote effective, activity-based, and learner-centred teaching and learning approaches. Addressing the low performance of students in biology requires identifying and addressing various factors, including teaching methods, learning materials, teacher factors, societal influences, and instructional strategies. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the Impact of the Science Process - Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

1. This study aims to investigate the academic performance of students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.
2. To determine the academic performance of Male and female students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in mean performance scores between students with varied abilities taught biology concepts using the Science Process Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the lecture method?
2. What is the difference in mean Performance scores of male and female students with varied abilities who were taught biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.
2. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between male and female students with varied ability levels who were taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Methodology

The pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design was used for the study, which involved two coeducational secondary schools and two classes in the Zaria educational zone, Kaduna State. The study population consists of 3 929 (Male, 1,623 and Female, 2,306) senior secondary school class two (SS II) government secondary school biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 133 (Male, 63 and Female, 70)

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were selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. The researcher designed the Biology Performance Test (B.P.T.) to measure the performance of students exposed to S.P.B.A. in Biology. The test consisted of 50 multiple-choice questions designed to measure academic performance in the concept of living taught, and it was used as the instrument for data collection. Pretests were administered before exposing the experimental group to the Science Process-Based Approach, with schools randomly assigned to experimental and Control groups. By the categorization that Ajewole and Okebukola had developed, the subjects were categorized according to their ability levels. The reliability of B.P.T. was assessed utilizing a test-retest reliability method. The first test was given, and after two weeks, a retest was administered to a different school that was not part of the school selected for the research. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics was used for analysis, and the result produced a reliability coefficient of 0.86; after a five-week teaching period, a posttest using the B.P.T. was administered, a posttest using the B.P.T. was administered, and data were analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation, ANOVA, ANCOVA, and Kruskal Wallis to answer research questions and hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in mean performance scores of students with varied abilities who are taught Biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Performance Test Scores in Experimental and Control Group

Ability Levels	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Low	Experimental	16	25.69	3.81	5.69
	Control	18	20.00	5.13	
Medium	Experimental	31	33.06	2.11	5.68
	Control	34	27.38	3.24	
High	Experimental	16	39.06	3.87	9.00
	Control	18	30.06	3.47	

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that the experimental and Control groups differed significantly across varied ability levels. Specifically, the experimental group exhibited a mean score of 25.69 for students with low ability levels, whereas the control group had a mean score of 20.00, resulting in a mean difference of 5.69. Among students with medium ability levels, the experimental group had a mean score of 33.06, compared to 27.38 for the control group, yielding a mean difference of 5.68. In contrast, the experimental group achieved a mean score of 39.06 for students with high ability levels, while the control group scored 30.06, resulting in a mean difference of 9.00. Hence, the analysis reveals that the mean difference is most pronounced among students with high ability levels, with a value of 9.00, followed by those with low ability levels, with a mean difference of 5.69 and medium ability levels, with a mean difference of 5.68.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean Performance scores of male and female students with varied abilities who are taught biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Performance Test Scores in Experimental and Control Groups

Ability Levels	Groups	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Low	Experimental	Male	7	28.86	1.07	5.64
		Female	9	23.22	3.27	
	Control	Male	9	21.56	1.24	
		Female	9	18.44	7.00	
Medium	Experimental	Male	10	35.08	0.79	3.29
		Female	19	31.79	1.62	

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High	Control	Male	18	27.78	1.70	0.84
		Female	16	26.94	4.4	
	Experimental	Male	10	39.30	4.55	0.63
		Female	8	38.67	2.73	
	Control	Male	9	31.33	3.28	2.55
		Female	9	28.78	3.35	

The findings presented in Table 2 illustrate that in the Experimental group, students with low abilities, both male and female, achieved performance scores of 28.86 and 23.22, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 5.64. Among those with medium skills, male and female students attained performance scores of 35.08 and 31.79, respectively, yielding a mean difference of 3.29. For students with high skills, male and female participants scored 39.30 and 38.67, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 0.63.

In contrast, in the Control group, male and female students with low abilities achieved performance scores of 21.56 and 18.44, respectively, with a mean difference of 3.12. Among those with medium skills, male and female students scored 27.78 and 26.94, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 0.84. Finally, male and female participants attained performance scores of 31.33 and 28.78 for students with high abilities, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 2.55. Consequently, the mean difference is highest among low-ability students in the experimental group, both male and female, with a value of 5.64, and lowest among high-ability students in the experimental group, both male and female, with a value of 0.63.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students with varied ability levels who are taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Table 3 (a) one - way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results of Students Performance in Experimental and Control groups

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	f-crit.	P
Between Groups	3865.036	5	773.007	62.323	3.00	0.000
Within Groups	1575.220	127	12.403			
Total	5440.256	132				

$\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Fieldwork (2019)

In Table 3 (a), the analysis indicated a calculated P-value of 0.000, which is lower than the 0.05 significance level, and a computed F-value of 62.323, which exceeds the 3.00 F-critical value. These results indicate significant differences in performance mean scores among the varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (Experimental) and Lecture (Control) methods. Consequently, the null hypothesis is currently rejected, stating that there is no significant difference in performance mean scores among varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach and Lecture method. Furthermore, the interpretation from Table 3 (a) demonstrates that significant differences exist in performance mean scores among the varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (Experimental) and Lecture (Control) methods. The data underwent a post-hoc test using Scheffe's test to establish the significance level, as shown in Table 3(b).

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Table 3 (b) posthoc Scheffe's Result of Students Performance in Experimental and Control groups

Groupings		N	Subset for alpha = 0.05				
			1	2	3	4	5
Low	Experimental	16		25.6875			
	Control	18	20.0000				
Medium	Experimental	31				33.0556	
	Control	34		27.3824	27.3824		
High	Experimental	16					39.0625
	Control	18			30.0556	30.0556	
Sig.			1.000	.800	.332	.204	1.000

In Table 3 (b), the Post Hoc analysis using the Scheffe test on performance revealed that the low control group, with a mean score of 20.0000, belongs to the minor subset. Following this, the low experimental group, with a mean score of 25.6875, and the medium control group, with a mean score of 27.3824, are categorized under subset 2. In subset 3, the high control group, with a mean score of 30.0556, is contrasted with the medium experimental group, with a mean score of 33.0556. Notably, the high experimental group, with a mean score of 39.0625, is significantly higher in subset 5, indicating the highest performance among all subsets.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between Male and female students with varied ability levels who are taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Table 4: ANCOVA results of students' Male and Female Performance in Experimental and Control groups

Source	Type III Squares	Sum of Df	Mean Square	F	P
Corrected mode	4150.286	11	377.299	35.391	0.000
Intercept	101488.575	1	101488.575	9519.698	0.000
Groups	1453.346	1	1453.346	136.325	0.000
Gender	211.808	1	211.808	19.868	0.000
Ability	2286.115	2	1143.058	107.220	0.000
Groups* Gender	7.657	1	7.657	0.718	0.398
Groups* Ability	50.086	2	25.043	2.349	0.100
Gender*Ability	39.059	2	19.530	1.832	0.165
Groups* Gender*Ability	29.588	2	14.794	1.388	0.254
Error	1289.969	121	10.661		
Total	119391.000	133			
Corrected Total	5440.256	132			

$\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Fieldwork (2019)

Table 4 indicates that the computed P-value for groups versus performance ability levels is 0.100, which exceeds the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the calculated P-value for performance ability levels versus gender is 0.165, surpassing the 0.05 alpha significance level. Additionally, the computed P-value for groups versus performance ability levels versus gender is 0.254, higher than the 0.05 alpha significance level. These results suggest no significant differences in performance mean scores among male and female students of varied abilities taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach and Lecture Method. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states no significant difference in mean performance scores of Male and female students with varied ability levels taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method, is retained.

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Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the impact of the Science Process–Based Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria educational Zone, Kaduna State. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested based on the subjects' scores obtained in Performance and Varied abilities of students' Concept of Living in S.S.I.I. Biology. The findings are discussed as follows:

The significant difference in performance observed can be attributed to the interrelated nature of science concepts and processes, as Mari (2012) noted. Understanding science concepts is only possible with knowledge of the processes used to generate knowledge. The superior success of the experimental group over the lecture group in academic performance can be further attributed to the in-depth teaching and thorough explanation of living concepts during the research. These findings are supported by Sani (2017), Ibrahim (2012), Gadzama (2012), and Shafiu (2014), who asserted in their separate studies that the experimental group exposed to the Science Process–Based Approach performed significantly better than the control group. The activities involved in the S.P.B.A. motivate learners to learn and concentrate on the concepts being taught and provide avenues for meaningful learning, thus enhancing students' academic performance.

Regarding gender's relationship to academic performance, this study reveals that the performance of male and female subjects in the experimental and Control groups is not significantly the same, implying that the Science Process-Based Approach is not gender-friendly. This finding agrees with Sani (2017) and Anaso (2008), who noted in their studies that gender did not significantly affect students' academic achievement in their subjects. Similarly, Agommuoh and Nzewi (2013) and Babajide (2020) observed no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement in science. However, Nwosu (2008) and Ibrahim (2012) disagreed with the findings of this study. They concluded that a significant difference exists in academic achievement involving activities for both boys and girls, yielding more effective learning irrespective of ability levels. The existence of gender differences in academic achievement refutes the assertion of Afuwape and Olupide (2008) and Ogunleye and Babajide (2011), who remarked in their studies that the era of male supremacy and dominance in science learning was fast winding up. The reasons for the lack of significant difference in academic performance in gender for experimental and Control groups account for the difference because of the area of research and the population involved compared to those who advanced significant differences between gender groups.

Conclusion

The Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) has emerged as a pedagogical framework to enhance students' academic performance by promoting active learning and critical thinking skills. It emphasizes inquiry-based learning, where students actively engage in the scientific process through observation, experimentation, and analysis. Studies have shown that S.P.B.A. can effectively promote the learning of complex scientific concepts by providing students with hands-on experiences and opportunities for exploration. However, despite its potential benefits, research suggests that the effectiveness of S.P.B.A. may vary across different student populations and contexts. While some studies have reported positive outcomes, others have found limited or no improvement in student performance compared to traditional lecture-based methods. Factors such as teacher training, classroom environment, and student engagement levels can influence the success of S.P.B.A. implementation.

Furthermore, gender differences in learning styles and preferences may impact the effectiveness of S.P.B.A. for male and female students. Research has shown that males and females may respond differently to specific instructional methods, with factors such as confidence levels, spatial reasoning abilities, and socialization playing a role. Therefore, it is essential to consider gender-specific needs and preferences when designing and implementing instructional approaches like S.P.B.A. While S.P.B.A. holds promise for promoting the learning of Biology concepts, its effectiveness may vary across different student populations and genders. Further research is needed to explore the factors influencing the success of S.P.B.A. implementation and to develop strategies for enhancing its efficacy for all students, regardless of gender or ability level.

Recommendations

4. Educators should tailor instructional strategies, including the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.), to meet students' diverse learning needs and preferences, taking into account factors such as gender, ability level, and prior knowledge.
5. School administrators and policymakers should prioritize professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their pedagogical skills and knowledge of practical instructional approaches, such as S.P.B.A.

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Influence of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics at Internally Displaced Persons Camps in North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The research was carried out to ascertain the influence of Boko-haram insurgency on students' enrollment in economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States. The research adopted a Correlational survey research design. There were two objectives and two research questions and two hypotheses that guided the study; population of the study is 2,349 male and female students. while the sample consists one hundred and three (103) students, using purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, 2 from economics education department while 1 from measurement and evaluation all from Ebonyi State University Abakaliki. The research questions were answered using bivariate correlation (specifically, the Pearson's r) and linear regression. The hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence level using the linear regression analysis. The study reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) between insurgency influence and enrolment in schools in the IDP camp. The result further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) is .81071. While enrolment for male and females are negative. relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively. It was concluded that students' enrolment, in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in North-East, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko-Haram insurgency. The study recommended based of the findings that Government should evolve more robust approach to managing security issues in Borno and Yobe States, adequate security should be provided to IDP camps especially in schools within the camps to give the students assurance of their safety.

Keywords: influence, insurgency, enrollment, IDPs

Introduction

The building block of life is education. Education is a veritable instrument and a cornerstone for the building and sustenance of any nation (Ekwipwre & Haruna, 2019). Whatever a nation becomes depends on the type and quality of education provided for her citizenry, because no nation can rise above her education system, since the school is the mirror of the society and agent of social change through education (Ikwumelu, 2019). Education is a module and mirror-image of social realities. Social realities are maintained, and reproduced by education and are at the same time changed by effective education (Ikwumelu, 2019). Education is very effective instrument of change, and a vehicle through which skills, knowledge and attitudes are acquired, transferred, or modified (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013). To acquire transform and modify

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society of any nation the need to develop the country's economy is inevitable. Education is widely accepted as a major instrument for promoting socio-economic, political and cultural development.

Economics is a Social Science which deals with the means by which limited resources are used to satisfy competitive wants. Economics is concerned with the patterns of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of goods and services. Economics as a subject, offers knowledge in the relationship between a given economic system and the way of life of the people concerned. According to Ameachi (2016) Economics is defined as a social science subject that studies human behaviors in the effort to allocate scarce resources efficiently and effectively in order to minimize cost. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, (NERDC, 2008), opined that there is a need to make the post-basic Economics curriculum responsive and relevant to Nigeria's quest to be among the top 20 players of the world economy come 2030.

Despite the important roles of Economics subject there is serious complaint that it lacks in developing analytical mind, critical thinking, in making judicious allocation of resources in the process of equipping Secondary School students with skills that enhanced their meaningful contributions to the economy, (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2019). The Chief Examiner while commenting on 2019 result, disclosed that there was a decline in students' achievement in Economics subject when compared with the previous years. Also, the available statistics at Education Resource Centres (ERC) in Maiduguri and Damaturu, the states capital revealed that no student scored distinction in Economics in 2022 West African Examination Council (WAEC) Examination in the two states (Education Resource Centre, 2023).

This trend of student's poor achievement could be attributed to frequent insurgence in the areas. As a result of this the education system in Borno and Yobe states has been devastated by nearly twelve years of armed conflict between Nigerian government and the Boko Haram insurgencies, (UNICEF, 2020). Boko Haram insurgency has targeted government facilities, especially public schools for attack with 279 schools forced to close in Borno and Yobe States (NUT, 2019), since the Boko Haram incursion from June 16, 2009- to date. This violence led the Borno state government to close all public schools in 22 out of 27 Local Government Areas for at least seven years (NUT, 2019) and also the violence led Yobe State Government to close 126 public schools in twelve Local Government Areas out of 17 in the state (Human Right Watch and NUT, 2019). The blanket closure has since affected Borno and Yobe States, as they are among the states that generally fall under the rubric of Educationally Less Advantaged States (ELAS) common classification used by educational planners in Nigeria (Abubakar, Mohammed and Yagana, 2018). School children were killed, schools burnt, facilities destroyed, abductions and kidnapping of school girls (Chibok Girls School in Borno state and Dafchi Girls School in Yobe state), persistent, threat, fears and displacement led to a high level of trauma in citizens (UNISCEF, 2019).

Many of the School facilities were destroyed and high population in the affected states have been displaced leading to thousands of children being out of school (UNICEF, 2019). The death toll of students was 228 while 178 teachers were killed (UNICEF, 2019) Therefore, it is not only the students and teachers that are lost but also all the classrooms, teaching materials, libraries, laboratories, school clinics and school records leaving students with nowhere to learn and teachers nowhere to teach. As a result of these attacks in Borno and Yobe states Government adopted double- shift schooling strategies to ensure the basic education need for IDPs students in schools nearby.

Double- shift schooling programme allowed normal students to attend classes from early-morning until-mid day (7:30 am to: 12 pm) for children from the school community but with a slight adjustment of school hours to allow for Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) students to run programme from the late afternoon to evening (1: pm to 6: pm) with their teachers, and each group has principal to govern the school activities (MNE and NUT, 2019). The schooling strategy was adopted to ensure continuation of basic Education needs for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) students in nearby schools which have limited resources/infrastructure within the states capitals.

Studies in Nigeria have established negative effects of insurgency on education and its stakeholders. Addullahi, Amadu and Habu (2017) observed that the level of school attendance under the crisis situation has been low. Musa and Nwachukwu (2014) compared self-identity of 600 adolescents displaced as a result of Boko-Haram insurgency with the non-displaced who are far from insurgency affected areas. Displaced adolescents were found to exhibit identity confusion –related symptoms which may exert adverse effect on learning. Adebayo (2014) found that as an insurgency group, Boko-Haram fighters force their ideology on people through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings, creating palpable fear and sense of insecurity in the polity. Hamman-Tukur, Atsua, Nwachukwu (2016) investigated the impact of boko-haram insurgency as perceived by teachers, administrators and students in Secondary Schools in Maiduguri and found that normal schools have been shut down, staff and student killed, abduction of teachers and students, took places, as well as destruction on of school facilities and increased absenteeism.

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Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study was to ascertain the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in Double-shift Schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States
2. The influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female Students' enrollment Economics in Double-shift Schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Research Questions

This study was designed to answer the following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?
2. What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for the study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States
2. There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational survey research design. This design seeks to establish relationships between variables or direct influence of one variable (X) on another variable(s) (Y). This study adopted correlational survey because its focus is on establishing the direct influence/impact of Boko Haram insurgency on school enrolment in Economics at the internally displaced Persons (IDP) camps.

The study was carried out in Borno state. The choice for these areas was because it is devastated by Boko- Haram Insurgency leading to destruction of school records, facilities and buildings, as well as killing, and adoption of students and teachers in the areas. The areas housed largest number of the internally displaced persons in the country which influenced students' enrollment in Economics subject. The population for this study was 2,349 (Male:1500 and Female:849) senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in IDP camps in Borno state. The sample size for this study was One Hundred and Three (103) comprises (Male:63 and Female:40) IDPs SS11 Economics students during the 2023/2024 academic session.

The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. both secondary and primary data collection for this current study were used. these include: Students school statutory records on Enrolment (SSSROE) to elicit record of student's enrolment in economics. Research questions were answered using bivariate correlation (specifically the Pearson's r). Hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence level using the linear regression analysis.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Table 1: Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Computed r	r^2	Adjusted r^2	Std Error
-.9004	.81071	.80884	6.6397

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

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Summary of result on Table 1 reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) correlation between Boko-Haram insurgency influence and enrollment in Economics Education Among Secondary School Students Internally Displaced Persons Camps. The Table further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) is .81071. This implies that 81% of school enrolment in the IDP camp is determined by the level of insurgency.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Table 2: Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States

Gender Categories	Computed r	r^2	Adjusted r^2	Std Error
Male	-.8887	.78974	.78641	7.13833
Female	-.9243	.85432	.85028	5.77953

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

As shown on Table 2 the Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is negative. As seen on Table 2 the relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively for males and for females. The coefficient determination of males is .7897 implying that males has approximately 79% while for females is 85%.

Hypotheses 1

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States.

Summary of result is presented on Table 3

Table 3: Significance of the influence Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Computed	r^2	Adjusted r^2	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig of T
-.9004	.81071	.80884	6.6397	-.900394	20.798	.000

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

As shown on Table 3, the significant of T is .000 while the alpha level is 0.05. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the alpha level is greater than the Sig. of T. Based on this decision rule the research rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economic in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States. As shown on Table 2 the Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is negative. As seen on Table 2 the relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively for males and for females. The coefficient determination of males is .7897 implying that males has approximately 79% while for females is 85%.

Hypotheses 2

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Summary of result is presented on Table 4

Table 4: Significance of influence of the Boko-Haram insurgency influence and enrollment on male and female in Economics Education Among Secondary School Students Internally Displaced Persons Camps in Borno and Yobe States.

Gender	Computed r	r^2	Adjusted r^2	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig of T
Male	-.8887	.78974	.78641	7.13833	-.888675	15.383	.0000
Female	-.9243	.85432	.85028	5.77953	-.924295	14.530	.0000

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Result of data analysis summarized on Table 10 indicates that for males the alpha level (0.05) is greater than the Sig of T (.0000). Based on the decision rule the researcher concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on Male Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant. The summary of result also indicates that for the females the alpha level is greater than the T sig value. As such the researcher also concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on female Students enrollment at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

The researcher discussed the findings of this study based on the two research questions and two null hypotheses that guided this study. The discussions were presented in two themes as follows:

Summary of result on Table 1 reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) between insurgency level and enrolment in schools in the IDP camp. The Table further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) is .81071. This implies that 81% of school enrolment in economics in the IDP camp is determined by the level of insurgency. On the test of significance of the relationship shown on Table 2 the significant of T is .000 while the alpha level is 0.05. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the alpha level is greater than the Sig. of T. Based on this decision rule the research rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

As shown on Table 3 the relationships between insurgency and enrolment for male and also for females are negative. As seen on Table 4, the relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively for males and for females. The coefficient of determination of insurgency on enrolment for males is .7897 implying that for males approximately 79% of enrolment of males is attributable to insurgency while for female it is approximately 85%. The researcher, in the tests of hypothesis, tested the significance of the relationships across gender with respect to levels of insurgency and enrolment. Result of data analysis summarized indicates that for males the alpha level (0.05) is greater than the Sig of T (.0000). Based on the decision rule the researcher concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on Male Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant. The summary of result also indicates that for the females the alpha level is greater than the T sig value. As such the researcher also concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on female Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

The finding agreed with the finding of Addullahi, Amadu and Habu (2017) who observed that the level of school enrollment and attendance under the crisis situation has been low. Musa and Nwachukwu (2014) compared self-identity of 600 adolescents displaced as a result of Boko-Haram insurgency with the non-displaced who are far from insurgency affected areas. Displaced adolescents were found to exhibit identity confusion-related symptoms which exert adverse effect on their willingness to get enrolled in schools. Adebayo (2014) found that as an insurgency group, Boko-Haram fighters force their ideology (that education is evil) on people through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings, creating palpable fear and sense of insecurity in the polity. This ideology sometimes becomes permanent and obviously manifest in their willingness to enroll in schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study: it is therefore concluding that students' enrolment at internally displaced persons' camps in north-east, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko Haram Insurgency. The study revealed a significant influence of Boko Haram insurgency for both male and female students' attendance to schools in the IDP camps. Also, Students' attendance to school in double-shift schooling at internally displaced person's camps in north-east, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko Haram Insurgency. The study also revealed a negative influence of Boko Haram insurgency for both male and female students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should evolve a more robust approach to managing security issues in Borno and Yobe States.
2. Adequate security should be provided to IDP camps especially in schools within the camps to give the students assurance of their safety. This will obviously increase their willingness to enroll, attend classes and also achieve in their respective

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subjects' while effective counselling services should be provided to people in the IDP camps. The focus will be on re-orientation of the members of IDP camps on the importance of education and the need to enroll and attend classes.

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Influence of Creativity and Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano

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Abstract

The study investigates the Influence of Creativity and Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education. Two research questions were asked and two null hypotheses were tested for the study. The study used descriptive survey design to guide it. The population of the study consists of all 100 level Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample size of 135 (65 male and 60 female) was selected using random sampling technique from the target population. The instrument used for data collection is Creativity and Technology of Academic Performance (IOCATOP) Questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts' senior lecturers due to remove all ambiguities of the instrument for the respondents. Pilot study was carried out at Federal College of Education Kano using thirty (30) 100 level business education students. The reliability coefficient of the instrument obtained was 0.87. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this research reveal that there is significant influence of creativity on academic performance among Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria (P-value, 0.000). The recommendations were made as creativity should be used by the lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.

Keyword: Business Education Students, Creativity, and Technology of University of Education, in Kano State Nigeria

Introduction

Business education students are students who are enrolled in Business education programmes, primarily at the 100 level in Business Education Department of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Educations Kano State. Business education students must be creative, particularly in connection to creativity and technology, in order to increase their academic performance in learning Business education courses and develop their originality. Students' creativity refers to their ability to apply their ideas to develop product that generates more revenue for the university and society at large. Creativity may be defined as the act of generating new issues of noteworthy ideas that boost the economic ability of an individual, organisation, and the nation at large in order to improve the nation's and the world's productivities (Haruna, 2016). The capacity to think mathematically regarding Business education courses is critical for performing tasks that increase students' productivity in Business education.

In the same vein, Vena et al (2023) stated that the ability to think creatively mathematically is one of the abilities required in the process of learning courses that dealt with mathematics such as Business education in their classroom in order to be functional members of the society where they found themselves for productivities. According to Tabach and Friedlander (2017), students' creative thinking abilities have an influence on students' conceptual understanding abilities during the Business education learning process because students with high creative thinking abilities will apply flexible and creative thinking when solving a problem related to Business education and will not stick to what the lecturers lecture them for technological enhancement of academic performance of Business education students.

Technology refers to a technique that enhances students' performance, skills, and tactics by using technological aspects that simplify and minimise most of the factors that hinder students' poor performance for easy communication of facts in time that allows students to improve their performance. This is consistent with their study's goal of contributing to the existing body of knowledge on successful educational practices and influencing policy choices related to the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) and class management tactics in secondary schools by analysing the interaction that exists between ICT, class size, and academic performance (Olusola et al 2023).

This study is tied to and based on one (1) theory: George Herbert Mead's (George Herbert Mead 1920) Symbolic Interactionism Theory. The theory was chosen because: it deals with the interaction between students' creativity and their skills

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in performing most of the activities that link and display their potentiality, particularly in Business education that deals with creativity and skills in teaching Business education using affecting teaching methods that allows students to interact with their creativity with technology while learning in the class before the time so as to improve their academic performance in Business education.

This theory of Symbolic Interactionism is based on the symbolic interaction meaning that people generate and rely on when interacting with two or more people while completing activities. Although symbolic interactionism derives from Max Weber's argument that individuals act according to their creativity, technology, and interpretation of the meaning of their reality, it was brought to American sociology in the 1920s by the American philosopher George Herbert Mead. This is consistent with Korgen and Write (2008), who stated that symbolic interaction theory focused on how people interact in their daily creative lives through symbolic interaction and how they create order and meaning, which led supervisors to correct the students' corrections such as amending, deleting, and editing the activities of answering Business questions those required creativity and technological techniques when performing activities in class and outsides.

Student's Creativity relates to the student's imagination, which is displayed particularly while addressing questions that involve the students' thinking abilities. This means that most Business education questions required creativity and critical thinking. Similarly, creative people can design novel solutions to address problems and confront challenges (Ayasrah et al, 2023). They can develop innovative ways to do their assigned responsibilities, solve problems and challenges, and so provide a unique viewpoint to their work (Jarwan, 2013). As a result, this helps organisations and businesses evolve to take a more productive approach (Ayasrah et al, 2023). Employers in this era value creative thinking skills (Majdoubi, 2020; Al-Rubaie, 2020; Nurhamidah et al., 2018). Generally, universities are accused of generating graduates that lack enough talent or expertise in creativity, innovation, and technology (Gube & Lajoie, 2020). As a result, countries, particularly developing and poor ones, and their various related organisations, such as the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Higher Education, should provide a broad space in the educational environment for students to gain and practise creative thinking freely (Ayasrah et al, 2023). Creative thinking is one of the greatest and highest skills and abilities that students at all educational levels should strive for (Akpur, 2020; Gajda, 2016; Safadi, 2015). Creative thinking becomes a life strategy that assists students in developing a thorough awareness of diverse life challenges, allowing them to solve such difficulties in creative and original ways, and adapting to changes in time, knowledge, and technology progress that follow it (Al-Aqbawi, 2019).

Furthermore, it helps to build a variety of human talents and capacities, such as the ability to assess, criticise, link, and apply. Akpur (2020) discovered a link between reflective thinking, creative thinking, and critical thinking in research of 227 first-year university students in Istanbul, Turkey. Furthermore, all these variables had a beneficial and significant impact on the academic performance of students, particularly Business students. Kim (2020) discovered a positive relationship between engineering students' creativity and academic success. Furthermore, it has been discovered that female students are potentially more creative than male students in executing their activities that deal with courses relating to mathematics, such as Business education. A research of 153 undergraduate students in Malaysian universities found that features of creativity are associated to academic achievement for both male and female students (Ayasrah et al, 2023).

Fatmawati et al. (2019) conducted a study on a sample of 30 students (fourth-semester), Department of Biology Education, IKIP Mtataram, Indonesia, to determine the association between learning performance and each of creative thinking skills and critical thinking skills. It was discovered that there was a link between learning performance and both critical and creative thinking skills. The study found a link between learning performance, critical and creative thinking skills, and student performance (Ayasrah et al, 2023). The relationship between self-perceived creativity and entrepreneurial willingness was studied among 559 Spanish university students (Lagua et al., 2019). Family and academic support for creativity, as well as participation in a creativity course, are major predicting factors of self-perceived creativity. Furthermore, teaching creative content and practice enriches entrepreneurship curricula. To address the growth of students' creativity throughout their university education in order to improve students' performance.

Students' performance refers to their capacity to achieve high grades in a test or examination after lecturers have taught them and given them a test or examination that they pass extremely well. According to Rothstein (2012), student performance refers to a successful completion of performance in a specific subject area of study at a given school by professional lecturers. According to Rothstein (2012), student performance is concerned with students' studies and how they cope with or complete various duties assigned to them by their lecturers throughout the course of a semester or year. Furthermore, Yeboah and Dominic (2014) defined student performance as the ability of pupils to study and remember facts, as well as transmit knowledge vocally or on writing. This is consistent with the findings of Norman (2014), who examined the characteristics that contribute to students' success in intermediate Business. Norman wanted to see if factors including students' performance in previous

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courses, age, gender, and major language of communication influenced Business education students' success. There is a link between having lower class numbers and receiving more individualised attention from teachers, higher levels of student engagement, and increased academic performance (Oyeniran 2014). As a result, doing research on the relationship between the number of students in each class and their performance could produce knowledge regarding the most effective learning environment for kids (Mugure 2020). This means that students should be given greater consideration in terms of learning environment in order to create a conducive environment for effective learning and development of students' performance.

Technology refers to a technique that uses technological aspects to improve students' performance, skills, and tactics by simplifying and reducing most of the factors that impede students' poor performance for easy communication of facts in time that allows students to improve their performance. This is consistent with the study's goal of contributing to the existing body of knowledge on successful educational practices and influencing policy decisions related to the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) and class management tactics in secondary schools by examining the interaction that exists between ICT, class size, and academic performance (Olusola et al 2023). The study's findings have the potential to provide valuable insights and ideas to educators, policymakers, and other stakeholders in Ekiti State and elsewhere.

As a result of the study's findings, secondary school students' experiences teaching and learning science topics will most likely improve (Olusola et al 2023). The impact of the number of students in a scientific class on overall student performance can be advantageous or negative, depending on the settings in the classroom (Kuhlemeier & Hemker 2016). A crowded classroom has a negative impact on both science teaching and student academic performance. When there are more students in a school, there are also more pupils in each class, which may cause issues with the students' performance. According to Olusola et al. (2023), class size has evolved into a phenomenon that is widely cited in educational literature as having an impact on student feelings and successes, as well as school administration, quality, and finances. According to him, the number of pupils in a class is almost usually chosen by administrators, and teachers have little or no influence in the matter.

Students' performance in science disciplines has been seen to be declining in Ekiti State over the years, according to researchers (Olofin & Kolawole 2020). Many arguments have been advanced in the literature for students' low performance, but it appears that little focus has been placed on pupils learning through ICT/internet facilities and conducive class-size. The researchers discovered that academic achievement of students in science disciplines has been declining in Ekiti State over the years. The study's participants are specifically secondary school students engaged in science programmes in the Nigerian state of Ekiti. Science classes are critical for developing scientific literacy, preparing students for future education, and preparing them for potential careers in science-related fields. Learning how information and communication technology (ICT) and the number of students in a class affect academic achievement in different courses has the potential to improve scientific education in the field (Olusola et al 2023). Based on this premise, the study studied the effects of ICT/internet facilities and class size on the academic achievement of secondary school students in science subjects.

Business education has been discussed by various authors who shared the same worldview based on their definitions. Business education is a process in which data relating to an organization's economic activities are measured, recorded, and disseminated to interested parties for the goal of analysis and interpretation in order to make proper Business decisions (Abdullahi, 2016). It informs owners/managers and other Business stakeholders about what is going on in the system. Business education informs a wide range of interested parties and eventually demonstrates how a Business has been managed over time-whether successfully or unsuccessfully. Business education also gives information about a firm's financial status as of the deadline for making decisions using skills, as well as to guide gender and increase student performance (Okoye, Uniamikogbo, & Adeusi, 2017).

According to the Business Education Change Committee (BECC), Business educators should focus on: businesses' organisational knowledge; Business systems must give information that represents the entire scenario. Unstructured problems: Because Business problems are generally unstructured, boosting candidates' analytical and analytical ability is more important than memorising. Another thing to notice is the increased emphasis on integrating active learning into pedagogy and technology across the Business curriculum. He also complained about the gap between the requirements of the real sector and the subjects taught in Business courses. He remarked that Business enrolment and attraction were declining, and Business academicians were dissatisfied (Yilmaz, 2022). Accountants must be able to use professional judgement and be skeptical. Business competencies are seen to need to work in tandem with management competencies. Worked up the Business education framework that allows students to have more understanding for handling Business in any situation (Yilmaz 2022).

Students' performance has been identified as an important issue for tertiary institutions, and research into the possibility of students' performance is also important for universities of education, their lecturers, and students, and can be effective in making policy on students' admission programme and changes in teaching method to improve students' performance while

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teaching Business education. Measuring students' performance in learning Business education at universities of education based on internal and external factors such students ability, interest, language speaking, background level as well conducive atmosphere, sophisticated learning materials especially those are related to Business education, the research attempts to identify and combine the most important factors while also highlighting the important results for selecting the most qualified candidates and, as a result, avoiding Business students' failure and drop-out (Velasco, 2021).

For the purpose of this study, below were considered as the empirical studies of the research: Ayasrah et al (2023) conducted a study titled `` Practicing Creative Thinking and its relation to academic performance among students of the Jordan University of Science and Technology. Three (3) objectives were raised as well as three (3) null hypotheses were tested for the study. One thousand and one hundred and fifty-nine (1159) Students of the university in the faculty served as the sample sizes of the study. The results of the study indicated that students of Jordan University of Science and Technology are practicing creative thinking at a moderate level reaching 2.96 at Likert scale. Moreover, it revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of practicing creative thinking due to gender favouring male students. A close relationship between the level of practicing creative thing and academic achievement was found, where 20% of the research sample having high academic achievement showed moderate level of practicing creative thinking.

This research work is similar in context with the previous because they both concentrated on the use of a creativity of the performance of Students. Both studies considered the participation of the students in the teaching process as of paramount importance for the study. The previous research work is relevant to the present study because it helped in the literature development. Despite their similarities, these research works differ to the extent that the previous research work was carried out at Jordan University of Science and Technology but the present work was conducted at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria. Hence, they differ in location. The previous study raised and tested only three (3) objectives, and three (3) null hypotheses in order to guide it. The present study raised and tested two (2) specific objectives null hypotheses for the study. The previous study did not specify the population used for the study. The present study does so. The previous study did not specify the statistical tools used in testing the null hypothesis, which is better to be identified for the help of the reader(s) in determining the reliability of the instrument of the statistical tools used to guide it.

Olusola et al, (2023) conducted a study, titled `` Impact of ICT and Class Size on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Science Subject in Ekiti State``. The study tested two null hypotheses in order to guide the study. The design used for the study were descriptive survey and ex-post-facto designs. The sample sizes of the study include 110 science teachers and 2444 students whose secondary schools were used. The students were selected using multistage sampling techniques. The data of the study were analysed using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficients. The result showed that there was significant relationship between availability of ICT and academic performance in schools. The study also revealed that there is significant relationship between class-size and academic.

This research work is similar in context with the previous research work because they both concentrated on technology on students` performance. In the previous study used Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficient to test the null hypotheses. While the present study used regression analysis to test the null hypothesis 1 and 2, in order to determine the influence of nexus creativity on performance of Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State. The previous research work is relevant to the present study because it helped in the literature development. Despite their similarities, these research works differ to the extent that the previous research work was carried out at Ekiti State Nigeria, but the present work was conducted at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State. Hence, they differ in location. The previous study tested only two (2) null hypotheses in order to guide it. The present study raised and tested two (2) null hypotheses. The previous study did not use proper statistical tools in determining the reliability coefficient of the instruments. This means that t-test is not supposed to be used in determining the reliability of the instrument. The previous study did not explain where the study used the two designs appropriately for the readers to be educated.

In a global competition for job specification and the placement of students appropriately, their performances have been identified as an essential determinant ingredient for providing students with more career opportunities, choices and job security. This is in line with the position of Mamman (2016) who stated that students` performances are the ingredients of students` enhancement and societal development to minimise poor performance of students. This is in line with the position of Bayram-Jacobs and Hayirsever (2016) who stated that neglecting students-centre while teaching increases the poor performance of students that are in line with the reasons that necessitated the conducting of this study from the researcher`s assessment on the declining of students` performance in universities of education. In confirmation of the above-mentioned statement, the researcher`s assessment of the recent performance of Business education students from their semesters results between 2019 and 2023 revealed that students` performances were very poor and declining. These poor performances of students agree with

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the position of Enwere and Enwere (2014) as well as Obidile, Amobi, Uzoekwe and Akuezilo (2017) that the major reasons for poor performance of students was neglecting students' creativity and technology while teaching students Business education. Most of the lecturers did not allow the students to participate fully in the process of answering questions. If the creativity and technology were not considered in teaching Business education the students' performance would not be improved.

Objectives of the study:

The following served as the objectives of this study:

1. Examine the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria.
2. Determine the influence of technology on academic performance of Business Education students at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were answered for the study

1. What is the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of technology on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

In line with the research questions of the study, the following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance on this study:

1. Creativity has no significant influence on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria
2. Technology has no significant influence on academic performance among Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Methodology

This paper used descriptive survey design to source the data using the opinion of the students with the help of structure questionnaire among the population of the study. The population of the study was made up of one hundred and thirty-five (135) 100 level Business education students in Business Education Department of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria. Based on the nature of the population and the topic, all students served as sample size of the study. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample sizes of the study. *Influence of Creativity and Technology of Performance (IOCATOP) Questionnaire* with five items each which were designed by the researcher and served as an instrument for data collection. The respondents' responses of the copies of questionnaire were rated using four scales. The scales are Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree which was analysed using the mean and standard deviation and regression analysis.

The instrument was validated by three experts' senior lecturers before carrying out the pilot study. The pilot study was conducted using (30) respondents such as twenty-one (21) male and (09) nine female Business education students at Federal College of Education Kano using degree 100 level students who are nearest to the population of the study. They have the same features with the population of the study. The result of the pilot study splits into two using split half test and tested the reliability using SPSS by Cronbach Alpha and derived the reliability coefficient of 0.87. The researcher administered the instruments to the students and retrieved back. Ninety-seven (97) copies of the questionnaire was collected back and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean and standard deviation and regression analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, if the P-value is equal or greater than the Alpha value ($0.05 \geq$), then the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant influence between the variables when the P-value is less than the Alpha then the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is significant effect between the variables.

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Results

Research Question 1:

What is the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Creativity on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Saadatu Rimi University of Education Business Education Students	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
Influence of Creative	97	22.52	12.62	
Academic Performance	97	18.82	1.99	3.7

Source (Field Survey, 2024)

Table 1 shows that the mean in the Influence of creativity mean was 16.52 and the standard deviation was 2.62 ($\chi = 16.52$; SD = 2.62), whereas the academic performance of business education students mean was 18.82 and the standard deviation was 1.99 ($\chi = 18.82$; SD = 1.99). The respondents at the influence of creativity on the academic performance among business education students of Saadatu Rimi University of Education Kano State had a mean difference of 3.7

Research Question 2:

What is the influence of technology on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Saadatu Rimi University of Education Business Education Students	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
Influence of Technology	97	23.87	13.73	
Academic Performance	97	18.82	1.99	5,10

Source (Field Survey, 2024)

Table 2 shows that the mean in the Influence of technology mean was 23.87 and the standard deviation was 13.73 ($\chi = 23.87$; SD = 13.73), whereas the academic performance of business education students mean was 18.82 and the standard deviation was 1.99 ($\chi = 18.82$; SD = 1.99). The respondents at the influence of technology on the academic performance among business education students of Saadatu Rimi University of Education Kano State had a mean difference of 5.10.

Hypothesis 1:

Creativity has no influence on the performance of Business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi of Education, Kano in Nigeria Data collected to address the null hypothesis one was summarised in Table 3

Table 3 Summary of Regression Analysis on the Creativity of Significant Influence of Performance of Business Education Students at Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign
Creativity	(4.467)	2.624	(2.803)	.727	.578	.460	0.000
Students' Performance	13.637	5.910	2.538				

Source: Field survey 2024 P>0.05

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The regression analysis on Table 3 was to determine the influence of creativity of students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso. The result revealed a constant Beta value of (4.467) (Nexus Creativity) with the t-value of (2.803) against the coefficient value of 2.538 (Students' Performance) and t-value of 4.467. The R-value was .727 with R²-value of .578 and Adjusted-r of .460 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that nexus creativity on students' performance of Business education with a variance of 58% (r² .578 x 100). This means that for each single increase on influence of creativity, there was an increase of students' performance in Business education of 58%. The observed=0.000 was less than the α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence of nexus creativity of students' performance. This implies that the influence of nexus creativity of students' performance in Business education was rejected and concluded there is significant influence of nexus creativity on students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi university of education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

Technology has no influence on the performance of Business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi of Education, Kano in Nigeria Data collected to address the null hypothesis one was summarised in Table 4

Table 4 Summary of Regression Analysis on the Technology of Significant Influence of Performance of Business Education Students at Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign
Technology	(5.567)	2.725	(3465)	.778	.678	.477	0.000
Students' Performance	14.657	5.945	2.579				

Source: Field survey 2024 P>0.05

The regression analysis on Table 4 was to determine the influence of technology of students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso. The result revealed a constant Beta value of (5.567) (Nexus Technology) with the t-value of (2.725) against the coefficient value of 2.579 (Students' Performance) and t-value of 5.945. The R-value was .778 with R²-value of .678 and Adjusted-r of .477 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that creativity on students' performance of Business education with a variance of 68% (r² .678 x 100). This means that for each single increase on influence of technology, there was an increase of students' performance in Business education of 68%. The observed=0.000 was less than the value (0.05) indicating a significant influence of nexus technology of students' performance. This implies that the influence of technology of students' performance in Business education was rejected and concluded there is significant influence of technology on students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question in Table 1 and hypothesis one in Table 3 show that the students who are the opinion on the influence of creativity in Business education agreed significantly that creativity influence the academic performance among of Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education to improve students' performance in Business education. The findings are consistent with that of Ayasrah et al (2023) who opine the results of the study indicated that students of Jordan University of Science and Technology are practicing creative thinking at a moderate level reaching 2.96 at Likert scale. Moreover, it revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of practicing creative thinking due to gender favouring male students. Akpur (2020) on a total of 227 first year university students, Istanbul, Turkey, showed a positive correlation among reflective thinking, creative thinking, and critical thinking. Moreover, all these parameters affected academic performance of students especially Business education students in a positive and significant way.

Kim (2020) found a positive correlation between the creativity of engineering students and academic performance. In addition, it is found that female students are potentially more creative compared to male students in performing their activity that deal with the course who are related the mathematics such as Business education. A study on 153 undergraduate students in Malaysian universities revealed that aspects of creativity are related to academic performance for both male and female students. The finding related to null hypothesis two in Table 2 revealed the result showed that there was significant relationship between availability of ICT and academic performance in schools. The study also revealed that there is significant relationship between class-size and academic. Mugure (2020) stated that students need to be given more consideration in term of learning

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environment for students' conducive atmosphere with effective learning and improvement of academic performance of students. This would enable them to perform very well in their learning engagement especially using technologies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings discussed in this study concludes that nexus creativity and technology are the appropriate skills to be used in teaching students Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi university of Education. It is also revealed that nexus creativity and technology help, assist and guide the Business education students to improve their performance regardless of their gender differences. The students who were taught using nexus creativity and technology can earn good grades which will enable them to have admission into the postgraduate studies. This will also make their parents proud of their students' performance and the students become productive members of the society after graduation for earning their living.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Creativity should be used by the business education lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.
2. Technology should be used by the business education lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.

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Integration of Mobile Technologies to Support Remote Learning at the Basic Education Level in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

The educational environment in Northern Nigeria faces significant challenges hindering teaching and learning progress, particularly in basic education, where security threats like banditry and kidnapping have complicated traditional educational methods, leading to disruptions and school closures. The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated these challenges, necessitating alternative instructional approaches. However, persistent security issues exacerbate difficulties faced by educators and learners, resulting in a decline in educational quality and continuity, while jeopardizing physical safety and hindering equitable access to education. Mobile technologies present a promising solution to address these challenges, especially in the Northwest region where banditry and kidnapping are prevalent. This research explores the dynamics of utilizing mobile technologies to support remote learning initiatives in basic education within Northwest Nigeria. Mobile learning, characterized by its accessibility, interactivity, and adaptability, holds immense potential to transform traditional educational practices, making learning more accessible, engaging, and personalized. By leveraging mobile technologies, educators can provide flexible and accessible educational solutions, ensuring continuity of learning despite security challenges. The TPACK model serves as a valuable framework for effectively integrating mobile technologies into remote learning environments, emphasizing the harmonious balance of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. Embracing mobile learning not only enhances educational accessibility but also empowers students to pursue self-directed learning, fostering a culture of lifelong learning.

Keyword: Mobile technologies, Remote Learning, Basic Education, Northern Nigeria, Security threats, TPACK model

Introduction

The educational environment in Northern Nigeria faces numerous obstacles that impede the progress of teaching and learning, particularly in the realm of basic education (Verspoor & Adriaan, 2008). The confluence of pervasive issues like banditry and kidnapping has resulted in an intricate situation, significantly impeding traditional educational methods (Sylvanus & Bernard, 2023). The region has grappled with disruptions attributable to security challenges, leading to the abduction of both students and teachers. The closure of schools in response to the COVID-19 pandemic prompted educational institutions to seek alternative instructional approaches (Adedoyin & Soyinka, 2023). Nevertheless, the existing security situation in the region, characterized by ongoing banditry and targeted kidnappings, compounds the difficulties faced by educators and learners (Abubakar et al., 2021). The prevailing apprehension of potential attacks has disrupted the learning environment, causing a decline in the quality and continuity of education. These occurrences have not only jeopardized the physical safety of students and teachers but have also fostered an atmosphere of fear and uncertainty, hampering equitable access to education (Amy & Klinger, 2018).

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The field of education is undergoing a substantial transformation propelled by technological advancements, and mobile technologies are playing a crucial role in reforming teaching and learning approaches (Crompton, 2013). In the northwest zone of Nigeria, where challenges like banditry and kidnapping are widespread, the adoption of remote learning has become essential. This research endeavors to unravel the nuanced dynamics of employing mobile technologies to support remote learning initiatives, focusing on the unique context of basic education in Northwest Nigeria (Haruna, 2017).

The ubiquitous presence of mobile technologies in contemporary society is undeniable. Smartphones and tablets have become integral components of our daily lives, offering unprecedented access to information, communication, and interactive content (Reid et al., 2018). In the educational arena, the potential of these devices to transcend temporal and spatial constraints is particularly compelling. The advent of remote learning, accelerated by global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has accentuated the need for flexible and accessible educational solutions (Cone et al., 2022). Kanno and Onyeachu (2015) characterize basic education as the fundamental level of education, which can also be construed as the most essential form of education provided to individuals. It serves as the cornerstone of education upon which all other educational progress relies. In this context, basic education can be likened to the foundation of a building, upon which all other structural elements and educational achievements are built.

Northwest Nigeria refers to the geographical region located in the northern part of Nigeria, which is a country in West Africa. It is one of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria, and it encompasses several states, including but not limited to Kano, Katsina, Sokoto, Kaduna, Jigawa, Kebbi, and Zamfara. Northwest Nigeria is known for its diverse culture, historical significance, and economic activities such as agriculture, trade, and industry. It is an area with both urban centers and rural communities, and it plays a significant role in the socio-economic and political landscape of Nigeria. This region has faced various challenges, including security issues like banditry and kidnapping, which have had an impact on its educational and social development.

In many separate incidents across four states, students and their educators have been forcibly taken. In these occurrences, heavily armed individuals forcibly entered public boarding schools, firing their weapons indiscriminately, and forcibly moved the students into dense forests (Ojo et al., 2023). The victims were subjected to deplorable living conditions and eventually released after days or even weeks once a ransom was paid. In February, armed men also abducted nearly 300 girls from a boarding school located in Jangebe, Zamfara state (Osimen et al., 2018). Fortunately, the majority of these girls were later liberated.

The global aspiration to decrease illiteracy, address lack of knowledge, and promote educational accessibility, especially at the grassroots level, led to the initiation of the Education for All (EFA) framework, as outlined in the Jomtien Declaration Easton, (Easton& Malam, 2019). This treaty was introduced and ratified during the conference held in Jomtien, Thailand, in March 1990 (Egbe & Eze, 2009). As outlined by Dada (2004), access to education entails the chance and entitlement to partake in formal learning. It also encompasses the provision of equal opportunities to individuals who meet the criteria for receiving universal primary education, without regard to their socio-economic status, religious affiliation, gender, and other factors (Dreze & Sen, 2003).

Concept and definition of Mobile Learning at the Basic Education level

Mobile learning, often abbreviated as m-learning, refers to the use of mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, or other portable electronic devices to facilitate learning and education (nail & Ammar, 2017). At the basic education level, which typically encompasses primary and secondary education, mobile learning can play a crucial role in enhancing the educational experience by leveraging the ubiquity and versatility of mobile technology (Dias et al., 2008). Accessibility of Mobile learning enables students to access educational content anytime, anywhere, as long as they have a compatible device and an internet connection (Motiwalla, 2007). This flexibility eliminates barriers to learning that may arise due to physical location or time constraints. Mobile devices offer interactive features such as touchscreens, multimedia capabilities, and educational apps that can make learning more engaging and enjoyable for students (Artal-Sevil, 2015). Interactive quizzes, educational games, and multimedia resources can enhance student motivation and participation (Zainuddin et al., 2020).

Mobile learning can be tailored to individual student needs and preferences. Educational apps and platforms often offer adaptive learning functionalities that adjust the pace and content of instruction based on each student's learning progress and performance (Zhu et al., 2016). Mobile devices facilitate collaboration and communication among students and teachers. Through messaging apps, discussion forums, and collaborative tools, students can interact with their peers and teachers, share ideas, collaborate on projects, and receive feedback in real-time (Sun et al., 2018; Dahal, 2022). Resource Accessibility of Mobile devices provide access to a vast array of educational resources, including e-books, videos, simulations, and online

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courses. This wealth of resources allows students to explore diverse topics, conduct research, and deepen their understanding of concepts beyond the confines of traditional classroom materials. Mobile learning fosters a culture of lifelong learning by enabling students to continue their education beyond the classroom (Criollo-C et al., 2021). With mobile devices, students can pursue self-directed learning, explore their interests, and acquire new skills even outside formal educational settings.

Mobile learning can accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences. Students can choose from a variety of learning materials and formats that best suit their individual needs, whether they prefer reading text, watching videos, listening to audio lectures, or engaging in interactive activities (Premlatha & Geetha, 2015). Mobile learning at the basic education level offers immense potential to transform traditional educational practices by making learning more accessible, engaging, personalized, and collaborative (Mehdipour, et al., 2013). However, it's essential to address challenges such as device accessibility, digital literacy, and equitable access to resources to ensure that all students can benefit from mobile learning opportunities.

Kadirire (2009) presents m-learning as a variant of e-learning that offers the flexibility of occurring at any time and in any place, facilitated by the use of mobile communication tools like mobile phones, personal digital assistants (PDAs), iPods, or similar compact and portable devices. However, contemporary viewpoints on mobile learning embrace m-learning as a transformative shift. In contrast, Keegan (2005) advocates for defining m-learning in a way that confines it to learning experiences facilitated exclusively through small, easily portable devices. He underscores the idea that these mobile devices can be carried with ease, fitting into a lady's handbag or a gentleman's pocket. Consequently, this definition aligns with a technocentric perspective, emphasizing the significance of mobile device size in defining m-learning. Furthermore, mobile learning entails establishing connections with institutional systems, including virtual learning environments (VLEs) and management information systems (MIS) (Hashemi et al., 2011).

According to Training Industry (2021) remote learning can be described as a mode of education in which the learner and the instructor, or the source of information, are geographically separated, making it impossible for them to convene in a traditional classroom environment. Typically, information is conveyed through technological means such as email, discussion boards, video conferences, or audio bridges, eliminating the need for any physical presence in a classroom setting; otherwise, it would fall under the categories of Hybrid or Blended Learning. Remote learning can take place either in real-time (synchronously) or at different times (asynchronously). It is also commonly referred to as Distance Education, Virtual Instruction, or Remote Training.

Theoretical Review

The TPACK model, introduced by Mishra and Koehler (2006), offers a valuable framework for effectively integrating mobile technologies into remote learning environments for basic education in Northwest Nigeria. TPACK underscores the intricate interplay among technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, stressing the importance of achieving a harmonious balance among these elements to enhance the teaching and learning process. In the context of Northwest Nigeria, where educational access is hindered by factors such as banditry, kidnapping, and other criminal activities, the TPACK model remains essential for adapting mobile technologies to facilitate remote learning.

Application of TPACK Mobile Technologies for Remote Learning at Basic Education Level:

3. **Technological Knowledge (TK):** Educators in Northwest Nigeria must acquire proficiency in utilizing mobile technologies, including smartphones and tablets, for remote learning. This proficiency is crucial to ensure accessibility and the uninterrupted continuity of basic education in areas affected by security challenges.
4. **Pedagogical Knowledge (PK):** To effectively apply the TPACK model, teachers should employ pedagogical strategies that align with the capabilities of mobile devices, thus ensuring that remote lessons are engaging and interactive. Pedagogical knowledge is vital for educators in Northwest Nigeria as it enables them to design interactive lessons that make the most of the capabilities and applications of mobile technologies.
5. **Content Knowledge (CK):** TPACK encourages educators to tailor the curriculum to the local context and culture of Northwest Nigeria, thereby making the educational content more relevant and meaningful to students. Aligning content knowledge with the local context and culture is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of remote learning in Northwest Nigeria.

The Implications of Mobile Learning at the Basic Education level in Northwest Basic Education are drawn from the above concept and definition of Mobile Learning

1. 1.Kadirire's definition of m-learning as a form of e-learning that can take place anytime and anywhere with the help of mobile communication devices is highly relevant to Northwest Nigeria (Kadirire, 2009). Given the security challenges and the dispersed nature of communities in the region, mobile technologies enable remote learning that is not bound by time or place. Students can access educational resources on their mobile devices, allowing for flexibility in their learning schedules and locations.
2. 2.Keegan's perspective on m-learning as a paradigm shift in education aligns with the region's needs and challenges (Keegan, 2005). In Northwest Nigeria, where traditional education may be disrupted by insecurity, m-learning represents a transformative approach. It allows basic education to continue despite security concerns, offering a lifeline for students who might otherwise be deprived of access to education due to kidnapping and banditry.
3. 3.Keegan's perspective, which emphasizes the size and portability of mobile devices, becomes particularly significant in light of the security situation (Keegan, 2005). The small and easily portable nature of mobile phones is advantageous for students in Northwest Nigeria, as they can carry their learning devices discreetly and safely. This minimizes the risk of drawing attention to areas affected by security challenges.

Incorporating mobile technologies for remote learning in Northwest Nigeria offers a practical solution to address the obstacles posed by insecurity, such as kidnapping and banditry, to basic education. Mobile learning provides students with the means to access educational content from secure locations, reducing the need for physical movement to attend traditional schools. This not only ensures their safety but also empowers them with the opportunity to continue their education, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and accessible basic education system in the face of adversity.

Conclusion

The adoption of mobile learning in basic education in Northwest Nigeria offers a practical solution to mitigate the obstacles posed by insecurity, such as banditry and kidnapping. Mobile technologies enable remote learning, transcending temporal and spatial constraints, and ensuring educational continuity in the face of adversity. Embracing the TPACK model facilitates the effective integration of mobile technologies into educational practices, enhancing accessibility, engagement, and personalized learning experiences. Mobile learning empowers students to access educational resources securely, contributing to a more resilient and equitable basic education system.

Recommendations

1. **Investment in Mobile Infrastructure:** Governments and educational institutions ought to allocate resources towards enhancing mobile infrastructure, encompassing initiatives such as improving internet connectivity and implementing programs for distributing devices. These measures are essential for promoting fair and inclusive access to mobile learning resources across Northwest Nigeria.
2. **Teacher Training:** Educators should undergo training to effectively utilize mobile technologies for remote teaching, integrating teaching methodologies that are compatible with the functionalities of mobile devices.
3. **Curriculum Adaptation:** The curriculum needs to be adjusted to suit the local context and cultural nuances of Northwest Nigeria, thereby ensuring that educational content is pertinent and significant to students.
4. **Collaborative Partnerships:** Regular monitoring and evaluation of mobile learning initiatives are essential to assess their effectiveness and identify areas for improvement, ensuring sustained progress in enhancing basic education in the region.
5. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Consistent monitoring and evaluation of mobile learning initiatives are crucial for evaluating their efficacy and pinpointing areas that require enhancement, thereby guaranteeing continual advancement in bolstering basic education in the area.

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Managing Community Development Programs for Productivity through Adult Education: Agenda for Citizens' Participation in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper focuses on managing adult education towards community development with emphasis on the inclusion of citizens' active participation in Nigeria. It discusses community development programmes through adult education and its relevance in conscientizing and mobilizing the citizens towards participating and engaging in community development activities. Programmes of activities such as; literacy education, vocational education, health education, agricultural education amongst others are responsible for raising human skills, knowledge and promote quality engagement towards sustainable development in Nigeria. The study employed secondary source of information and further contends that citizens' participation in community development could be propelled through adult education programme in Nigeria. The study concludes that citizens' participation in any community development is vital to improving their living standard, enhance productivity and reduce poverty, ignorance and illiteracy within the society. On the bases of these, the paper recommends that managing adult education towards community development in Nigeria implies but not limited to all-inclusiveness of the citizens who identify what constitute development and work toward achieving it for the overall wellbeing of the populace.

Keyword: Management, Community Development, Adult Education, Participation

Introduction

One important strategy for effective community development is the participation in rural development efforts involving diverse citizens to form a common front within the community. In this aspect Cohen and Uphoft in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) conceived participation to mean the involvement of a significant number of persons in situation or actions which enhance their wellbeing. They posit participation as the active process in which a people in question take part in the initiative and implementation of decision. Participation therefore, refers to the ability of individuals to make impute into the decision making process and play a vital role in improving the quality of life in the community and the society. Consequently, community development programmes involve and include job employment, identification of health needs, economic empowerment in which the people are in partnership with those able to assist them identify their needs and increasingly assume the responsibility to plan, manage, control, and assess the collective actions that are necessary for community development to strive (Esuefieni,2020).Citizens' participation becomes imperative as it can only be achieved when individuals are sensitized and informed about the need to engage in community development programmes. Adult education becomes a resource development because it is an organized learning activities arranged within an organization in order to improve performance or personal growth for the purpose of improving the job, the individual, or the society where the person lives (Bello, 2022).

Education serves as a bridge that links an individual and his community, reduces unemployment and fasten community development. Seya (2014) opts that investment in the development of human capital through education (adult education) is crucial for developing a labour force and managerial know-how able to compete to today's global economy. Invariably, adult education contributes to human capital development of individuals and instill in them managerial skills to participate in the development of their communities. Development in this instance can only be made possible if it is human centered process and this can only be achieved through adult education programmes. Adult education programmes provide literacy education, vocational skills and knowledge relevant to developing a community; this is why Okafor (2022) stated that adult education is the most needed education because it helps communities to be easily mobilized toward their development for their survival and

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their future generation. Therefore, community development as seen by Akintayo and Oghenekohwo (2004) cited in Okafor (2022) is a mechanism and a process which must arouse the interest of the community members as to participate in community development activities. The community members must be first sensitized about the need to participate in community development programme as it affects their individual and community wellbeing.

Bello (2021) states that managing adult education to achieve its set objectives and goals involve inclusiveness of the citizens to partake in the processes, programmes and activities for effective development of the individual and the community. Ebisine (2015) opts that management is the process of supervising, coordinating and organizing the activities of people in an organization to achieve results not achievable without planning, supervision, coordination, and organization. Adult education is targeted to improving adults towards acquiring vocational skills, economic empowerment; improve literacy and sustainable development which require good managers who will act as change agents. Managing community development programmes through adult education will proffer solvable solutions hindering community development and productivity due to lack of citizens' participation. Therefore, the nucleus of the study is to find out how adult education programmes will enhance citizens' participation and promote community development in Nigeria.

Adult Education Programmes in Nigeria

Adult education has been defined, seen and acknowledged by different authors, practitioners, and stakeholders based on their philosophical perspectives. Chijioko (2010) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2020) sees adult education as the practice of teaching and educating adults. Okafor and Arikawei (2020) citing Rogers opined that adult education comprises "all planned and purposeful learning opportunities offered to those who are recognized and recognize themselves as adult in their own community and in the formal (initial education system or who have passed beyond the possible state of initial education if they are not in it), whether such opportunities treat the learners as adults in decision making, use of appropriate adult learning methodology and style and purpose and to meet their own needs". In a more comprehensive definition of adult education, Seya (2014) believes that it is a transmission process of general, technical or vocational knowledge, as well as skills, values and attitudes, which takes place out of the formal education system with a view to remedying early education inadequacies of matured people or equipping them with the knowledge and cultural elements required for their self-fulfillment and active participation in the social, and community development amongst others.

Adult education as an academic field of study is saddled with the responsibility of solving socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems. According to Owede (2022) adult education offers opportunities that help adult learners to acquire relevant knowledge and skills including information and attitudinal change for immediate application to address prevailing human and community development problems. Adult education is a veritable instrument for transmitting knowledge, competences and skills. It is also an empowerment that promotes self-determined bottom-up development of communities and individuals through active citizenship and social inclusion. Therefore, adult education fills the inadequacies or lack of education. Education and mostly adult education is a path to enlightenment and plays a key role in improving the functional role of individuals in a community (Okafor and Arikawei, 2020).

Knowles, Elwood and Swanson (2015) adduce that the dynamics of adult education (through non-formal) lays in the potentials of social transformation to individual beneficiaries in character, skills, literacy, political participation and community development activities. In his own assertion Asiyai (2015) states that obtaining a quality education is the foundation to improving citizens' lives and sustainable development as it is only quality education that can sharpen the minds of the individuals and helps transform the society economically, socially and politically. In this circumstance, Hussain (2013) opts that adult education programmes (community development inclusive) confirm increased levels of self-esteem and high levels of knowledge and skills which encourage positive and active engagement of people in their own development and wellbeing. Adult education should be transformed and managed to incorporate citizens' participation and engagement in community development of their communities. It is a human driving force geared toward solving the numerous cultural, political, educational, and socio-economic problems hindering human development. For Onyenemezu (2012), education is a means to provide a balanced individual capable of surviving in his environment and contributing meaningfully towards the survival of that society he belongs. Therefore, it becomes a tool that equip individual to improve himself and make him socially and politically relevant.

It is in this regard that Ekuri, Betiang, Andong and Eyam (2022) state that adult education is the fertilizer needed for development and democracy to take root and grow. It is the invisible ingredient in any successful strategy for eradicating poverty, illiteracy, superstition, and achieving gender equality. It is a mechanized instrument that exposes and empowers beneficiaries to be on their own, contribute towards their children education and mostly participate in community development

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(Ekuri et. al., 2022). It proffers solutions to all human socio-economic, political, religious, and community underdevelopment. Adult education is an education that is programmed to conscientize, sensitize and re-direct adults of a community towards solving their immediate problems for community wellbeing and development.

Community Development Programmes in Nigeria

The term community development has been a concept since the beginning of the world. It is a process where community members come together to identify their felt-needs, partake in community participation and engagement, assemblage of human, financial and material resources towards solving the identified felt-needs for community welfare and upliftment. It is on this premise that Frank and Smith (2013) see it as a gathering where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) citing Chukwueze submitted that development programme is a process whereby the efforts of the community are combined with the efforts of the governmental authorities to improve the living condition of the people thereby encouraging development of various human potentials within the community. According to Powell and Geoghegan cited in Okafor (2022) community development is described as an interactive process of knowledge and action designed to change conditions which marginalize communities and groups and is underpinned by a vision of self-help and community self-reliance. It is because community development has been a process since the beginning of the world that Onyekwelu (2018) states that there has being vigorous indigenous efforts to improve the welfare of the communities in various parts of the country with little dependent on the government or donor agencies. It shows that community development does not thrive on individuals, government, and, or, donor agencies but identified felt-needs of the community. This captures community development as a phenomenal mechanism and a system which must promote the interest of the community members to participate in community development.

Obeta and Charity (2012) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) submitted that substantial participation and sustained interest could only be achieved through community development efforts of the people and in direct consonance with the people's social, cultural, and religious values. In another development Etigbamo (2013) believes that it is a deliberate plan of action undertaken by an individual or group of persons with the active participation of the members of the community with or without the support of external agencies in order to bring about economic, social, political, technological, and cultural improvements in the overall living condition of the people of the community. In this narrative, community development is aimed at providing and promoting better living conditions for the entire community members, relying on their resources, initiatives and active involvement and engagement. To enhance participation towards development, a systematic policy of mobilization of the community people in the developmental outlook is imperative. The focus on active participation, involvement, and engagement of people on the issues which affect their lives; should be directed towards encouraging empowerment, self-help, and sharing skill, knowledge and experience (Okafor and Onukwu, 2020).

Therefore, community development becomes a strategy or approach for improvement that is directed towards the upliftment of community members to a better living. Community development provides better living standard to the people. It is on this base that Okafor (2022) citing Sander opined that community development is a process moving from stage to stage, a method of working towards a goal; a programme of procedures and as a movement sweeping people up in emotion and belief. He argued that community development means better living both materially and socially. He further stated that it is a process whereby people are taught to improve themselves not only by doing things together but also by planning together with a view to providing the actual technique for doing the job or finding suitable solution to their problems. In these circumstances therefore, community development can be conceptualized as a change process causing improvement to life activities and programmes, and social relations that aim to meeting the needs and aspirations of people of similar historical and cultural heritage living together to reduce complete dependence on external sustainability (Bello,2022).

Community development is one major modern traditional heritage in Africa, Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008) as cited in Etigbamo (2020) agree that it is a flourishing heritage in African societies involving community citizen engagement. They stated that it is an indigenous mechanism and technique developed and employed by the people to identify their felt-needs, choose what they want and take cooperative actions to satisfy their needs. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) opt that community development relies on the interaction between people's joint actions rather than individual activities. This is the reason why development involves active participation of all the citizens within the community. Therefore community development becomes a process whereby people are taught to improve themselves not only by doing things together but also by planning together with a view to providing the actual technique for doing the job or finding suitable solution to their problems (Bello, 2022).

Community Development Programmes for Productivity in Nigeria

Community development as a component unit of adult education is very useful for sustainable development of any community, society or nation. The developmental programmes which enhance citizens' productivity are various but not limited to these: literacy education, vocational acquisition skills, community education, agricultural extension education, cooperative societies, health education, amongst others.

Literacy Education:

literacy education is an inseparable part of development and the rights of every citizen. The ability of every individual to acquire the skills of reading, writing, and computation transform and mobilize the people to participate actively in their self-help projects which transform to national development. According to Bello (2022) citing Imhabekhai the desire and ability to read, write, and compute materials promote productivity and enhance development in any society. It enables the recipients (adults) to understand higher concepts of development and productivity which maintain a sustainable community development.

Vocational Education:

Adult vocational education is conceived in the context that at the end of the training the beneficiaries must have successfully acquire a skill which will enable them (adults) to be self-sustaining and, or improve their productivity where such adults are employed. This is why Egunu, Akpotohwo and Ogeibiri (2017) believe that it is designed to prepare individual or skilled personnel for an occupation, a trade or a job. Therefore, vocational education is tailored to enhance citizens' engagement and participation for productivity at the end of programme participation.

Community Education:

Community education programme is hinged on the premise that the consciousness of people themselves plays a vital role in affecting positive change (Bello, 2022). He maintained that community education will affect change in attitude, skill, ways of participating in community development programmes and knowledge of contemporary issues. Bello (2022) opts that it is educational process that involves community mobilization for development and sustains wellbeing of the people.

Agricultural Extension Education:

Most communities in Nigeria are mostly subsistence farmers who hardly produce enough for family consumption due to analog equipment and lack of modern mechanized method of farming. In order to change this crude method of farming, Bello (2022) citing Ezimah states that agricultural extension education service provides a sound base for rural development. He maintained that extension is conceived as the development of the individual, community members, and the rural society as a continuous education process for productivity and better living of the citizens.

Health Education:

The most significant ingredience for any development is health. It is therefore one of the cardinal required basic social needs of the rural communities. This is because health services have being the driving force for community development. Health education becomes imperative for health delivery designed to mobilize the rural citizens to participate and cooperate in the task of health care delivery for community development (Nnabuihe, Emenike and Odunze, 2017). In view of the importance of community health services and development, Ibama and Dennis (2016) opt that community health and natural development are inextricably tied together, in which the evaluation of national development cannot be complete without community health component. Health education is primarily meant to cater for the health existence of the citizens, which will increase their effective participation in national life and their increased productive capacity.

Cooperative Societies:

Cooperative societies are important tools for real transformation of communities. They assist members to pull their resources together hence ensuring sustainable business enterprise and wellbeing of the people. Bello (2022) citing Dokubo says that it is very essential that cooperators work with other like-minded people in groups to make a meaningful achievement not only satisfying the basic human needs but also raising the conditions of living of the rural people to acceptable standards. According to Baarda in Bello (2022) cooperative societies is a collective action in which individuals join together to accomplish

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what would be more costly or impossible to achieve individually. Cooperative organizations by their nature serve as an effective development vehicle; they build economic self-reliance and development (Akpan, 2015).

Managing Adult Education and Community Development for Citizens' Participation in Nigeria

Management is the whole process which involves the control of human, material and financial resources to achieve a set goal and objectives. Okafor and Onukwu (2020) cited Nigeria Institute of Management stated that management is the process of planning, organizing, leading, controlling, directing, staffing, and channeling efforts and resources to achieve planned goals. In another development, Bayefa (2020) citing Peretomode opined that management is the guidance, leadership and control of the efforts of a group of people towards some common objectives. Okafor and Onukwu (2020) see management of education (adult education inclusive) as a process of human engineering of a leader with the capacity to produce and nourish ideas, stipulate thought, motivate action, introduce and manage resources and change in education. They further stated that management of adult education implies holding and practicing managerial skills, determination and courage in taking responsibility for the implementation of changes that trigger progress, development and performance in the process of training adult learners towards community engagement and participation. Therefore, managing adult education requires all-inclusive citizens' participation in order to achieve the goal of community development. The goal of citizen participation is to move from where one is to where one wants to be in terms of sustainable community development and wellbeing.

Development either political, social, economic, and or educational cannot take place without basic education. Education as a social amenity must be accessible, free and at the reach of both the young, and the old so that they can play their developmental role. It is due to the imperative nature of development that Adekola and Abanum in Okafor and Arikaiwei (2020) state that the only difference between the developed and undeveloped countries are related to the level of literacy among the populace. Therefore, for the citizens to participate actively in community development, they must be integrated in decision making, planning, execution, and at the same time must have acquired certain degree of education. The most adoring and interesting aspect of education as stated by Gbesoevi (2019) is that education is a process of training and developing the knowledge, skill, mind and character of people. He further stated that education can as well be seen as the process by which latent abilities of individual are developed so that they can be useful to themselves and the society at large. It is an institution that enables individuals to think freely and rationally which makes social progress, development and innovation possible.

Seya (2014) opines that investment in the development of human capital through adult education is crucial for developing a labour force and managerial know-how able to compete in today's global economy. Adult education as an educational institution helps to instill in the citizens managerial skills which enable adults or the beneficiaries to participate in the development of their communities. Education (formal, informal and non-formal) is the best option for developing a community using the citizens. In this circumstance adult education is the most needed education due to it helps community citizens to be easily mobilized and conscientized towards contributing in their own development for their survival and their future generation (Okafor, 2022). Community development as one of the principles of community felt-need must be made all citizens' inclusiveness if it is made human- centered programme.

The concept of citizens' participation states that people are ready and willing to participate in activities and projects that will help them improve their lives and the community. Citizens' participation is a systematic way of freely involving community members to identify and profile solutions to their needs and that of their communities. McCloskey, et al (2015) posits that participation involves planning, generation of ideas, decision making, and sharing responsibility to community members. This is why Kobani and Alozie (2019) believe that community development is channeled towards enhancing people's capacity to solve their problems through organizational structures that promote citizens' voluntary participation in self- help projects. Adult education comes handy because it is a veritable instrument to promote a sense of cohesion, purpose, and achievement among members of the community (Babatunde, 2022).

Community as a legal entity is made up of man (youths, women and men) and development cannot be possible without the active involvement, engagement and participation of all the citizens. It is a pretense, according to (Emeh, Eluwa and Ukah, 2012) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) to believe that development could occur in a community without active engagement of the people, particularly the large number of citizens who reside in the community. Abiona (2009), Imhabekhai (2009) and Okafor and Onukwu (2022) opined that the principle of citizen's participation is the hub of all other principles of community development. They further stated that the principle implies that the people in the community should take part in the identification of needs, planning, execution, utilization and evaluation of programmes and projects. Therefore community development could be a mirage without the collective involvement, engagement, and participation of citizens towards solving their felt-need. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) argued that substantial participation and sustained interest in community

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development could only be achieved based on educational, cultural, and religious values of the people. To enhance participation, mobilization and engagement towards community development, a systematic policy of mobilizing the citizens in the development outlook is imperative. It is therefore, a process moving from stage to stage; a method of working towards a goal, a programme of procedure, and as a movement sweeping people up in emotion and belief (Okafor, 2022).

Owede (2022) insists that adult education plays a key role in sustainable development and promotes economic, social, and environmental dimensions of community development creating a favourable conditions for empowering active citizens. This is as a result of the functionality of adults as managers of resources (human and material) which are dependent on knowledge and skills which can be properly provided by adults and adult education programmes (Rogers, 2016). Adult education is a trigger of human development and sustainable development in both communities and on any other levels.

Conclusion

Citizens' participation in any development programme is vital for productivity and sustainability. This is because community development is one sure way of improving the overall living conditions of the citizens in any society especially those in the rural communities. Adult education which is one of the components of education encourages citizens on the need for community participation, enhances citizens' skills and knowledge, mobilizes and sensitizes the populace on the way to manage and improve their human, material and financial resources towards the betterment of individuals and their communities. It also highlights and enlightens the citizens on some of the community development programmes such like literacy education, vocational training, skill acquisition, and health education amongst others which promote productivity and wellbeing of the people. Hence, the need for all citizens of a community to be actively involved from the planning stage to the physical execution of community felt-projects to ensure completion and sustainability of community development programmes.

Recommendations

Based on the reviewed literature, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is the need for all-inclusiveness of the adult citizens to participate in community development programmes in their communities to enhance productivity and wellbeing.
2. Education in Nigeria is so broad that there is a need that Ministry of Adult Education be created to take over the management and administration of adult education programmes in Nigeria.
3. The utilitarian value and nature of adult education in improving the living standard of adults, reduction of poverty, ignorance and illiteracy among others cannot be overemphasized. Therefore, there is the need for adults to be conscientized and sensitized to participate actively in adult education programmes in Nigeria.
4. Adult education professionals and qualified adult educators should be engaged to manage and administer community development programmes for community sustainable development.

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Overview of Qualitative Study on Trafficking in Persons: Implication for National Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper deals with overview of qualitative study on trafficking in persons (TIP) and implication for national development in Nigeria. The incidence of human trafficking involving many Nigerians began in 1990s as a result of the decline in the economy of the country and consequent increase in unemployment, poverty, inflation, low wages and general social misery among the masses. This paper therefore highlights poverty, bad leadership, corruption and cultural practices as some of the causes of TIP; and identified the socio-economic consequences and the implication on national development. The paper concludes that the Nigerian government should swiftly endeavour to address the issue of massive unemployment and poverty in the state as well as create enabling environments for entrepreneurship for the citizenry; also the national laws, international conventions and protocols that have legal potencies to curb trafficking must be implemented or strengthened; and finally, fighting human trafficking in Nigeria requires more efforts to create public awareness of the crime, organize counseling, rehabilitation and re-integration program for the victims. The paper therefore recommends that there is need to alleviate poverty among Nigerian families as a way of stemming the tide of human trafficking in the country. It is widely believed that poverty is at the root cause of women and children trafficking in Nigeria society.

Keywords: Trafficking in Person, Consequences, Implication, National, Development

Introduction

Trafficking in persons also known as human trafficking has been a lucrative trade for centuries, but recent opportunities created by globalization have contributed to an increase in the numbers of persons trafficked in Nigeria. The issue of human cross border trafficking is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon involving multiple stakeholders at the institutional and commercial level. Human trafficking is a demand-driven global business with a huge market for cheap labour which is often confronted with insufficient or unexercised policy framework or trained personnel to prevent it. Virtually no country in Africa is immune from trafficking. It has taken many forms, but in the context of globalization, has acquired shocking new dimensions. It is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon involving multiple stakeholders at the institutional and commercial level. Trafficking in person has become a major issue in the world today because people are not commodities and should not be sold and also because of the inhuman treatment meted to victims. All over the world trafficking in person exists. It is prevalent in Asia, Latin America, South America and Africa. Slavery, the precursor of human trafficking became an issue in the 19th century following advances in transportation and technology, which resulted in increasing rates of migration. With industrialization came the migration of people from rural to urban areas. Technological advances of 19th century helped to bring about the new and greater international mobility of labour and this made it possible for traffickers to react quickly to the growing demand for sex trade and cheap labour (Badejo, 2016 in Eze&Oli, 2021). The beginning of mass migration and technological development is significant because it is a trend that has continued to the present. Technological advancement and globalisation enabled and encouraged people to migrate to places with better economic and social opportunities. This means that as many people migrate legally, many were forced to migrate illegally in form of human trafficking. Advances in technology and globalisation also made it easier and more efficient for those involved in the trafficking process to network and operate more efficiently.

Nigeria is rich in resources, but political instability and widespread corruption have facilitated trafficking in persons and hindered national development. Nigeria acts as a source, transit and destination country for trafficking men, women and children to Europe, the Middle East and other countries (Mashil, 2005). Nigeria also has acquired a reputation for being one of the leading African countries in human trafficking with cross border and internal trafficking. The Nigerian women, men and children are taken from Nigeria to other countries and they are subjected to hazardous jobs (UNESCO, 2006). The phenomenon

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of trafficking in person in Nigeria especially of young boys, girls, children and women into exploitative sexual and forced labour, has recently began to attract local, national, regional and international attention from world leaders, academics, the mass media, advocacy groups, the clergy and humanity in general. Human trafficking, like money laundering, advanced fee fraud, cyber scams and illicit trade in arms and narcotics has elicited a great concern as a contemporary social problem worldwide (Poulin, 2004).

Human trafficking for the purposes of sexual and other forms of exploitation has become a global business reaping huge profits for traffickers and organized crime syndicates, causing flagrant human rights violations and creating serious problems for governments across the globe. Trafficking in persons represents the world's third largest area of organized crime – after drugs and arms trade. It is an illicit trade that is unbearable to the human heart. The two methods used by traffickers to get their victims are deception and through force. Human trafficking for the purposes of sexual and other forms of exploitation has become a global business reaping huge profits for traffickers and organized crime syndicates, causing flagrant human rights violations and creating serious problems for governments across the globe. Trafficking in persons represents the world's third largest area of organized crime – after drugs and arms trade. It is an illicit trade that is unbearable to the human heart. Trafficking in persons is inhuman, immoral and an offence under the laws. (UNHCR, 2000). The United States government considers trafficking in person to include all the criminal conduct involved in forced labour and sex trafficking, essentially the conduct involved in reducing or holding someone in compelled service (United States Department Report, 2013). Nigeria is a transit and destination country for men, women and children subjected to trafficking in persons, specifically conditions to forced labour and forced prostitution. Trafficked Nigerian men, women and children are recruited from rural areas within the country's borders – women and girls for involuntary domestic servitude and forced commercial sexual exploitation, and boys for forced labour in street vending, domestic servitude, mining, and begging. The children are subjected to domestic servitude, forced labour, sexual slavery through forced marriages and suicide attacks in Nigeria. Within Nigeria, girls are trafficked primarily for domestic servitude and commercial sexual exploitation. Boys are trafficked for forced labour in street vending, agriculture, and as domestic servants. Islamic religious teachers also traffic boys called Almajiri for forced begging (United States Department Report, 2009) Besides prostitution, forced marriage and forced labour, some of the victims are used for rituals, begging and even for organ transplanting (Ndifon, Apori&Ndifon, 2012) Nigerian women and children are taken from Nigeria to Europe, Arabian countries and African countries, primarily Libya, Gabon, Cameroon, Ghana, Chad, Benin, Togo, Niger, Burkina Faso, and the Gambia, for the same purposes. But the recent economic crisis, poverty, social and political conflicts, insurgency, natural disasters and the contemporary climate change have profoundly influenced the alarming dimension with which people are being pulled-up as clients for human traffickers (UNHCR, 2000) It should be pointed out that many are of the opinion that poor economic conditions in Nigeria which concomitantly led to poverty among large concentration of the population. These socio-economic factors coupled with socio-cultural factors such as the breakdown of the extended family system, gender inequality, child fosterage, high fertility and population growth, the widening gap between the rich and the poor, break-down of societal values amongst others, seems to account for trafficking in person in Nigeria. In addition, human trafficking exposes some Nigerian citizens to all forms of inhuman treatment in foreign countries. These include physical assault, rape, detention and in some extreme cases execution. Many Nigerians are also known to be languishing in prisons in some countries of the world due to the misadventure associated with human trafficking. Dangerous journeys expose trafficked victims to injury and even death. While overcrowded and unhealthy conditions, lack of food and water increase the risk of spreading infectious diseases. Finally, human trafficking creates an environment of violence, crime and fear, separates families, destroys social bonds and support networks, and undermines the economic prospects of the country. It equally gives rise to frequent deportation of Nigerian citizens from foreign countries with its associated diplomatic implications.

The menace of human trafficking in Nigerian state has taken an indescribable facet in the last two decades owing to the factors of; massive unemployment, poverty, recession in the economy, conflicts, globalization, existing weak legal system, and inadequate legislation, and political will. Efforts have been made by Nigerian government to tackle this menace of trafficking in person, for instance, Nigeria ratified most of the important international instruments fighting human trafficking and protecting women and children. Among them are the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (2000) and the Palermo Protocol in 2001, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Optional Protocol to it on the Sale of Children. Nigeria enacted the Trafficking in Persons (prohibition) Law Enforcement and Administration Act 2003 and Child Rights Act 2003 (Huntley, 2013). The National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) and other related matters was established to combat human trafficking. However, these initiatives, human trafficking remains a critical problem in Nigeria thus, paints a bad picture of Nigeria in the international community. Despite Nigeria's legislative efforts to combat trafficking, it still thrives in Nigeria. One is of the opinion that there are negative consequences if

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the able body men, women and children are trafficked out of the country and will have compelling effects on socio-economic that have far reaching outcomes on humanity and the society. In actual fact, the physical torture and abuse of victims from the emotional and psychological ordeal witnessed or gone through by victims in the hands of traffickers, and the attendant impacts on such individuals and society are evidently destructive. It is against this background that the paper focused on the overview of qualitative study on trafficking in persons (TIP) and implication for national development in Nigeria.

Concepts of Trafficking in Persons in Nigeria

A more recent but aptly coined term for human trafficking is the nomenclature, 'trafficking in persons.' There is a national government agency that is saddled with the responsibility of prohibiting trafficking in persons in Nigeria. It is known as National Agency for Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP). The concept of Trafficking in Person is defined as all and attempted acts involved in the recruitment, transportation within or across nation's borders, purchases, sales, transfer, receipt or harbouring of a person involving the use of deception, coercion or debt bondage for the purpose of placing or holding the persons, whether for or not involuntary servitude (domestic, sexual or reproductive) in forced or bonded labour, or in slavery-like conditions. In the same vein, human trafficking according to Article 3(a) of the United Nations Palermo Protocol is conceptualized as recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, and receipt of persons, by means of threat, use of force and other forms of coercion. It also entails use of abduction, fraud, deception, the abuse of power in giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person for the purpose of exploitation (United Nations Palermo Protocol, 2000). Also, UNESCO (2006) on trafficking in person defined it to be a process which involves the exploitation of a vulnerable person through recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, abduction, fraud, deception and abuse of power.

Trafficking in Persons is a relatively recent term and is used to describe the act of the acquisition or transportation of a person away from the community in which they live through the use of violence, coercion or deception for the purpose of exploiting them. In the case of children, their vulnerability is a factor, thus coercion does not have to be present. United Nations (2013) defines human trafficking in person as:

“the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, (male or female) by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power, or of a position of vulnerability, or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include at a minimum the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the renewal of organs”.

In a similar view, Oloko cited in Okpalakunne (2006) explained that human trafficking consists of both national and trans-national recruitment and movement of persons for the purpose of providing cheap, manipulatable and exploitable labour for domestic and agricultural work, commercial sex work or prostitution, begging, unregulated industrial work and street trading. Adepelumi (2015) argues that trafficking in person is a transnational organized crime that impacts not only on the individual victims but the entire society. Trafficking either occurs within the shores of a country (internal) or outside its shores (external). Internal trafficking involves trafficking of a person from one community or village to another, within the states or outside the states. It is trafficking of persons within a country. The purpose of internal trafficking is usually for domestic labour, child labour, illicit adoption, begging, sexual exploitation, ritual, organ harvesting etc. External trafficking of persons on the other hand is carried out outside the shores of the victim's country. The menace is seen to have been undermining the national peace, development and security of Nigeria. Trafficking has become socio-economic problems of significant magnitude in Nigeria. Many writers on the subject have suggested some probable causes of this problem. There is an urgent need to determine the veracity of some of the identified causes through this paper.

The Factors Aiding Trafficking in Persons Activities in Nigeria

Socio-economic factors such as poverty, unemployment, economic downturn as the nation is currently undergoing, inadequate educational opportunities etc. fuel human trafficking. All these were the problems that confronted the victims of human trafficking that make them vulnerable to traffickers and their agents. Abiodun, Akinlade and Oladejo (2021) highlight the factor aiding trafficking of persons as follows:

1. In the first instance, victims are made to shift a base from rural areas to urban areas and this is widely known as rural-urban trafficking. Victims in this class are usually trafficked for farming purpose and also there could be rural-rural

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- trafficking a situation where traffickers convey victims from one village or rural area to another. There is also urban-urban trafficking, a situation where traffickers move their victims from one urban area to another.
2. Secondly, there exists the usual tradition of entrusting poor children to more comfortable relatives and this may generate exposure to human trafficking. This is very common in a situation whereby some parents would sell their own children, and it is not just for the monetary gains, but with thought or belief that their children would find their ways out of abject chronic poverty ravaging the land and move to a place where they would live a better life with more prospects.
 3. Also in Nigeria, these women and young girls usually fall victims of being trafficked from their original place of abode to another location or across the national borders having been lured, tricked or deceived that they would be gainfully employed and live an accomplished life. But at the end of the day, they actually get trafficked for commercial sexual exploitation and domestic servitude in foreign lands.
 4. Another striking factor responsible for human trafficking in Nigeria is abject poverty that has ravaged the land. Studies have revealed that over 10 million Nigerian girls and boys are being trafficked across the country's borders due to poverty. The victims are trafficked to different destinations which include; African states of Benin Republic, Mali, among others while the states in the Europe include; United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Germany and the United Kingdom respectively.
 5. In recent time, the World Bank report indicated that over 1.8 billion people live in the various nations prone to or engulfed in violent conflict are have been trafficked abroad. So it is established that the Boko Haram, Fulani-herdsmen crisis and armed banditry remain the push factors for trafficking in persons and migration; this is evident in a situation where young male children are being trafficked and used as soldiers and militias and young girls as sex toys by the insurgents. The kidnapped young girls are sold off into slavery and forceful marriage.
 6. In addition, there is a weak legal system in place in the country; ninety percent (90%) of Nigerian borders are porous, government officials are absolutely corrupt in all ramifications, while a large number of Nigerian youths also belong to the various international organized criminal syndicates or networks while the limited capacity or commitment by immigration and law enforcement officers to control borders remain contributory factors to the menace.
 7. There also exists lack or absence of adequate legislation and of political will on the part of Nigerian government to enforce existing legislation or mandates, Acts, and penalties for trafficking offenders that could prohibit all forms of human trafficking.

Causes of Trafficking in Person (Tip) in Nigeria

Trafficking becomes more worsened by conflicts, natural disasters, socio-economic problems, among others, thereby pushing people to seek greener pastures or migrate to other locations for survival (Dodo, 2012). In addition, there are other macro-level reasons or factors associated with human trafficking which include: abject poverty, wars, economic injustice, globalized of the consumer markets, global sex tourism, among others while the micro-level risk factors entail: child abuse and neglect, family breakdown, poor family relations, mental illness, child homelessness, among others (Dodo, 2012).

1. **Poverty:** Poverty is a state of being poor or lack of basic necessities of live. Poverty can make people vulnerable to human trafficking and child labour. Parents may give up their children to be taken to cities and work as house helps. Some parents may even sell their children totally into slavery while others go to cities or travel abroad to engage in prostitution in order to make money. Apart from poverty, many of the victims of human trafficking abroad particularly women and girls are ignorance of the fate that await them in their country of destination. The situation is such that many of the women and girls had little or no education hence they are easily carried away by the picture of good lives painted by their sponsors. Particularly African and Nigerians with a large concentration of polygamous family for the purpose of egalitarian settlements in the villages and slums where means of livelihood became cumbersome, hence adolescents strive to find solace outside the home, thereby making them vulnerable to the tactics of traffickers (Rotimi, 2001)
2. **Greed and Crave for Wealth:** People who are not contented with what they have or those who want to accumulate fast wealth may find themselves engaged in human trafficking. Crave for wealth is another factor. The high propensity to acquire wealth regardless of the legality and morality of the source. Previous 'success' of some trafficked women lured some others into trafficking, unfortunately sources of those 'successes' are unknown until they become victim of prostitution. On coming back home, they were able to acquire land, buy houses, luxurious objects such as gold, necklaces, etc which they would not have been able to afford if they had remained in their villages. The illicit traffickers, on the other hand, were primarily motivated by materialism. Ofido (2000) remarked that the major underlying factor for

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- prostitution is greed. Ruth (2000) contended that the willingness of our ladies to travel abroad and offer themselves for sex trade is equally a pointed to the level of the crave by our youths to do anything for money
3. **Bad Leadership and Corruption:** The levels of bad leadership and corruption have led to increase in unemployment rate in Nigeria. To the extent that men and women chose to migrate for labour or sex work because of the realization that Europe and Western nations have a valued currency hence labour and sex will be profitable. The implication is that people choose to work in richer countries in order to improve their economic standing back in Nigeria with a hopeless economic situation. The double explanation was that while job opportunities abound for male migrants in Europe and North America, women migrants who had no access to jobs often take to prostitution as an option. Human traffickers bribe government's officials with money and material things so that they can continue to carry out their business without being caught or hindered by government. In addition to the above, our weak legal system also contributes to the cases of human trafficking. Porous borders, corrupt government officials, the involvement of international organized criminal groups or networks, capacity of or commitment by Immigration and law enforcement officers to control borders; and because of adequate legislation and a political will and commitment to enforce existing legislation or mandates are other factors that facilitate trafficking in persons.
 4. **Ignorance:** Ignorance on the part of the victims of human trafficking contributes to the prevalence of the scourge on trafficking in persons. Vulnerable members in the society can easily be deceived by human traffickers who will promise them greener pastures and better lifestyles in the cities or abroad and because everybody wants a better and improved life, they innocently follow these traffickers only to discover that their intention was to exploit and use them to make money. Some of these people may even be forced to take oaths not to disclose their secret or try to escape. Several victims of the scourge, especially boys, girls and children, have claimed ignorance of what bargain they struck until they were caught or eventually taken to Europe to engage in sex trade, illicit drugs and force labour. Ofido (2000) observed that nowadays, Nigerian boys and girls are in overseas countries, mainly Italy, France and Belgium eking out an unreasonable livelihood through prostitution and illicit drugs. She noted that most of the boys and girls were lured into the act by a carted that promised them fabulous jobs but seized their passports when they got to overseas and forced them into prostitution.
 5. **Unemployment:** This is also another reason for the increasing incidence of human trafficking involving Nigeria women and young boys. Nevertheless, the government should make deliberate efforts to humanise the societal environment through provision of gainful employment and other economic empowerment that will ensure improved living standard for the people.
 6. **War, Conflict and Natural Disaster:** During prolonged war, children are forced to join the army and are trained to carry guns and ammunitions. Although this may not be done for money, it is also a form of human trafficking e.g during the Second World War, some Africans were trafficked to Europe so as to fight in the war. Trafficking of persons, conflict and natural disaster can lead to economic instability and lack of human rights, giving traffickers an advantage and making people more vulnerable to human trafficking situations. In conflict zones and wars, some rebel or military groups will use child soldiers and keep sex slaves. Additionally, both conflict and natural disaster can lead people to migrate out of their hometowns and home countries, making them more vulnerable to traffickers, especially if they are looking for work or paying smugglers to get where they want to go. And with increased economic instability, traffickers have opportunities to offer false job offers to people, leading them into trafficking situations.
 7. **Demand for Cheap Labour/Demand for Sex:** Basic economics tell us that for a market to form, supply and demand need to exist. The demands for cheap labour and for commercialized sex lead to opportunities for traffickers to exploit people. Traffickers can make a large profit by producing goods and services through cheap or free labour and selling the products or services at a higher price. Commercialized sex is a lucrative market that allows traffickers and pimps to become the only benefits from their victims through an endless cycle of buyers and high prices.
 8. **Lack of Human Rights for Vulnerable Groups:** In many countries, groups that are marginalized in society lack institutionalized human rights, which can lead to them to be potential victims of trafficking. Traffickers can prey on these marginalized groups because they lack protection of the law enforcement, their families, and even the society they live in. Also, when countries lack fundamental laws regarding human rights, traffickers feel as though they can get away with what they are doing more easily. A lack of human rights laws can also end in punishment for victims, if the laws and government don't recognize that human trafficking is exploitation of other people.
 9. **Lack of Legitimate Economic Opportunities:** When people lack legitimate economic opportunities, which can also lead to increased vulnerability to human trafficking. Groups that are especially vulnerable in this area are migrants without

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work permits, those who lack education, those who live in rural areas where there are fewer jobs available, as well as women and certain ethnic groups who may not be able to get jobs due to discrimination. Traffickers offer seemingly legitimate jobs to people who cannot get them otherwise, only to lure them into forced labor, sex trafficking, bonded labor, and more.

10. **Social Factors and Cultural Practices:** In many countries, cultural practices and social factors are a major cause of human trafficking. In some places, bonded labor is seen as an acceptable way to pay off debt. In other places, selling children to traffickers is the norm, especially for poorer families in rural areas. Some countries, such as Mauritania, still practice antiquated slavery, where families are held for generations by slave-masters. There are also instances, like in Uzbekistan, where forced labor is institutionalized. During the cotton harvest, all adults and children are expected to work in the cotton fields until the crops are harvested. Cultural and social factors can also lead victims not to speak up about being trafficked or who their traffickers are, especially if they come from groups who lack human rights protections.
11. **Trafficking Generates a Huge Profit:** One major cause of human trafficking is the huge profit that traffickers gain. This is an incentive for them to continue trafficking people in both forced labour and sex trafficking. For traffickers using forced labourers and bonded labourers, they get cheap labour and can sell their product or service at a much higher cost. For those using sex trafficking, they can easily take all of the profit, forcing women to make a certain amount each night, and keeping them in the situation through drugs, violent force, threats, and more.
12. **Lack of Safe Migration Options:** For those looking to migrate out of their home countries due to safety concerns or economic opportunities, they are especially vulnerable to traffickers. Traffickers can use illegal smuggling as a way to trick people into forced labor or sex trafficking. And for migrants looking for jobs in other countries, traffickers typically offer them job opportunities that seem legitimate, only to force them into a trafficking situation. For instance, when Russia was preparing for the Olympics, several men from Serbia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and other nearby countries were promised construction jobs, only to be paid very little and be treated poorly. And many women from countries like Nigeria, Ukraine, and other Eastern European and African countries are offered nanny, house help or restaurant jobs in Western Europe, Asian, Saudi Arabia only to be trapped in sex trafficking and human organ harvest.
13. **Gender-based discrimination** is an all-pervasive reason why women and girls make up the majority of persons who are trafficked. Gender-based discrimination is shown by the low status of women, particularly in developing countries, the lack of education for girls, the expectation of women to perform certain roles and to be solely responsible for her children, and the discrimination against women in political participation, sexuality, religion, customs and social practices. Sexism is imbedded in all institutions of society in general, and particularly in the structure of the labour market and the job opportunities available for women. A feminist perspective to protect the rights of migrant and trafficked persons is important to ensure that responses do not work

Consequences of Trafficking in Persons (Tip) in Nigeria

The consequences of trafficking in persons can be social, political and economic. But as the main focus of this paper is the victim's perspectives, the socio-economic consequence outshines the other one. Most of Nigerians become victims of human trafficking in their process of migration to earn a better livelihood. Earning a better livelihood was an overriding factor for Nigerians' migration in general and trafficking in particular. The end result of trafficking is exploitation of victims for different purposes. Traffickers receive huge amount of money from potential victims and their families too. Trafficking in person exposed some Nigerians to all forms of inhuman treatments in foreign countries. These include physical assault, rape, physical abuse, detention, and in some extreme cases execution. Many Nigerians are also known to be languishing in prisons in some countries of the world due to the misadventure associated with human trafficking. Aondover, (2018) reports that victims are more likely to experience fear, guilt, sense of betrayal, lack of trust, suspicion, sense of apathy, shame, withdrawal, resignation to fate, hopelessness, extreme form of submissiveness, maladaptation, and a sense of loss of personal autonomy; initiative and integrity. It has given rise to frequent deportation of Nigerian citizens from foreign countries with its attendant diplomatic implications.

These consequences are categorized into:

1. **Physical injuries:** These are marks on the body, loss parts of the body. etc such as burns, bruise, wounds, cuts, dislocations etc .which are usually inflicted on the victims through physical abuse and maltreatment. It violates the human right of victims; degrading and dehumanizing. It results in loss of, or deprivation of property rights
2. **Sexual Abuse:** Human trafficking victims are likely to be sexually abused or exploited especially during the process of moving the victims from one location to another. There are usually cases of rape and sexual intercourse between some

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perpetrators and the victims. E.g., female domestic servants are turned to sex object by their master and his sons, while female master turned the male domestic servants to gigolo or sex partner.

3. **Stigmatization:** The victims of human trafficking are stigmatized when they are with their masters and even when they return home due to inhuman acts they are exposed to. In their master's house, they are seen and treated as second class citizens.
4. **Health Hazard:** Most of the victims are exposed to health hazards and challenges due to indiscriminate sex which often leads contracting Sexually Transmitted Disease and other deadly diseases like HIV/AIDS. Some may end up with health challenges due to the physical consequences of trafficking.
5. **Death:** Death is the most fatal consequence of human trafficking. Most victims, who have experienced sexual abuse, rape, and have been exposed to health hazards, may end up dying. Some may end up committing suicide.
6. **Loss of Human Resources:** The loss of youths, children, and women will have an effect on the man-power of the nation which will further affect the socio-economic development of the nation. Undermines human capital development potential and promotes money laundering and other financial crimes which can distort the economy.
7. **Separation from Loved Ones:** Children and the victims that are trafficked are separated from their loved ones, thereby denied the mutual love that is supposed to exist among the family members. This can make such victims be hostile in the near future.
8. **Crime:** One of the social consequences is a high rate of crime. The victims due to lack of proper upbringing can get involved in criminal acts such as armed robbery, cultism, prostitution, unruly behavior etc thereby causing social problem in the society. It can bring about a negative image of the country. As an organized crime, it can diversify into other types of crimes like drug trafficking and arm smuggling;
9. **Fear and Anxiety:** These acts of moving people usually bring fear and anxiety hereby causing insecurity in society.
10. **Migration:** Human trafficking involves the movement of people, this brings about migration which in effect populates the urban areas and depopulate the rural areas
11. **Social Disorder:** Victims of human trafficking became maladjusted in society, meaning they fail to cope with the demands of a normal social environment. It can yield future insecurity through social breakdown and exclusion

Human trafficking has negative consequences on individual, mainly the victims and the society in general.

Conclusion

The problem of trafficking in person has persisted in Nigeria despite several campaigns, conferences, workshops, and seminars organized by the government and NGOs to curb the menace. The menace of trafficking in person is damaging, disastrous and devastating to the victims, the family and the society at large. In view of the pervasive and penetrative effects and consequences trafficking in persons on Nigeria and Nigerians, there is need for a continuous synergy of efforts to curb the menace.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should intensify public awareness campaigns on child trafficking by organizing sensitization programmes such as workshops, seminars and campaigns to educate and enlighten both parents and children on the social, emotional and psychological consequences of child trafficking on the victims.
2. Government in particular should make the country attractive to citizens especially the youths through qualitative public education, job creation and provision of social infrastructures, which often constitute the push factor for emigration.
3. Government should also take positive steps to provide employment opportunities for the youth, and create an enabling environment for the private sector to invest and increase employment opportunities.
4. There is need to alleviate poverty among Nigerian families as a way of stemming the tide of human trafficking in the country. It is widely believed that poverty is at the root cause of women and children trafficking in Nigeria society.
5. Ensure the activities of the NAPTIP receive sufficient funding, particularly for prosecuting trafficking offenders and providing adequate care for victims; implement programs for the disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration of former child combatants that take into account the specific needs of child ex- combatants;
6. Governments, civil-society groups and media houses can liaise to fight this crime by running special broadcasts during major, sports and entertainment events (e.g. World Cup, Cup of Nations UEFA Champions League, Miss Universe, etc.) when it is certain that a large proportion of viewers would get the message.

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Qualitative Study on Implementation of Public Primary Schools Early Childhood Care Education Programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the implementation of public primary schools early childhood care education programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design which was carried out in 12 randomly selected public primary schools in Abuja. 309 respondents were sampled using multi-stage sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was researcher adapted 40-item questionnaire titled Public Primary Schools Early Childhood Care Education Programs (PPSECCEP) with a reliability coefficient of 0.92. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. However, a key finding indicated that most parents and society lacked adequate awareness of ECCE programs' significance. While staff demonstrated necessary skills, facility provisions for program implementation were insufficient. Based on these findings, the study recommends awareness campaigns to increase parental and societal support, staff incentives to enhance service delivery, and regular facility assessments to address resource gaps.

Keywords: Early Childhood Program, Effectiveness, Examined, Implementation & Primary Schools

Introduction

In our daily observations of children, we can identify childhood as the time when we are not responsible for anything and rely on adults for protection and care. It is also the period we learn mostly through play and imitation. The childhood stage begins at birth and lasts until puberty, usually between 10 and 12 years of age. As society's ideas about childhood change over time, research has led to a better understanding of each stage's development. Childhood period has been universally acknowledged as a period when development of an individual is most crucial. Early childhood comprises a number of life stages, marked by developmental milestones. Early childhood is a time of bridge building. It is a time in a child's life when bridges are built between the shelter of home and the demands of the school; between play with a few neighborhood friends and relationship with many children. It is that period of human development which falls between birth to eight years (birth-8 years). The time from birth to eight years is a critical period in the development of many foundational skills in all areas of development. This is the time when environmental enrichment or deprivation makes its greatest impact. It is a period marked with significant changes and reorganizations in the child's behaviour. At this period a lot of changes and progress are made in terms of learning, reasoning and in the child's social relationship with others. It is indeed the period the child gains a sense of self-worth, or lack of it, and confidence, or lack of confidence, as he experiences success or failure in everyday contacts.

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Early childhood education as contained in the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004) is the education given in an educational institution to children prior to their entering the primary school. Maduwesi (1999) as cited by Ogunode et al. (2021) defines early childhood education as a semi-formal education arrangement, usually outside the home, whereby young children from about the age of three are exposed, through play-like activities in a group setting, to mental, social and physical learning suited to their developmental stage, until the mandatory age of government approved formal schooling. In the same vein, several other terms used to describe early childhood education include nursery school, pre-primary and pre-school. Oduolowu (2003) as cited by Okewole (2009) asserted that early childhood education is part and parcel of education program or package whether formal or informal of every culture. Some schools of thought opined that early childhood education is universal; and that there is no society where human beings exist without early childhood education. Akinola (2004) sees it as the education given in an educational institution to children aged three to five plus prior to entering the primary education. Early Childhood Education is a term that has a scope that varies and is often linked to geographical locations. Different definitions focus on different aspects of the educational experience. Some emphasize the age range of the children involved, while others place more importance on the environment in which the education is delivered. Still others combine both of these elements. Generally, Early Childhood Education refers to pre-school or pre-primary education that is delivered outside of the home in a semi-formal setting. This can include programs like crèches, daycares, nurseries, and kindergartens, and is typically designed for children between the ages of 0 and 5 years.

ECCE is a special field of education for development of children. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) recognizes the importance of ECCE and thereafter, began to explore ways of implementing the Early Childhood Care Education for general development of the child. The purposes of ECCE as stipulated in the National Policy on Education by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013:5) include: to effect a smooth transition from home to the school, prepare the child for the primary level of education, provide adequate care and supervision for the children while their parents are at work, inculcate social norms in the children, inculcate in the children the spirit of enquiry and creativity through the exploration of nature, environment, art, music and playing, develop a sense of co-operation and team spirit, learn good habits, especially good health habits, and teach the rudiments of numbers, letters, colours, shapes and forms through play. These objectives must be implemented in the schools by ECCE proprietors and society.

On this background, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in Nigeria, with both public and private primary schools incorporating ECCE in their school programs. ECCE refers to a range of services and programs that are designed to promote the development of young children, from birth to age 8, in all areas of their lives, including physical, emotional, social, and cognitive development. While the incorporation of ECCE in primary schools is a positive development, it is not clear whether these ECCE centers are operating within the context of the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) curriculum. The NERDC is the body responsible for developing and implementing curriculum guidelines for all levels of education in Nigeria, including ECCE. The lack of clarity regarding the implementation of ECCE curriculum in Nigeria is a cause for concern. The quality of early childhood education is crucial, as it can have a significant impact on a child's development and future academic success. If ECCE centers are not operating within the context of the NERDC curriculum, there may be inconsistencies in the quality of early childhood education provided to children across the country. To address this issue, the thrust of this study is to assess the qualitative implementation of public primary schools early childhood care education programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The study aims to identify gaps in the implementation of ECCE policies, assess the quality of early childhood education provided, and provide recommendations to improve the quality of ECCE in Nigeria.

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) has been identified as a vital component of educational development in Nigeria. Over the years, there has been a growing emphasis on the importance of ECCE in Nigeria as it is believed to play a significant role in laying the foundation for future learning and development (FRN 2012). Of recent, it should be noted that both public primary schools and private primary schools in Nigeria incorporate ECCE in school programs. However, it is not certain whether these ECCE centres are operating within the context of the National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) curriculum. The Nigerian government recognizes the importance of ECCE and has put in place policies and frameworks to promote its implementation (FRN 2013). The Federal Ministry of Education has developed the National Policy on Education, which recognizes ECCE as an integral part of the education system. The policy recommends that ECCE should be provided for children between the ages of 0-5 years (FME, 2013). Furthermore, the National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) has also developed a curriculum for ECCE (UNESCO, 2007). The curriculum is designed to provide a comprehensive framework for the development of children in the areas of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor

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domains. The curriculum covers various aspects of child development such as language, literacy, numeracy, science, social studies, creative arts, and physical education.

Despite the existence of these policies and frameworks, there are still gaps in the implementation of ECCE in Nigeria (Akinrotimi & Olowe, 2016). One of the major challenges is the lack of adequate funding for ECCE programs (Amadi, 2013). Many ECCE centres are poorly equipped (Akinrotimi & Olowe, 2016), and teachers are often poorly trained (Olaleye & Omotayo, 2009), which affects the quality of the education provided. In addition, there is a lack of awareness among parents and society about the importance of ECCE, which often leads to low enrollment rates. Many parents in Nigeria still believe that the primary responsibility of childcare and early education lies with the family and not with the school.

Against this background, a comprehensive ECCE curriculum was designed for implementation to equip the children with the desired skills needed for effective primary education and social life. And it is however uncertain whether these schools are implementing the curriculum. It is on this premise that the thrust of this paper is predicated to assess the effectiveness of the implementation of public primary schools' early childhood care education program in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study is undertaken to:

1. Investigate the extent to which ECCE programs benefit public primary school children in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
2. Determine the level of adequate awareness among parents and society regarding the importance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
3. Explore the extent to which staff possesses the necessary skills to effectively implement the ECCE program in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
4. Ascertain the level of the availability and adequacy of the facilities required for the implementation of the ECCE program in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent does an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
2. To what extent do parents and society lack adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
3. To what extent does staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
4. What is the level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is descriptive survey research. The study population comprised head teachers, classroom teachers, parents of early childhood education centers, and Ministry of Education officials in Abuja. According to the Open Education Data (2023), there are 1573 schools that include nursery and primary levels in Abuja, Nigeria. However, the target population for this study consisted all the 597 Public Primary Schools in Abuja, the sample for the study comprised 309 respondents (www.raosoft.com/samplesizecalculator), consisting of 72 head teachers, 144 classroom teachers, 144 parents of early childhood education pupils, and 21 Ministry of Education officials (state the academic session). A multistage sampling technique was adopted to select the sample for the study. The researcher selected 12 public ECCE schools from each stratum (from each Local Government in Abuja) using stratified random sampling technique, from a total of 36 public ECCE schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. From each school selected, 4 head teachers and 8 classroom teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique based on their qualifications as experts in early childhood education, while 4 parents were selected using accidental sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 21 State Ministry of Education officials.

The research instrument for this study was questionnaire adapted by the researcher. The instrument was given to the experts in early childhood education to establish the content validity while experts in test development were consulted for construct validity. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instrument. In computing the reliability of this research instrument, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instrument, the instrument was administered to 40 stakeholders comprising 10 head teachers, 10 ministry officials, 10 classroom

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teachers and 10 parents. Their responses to the items on this instrument were used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which yielded a reliability of 0.92. Descriptive analysis was employed to analyze the data collected for this study. Specifically, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the raised research question.

Results

Research Question 1:

To what extent does an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the extent an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	ECCE programs offer the opportunity to socialize with peers and adults.		2.65	0.74	Agreed
2.	Children learn how to interact with others in ECCE centers.		2.71	0.58	Agreed
3.	Children develop social and emotional skills such as empathy, self-awareness, and emotional regulation in ECCE centers.		2.68	0.71	Agreed
4.	ECCE programs provide opportunities to develop cognitive skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and language development.		2.53	0.80	Agreed
5.	ECCE programs laying the foundation for academic success later on.		2.89	0.46	Agreed
6.	ECCE programs promote physical health through healthy meals, opportunities for physical activity, and health screenings.		2.51	0.49	Agreed
7.	ECCE programs develop child pre-academic skills such as numeracy, literacy, and fine motor skills.		2.97	0.64	Agreed
8.	ECCE programs expose children to different cultures, languages, and perspectives, promoting cultural awareness and appreciation.		2.50	0.66	Agreed
9.	ECCE programs foster creativity by providing opportunities for imaginative play, artistic expression, and critical thinking.		2.52	0.50	Agreed
10.	ECCE programs support language development, an essential skill for academic success and communication.		2.70	0.61	Agreed

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the extent to which ECCE programs benefit public primary school children in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The results indicate that respondents perceive these programs as beneficial, with all mean scores (\bar{X}) exceeding the criterion mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 for the 10 items. Notably, no item fell below this criterion. The consistency of responses, reflected by small standard deviation values, suggests a high level of agreement among respondents. Overall, this translates to a decision level of 'great extent,' suggesting the ECCE program is highly beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Research Question 2:

To what extent do parents and society lack adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

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Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the extent parents and society adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	ECCE is a term every parent is familiar with.		2.01	1.16	Disagreed
2.	Early childhood education is considered to be very important for young children		2.22	1.02	Disagreed
3.	Young children need early childhood education to develop properly.		1.93	1.05	Disagreed
4.	The long-term effects of ECCE on their child's education and future success are known by parents and society.		1.88	1.11	Disagreed
5.	Parents and society are being educated on how ECCE can support their child's cognitive growth.		2.10	1.23	Disagreed
6.	The significance of ECCE in laying the foundation for child's academic success is recognized by parents and society.		2.12	0.90	Disagreed
7.	Parents and society know the different ECCE programs available and which ones are best suited for child's needs.		1.85	1.01	Disagreed
8.	Parents and society are well-informed about the importance of high-quality ECCE programs for their child.		2.00	1.41	Disagreed
9.	The roles of ECCE in child development are known by parents and society.		1.54	0.42	Disagreed
10.	The value of ECCE in enhancing child's social and emotional development is appreciated to a sufficient extent by parents and society.		1.99	0.67	Disagreed

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The mean and standard deviation of responses to a 10-item survey were presented in table 2. The findings revealed that the respondents did not perceive parents and society to be sufficiently aware of the importance of ECCE programs, as indicated by mean scores (\bar{X}) that were lower than the criterion mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 for all items. None of the mean scores (\bar{X}) were higher than the criterion mean (\bar{X}). The low standard deviation values indicated a low variation among responses, implying that to a great extent the majority of parents and society lacked adequate awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja.

Research Question 3:

To what extent does staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the extent staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	The staff's have knowledge about the principles and goals of the ECCE programs.		2.51	0.60	Agreed
2.	There is confidence in staff's ability to effectively teach the curriculum of the ECCE programs.		2.73	0.63	Agreed
3.	ECCE staff have received adequate training on the specific teaching methods and techniques required for the ECCE programs.		2.88	0.78	Agreed
4.	ECCE staff are capable of creating a positive and supportive learning environment for children participating in the ECCE programs.		2.50	0.63	Agreed
5.	ECCE programs effective implementation depends on how well the staff works together as a team.		2.50	0.53	Agreed

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6.	The ECCE staff have experience working with diverse groups of children and families, as required by the ECCE programs.	2.69	0.42	Agreed
7.	The ECCE staff are familiar with and able to apply the appropriate assessment and evaluation techniques for the ECCE programs.	2.53	0.61	Agreed
8.	ECCE staff received ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs.	2.35	0.42	Disagreed
9.	ECCE staff undergo retraining professional development opportunities to upgrade their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs.	2.41	0.46	Disagreed
10.	ECCE staff is very effective in communicating and collaborating with families and society of children enrolled in the ECCE programs.	2.19	0.51	Disagreed

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The results presented in table 3 show the mean and standard deviation of respondents' opinion on the extent to which staff's possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs. The results revealed that staff have the necessary skills to implement the ECCE programs, as indicated on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. These items have their mean (\bar{X}) values greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 ($\bar{X} < 2.50$). The values of the standard deviation on the items indicate less variation in the responses of the respondents (teachers) due to the closeness of the values. Items 8, 9 and 10 had mean scores below the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 which indicates that ECCE staff do not undergo retraining professional development to upgrade their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs. This implies that the majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja.

Research Question 4:

What is the level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are adequate.		2.12	1.23	Disagreed
2.	There are no any specific facilities that are lacking for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		2.16	1.00	Disagreed
3.	I am satisfied with the quality of the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		1.90	1.24	Disagreed
4.	When implementing the ECCE programs, I faced some issues related to the facilities.		2.00	1.34	Disagreed
5.	I believe the current facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs meet the requirements of the program curriculum.		2.24	1.00	Disagreed
6.	There are no additional facilities that should be provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		1.88	1.40	Disagreed
7.	I often use most of the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		2.79	0.51	Agreed
8.	I think the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are safe and secure for the children.		2.90	0.63	Agreed
9.	The facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs enable children to learn effectively.		2.75	0.62	Agreed

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- | | | | |
|--|------|------|--------|
| 10. I believe availability of adequate facilities very important for the success of the ECCE programs. | 3.02 | 0.43 | Agreed |
|--|------|------|--------|

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The result in table 4 displays the mean and standard deviation of adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The results revealed that facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are not adequate, as indicated on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. These items have their mean (\bar{X}) values lower than the criterion mean of 2.50 ($\bar{X} < 2.50$). The values of the standard deviation on the items indicate less variation in the responses of the respondents (teachers) due to the closeness of the values. This implies that the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs in public primary schools in Abuja are insufficient.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that ECCE program's in public primary schools are beneficial to children in FCT Abuja. The reason for this might be that ECCE programs provide a strong foundation for lifelong learning, improve access to education, and enhance children's cognitive, social-emotional, and health outcomes. The finding confirms those of Shekarau (2014) who in his study noted that uniform programs related to early childhood education facilitates Human Development (HD) and can bring about development in education, health, social capital and equality that will help develop children that participate in the program even up to the future. This result corroborated the finding of Gorba (2012) which revealed that self-regulation, moral development, physical growth, personality development, and gender socialization are among the defining features of early childhood education. The implication of this finding is that ECCE programs in public primary schools may be an effective way to support children's development and prepare them for formal schooling.

Most interesting of the findings in this study is that majority of parents and society lacked awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja. The reason might be attributed to limited availability or accessibility of ECCE programs in public primary schools, particularly in underserved or remote areas, which may contribute to a lack of awareness among parents and society. This agrees with the findings of Reap (2010) that, the importance of Early Childhood has not caught the full attention of society. He went ahead to put that the lack of awareness and the uncertainty of parents on the influence of Early Child Education on the school readiness of their children lead many parents to place Early Child Education far from the top of the education priority list. The implication of lack of awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools is parents may not prioritize their child's participation in these programs which leads to low participation rates, and schools may struggle to secure funding and resources for these programs due to limited support from parents and society, limiting their effectiveness.

It is important to note that the finding of study revealed that the majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs in public primary schools. The possible reason could be that the staff members have received the necessary training and qualifications to implement the ECCE programs, and they have gained practical experience and developed the skills required through their work in the education sector. This aligns with the submission in an Issue Brief by National Governors Association Centre for Best Practices (2010) that the knowledge and skills of early childhood care providers and teachers are critical factors in their delivery of high-quality developmental and educational experiences to young children. In confirmation of this, Goble and Horm (2010) have submitted that whatever a person's profession is, the need for professional development is universal because professionals need to continually enrich their knowledge and increase their sense of professionalism over the course of their careers so as to implement current research based practice. The implication could lead to the successful implementation of the program, better learning outcomes for young children and improve the overall quality of education in public primary schools in Nigeria.

Similarly, findings of this study showed that the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs in public primary schools in Abuja are insufficient. The reason could be as a result of the fact Public primary schools may not receive adequate funding to support the development of ECCE programs which lead to a lack of resources such as teaching materials, toys, and equipment necessary for learning and development. The result of this study supports the findings of Good Planet Foundation (2013) on Nigeria that spending on essentials such as textbooks, instructional materials, in-service training, operations and maintenance is inadequate. The findings confirm those of Akinrotimi and Olowe (2016) who in their study found that Nigerian ECCE programs are ridiculously underfunded and could be linked to the low budgetary allocation to the education sector in the nation. The implication of this findings is that the effective implementation of the program may be hindered which in turn potentially limiting the quality of early childhood education provided to children.

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Conclusion

The study concludes that the Early Childhood Care Education (ECCE) programs in public primary schools have not been effectively implemented. Equally, ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja are perceived as beneficial to children. However, it could be concluded here that the lack of awareness among parents and society about the significance of these programs is a cause for concern. The majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the program, but insufficient facilities hinder its implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. ECCE programs should be continued and expanded in public primary schools to provide more benefits to children. Additionally, efforts should be made to improve the quality and effectiveness of these programs through regular evaluation and training of teachers.
2. Awareness campaigns and outreach programs be conducted to educate parents and society about the benefits of ECCE programs. This will help to increase participation and support for these programs which will lead to better outcomes for children.
3. Incentives such as recognition and career advancement opportunities could be provided to motivate staff members to continuously improve their skills and performance.
4. Government should conduct regular assessments to identify the gaps and areas for improvement in the facilities and resources for the ECCE programs in public primary schools and take necessary actions to address them.

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Qualitative Study on Jigsaw Instructional Strategy among Entrepreneurship Education Students at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: Features, Methods and Way Forward

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Abstract

This paper examined qualitative study on jigsaw instructional strategy among entrepreneurship education students at tertiary level of education in Nigeria: features, methods and way forward. It went further to discuss the topic under the following sub-headings: jig-saw cooperative learning features at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, jig-saw teaching technique of students in entrepreneurship at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, planning and preparation of jigsaw strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, implementation of jigsaw instructional strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, methods of teaching entrepreneurship at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, impact of jigsaw strategy on academic achievement of entrepreneurship education students at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. It was concluded that jig-saw has effects on academic achievement of entrepreneurship education students through: critical thinking and problem-solving skills, creativity and innovation, self-confidence, practical application of knowledge, communication and presentation skills, networking opportunities, interdisciplinary learning, team work skills. It was recommended that Jigsaw teaching method should be adopted in teaching entrepreneurship due to its effect on the acquisition of entrepreneurial concepts. Conducting training courses for the entrepreneurship teachers on the effective and proper use of the Jigsaw strategy in teaching entrepreneurship education among others.

Keywords: Jig Saw Cooperative learning, Academic Achievement, Entrepreneurship Education, Students, Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

Modebelu (2017) defines teaching as an activity comprising of a set of actions and programmes planned and targeted towards inculcating learning through conscious and deliberate efforts of a teacher. A teacher in this situation is expected to be a core professional who consciously and deliberately utilizes his or her wealth of experience, skills, competencies, attitudes, interest and mastery of the subject matter to facilitate learning in students. The product of teaching is learning activities that is, knowledge acquisition. Teaching and learning encounter is a two-directional affair whereby the teacher sends out the information while the learners communicate via evaluation, but this in and out processes can be good if teaching methods are appropriate. Ajoma (2017) views teaching method as professional technique that teachers adopt regularly in instructional exercises to enable them impart relevant knowledge and skills to the learner. Entrepreneurship teachers also employ various teaching methods to impact knowledge.

Jigsaw is one of the strategies of cooperative learning as it exercises the effort of working in teams for each of the students by reaching a favorable outcome (Halimah & Sukmayadi, 2019; Morera-Fernandez et al., 2020; Qiao & Jin, 2010; Vijayan et al., 2016). Jigsaw is formed when each student in a team becomes responsible for teaching other peers through a set of learnt materials (Jainal & Shahrill, 2021). It reduces students' reluctance in participating in class discussions and shown to create active learning". Cooperative in general as described by the Search for Common Ground (2003) is a joint effort between parties to determine facts where discussions are made face-to-face which encouraged participation among everyone.

Moreover, respect is emphasized, decision is authorized by each of the members, the outcome need to be in satisfaction by everyone and the relationships are promoted through trust and being positive with each other. Being cooperative in classroom settings focused on students working together which could offer outcomes that enable the students learning to be more conducive and productive. The pedagogical practice of cooperative learning has increasingly attracted the attention of researchers. There is a large body of literature which indicates that students improved both academically and socially when

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students are given the opportunities to interact with each other to achieve shared goals. Cooperative learning approach provides a significant gap when compared to teacher centered learning. It enables students to work with their peers socially and practice the skills that are required for development (Dollard & Mahoney, 2010). Furthermore, using cooperative learning such as Jigsaw in the classroom have many effects such as improvements of academic performance, higher self-esteem and more positive views about school altogether (Winslow, 2020). Jainal, & Shahrill, (2021) mentioned that when students worked cooperatively, they put more effort into achieving positive outcomes because of the supportive relationships with their peers in constructive ways. In order for cooperative learning to be successful, five important features are crucial to be developed over time. They are positive interdependence, individual accountability, face-to-face interaction, social skills and group processing (Benek & Bezir Akcay, 2019; Jones & Jones, 2008). The use of cooperative learning strategies could assist students in the development of the 21st Century skills that comprised of collaboration, creativity, critical thinking and communication skills (Lai & Viering, 2012).

There are several cooperative learning strategies available, such as think-pair-share, thinking-aloud pair problem solving, the three-step interview, STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division), Jigsaw, TGT (Teams Games Tournaments) and GI (Group Investigation) (Astarini et al., 2019; Azmin, 2016; Benek & Bezir Akcay, 2019; Damit et al., 2015; Duraman et al., 2015; Halimah & Sukmayadi, 2019; Kani & Shahrill, 2015; Lee et al., 2018; Lim et al., 2016; Mahari et al., 2019; Morera-Fernandez et al., 2020; Simpoh et al., 2018; Sulaiman & Shahrill, 2015; Vijayan et al., 2016). Cooperative in general is defined as providing group work where everyone participates on a collective task to help each other in completing the task provided to them by the teacher (Barron & Hammond, 2008). This will produce a great output because students are working together in achieving the shared goal agreed among each and every team member (Ransdell & Moberly, 2003). Similarly, Akinbolola (2009) stated that cooperative learning is an instructional approach that allows students with different working ability to work in teams in order to accomplish a purpose. This is because the setting of the classroom for cooperative learning to take place allows the students to freely set themselves for discussions in complementing each other's understanding (Veenman et al., 2002).

Academic achievement represents that which learners attain in his/her class room activities and ways to manage various teaching encounters expected of students by tutors. Ibrahim (2011) reports that in academic environment, progress is established by academic achievement. Morgan (2010) describes academic achievement as an evaluation technique whereby results of learners are collated via learners' task in a particular time. Therefore, it simply implies that performance quantifies the behaviours of a learner that is visible at a given time. Performance of students is highly vital because, this look like main standard whereby efficiency and progress of an institution of learning might be justified.

Academic achievement is an output of learning, in the sense that, level of attainment of educational aims and objectives of learners, instructors and schools/colleges. According to Jimoh, Idris and Olatunji (2016), academic achievement is the degree of success attained by students after being exposed to one form of learning or the other. Jimoh (2014) confirms that achievement in academic is the extent of progress achieved by learners in their course of study. Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2013) noted that academic achievement is commonly measured using classroom exercise, assignment and continuous assessment as well as internal and external examination. It can be used to indicate students' level of success in a particular task students were previously exposed to and it can also be used as indices for determining students' capability to effectively undertake another task (Jimoh, 2014).

Oguntimehin (2017) stated that the rationale for the inclusion of entrepreneurship curricula in universities, polytechnics and colleges is to help graduates to acquire increased understanding of entrepreneurship, equip them with entrepreneurial approach to the world of work and prepare them to act as entrepreneurs and managers of new businesses. Entrepreneurship Education has been view as a systematic training and instruction that transmit entrepreneurial knowledge and development of skills in students. Entrepreneurship education is meant to change students' behaviour pattern in the desired direction. Therefore, Entrepreneurship education is a continuing development of relevant entrepreneurial skills and habits whose understanding and application enable the Business students to contribute meaningfully towards the growth and development of Nigerian economy.

Similarly, Entrepreneurship education is the process of imparting knowledge and teaching skills to potential entrepreneurs on how to venture into business that is relatively small in nature for future development or advancement (Aminu, 2012). According to Adiele (2010) entrepreneurial education is designed to communicate and inculcate competencies, skills and values needed to recognize business opportunity, organize and start new business venture. It is regarded as a vital tool for reduction of unemployment.

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Jig-Saw Cooperative Learning Features at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Cooperative learning is an instructional strategy in which small groups of students work together to achieve a common goal. This approach fosters collaboration, communication, and mutual support among students. Examples of some key features of cooperative learning are:

1. **Positive Interdependence:** Students are dependent on each other to achieve a common goal. Success is linked to the success of the group, fostering a sense of collective responsibility.
2. **Individual Accountability:** Each student in the group is responsible for their own learning and contributes to the groups success. Individual assessments may be used to ensure that each student is actively participating and mastering the material.
3. **Face to Face Interaction:** Students work together in small face to face groups. Interaction is essential for communication, sharing ideas and resolving conflicts within the group.
4. **Interpersonal and Small Group Skills:** Cooperative learning enhances social skills, such as communication, leadership and conflict resolution. Students learn to work effectively in a team, respecting diverse opinion and backgrounds.
5. **Group Process:** Groups periodically reflects on their performance and make adjustments to improve their collaboration. This reflective process helps students identify what is working well and what can be improved within the group.
6. **Promotion of Critical Thinking:** Cooperative learning activities often involve problem solving and critical thinking. Students learn to analyze information, evaluate ideas and apply their knowledge in real world situations.
7. **Heterogeneous Grouping:** Groups are often formed with students of varying abilities, backgrounds and skills. Heterogeneous grouping promotes diversity and provides opportunities for peer teaching and learning.
8. **Promotion of a Positive Learning Environment:** Cooperative learning fosters a supportive and positive classroom atmosphere. Students feel a sense of belonging and are more motivated to participate actively in their learning.
9. **Teacher as a Facilitator:** The role of the teacher shifts from a lecturer to a facilitator. The teacher provides guidance, support and structure, but the emphasis is on student led learning.
10. **Integration of Individual and Group Goals:** Individual and group goals are aligned to create a cohesive learning experience. The success of the individual is connected to the success of the group, and vice versa.
11. **Promotion of Social Skills:** Cooperative learning helps students develop social skills, such as communication, teamwork, and conflict resolution. Interacting with peers in a collaborative setting prepares students for real-world social interactions.
12. **Varied Learning Activities:** Cooperative learning can be applied to a variety of learning activities, including discussions, projects, problem solving task and more. This versatility allows teachers to adapt the cooperative learning approach to different subjects and learning objectives.

Jig-Saw Teaching Technique of Students in Entrepreneurship at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The jigsaw teaching strategy is a collaborative learning approach, which was first developed by Elliot Aronson and his students at the University of Texas and the University of California in the early 1970s. In jigsaw, each student in a group takes responsibility for one chunk of the content, then teaches it to the other group members. Like the pieces of a jigsaw puzzle, students fit their individual chunks together to form a complete body of knowledge. The goal of the approach is to study the learning material in groups to achieve specific objectives. This strategy draws a direct image of a jigsaw puzzle where each student represents a piece of the puzzle. As the final image of a puzzle constructed from fitting together separate pieces, each student presents his/her assigned task to complete the puzzle.

Jigsaw strategy is based on “cooperation by design” where no student can succeed completely unless everyone works well together as a team. This understanding leads students to value each other as contributors to a shared task. Jigsaw strategy empowers students to take charge of their learning, and aids retention, peer tutoring, communication skills and retrieval of concepts (Sabbah, 2016). In studies comparing Jigsaw with traditional direct instruction, students taught with the Jigsaw method demonstrated increased feelings of autonomy, competence, and intrinsic motivation (Hänze & Berger, 2007).

Imagine you are an entrepreneurship teacher who wants to do an overview of different types of business using the jigsaw method. You can divide your content into these chunks; tailoring, hair dressing, soap making, and bead making. In this case, you will need 4 home groups, and 4 expert groups to study each chunk as displayed in Figure 1. You will assign each expert group one chunk to study. The student in the expert group will be responsible to teach that chunk to the rest of the students in the home group.

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Figure 1. Jigsaw Approach

(Adapted from Jigsaw Cooperative Approach in Professional Studies)

Planning and Preparation of Jigsaw strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

1. The teacher selects the content to be taught for the next lecture.
2. The content is divided into subtopics (according to the number of the students in a group).
3. The teacher should prepare clear instructions for students, and she/he should also explain the critical terminology so that students can understand the topic easily

TIP: Jigsaw works best when you have the same number of students in each team (Newbury, 2015)

Implementation of Jigsaw instructional strategy at tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

1. Divide students into groups of 4 to 6.
2. Divide your content into 4 or 6 chunks (i.e. the number of the chunks depends on the number of the students in each group).
3. Give each student in the home group a different chunk to master. Make sure they read and study their chunk individually.
4. Have students meet in expert groups. Gathering with all the other students assigned with the same chunk will give them the chance to compare their ideas and work together to get prepared. This also helps to enhance their communication skills and help them to solve any queries. This is particularly helpful for the students who find it challenging to understand the task on their own.
5. Students in the expert groups then return to their home groups to present their chunk to other members of the team. Meanwhile, others in the group listen carefully, take notes and ask a lot of questions. Here, students are accountable for individual learning and the success of the group.
6. Walk around the classroom to observe and offer any kind of help if necessary.
7. At the end of the class, give a quiz on the material to make sure all students got a basic understanding of all the material.

TIP: In each home group, appoint one of the students to be the discussion leader, on a rotating basis. It helps the groups run more effectively (Newbury, 2015).

Methods of Teaching Entrepreneurship at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The Consortium for Entrepreneurship Education (2008) defines entrepreneurship education as one which seeks to prepare people, especially the youth, to be responsible, enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers and who contribute to economic development and sustainable communities. Such education is not just based on text-book courses; instead students are immersed in real-life learning experiences where they have an opportunity to take risks, manage the results and learn from the outcomes. By implication, entrepreneurship education at undergraduate level is expected to inspire and motivate students to develop knowledge and skills of self-reliance, fashion for venture creation and innovative skills for sustainable development. Students, irrespective of their gender and the location of their institutions, who have acquired

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all these skills through entrepreneurship education are likely to be positioned not only for self-reliance but also to create jobs for others.

This collaborative learning technique helps to engage all students in their learning by motivating students to learn a topic or skill well enough to demonstrate it and teach it to their peers. Jigsaw is “also an efficient strategy for extending the breadth, depth, and scope of learning because students learn and teach multiple topics simultaneously during the same class session” (Barkeley, Cross and Major, 2014).

Impact of Jigsaw Strategy on Academic Achievement of Entrepreneurship Education Students at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

By structuring small group discussions and assignment deliverables, Jigsaw as a collaborative learning tool also helps to foster a welcoming and equitable learning experience for students (Theobald et al. 2017). Entrepreneurship education can have several positive impacts on students, both academically and personally through:

1. **Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills:** Entrepreneurship education often encourages students to think critically and develop problem-solving skills. This can enhance their ability to analyze situations, make decisions, and solve problems, which are valuable skills in academic settings. These skills can contribute to academic success by promoting a deeper understanding of subject matter and the ability to apply knowledge in diverse situations.
2. **Creativity and Innovation:** Entrepreneurship programs often foster creativity and innovation. Students learn to think outside the box, come up with new ideas, and explore innovative solutions. These qualities can positively influence academic performance, especially in subjects that require creative thinking.
3. **Self-Confidence:** Entrepreneurship education can boost students' self-confidence by challenging them to take risks and step out of their comfort zones. Increased confidence can lead to better academic performance as students become more willing to participate in class discussions and take on challenging tasks.
4. **Practical Application of Knowledge:** Entrepreneurship education is often hands-on and practical. Students may have the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios. This practical application can deepen their understanding of academic subjects and make learning more engaging.
5. **Communication and Presentation Skills:** Many entrepreneurship programs emphasize communication and presentation skills, which are valuable in academic and professional settings. Improved communication skills can enhance students' ability to express themselves clearly in essays, presentations, and discussions.
6. **Networking Opportunities:** Entrepreneurship programs often provide networking opportunities with professionals, mentors, and fellow students. Networking can open doors to academic resources, research opportunities, and collaborative projects, positively impacting academic achievement.
7. **Interdisciplinary Learning:** Entrepreneurship often involves knowledge from various disciplines, such as marketing, finance, and management. Integrating these diverse fields in an entrepreneurial context can lead to a more holistic understanding of academic concepts.
8. **Teamwork Skills:** Entrepreneurship education often involves collaborative projects, fostering teamwork and communication skills. These soft skills are valuable not only in entrepreneurial endeavors but also in academic settings.

Conclusion

Cooperative learning is recommended for teachers to use as part of their teaching strategy because it provides ample evidence of support in students learning. Students participate more and since members in a group consisted of heterogeneous ability, provided that teachers structure the group properly, it enhances students learning with better understanding. As a cautionary advice, teachers who decide to use Jigsaw as their teaching strategy, they need to have adequate understanding of how the method works. Besides, teachers will need to have excellent resources and knowledge of why and how they want to incorporate this learning strategy into their teaching. By doing so, the learning process will be more organized. In addition, teachers need to emphasize to students the importance of equal participation, being interdependent and accountable, and to have cohesion with each team member. Teachers need to inform their students to take control of their learning by becoming actively involved. This would ensure the success of the cooperative learning being incorporated. Teachers will also need to provide students with the opportunity to evaluate their own ability during the group work to ensure that the five features to cooperative learning had been achieved.

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Recommendations

Based on the study of jigsaw, the following recommendations are made:

1. Adopting a teaching method by using (Jigsaw) in teaching entrepreneurship due to its effect on the acquisition of entrepreneurial concepts.
2. Conducting training courses for the entrepreneurship teachers on the effective and proper use of the Jigsaw strategy in teaching entrepreneurship education.
3. Conducting further studies and research on using the Jigsaw strategy in teaching other courses, such as Accounts and marketing, and studying students' attitudes towards using them.
4. The teachers need to diversify the method of teaching entrepreneurship such as jigsaw as it will assist in higher academic achievement of students.
5. Jigsaw technique should be adopted in universities by business education teachers for teaching of financial accounting so as to improve the academic achievement of students.
6. Governments should employ qualified hands to teach various vocational subjects because it is only a qualified teacher with effective teaching method that can remedy students' poor academic achievement in entrepreneurship and other vocational subjects.
7. All learners should be given equal opportunity and the same level of encouragement irrespective of the gender.

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Qualitative Study on Management of Nigerian Education System using Community Participation Models at Secondary School Level of Education

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Abstract

This paper focuses on qualitative study on management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education. Based on the critical role these models play in understanding the different phenomenon in community participation practice in education, this paper aims to deconstruct the models in the context of Nigerian secondary school education system. The significance of this exegesis is to contribute to better understanding of the different models in shaping the policy, and practice of community participation in educational management at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. In addition, a brief review of the literature shows a lack of focus in that direction thus, serving as a contribution to the body of knowledge in that regard. Literature survey design was employed to compose the paper. Bhusham, S. Model that posits on community participation strategies like Adopting community resources for enhancing quality instruction through child centred approaches, was explored among others in the paper. The paper concludes that community participation goes a long way in better management of secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper recommends, among others that, rigorous campaign have to be mounted to reorient Nigerian people on the significance and importance of community participation in the management of secondary schools in Nigeria.

Keywords: community participation, models, education system, management & Secondary Schools

Introduction

Education serves as the cornerstone of societal development, playing a pivotal role in shaping individuals and preparing them for active participation in the community, (Fagerlind and Saha 2016). Education is multifaceted in nature and transcends the mere transmission of knowledge; it encompasses the cultivation of skills, values, and critical thinking abilities, contributing to the holistic development of individuals and society. In the new world order impacted by internet and digital technologies, education prepares individuals for life and provides them the skills to navigate the complexities of the inter-relations between man and his environment. Education provides the tools for critical thinking and problem solving (Abbas, Aman, Nurunnabi, & Bano (2019). Considering the role of education in shaping the growth and development of society, (Depaepe, 2012), the effective management of education is imperative.

Against this backdrop, educational institutions from lower-level schools (particularly at secondary school level) to tertiary or universities require a strong and focused leadership to forge a school climate within the components that constitute an effective and efficient learning environment. Education management is the coordination of policies, curriculum development, human resources, finances, and community engagement to create a conducive space for both educators and learners, (Medina, Cosby, & Grim 2020). An important component of education management is community participation, since education is a collective endeavor, fostering community involvement is an integral and critical component of the educational system. Community participation in education management is the active engagement of parents, local community or residents within and around the school and various stakeholders in decision-making, planning, and support for educational venture, (Kusumaningrum, Ulfatin, Maisyaroh, Triwiyanto, & Gunawan, 2017). This collaborative approach underscores the

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interdependence between educational institutions (like secondary schools) and the communities they serve, thus, reinforcing shared responsibility for the success of the educational enterprise. The interconnection and relationship between education, education management and community participation is very essential for the creation of a dynamic, inclusive and responsive learning environment (Kusumaningrum et al., 2017). Understanding these relationships can enhance the quality of education, promote students' success and contribute to the development of the broader society. A comprehensive exegesis of the models that explains different strategies and approaches to facilitate effective community participation at secondary school level of education management is therefore significant.

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2024) defined Model as usually miniature representation of something; a pattern of something to be made; a type or design of product; an example for imitation or emulation and a set of plans for a building. In education management, model refers to a structured and systematic representation or framework that describes, guides, and prescribes the processes, interactions and elements involved in managing educational institutions, (Bush, 2006; 2020; Ghasemy, & Hussin, 2014). Model in the context of this paper refers to a means of explanation and or imitation for good way of managing education system. Over the years, some models of community participation in education management have emerged in different communities and have gained popularity and significance in the community practice field (Mukhtar, 2021). These models include Goodland, J. Model, Bhusham S. Model and Ubuntu Theory of Management. Because of their popularity and significance, these models appear to be some of the most prominent in community participation discourse and practice.

Based on the critical role these models play in understanding the different phenomenon in community participation practice in education, this paper aims to deconstruct the models in the context of Nigerian education system at secondary school level. The significance of this exegesis is to contribute to better understanding of the different models in shaping the policy, and practice of community participation in educational management at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. In addition, a brief review of the literature shows a lack of focus in that direction thus, serving as a contribution to the body of knowledge in that regard. Consequently, the details in the paper will serve as an adroit cudgel for educationist, educators, education managers and relevant stakeholders in the Nigerian education ecosystem. The rest of the paper is structured in the following order: presentation of the different models in focus, discussions on the models, contextual relevance and its implications as well as the summary and conclusion and recommendations.

Goodland J. Model

Goodland (1984:35-39) in Rolfe (2015) in his massive study "A Place Called School" schooling over 300 years history, Goodland and his colleagues identified four broad goals of the school management

- Academic, including a broad array of knowledge and intellectual skills.
- Vocational aimed at readiness for the world of work and economic responsibilities.
- Social, Civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society.
- Personal, including the development of individual talent and self-expression

Figure 1: Goodland Goals of School Management

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Implications of Goodland J. Model in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education

In this model (Goodland J. Model) social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society have been highlighted as one of the goals of school. This goal can never be met without the participation of the community. This is because the social, civic values and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society are determined by particularly the culture and or orientation of the community. The community therefore is in the best position to be involved in meeting that goal of social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society and that makes the community a key stakeholder in the management of Nigerian secondary school and as well the education system. Therefore, in managing secondary school education system in Nigeria, particularly in designing and executing educational curriculum, culture and orientation of communities have to be religiously considered. This will go a long way in building confidence in the communities members in the viability and validity of the education system, it will also create and project a sense of ownership of the education system in the communities. This will as well play a good role in avoiding resistance from the communities as it happened when Western Education was introduced in Nigeria and particularly in Northern Nigeria. Northern Nigerian people resisted Western and or colonial education when the British colonialist introduced it. They did not begin to accept it until when subjects like Islamic Studies and local Malams/Anakallahu (local Islamic teachers and scholars) were involved in the teaching-learning operations in the education system.

Another point that supports the assertion is the debate around introduction of Sex Education, into the Nigerian Secondary schools curriculum. When it was introduced into the curriculum without adequate consultation and community involvement, it was vehemently rejected. This was because Sex Education sounded alien to the culture and orientation of some of Nigerian communities. Another case in point is the case of Adolescent Girl-child Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) in 2023 in Kano and Katsina States. AGILE is a project of the World Bank that is focused on the promotion of girl-child education. The project faced resistance from particularly Islamic scholars in Kano State and it was rejected by Emir of Katsina. In Kano, there had to be a review of the AGILE document to address the cultural and orientational concerns of the community by the teaming-up of the project officials and some Islamic scholars in the State before it was accepted. Therefore, community culture and orientation have to be handled with care as they are organic in achieving the goals of school and by extension the education system goals.

Bhusham, S. Model

Bhusham (2000:77) in Chima and Itabita (2018), stated that interaction and networking for mutual benefit partnership have become an integral part of any educational programme. This trend considerably reflected the school and community and their purposeful interaction as a focal for changes in school education. In Bushman's own words, "A meaningful partnership between school and community would enhance individual student education, promote parent organizations, participation in school's daily operations. It is basically a change initiative". Realizing the importance of school community partnership for quality education, the following strategies may be considered for optimal efficiency

1. Developing school-based management and community participation in the affairs of the school by forming a coalition between communities and government.
2. Transferring some degree of ownership of school to the local communities by empowering them to demand quality education.
3. Adopting community resources for enhancing quality instruction through child centred approaches.
4. Development of school staff as a team that establishes links and respect with the community.
5. Promotion of mutual trust and faith while taking collaborative decisions

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Source: Bhusham (2000)

Figure 2: Conceptual Model of School Community Participation

Implications of Bhusham, S. Model in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education

The model in Figure 2 also supports the advantage of community participation in the management of secondary schools in Nigeria. This is clear and categorical where the model mentions developing school-based management and community participation in the affairs of the school by forming a coalition between communities and government. The coalition can be made in form of forum where the communities and the government meet together to deliver on issues that matter in progress and development of secondary school. This supports the idea of School-Based Management Committee (SBMC) in our Nigerian secondary school.

Ubuntu Theory of Management

The evolution of Ubuntu Theory of Management (UTM) can be dated to the early 1930s by Mugumbate and Nyanguru; Tran and Wall when the saying was determined from the adage 'I am because we are.' This saying was raised from communal engagements and commitment toward shared community goals through love, selflessness, and communalism (Mugumbate and Nyanguru, 2013 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). The development of Ubuntu was slow because of the infiltration of Western paradigms that came with education in Africa (Swartz and Davies, 1997 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). This was evident in the Western scholarship and literature that generally relegated the values of Ubuntu espouses to the back in the league of other management theories.

These Westernized theories, however, failed to address learner indiscipline in the African context because the expected goal of the theories was defeated because of the lacuna set between objectives and achieved objectives (Inyang, 2008 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). In the struggle to find an indigenous effective solution to an African educational management setting, Ubuntu gradually became a suitable approach to a more humane approach to scientific management theory and has become a strong force to reckon with over the years (Ngubane and Makua, 2021 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). The indiscipline in schools today points to the fact that leadership theories that emanated from the Western context and ideologies have provided limited means to manage the problem in the African context (Msila, 2008 and Ncube, 2010 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023).

Implications of Ubuntu Theory of Management in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education

Africans are known to have a lifestyle of living in kinships and based in communal life in form of villages, town ships and extended families. This makes them to have an idea of coming together to identify their problems and work together to solve them. This is because they learn that a damage to one is a damage to all and thus the emergence of the adage “I am because we are” as explained by UTM. The adage means an individual cannot live in isolation, he has to come together with the others to have a better and fulfilled life. Therefore, in managing issues in secondary schools in Nigeria UTM buttresses the effectiveness of community participation. This is clearly indicated at the instance when Western school management theories failed to address issues in schools like indiscipline as explained by the UTM. This testifies to the fact that indigenous problems are effectively solved by indigenous solutions. Therefore, community would be the answer in better management of secondary school in Nigeria.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the exploration of various models of community participation in education management has provided valuable insights into the diverse approaches and strategies employed to foster collaboration between educational institutions like secondary schools and their surrounding communities. The examination of models such as Goodland, Busham and Ubuntu Theory of Management has revealed a rich tapestry of theoretical frameworks, each offering unique perspectives on the dynamics of community involvement. A common feature among these models is the recognition of community participation as an important component in the effective governance and enhancement of educational outcomes. Whether through Goodland's emphasis on social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society or Bhusham's that stated that interaction and networking for mutual benefit partnership have become an integral part of any educational programme or UTM that encourages communal engagements and commitment toward shared community goal; the models collectively underscore the significance of engaging stakeholders beyond the school walls.

However, differences also exist among the models, reflecting the complexity of community participation in diverse educational contexts. The nuanced differences in emphasis, implementation strategies, and stakeholder roles presented by the various models highlight the need for tailored approaches that align with the specific needs and dynamics of individual communities. As educational leaders and policymakers consider the implications of these models in the Nigerian context, it becomes evident that a one-size-fits-all approach is inadequate in the management of secondary school education. Therefore, the nuanced understanding gained from examining the models of community participation encourages a more comprehensive and context-specific approach to community participation in education management particularly in Nigerian secondary schools. The synthesis of these models not only contributes to our theoretical understanding of community participation but also provides practical insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers particularly in Nigeria. The multifaceted nature of these models challenges us to adopt adaptive and responsive strategies that consider the unique socio-cultural, economic, and demographic characteristics of each community. In moving forward, it is imperative that future research and practice continue to build on these insights, acknowledging the evolving nature of educational landscapes and the dynamic relationships between schools and communities. By embracing the diversity of models presented in this paper, we can foster a more inclusive, collaborative, and effective approach to community participation in secondary school education management in Nigeria.

Recommendations

From the foregone, the paper recommends as follows:

1. People in Nigerian communities should be made to understand that education is enormous and government cannot single-handedly provide it without the help from the other quarters in the communities. To provide education particularly at secondary school level there is need for good management that communities have to be involved to do it effectively and efficiently
2. Rigorous campaign have to be mounted to reorient Nigerian people on the significance and importance of community participation in managing secondary schools
3. Government should consider communities as key stakeholders in the formulation and execution of education policies particularly at secondary school level and relate with them as such. This will go a long way in boosting the morale of the communities members and promoting sense of ownership and belonging in managing the secondary schools

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4. Community participation fora in managing secondary schools like SMBC should be established where there is none in all the secondary schools in Nigeria and be reinvigorated where there is
5. Government and communities should come together and brainstorm to come up with more alternatives and innovations in community participation for better secondary schools management.

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Relationship Between Cultural Variables and Marital Stability among Couples in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between cultural variables (cultural background, religious affiliation and value attached to children) and marital stability among couples in Cross River State Nigeria. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The researcher sampled 400 married couples out of the total population of 49,317 registered couples in the state. Two instruments were used for the study: self-developed questionnaire titled Cultural Variables Questionnaire (SCVQ) and an adapted version of Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). The instruments were subjected to face and content validation. Point Biserial Correlation was used to test hypothesis one while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses two and three at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state among others. It was concluded that religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. It was recommended amongst others that religious affiliations should not be used as a criteria for marital stability but rather, it should be used as a way of life and as a tool to breed peace in the family for the general wellbeing of the family and the society at large.

Keywords: Culture, variables, marriage, couples, stability

Introduction

Marriage is an important aspect of human society which creates identity. It is a legal and social commitment that two people (adult male and female) make to share their lives for procreation, love, companionship, security, status, religious obligations, economic consideration and conforming to social standard. Marriage as a lifelong commitment, is signified by a contract sanctioned by law for people (Animasahun & Fatile, 2011). Marriage, as an institution, is an avenue of maintaining the life-line of a people. It allows and gives the legal and social backing to individuals to come together, live together and birth the next generation of the group. In this line, social, cultural and religious tenets are passed on from one generation to the other. The individuals so joined and permitted to live as one within the community learn to live together, love their off-springs, themselves and the community.

In African tradition, separation is considered as an offense. This is supported by Arugu (2014) that within the traditional African socio-communal life, divorce is an aberration: it is neither encouraged nor accepted except in extreme situations like barrenness and incompatibility. A union without children is seen as incomplete and unfulfilled. The irony in this is that the man is encouraged to remarry while it becomes incumbent on the woman to continue in the marriage or until she is able to give birth. Consequently, more often than not, a few individuals are denied certain responsibilities, not because they are not qualified or capable of handling such but because they are not considered matured enough: they are not married. For example, in Northern Nigeria, bachelors who are seen capable of being married but not yet married are often not allowed to lead people who are married in prayers. This does not mean that God will not accept their prayers, but that they lack the

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credibility of leading such prayers. Also, in taking decisions in the family, the opinions of married people are more respected than those of the unmarried (Perelli-Harris, & Styr, 2018).

Marital stability refers to the ability of a married couple to maintain their relationship over time despite challenges that may arise. Marriage is essential for humans as it helps provide the necessary support, care, and love needed for socialization and emotional wellbeing. A stable marriage provides a sense of security and emotional stability for the couple, their children, and society at large. Marital stability is crucial in shaping family dynamics, individual lives, and broader society, highlighting the need for research on factors that promote stable marriages.

Marital stability or instability do occur as a result of certain factors that may be beyond the control of the partners. This is confirmed by Ojukwu and Obiji (2016) that marital success versus marital failure relates to causal process model that provides a chain of preferences among married persons such as satisfied versus dissatisfied. More often than not, our daily social experiences show that marital failures arise from some certain behaviours or attitudes formed and exhibited by one of the married partners, which is taken as unacceptable by the other. This means that, it is the negative beliefs, knowledge, attitude and wrong perception that contribute to dissatisfaction and accusations which result into marital instability. According to Oyafunke, Falola and Salau (2014), marital stability may at times be determined by certain cultural variables including religious affiliations, cultural background and value attached to children among others.

Religion is defined by Yelnick and Danahy (2021) as the entire collection of beliefs, values, and practices that a group holds to be the true and sacred. A group's religious beliefs explain where the people fit in relation to the universe and how they should behave while here on Earth.. Couples who acknowledged a divine purpose in their marriage are more likely to collaborate, to have greater marital adjustment, and to perceive more benefits from marriage. Religious beliefs concerning relational values (for example forgiveness, commitment and sacrifice) appear to indirectly improve marriage stability and quality and beliefs about the sanctification of marriage may help married couples resolve conflict by preventing conflict, improving conflict resolution and enhancing relationship reconciliation (Nathaniel & David, 2016).

Considering the relationship between religion and marital stability, Aman, Abbas, Nurunnabi and Bano, (2019) looked at the relationship of religiosity and marital stability and found out that religious commitment and religious practice are vital for a happy married life. The findings help explain the social dynamics of marital satisfaction in Pakistani culture. Also, Skipper (2016) researched on the role of religious coping in the marital stability of strong, African American couples: A Strengths-Focused Approach and findings revealed that each of the couples interviewed self-identified as highly religiously involved and utilized religion as a source of coping and it aided marital stability among couples.

Cultural background is the context of one's life experience as shaped by membership in groups based on ethnicity, race, socioeconomic status, gender, exceptionalities, language, religion, sexual orientation, and geographical area. It incorporates all beliefs, values, stereotypes, and rules, characterizing the members of a society and differentiating it from other societies. Iriogbe (2015) asserted that the cultural background of the couples is a very strong determinant of marriage stability. He stressed that in Nigeria, cultural background and affiliation of couples could determine how they relate to each other, find solutions to common marital issues which when handled early and appropriately will minimize distress in the family. He added that couples who hail from same cultural background and possibly speak the same dialect will blend better due to similarities in ways of approaching family matters.

Determining the relationship between cultural background and marital stability, Odunayo and Oyewole (2019) investigated the influence of traditional marriage customs and cultural background on marital stability among married people in Yoruba ethnic group and the finding revealed that there exists a significant relationship between variables of traditional marriage customs and marital stability among Yoruba. Similarly, Tandi and Osarhemen (2020) investigated influence of spousal ethnicity and locus of control on marital instability of post-graduate students in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. finding from this research showed that students with intra-ethnic spouse reported significantly lesser level of marital instability than those from inter-ethnic marriage.

Moreover, in Nigeria and Africa generally, it appears that one of the foundations upon which stable marriage is built is ability for couples to have children with the desired sex of children. Among the most important social goods produced by the institution of marriage (of a man and a woman) are children. Child is a person given birth to, son or daughter, a person who hasn't yet grown up, someone inexperienced in a certain thing or someone behaving in an immature manner. Marriage does not only define the social status of people in the society, it also proves to be a most effective way of transforming a man into a husband/father and a woman into a wife/mother and ensures a child might know and be cared for by his/her biological parents. For most modern people, getting married and having children are principal life events that mark the passage into mature adulthood (Stephen & Sunday, 2017).

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To ascertain the relationship between value attached to children and marital stability, Igbolo and Gyong (2014) investigated male preference and marital stability in Cross River State, South - South Nigeria and it was also found that preference for male children was mostly expressed by the female participants, with the major reason being the stability of their marriage. Similarly, Obiyo (2016) investigated the impact of childlessness on marriage and found out that children are the uniting link in the rhythm of life guaranteeing the continuation of the family from one generation to the next.

Marriage is expected to be comfortable and stable as ordained by God but the researcher observed that many marriages are not following the religious injunction thus, marital instability (divorce, separation and remarriage) are common phenomena across globe, in Nigeria and particularly in Cross River State. Despite efforts being made by marriage counsellors, churches, mosques, among others to curb this menace, stakeholders are at a loss on the options available for identifying the causes of this situation in their attempt to proffer solutions. Many couples continue to experience turbulence in their marriages manifested in fighting, quarrelling, suspicion, unhappiness and even separation and divorce.

Given that cultural values, beliefs, and practices are often integral components of an individual's identity, it stands to reason that such variables could potentially shape one's expectations and experiences within the context of a marriage. However, the researcher observed that some marriages in Cross River State are peaceful and stable. It is against this background, that this study investigated whether cultural variables such as religious affiliation, cultural background and value attached to children correlate with marital stability among couples in Cross River State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.

Main and Specific Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the relationship between cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples.
2. Determine whether cultural background has relationship with marital stability of couples or not
3. Ascertain whether value attached to children has relationship with marital stability among couples or not

Research Questions

The following research question were posed to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples?
2. What is the relationship between cultural background and marital stability of couples?
3. What is the relationship between value attached to children and marital stability of couples?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant relationship between cultural background and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.
3. There is no significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.

Methodology

Correlational survey design was used to determine the relationship between socio-cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This design is justified by the fact that the purpose of the study is to establish the relationship that exists between the independent variables which are cultural factors (religious affiliation, cultural background and value attached to children) and the dependent variable which is marital stability among married couples in Cross-River State.

The population for the study comprises 49,317 registered couples in 18 Local Government Areas in the three (3) Senatorial District of Cross River State, which consist of all married spouses in Cross River State (Marriage Registry of the 18 Local Government Headquarters, Cross River State, 2020). A total of 400 married persons were selected for the study using the Glenn (2012) formula for sample size determination. In determining the sample size, the researcher considered all the Local Government areas in the three Senatorial Districts. A total of 210 couples were selected from the South, 110 couples from Central and 80 couples from the North making a total of 400 married persons through the process of convenient sampling technique. By convenient sampling, the researcher sampled the participants in the different Senatorial Districts at his convenience and ensured that all the Local Government are represented in the sample.

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Two instruments were used for the study which include: self-developed questionnaire titled: Cultural Variables Questionnaire (CVQ) and an adapted version of Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). For the reliability of the instrument, the questionnaires were administered on 50 married persons. Both questionnaires yielded split-half reliability coefficient .620 and Cronbach's Alpha .850 were reported accordingly for the study. The instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts: One in Measurement and Evaluation, another one in Guidance and Counselling, and one in Educational Psychology; from the Department of Educational Foundations, Benue State University. Point Biserial Correlation were used to test hypothesis one and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test hypothesis two and three at 0.05 level of significance

Results

This section handles the hypotheses that were formulated for the purpose of this study.

Hypothesis 1:

Religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state. This hypothesis was tested using Point Biserial correlation and the result is presented in table 2.

Table 1: Point Biserial Correlation showing the Relationship between Religious Affiliation and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Spousal Communication	Marital Stability
Religious Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	1	.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.608
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.026	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.608	
	N	400	

Data in table 1 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .026 at $p = .608 > .05$ [$r(398) = .026; p > .05$]. Since $p .608$ is greater than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that 'religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state' was therefore retained. This implies that there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

Hypothesis 2:

Cultural background has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the result is presented in table 3.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the Relationship between Cultural Background and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Cultural Background	Marital Stability
Cultural Background	Pearson Correlation	1	.678**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.678**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	

**** Correlation is Significant at .001 (2-tailed)**

Data in Table 2 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .678 at $p = .000 < .05$ [$r(398) = .678; p < .05$]. Since $p .000$ is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that 'cultural background has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State was therefore reject. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between cultural background and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

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Hypothesis 3:

Value attached to children has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the result is presented in table 4.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the Relationship between Values Attached to Children and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Value Attached to Children	Marital Stability
Values Attached to Children	Pearson Correlation	1	.259**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.259**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	

**** Correlation is Significant at .001 (2-tailed)**

Data in Table 3 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .259 at $p = .000 < .05$ [$r(398) = .259; p < .05$]. Since $p .000$ is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that value attached to children has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state was therefore reject. This implies that there is a significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

Discussion of Finding

The finding in hypothesis one showed that there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This means that no matter how religious couples are, it has nothing to do with their marital stability especially if they are not willing to work on their marriage particularly in Cross River State. This study finding goes against that of Aman, et al (2019) who looked at the relationship of religiosity and marital satisfaction with the role of religious commitment and practices on marital satisfaction among Pakistani respondent and found out that religious commitment and religious practice strengthened and promoted marital satisfaction thereby strengthening marital stability. This assertion was advanced earlier by Skipper (2016) who researched on the role of religious coping in the marital stability of strong, African American couples and found that while religious affiliations may be a factor in marital stability in other cultures, most part of the world do not see religion as a way of strengthening their humanity relationship and this is applicable to marital stability. This finding is contrary to some other findings because none of them apply to this area of study. In the area of study, religion has nothing to do with marital endurance therefore couples feel that they can be committed religiously but not on marital ground.

Result in hypothesis two showed that there was a significant relationship between cultural background and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This means that the more people cling to their cultural values, the more their level of marital satisfaction as most of the cultures have strong marital values, some with deities where people are most of the times afraid of not necessarily for the sake of marriage but for the fear of their traditional values. This finding is consistent with that of Odunayo and Oyewole (2019) who investigated the influence of traditional marriage customs and cultural background on marital stability among married people in Yoruba ethnic group and found that there exists a significant relationship between variables of traditional marriage customs and marital stability among Yoruba as the cultural and traditional values and customs significantly contribute to marital stability. This is also in agreement with Tandi and Osarhemen (2020) who investigated influence of spousal ethnicity and locus of control on marital instability of post-graduate students in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. And found out that students with intra-ethnic spouse reported significantly lesser level of marital instability than those from inter-ethnic marriage.

Result in hypothesis three showed that there is a significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This is an implication that the more couples attach values to children in marriage, the more they are satisfied if they have children. But in events where there are no children, values attached to children may create some level of instability in the marriage among couples. The finding agrees with Igbolo and Gyong (2014) who investigated male preference and marital stability in Cross River State, South - South Nigeria and also found that preference for male children was mostly expressed by the female participants, with the major reason being the stability of their marriage. This finding is consistent with that of Obiyo (2016) who investigated the impact of childlessness on marriage: a study of married

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couples in Lowa community, Imo State Nigeria. The study found that for the Lowa people, children are the uniting link in the rhythm of life guaranteeing the continuation of the family from one generation to the next indicating that most of the cultures and traditions attach much values to children and if there are no children in the marriage, there could be problems.

Conclusion

On the basis and strength of the findings of this study, it is concluded that no matter how religious couples are, it has nothing to do with their marital stability especially if they are not willing to work on their marriage particularly in Cross River State. The more people cling to their cultural values, the more their level of marital satisfaction as most of the cultures have strong marital values, some with deities where people are most of the times afraid of not necessarily for the sake of marriage but for the fear of their traditional values. It can also be concluded that the more couples attach values to children in marriage, the more they are satisfied if they have children. But in events where there are no children, values attached to children may crease some level of instability in the marriage among couples

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Religious affiliations should not be used as a criteria for marital stability but rather, it should be used as a way of life and as a tool to breed peace in the family for the general wellbeing of the family and the society at large.
2. Cultural background has been found by the researcher to be a significant tool in marital stability. Couples should be counselled to have in-depth knowledge of their partner's cultures and traditions to avoid marital instability.
3. Couples should be counselled to be patience and tolerant on the account of childlessness or inability to get required sex of a child

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Social Collectivism and Existentialists (Ubuntu) Ideology: Panacea For Improved and Sustainable Standard of Living among Vulnerable Citizens in Nigeria

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Abstract

African ideology of social collectivism, inclusiveness, and communism is primarily derived from the ‘Ubuntu ideology’ the innate and natural instinct of humans to render help to others and allows every member of the society to exist in a collective and mutually sustaining environments. Social collectivism (Ubuntu) is a multidimensional existentialist model of development that guarantees continuity and sustainability through collective efforts and participatory approaches. Collectivism and existentialist ideology recognize the need for meaningful cohesive community engagement in improving the lives of citizens. Vulnerable people are the weak, the infirmed, the sick, deprived, the neglected and abandoned, usually physically and emotionally challenged persons, the exceptional persons and less privileged in society. These vulnerable populations especially in Nigeria and Africa in general suffer untold hardship which can be addressed principally by relying on the ubuntu ideological orientation of; ‘we exist because you exist’, which is fundamental and germane to human existence. This paper, therefore, adopts a descriptive and theoretical methodology in examining “social collectivism and existentialist ideology as a panacea for the improved sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria. It places emphasis on the interconnectedness of its application for group and short-term social and psychotherapy in human development and learning informed by relying on group-oriented approaches rather than individualism. Particular attention will be focused on the influence of Ubuntu in meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and sustaining its gains in humanitarianism. The paper concludes that social collectivism and existentialist ideology are essential in building relationships giving meaning to existence, and improving a sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens, and recommends that groups' interconnectedness should be promoted as a strategy for promoting and improving sustainable standard of living of vulnerable populations in Nigeria.

Keyword: *Social collectivism, Existentialist, Ubuntu, Vulnerable citizens, Sustainable standards*

Introduction

The world is in constant flux, laced with social problems and humanitarian emergencies created by human interactions with nature and the environment creating imbalances and challenges in society. Many people for one reason or the other fall victim to circumstances and are disadvantaged. Thus, they are categorized as vulnerable populations and citizens. Existence and Life only have meaning when we interact with one another in a mutually inclusive manner. The essence of existence generally is impactful when we live for one another, and when we are multiple prisms in providing solutions to ‘order’ the society and thus, addressing one of the Hobbesian existentialist questions; “*How is life and or society possible*”. All through human existence and interactions, problem-solving has remained one of the most important and herculean tasks in society because all attempts to create and stimulate sustainable growth and development and improve the living standard of citizens are accompanied by socioeconomic and cultural problems needing specific interventions and solutions.

Man’s existence and daily activities have brought about lots of challenges; social, economic, cultural, religious, environmental, and geographical problems. These challenges have inadvertently affected the serenity, security, peace, and the

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pace of development of society in diverse ways and have in no small measure affected the living conditions of the citizens. The magnitude and impact of these problems make it even more difficult for individuals, groups, families, and communities to handle unaided thus, necessitating collective intervention by, groups, local, national, regional, and international bodies; like the Community-Based Organizations (CBOs), and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), World Bank, UNICEF, UNESCO, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). However, within this macro-organizational outlook, there are webs of microcosmic building networks that promote inclusiveness, collectivity, and unity of purpose which depicts the ubuntu ideology and philosophy. Families, groups, and communities like these macro-organizations play key leading roles during humanitarian emergencies, from the provision of food to security, economic recovery, and safeguarding the environment, caring for the sick and vulnerable in society. Man, in essence, is a product of interaction and relationship which gives meaning the life, therefore care and services have been in existence in Africa since the pre-historic and medieval periods and inherent in man. Certain problem-solving approaches and strategies have been used within the African context which have yielded many results in solving problems while other methods proved counterproductive because of not taking into confidence the interconnectedness and collectiveness of people, their space, and the environment of others as participants and collaborators in advancing social and economic benefits in society. But what has consistently not failed is the reliance on the ‘building blocks’ of the African survival and ideological creation, the Ubuntu philosophy, ‘*we are because you are*’, the bond of unity and commitment to one another. The concept of ubuntu is an alternative to individualistic and utilitarian ideologies that tend to dominate the Western world. It is this belief in collectiveness, cohesion, and community existence that makes Africa and Africans different from other races and continents, and even more plausible in managing and solving social problems within the society, especially as they affect vulnerable populations. The ideology supports collectivism over individualism.

Vulnerability is a convergence of risk, measured in and by four key dimensions that relate and connect empathy, integrity, adaptability, and authentic leadership, for trusted working environments. These key dimensions of empathy, integrity, adaptability, and leadership are inextricably the driving force of successful intervention practices and managing vulnerable populations. To a very large extent, every individual in society is vulnerable at one point or the other. Vulnerable population according to Wikipedia (2018), refers to the quality or state of being exposed to the possibility of being attacked or harmed either physically, socially emotionally, and economically. It involves some risk combined with the level of social and economic liability and the ability to cope with the resulting events. It often emanates from non-inclusiveness and non-participation in development, and care agendas, deprivation, poverty, and lack and or poor access to basic needs and services especially health, education, water and sanitation, security, and safe environment in tune with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1- Poverty; 2-Zero hunger; 3-Good health and wellbeing; 4- Quality education; 5-Gender equity; 8-Descent work environment; 10-Reduce inequality, 11- Sustainable cities and communities; 15-life on land, and 16- peace and justice strong institutions. Other factors that influence social problems are natural and man-made disasters, crises, and the absence or non-existent strong judicial and political institutions.

Espousing the Existentialists (Ubuntu) ideology in Nigeria:

In all Nigerian and African societies, the idea and the concepts of ‘*We or Ours*’ and ‘*we rise by lifting others collectively*’ is an organic and functional solidarity that existed from ancient times. Nigeria’s cultural and religious beliefs and practices are anchored on the philosophy of collectiveness, togetherness, and inclusiveness which makes the people of Nigeria and African descent unique and distinctive in all interactions and relationships. The concept of existentialism (ubuntu) is a concrete claim that the starting point for all actions is human existence and the meaning created out of it (Asouzu 2004). This is a compelling group dynamic model derived from the idea “*we exist because you exist*” which can be likened to “*one for all, all for one*” This indeed is what makes Nigerians and Africans bold and pronounced in terms of helping to meet family, group, individuals, and community’s needs as well as help others to survive. This hand-holding philosophy provides and enhances participation and inclusiveness in decision-making and in providing sustained living standards and livelihood options for family, group, and community members. Africans from Nigeria, South Africa, Uganda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Kenya, Congo, Guinea, Ghana, Liberia, Malawi, etc., are fixated on the idea of community living building a network of sustainable approaches to promote communal living standards and lifting and assisting others to meet their needs. This means that man is always in the process of creating meaning, making himself, and facing his choices. That man possesses human nature which is the conception of a human being, and is found in every man. Thus, this collective coexistence (ubuntu) approach strengthens partnership opportunities for vulnerable citizens and populations, the poor, and the weak in society.

According to some of the foremost pan- African leading icons in African identity and by far the biggest advocate of Ubuntu, Archbishop Emeritus Desmond Tutu (2000), Dr. Kenneth Kaunda of Zambia, Julius Nyerere of Tanzania, and Nelson

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Mandela of South Africa, Nnamdi Azikiwe and Obafemi Awolowo, Anthony Enahoro, Bishop Samuel Ajayi Crowther who had consistently seen social collectivism as a moral compass of communism and ideological creation to pursue and improve the standard of living. Ubuntu emphasizes collectivism the sacredness of human life and the centrality of the community in meeting individual, group, and community needs. Like the Indian and Portuguese “*Ahimsa*” practiced by the Hindus, Buddhists, and Jainism, as a doctrine of non-violence, concerned with the sacredness of all living things and the effort to avoid causing harm to others is a derivative of social collectivism (ubuntu) ideology. In Nigeria and Africa in general, the sanctity and sacredness of life are not detached from man’s interactions and communication especially when compared to acclaimed Western culture and civilization. If one considers the fact that, Egypt was the cradle of civilization and center of commerce during the pre-industrial and medieval eras, the Industrial Revolution and Renaissance periods point to the fact that the Nigerian economy and social network systems were anchored on collectivism and communism which are ubuntu model in coalescing efforts to promote inclusiveness and enhance participation among the populace, thus improving the standard of living. Ubuntu preaches communism, unlike the European and American social and economic determinism which are consciously detached from the shelves of humanism and communism because of their socialist and capitalist orientations. Within the African and Nigerian soil, virtually every society practice communism and explores ubuntu philosophy as an approach to meeting their needs, especially the vulnerable citizens, and what could be considered as ‘ubuntu descent’ though in different co-names. For example, among the ‘*Yako-Ekoi*’ tribe of southern Nigeria, the doctrine of ubuntu is known and referred to as ‘*amon-amon*’ a concept that convokes a sense of love, belongingness, partnership, and mutual protection.

All over the African continent, and Nigeria in Particular, the term ‘ubuntu’ is traceable to many African societies, as it is used to express bonding or affiliation with others. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), and Mbigi (2005), Ubuntu is derived from the Nguni and Bantu languages of Africa. In the Zulu language of South Africa, the word symbolizes being human. This meaning is also expressed in other languages. In Shona, a Zimbabwe language, the word unhu means the same thing. The same meaning is expressed by Ubuthosi in Ndebele, another Zimbabwe language. In Botswana, the word both expresses the same meaning whilst, in Tanzania, it is ubuntu. Congo, Angola, Makwi, Mozambique and Uganda use the words bomotu, gimuntu, umunthu, vumuntu and umuntu respectively. Similarly, in Kinyarwanda, the mother tongue in Rwanda, and Kivundi, the mother tongue in Burundi, Ubuntu means human generosity as well as ‘humanity’ in Runyakifara, the collection of dialects spoken by the Banyankore, Banyoro, Bafooro, and Bakiga of Western Uganda and also the Bahaya, Banyambo, and others of Northern Tanzania, Ubuntu refers to the human characteristics of generosity, protection, consideration and humaneness towards others in the community.

Existentialists (Ubuntu) ideology: Conceptual clarification

Ubuntu echoes the African thought of acceptable ideas and deeds, ideas that reflect a sense of bonding and unity, a sense of community. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), Ubuntu can best be described as humanism from the African perspective as proposed by the former head of the Zambian government, Dr. Kenneth Kaunda. Thus, Ubuntu is Africa’s world view of societal relations, social collectivism, and existentialism. It is a social and humanistic ethic, a prism of enthusiastic social relations and engagement that enhances collectivism. The word social collectivism (ubuntu) can be described as the capacity in the African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, cooperation, sympathy, humanity, and mutuality in the interests of building and maintaining communities with justice and mutual caring (Khoza 2006:6; Mandela 2006:444; Tutu 1999:34-35). This view of Ubuntu expresses in totality the innate beauty, perception, belief, and dignity with which the Africans (s) shared among themselves as collective beings before it was colonized. Africans see each other of different tribes and origins as one sharing the same heritage and ideology. Similarly, the New World encyclopedia sees Ubuntu as embodying all those virtuous that maintain harmony and the spirit of sharing among members of a society. Thus, it implies an appreciation of traditional beliefs, cultural patterns, and distinct practices, and a constant awareness that an individual’s actions today are a reflection of the past and will have far-reaching consequences for the future not only to the individual, family, or group but also the society.

Furthermore, Nelson Mandela (former President of South Africa) describes Ubuntu as a philosophy constituting a universal truth, a way of life, which underpins an open society (Mandela, 2006). A society that is open to ideas, changes, and actions that can promote oneness, in terms of the development, growth, and sustenance of the society. This is similar to the Mahatma Gandhi *Ahimsa* of India. This could be further expanded to mean a society based on inclusiveness, one in which every member is a reflection and mirror of the other members and the society, participating fully and actively towards achieving a common goal with love, sincerity, fairness, equity, justice, and empathy to the vulnerable population, and non-violence. It is a movement of consciousness devoid of prejudices and imbued with a sense of equity and justice.

Existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology and Vulnerable Citizens

Vulnerability refers to the unavailability of protection which renders people, families, organizations, and societies incapable to withstand adverse conditions and impact from multiple stressors when they are exposed. Vulnerability is most likely being exposed to the chance of being attacked or harmed physically or emotionally, socially, and economically thus rendering the victims powerless, helpless, defenseless, and unguarded. Vulnerability is both structural and situational, often as a result of lack of access to basic existent political representation or power. Due to its versatility, the word vulnerability can be discussed in different areas of endeavors, such as health, education, economics, religion, social and environmental. In the words of Zakour and Gillespie (2013); and Cohn (2016), vulnerability can also be attributed to the way the lives of different groups are structured and shaped by structural patterns based on politics, economics, environmental management practices, race and class relations, the gender-based divisions of labour and other factors. According to Yolanda (2022), a vulnerable population is a term used to describe a group of people who possess some sort of disadvantage. These disadvantages could be social, physical, security, economic, health, etc. Similarly, David and Tanner (2007) see a vulnerable population (citizens) as a population that is highly susceptible to harm, and this can result from interactions between the resources available to individuals and communities, and the life challenges they face. These challenges hinder their collective goal attainment and compromises their existence, limiting and preventing the vulnerable citizens from accessing or performing task unaided as well as meeting their needs and improving their living conditions.,

Thus, vulnerability results from developmental problems, personal incapacities, disadvantaged economic and social relations, the inadequacy of interpersonal networks and supports, degraded neighborhoods and environments, poor or unavailable linkages to build synergy and partnership, and the complex interactions of these factors over the life course. Thus, by implication, every member of a population is susceptible and vulnerable in one aspect or the other. The difference could be that some persons are more susceptible than others or are faced with various degrees of vulnerability.

What Constitute Key Vulnerable Populations

The complexity of life, generally speaking, makes everyone potentially vulnerable over an extended period, due to the differential susceptibility to predisposing factors and risks. Some individuals and groups of the population face greater risk than others and respond to these dislocations of both physical and emotional issues differently, due to some functional and dysfunctional systems in the society. These groups according to Leiyu (2001); Aday (1994); and Lurie (1997), represent diverse groups of individuals who experience wide disparity in access to education, health care, and economic and cultural services and outcomes, and higher relative risk of poor physical, psychological, and/or social health than the population as a whole. This is what makes collective intervention a panacea for the sustainable standard of living for these categories of the population.

An intervention anchored on the ideology of interconnectedness, reciprocity, communism, and mutual relationship. There are many dimensions and classifications of the vulnerable population but there is no definite characteristic classification of key vulnerable populations. This is because every individual in the population experiences one form of vulnerability or the other. However, scholars and the United Nation High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR), (2006), has identified the following populations that can be considered key vulnerable population: These are a group of people who may be physically, mentally, or educationally, economically socially disadvantaged and who may be unable to meet their basic needs and may therefore require specific assistance. Assistance that may likely come from within the community groups or otherwise;

1. Persons exposed to and/or displaced by conflict or natural hazards.
2. Individuals who are cognitively impaired, including those who may not be capable of giving informed consent or standing trial.
3. Children, youth, and women
4. Individuals who are homeless or living in unstable housing situations and loss of income and revenue
5. Those in correctional institutions/prisoners, parolees, and probationers
6. Children in foster care or unstable home environments.
7. Individuals with mental health issues and disorders, particularly those with active psychoses, major depression, suicide ideation, self-harming behaviors, and addiction.
8. Individuals with chronic or acute illness or conditions; medically underserved or underinsured.
9. Caregivers and others who may be especially subject to secondary Post Traumatic Stress Disorders (PTSD) or burnout.
10. Individuals experiencing trauma, violence, abuse, or bullying
11. Individuals who may be at risk for coercion such as students and employees
12. Elderly individuals, particularly those in assisted living or nursing homes or with intersecting risk factors.

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13. Individuals who are socioeconomically or educationally disadvantaged.
14. Individuals from communities of color or indigenous or immigrant communities, particularly when studies focus on experiences of discrimination.
15. Individuals who have engaged in criminal activities, including the use of illegal substances, prostitution, or sexual trafficking and crime.

Other classification of the vulnerable population includes children themselves as children, exceptional children, forcefully and internally displaced persons, the emergent and abject poor, and those in abusive marriage and relationships as well as those with employment issues.

Problems with Vulnerable Populations

Our society is braided with complexities resulting from everyday natural and human activities and interactions; social, economic, educational, agricultural, cultural, religious, information, and technological activities which inadvertently create flux and imbalances in society. One would, therefore, say the problems of the vulnerable populations are the creation and function of the society itself. These problems form the nucleus and value of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) initiative; they include by not limited to the following:

1. Problems of finding safe, affordable housing as most of them live in crowded conditions and places as well as a safe environment
2. Problems of reliable means of transportation to their various areas of endeavors such as work, school, farms, markets, healthcare facilities, etc.
3. Hunger, starvation poor feeding, and general poverty.
4. Problem of unemployment and underemployment. These have contributed to poor financial security which in turn increases vulnerability.
5. Inadequate physical, social security, and insurance, and poor government attention or presence.
6. Susceptibility to diseases and illness as a result of poor access to medication, nutrition, poor sanitation, and a healthy environment.
7. Partnership opportunities to achieve reliable goal
8. The problem of achieving Peace and justice strong intuitions
9. Equitable resource allocation and distribution among the populations
10. Inequality gender disparity and discrimination
11. Sustainable communities and societies where equity and justice prevail
12. Problem of illiteracy poor education, and infrastructural development
13. Building innovative and supportive infrastructures and institutions that enhance the lives of disadvantaged and challenged persons.
14. The problem of creating pathways and linkages to resource systems, opening up opportunities, and promoting partnership and synergy among individuals, groups, and communities.

Existentialist (Ubuntu) Ideology as a Social Therapy for Vulnerable Citizens

The Ubuntu philosophy according to Mbigi, (1997; 1995), Van Den Heuvel, Mangalis & Van de Bunt, (2006:48), represents an African conception of human beings and their relationships with the community that embodies the ethics defining Africans and their social behavior. Nigeria as a major component of the African heritage is equally known to have developed these social collectivism and existentialist orientations as part of its national cultural outlook. They explain that Africans are social beings that are in constant communion with one another in an environment where a human being is regarded as a human being only through his or her relationships with other human beings According to Tutu in Battle (1997:39-43). Therefore, the survival of a human being, especially the vulnerable population is dependent on other people, the community, and society at large. The ecosystem interaction is based on political, social, economic, environmental, cultural, and religious determinants which centrifugal forces in vulnerability and shape the sphere of intervention in these regards. Managing vulnerable populations is a complex web of processes that are tailored towards promoting sustainable livelihood. These approaches follow a pattern of assessment modalities, social inquiry, and implementation considered against specific, weaknesses, opportunities, and likely threats (SWOT), and specific, measurable, achievable, reliable, and timely (SMART) interventions theory and application. The underlying ubuntu interventions towards vulnerable populations are equally anchored on SWOT and SMART concepts. This intervention matrix allows for effective and efficient monitoring and evaluation of interventive procedures, documentation, and

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reportage, and provides a feedback mechanism for assessing outcomes, budgeting, and scaling up interventions as well as providing avenues for strengthening decisions, implementation strategy, and re-planning. This is the hallmark of Ubuntu's ideology in managing vulnerable populations, which relates to Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. By and large, Ubuntu portrays everything good and beautiful and seeks a healthy and peaceful society for all, an egalitarian and just society where every member of society is capable of realizing their potential.

1. Ubuntu and love for the vulnerable: Love in this context is described as an extension of deep affection and goodwill to every member of society. Just as the popular saying "Love your neighbor as you love yourself", Ubuntu preaches compassion, empathy, and communion with others. Just as an individual would want everything good for himself, the Ubuntu philosophy endeavors to see vulnerable populations not as an isolated group to be treated differently, but as an extension of a family whose needs and care are of great concern. This according to Samkange and Samkange (1980), is a virtue encompassed and embedded in Ubuntu. We must continue to be our brother keepers irrespective of the challenges and demands at hand. Children of the society in this context are never orphans. They are and belong to the community and as such must be taken care of by those who profess Ubuntu whether closely related or not.
2. Ubuntu and Social Justice for the vulnerable: SDGs Goal 16 particularly emphasizes peace and justice in strong institutions to promote equity and fair play in human interactions and to give members of the society hope for an egalitarian society irrespective of culture, creed, race, or language. Building strong justice institutions and an egalitarian society that will guarantee and enhance democratic processes and equal opportunity to all categories of people in the society. Institutions that promote quality education, good health, and well-being. According to Proven, Du Toit, and Engelbrecht, (2006), the practice of Ubuntu unlocks the capacity of an African culture in which individuals express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, humanity, and mutuality in the building and maintaining communities with justice and communalities. Social justice according to Obeten (2021), refers to the application of justice in a social context concerning how society is organized how people relate with one another, and the extent to which they have responsibilities towards one another. Thus, the essence of social justice is to provide and ensure even distribution of resources that will benefit the generality of the public and opposed to sectionalization or individualization as professed by the apostles and disciples of capitalism (Obeten 2021). Social justice is therefore embedded in the ubuntu ideology and explains why collective responsibility is central to Africans. Therefore, ubuntu speaks of communal living and a social justice system that involves group support, sharing of resources, and cooperation. These also extend to sharing burdens at difficult moments with the view of finding and solving challenges as they arrive. The social justice system as preached by Ubuntu philosophy, creates a balanced scale for actions and intervention and vulnerable populations are ensured of a fair deal in resource allocation and an all-inclusive conflict resolution mechanism based on justice, equity, and fairness. Justice is sought out at community bases and is restorative where justice is seen to be served and the bearer being compensated equally.
3. Ubuntu and Security/Protection of the Vulnerable Population: Vulnerability threatens the security of the larger population both economically and socially. Every breakdown, lawlessness, mischief, and compromise of security architecture in society is tied to the failure of the community to represent itself through communal engagement by the people's failure to recognize their strengths and weaknesses. Most of the threat to peaceful coexistence is due largely to joblessness, underemployment, scarcity of resources untold poverty, and lack of or inadequate access to resource systems and linkages. Thus, exposing vulnerable populations and denying them their fundamental and inalienable rights spells a doom for their collective existence and enterprise.
4. A typical example of a failed social justice system is the 2021 protest against the Nigeria Police Force - End Special Armed Robbery Squad (ENDSARS), the protest that was hijacked by politicians and hoodlums to wreak havoc in the society, public, and government infrastructures.
5. The application Ubuntu model is to enhance collective social and conventional security and insurance for its members including the weak, the vulnerable, and the strong. These categories of vulnerable people can be connected or linked to unemployment benefits, pensions, and gratuity, work compensation benefits, etc., for self-reliance and even community development. Ubuntu adopts the military dictum 'An injury to one is an injury to all'. That means every member of the community irrespective of class, status, creed, color, race, culture and religion to be treated on an equal basis. The community with prejudices is constituted and expected to stand shoulder to shoulder with all its members in all circumstances and situations. There is solidarity and concern for its members who are bereaved or confronted with one challenge or the other. These according to Broodryk (2005) include visiting sick people who are not necessarily one's relatives, sending condolences to a bereaved family, adopting an orphan as one's child, providing food for the needy in the community, assisting the elderly in many ways, and greeting others in a loving, friendly and compassionate way.

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6. Ubuntu and Good Governance for the Vulnerable Population: In every society, the administrative structure and governance strategy play a key leading role in the sustainability of the society. The principles of ubuntu underscore the importance of good governance because it promotes acceptance, confidence, partnership, trust, probity, and equitability in resource management and human development. Good governance, which is intertwined with business ethics, is considered critical in organizational practice, as well as in general corporate productivity (Rossouw, 2005:105). The founding principles of business ethics and corporate governance are in line with the Ubuntu philosophy of regarding all members of an organization as part of the community. It is this direct involvement of and with community members that brings about greater solidarity, love, caring, and sharing within a grouping and organization.

A major governance challenge in current governance issues has been corruption, which reveals the moral depravity and badness of the perpetrators (Broodryk, 2005; Moloketi, 2009; Nyarwath, 2002). Generally, corruption is caused by a lack of commitment to moral beliefs by the perpetrators, which in turn is due to weak value systems and the moral will of an individual towards other people. Corruption is a moral issue and blitz to sustainable development especially, where the perpetrators are fundamentally and fantastically corrupt, as Prime Minister of England Boris Johnson described Nigeria in 2018. This suggests insensitivity on the part of the government to meet the needs of her citizenry in raising their standard of living. It presupposes a negative dive and a departure from positive curves of development expected to trickle down to the populace. Such a moral issue affects human life in a negative way where individuals abuse their personal and official powers (Broodryk, 2005:198). Corruption comes in different forms, which include nepotism, misuse of power, favoritism, and bribery, as well as prejudices and compromises. While corruption manifests itself in the relationship between individuals and institutions, as a practice, it is mostly rooted in the operations of market forces (Moloketi, 2009:239). Unlike the Ubuntu teaching, corruption is a pursuit of individual prosperity, as opposed to the common good of all and society. Corruption erodes the common fabric, undermines community perpetuates poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment, and further widens the economic and social gaps between the various class structures. Ultimately, corruption leads to a rise in the blatant pursuit of individual gains. When the awareness of moral rights and wrongs is strong, corruption can easily be rooted out. This is the principle behind the community-based Ubuntu philosophy. To curb corruption, for instance, the Ubuntu philosophy must be the essence of a value system that underpins a commitment to eliminate corruption (Moloketi, 2009:243, 247). There is also a need for strong robust democracies, where all sectors of society, including the media and organizations of civil society, the private sector, trade unions, traditional leaders, and faith-based organizations have a responsibility to educate and promote the values of Ubuntu philosophy and anti-corruption. The above observations indicate that there is much that the Ubuntu philosophy can contribute towards business ethics and good corporate governance issues. Under the African Ubuntu philosophy, people should be aware that individualism greed, and profit achieved by sacrificing other community members, contravenes the true foundations of humanity (Ubuntu). The notion of Ubuntu or humanity teaches community and organic solidarity, caring, and sharing among the members of a community or organization.

Conceptualization of the problem

Man's existence and daily activities have brought about lots of challenges; social, economic, cultural, religious, environmental, and geographical problems. These multifaceted challenges have seriously affected the serenity, security, peace, and the development of society in diverse ways and further polarized the living conditions of the citizens and society. The magnitude and impact of these problems make it even more difficult for individuals, groups, families, and communities to handle unaided thus, necessitating collective intervention and building nexus for communalism and by, groups, local, national, regional, and international bodies for inclusivity. In all of these, the African inclusive ideology and philosophy of "Ubuntu" is multifaceted strong internal mechanisms for promoting general development and safety nets to meet people's needs, and assistance to engender adjustment processes and optimal functioning at the individual, group, family, and community levels. This paper, therefore, adopts a descriptive methodology in examining social collectivism and existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology as a panacea for the improved and sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria.

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

The Maxims of Existentialist Ideology -Ubuntuism

Maxims according to Obeten (2021), are rules that guide an individual or group of individuals to act and react in a certain way in a given circumstance. Maxims could also be said to be ethical principles guiding and directing individuals or groups to behave in certain ways and manner wherever they find themselves. Ubuntuism is an African philosophical framework that is characterized by the interconnectedness of all things and beings; the spiritual nature of people; their collective/individual

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identity and the collective/inclusive nature of family structure; oneness of mind, body, and spirit; and the value of interpersonal. It promotes collective engagement in problem-solving over individualism, therefore, all actions for the care of vulnerable people must be considered against the backdrop of collectivism.

Externalism connotes that, individuals are responsible for creating purpose or meaning to their own lives and situations. Therefore, creating conditions that promote the growth and sustainable living standards of people, especially the vulnerable people is innate inertia, thus defining our collective existence which is made up of our relationship to other people and things around the world with each choosing and committing to meaning and direction of life. It entails taking decisions or actions that are beneficial and in the best interest of the society. Thus, Ubuntu which is rapidly gaining worldwide acceptance and coverage is based on the following three principles or rules innate in its beliefs (Samkange and Samkange 1980);

1. To be human is to affirm one's humanity by recognizing the humanity of others and on that basis, establish respectful human relations with them. These maxims could be likened to the popular golden rule which says "Do to others what you would like them to do to you".
2. If and when one is faced with a decisive choice between wealth and the preservation of the life of another human being, then one should opt for the preservation of life for its sanctity and sacredness. This is to say; human life remains sacred based on the ubuntu philosophy and by no means or reason should anybody take the life of another or temper with it. This principle is the model of non-violence a component of Ubuntu ideology.
3. The third maxim posits that as a principle deeply embedded in traditional African political philosophy, the king owed his seats, including all the powers associated with it, to the will of the people under him. This maxim speaks volumes of the expected role, duties, and functions leaders in all climes ought to perform. They are the custodians of the people's will and must function and act in the interest of the people. They are indeed leaders to execute resolutions of those they are leading. There cannot be a king, if there are no subjects to be governed. The subjects elect or select the king but then they give their enterprise as subject to the king in words and deeds.

Thus, Ubuntu as a philosophy is associated with words such as sympathy, compassion, benevolence, solidarity, hospitality, generosity, sharing, participation, cooperation, openness, mutuality, affirming, available, kindness, caring, harmony, interdependence, obedience, collectivity and consensus. The term is the opposite of vengeance and the opposite of violence, confrontation, opposite to retribution, and Ubuntu values life, dignity, compassion, humaneness, harmony, and reconciliation (Hailey, 2008; Wichtner-Zoia 2012; Tutu 1997).

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Ubuntu is an existentialist and a social collectivist approach to mutually sustaining the gains of communalism and inclusiveness in the affairs of the society which gives every member of the society a sense of belongingness. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), Ubuntu can best be described as humanism from the African perspective as proposed by Dr. Kenneth Kaunda. Of Zambia, Julius Nyerere Nelson Mandela and Desmond Tutu. Ubuntu is Africa's world view of societal relations, social collectivism, and existentialism. It is a social and humanistic ethic, a prism of enthusiastic social relations and engagement that enhances collectivism. Social collectivism is the capacity in the African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, cooperation, sympathy, humanity, and interests in bounding members of the society (Khoza 2006:6; Mandela 2006:444; Tutu 1999:34-35). Thus, existentialism and social collectivism in African is seen in the prism of our collective enterprise and implies an appreciation of traditional beliefs, cultural patterns, and distinct practices that have positive impact on our collective lives as a people with diverse cultures and orientations.

Conclusion

Ubuntu ideology within the African soil is a critical mass in human development that promotes inclusiveness and collective enterprise in all environmental and human interactions, activities, and interventions in society. This ideology plays a prominent role in African cultural, political, social, and economic life as well as in managing social problems. As a multidimensional model of development, it guarantees participatory approaches, interconnected in activities and developmental sustainability, and in managing humanitarian emergencies, especially as it affects vulnerable populations, the poor, infirmed, the sick, the deprived, the neglected, the physically and emotionally challenged persons and the less privileged in society. Thus, the vulnerable populations are protected by a systemic network of communal interventions that guarantees them a sense of belonging, welfare, and sustainable livelihood options. This paper, therefore, relied on descriptive methodology to amplify social collectivism and existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology as a panacea for the improved and sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria.

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Recommendations

The essence of life generally is to create a better and more formidable front for other humans to strive for. This is the ideological imperative of social collectivism (ubuntu) and the existentialist model to assist, midwife, mitigate, ameliorate, and promote collectivism in all circumstances of interventions.

1. Managing humanitarian crises and interventions should be built on the scale of empathy, integrity, trust, adaptability, and authentic leadership structure that will provide the needed support and results especially when managing vulnerable populations
2. Group dynamics and interconnectedness should be promoted as a strategy for promoting and improving the lives of citizens as well as sustaining the gains and synergy of these social collectivities in driving policy options for addressing the needs of vulnerable populations in Nigeria.
3. Vulnerability is not a curse, therefore, interventions towards vulnerable populations should not be anchored on victimization, favoritism, labeling, and stigmatization rather they should promote affectionate relationships, mutual respect, dignity, competence, confidence, and capacity building that will enhance their adaptation, readjustment, and full functioning as members of the society.
4. Social collectivism (Ubuntu), in itself is a security mechanism for data and information management in society. Identity and identification of vulnerable citizens are easier to manage within that nucleus; hence, interventions should be specific and center-based within this communal ideology

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An Investigation on Perception of Teaching Practice Exercise among Mathematics Education Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study adopted descriptive survey research design to investigate the perception of teaching practice exercise among Mathematics education students in public University in Cross river State, Nigeria. It was guided by two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of 410 (195 male and 215 female) final year science education students during the 2021/2022 academic year in both University of Calabar and Cross River State University who were selected through census approach were used sample for the study. One instrument titled “Perception on teaching practices Questionnaire (PTPQ) was employed to gather the data. The reliability of questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha method yielded 0.89. The first hypotheses were tested using population t-test and the second null hypothesis was were tested using the independent t -test for hypothesis two inferential analysis. Both were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed there is significant difference in the perception of Mathematics student-teacher on the practice exercise and there was a significant difference in male and female Mathematics student-teacher perception toward teaching practice exercise in public universities in Cross River State. it was concluded that student teacher perception influences in their involvement and interest in teaching practice exercise. Based on the conclusion of this study, it was recommended, amongst others, that workshops, conferences and seminars should be organised regularly for student - teacher to sustain and or maintain the high level of interest and motivation toward teaching practice exercise they claimed to have.

Keywords: Student-teacher, teaching practices, Mathematics Education, gender

Introduction

Mathematics is a core subject in most educational systems, and its importance cannot be overemphasized. Mathematics provides students with problem-solving skills, logical thinking, and analytical skills that are essential for success in various fields. Every individual needs the knowledge of Mathematics to function intelligently and efficiently because the subject is an integral part of the human life (Ibok, Meremikwu, & Umoh, 2020). There is virtually no discipline one can think of which does not require Mathematics or have inputs from Mathematics. It is important for prospective math teachers to engage in teaching practice exercises (Ibok, Thomas, & Nyong, 2019). Nonetheless, it doesn't appear like a very good impression of the crucial teaching methods exercise was given to the student-teachers of mathematics during their training. Their perspective on the activity deviates from the goal for which it was intended. They usually approach the practice with amusement and a

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lukewarm attitude. Their behavior throughout the teaching practice exercise appeared to be a combination of cooperation and insincerity. This had an impact on the program's proper execution and explains why there are currently too few high-quality math teachers in our educational institutions (Ibok & Unoh, 2019). A key component of professional mathematics teachers' training is teaching practice exercises. For a vocation to be considered perfect, it must possess certain attributes and characteristics. Across the globe, teaching is regarded as one of the primary occupations. As a result, it is crucial that it fulfill the prerequisites for a vocation. In addition to offering social services, having professional ethics, and having the freedom to work, it is essential that aspiring professional teachers have both theoretical and practical training. The goal of this is to introduce the students to the necessary practical side of their chosen field of study. The aspiring professional educators are equipped with the fundamental resources necessary to meet the demands of their line of work. According to Parr et al. (2021), teaching is the process by which a person who is thought to be more educated imparts knowledge to students.

During the teaching practice phase of their apprenticeship, pre-service teachers can use the skills they have learned in the classroom. During this internship, a variety of theoretical pedagogical skills are implemented in real-world settings. It offers student teachers the chance to apply what they have learned in the classroom. They have direct interactions with the pupils, the course materials, and the educational setting. Pre-service teachers benefit from this by having the chance to expand their knowledge and skill sets as well as learn new ideas, approaches, and strategies for the real classroom and teaching in general. The goal of teaching practice is to develop successful, purposeful, and effective teachers who will in turn develop successful citizens in the future.

The teaching process gives the students the chance to grow personally in terms of their professional competencies, knowledge, comprehension, abilities, and pedagogical ideals. But Goller et al. (2019) provided the following summary of the goals of instructional practice:

i) giving students the chance to put theory into practice; ii) providing real-world experience, chances, and resources to help them become more confident and knowledgeable; iii) giving them the capacity to plan, direct, and oversee a classroom with appropriate disciplinary measures; iv) developing a global and mutual sense of cooperation as well as the exchange of ideas and attitudes. According to Escribano and Hervis (2018), there exists a high correlation between the caliber of teachers and the caliber of educational systems. This makes it more difficult for new teachers to receive their training and emphasizes the necessity to find student teachers who are highly motivated to teach. The view of the reasons behind pursuing a teaching career has generally been linked to prospective teachers' professional work performance and persistence (Abós et al., 2018; Muñoz-Fernández et al., 2019; Watt & Richardson, 2020). Research indicates that educators who perceive their students' motives highly are more dedicated to their students' learning and professional growth (García-Poyato et al., 2018; Goller et al., 2019; Watt et al., 2017). According to Abós et al. (2018), there is universal consensus that student-teachers who exhibit higher levels of professional commitment, lower levels of burnout, and extraordinary adherence to teaching techniques are the most motivated. In fact, there is evidence linking student teacher perception to professional burnout, teacher optimism, and feelings like delight or anxiety (McLean et al., 2019; Parr et al., 2021). Under this situation, knowing how student teachers view becoming teachers and growing as future educators will assist shape policies that draw in quality educators (Han & Yin, 2016). Additionally, it permits the consideration of how to more effectively support student-teachers during their formative years and as they enter the teaching profession (Tardif & Tremblay-Gagnon, 2021).

However, there isn't much research examining the impact of demographic factors like age, socioeconomic status, and sex on teaching practices in the empirical studies currently available on students' and teachers' perceptions of those practices (Alexander et al., 2020; Stolk et al., 2021; Watt et al., 2017). Variations in the traits, dispositions, and skills of male and female student-teachers may have an impact on their willingness to actively engage in instructional activities (Ibok, et al., 2022).. In their research, Klassen et al. (2011) discovered that gender roles had a major impact on Omani people's decisions to become teachers, but not Canadian people. Azman (2013) conducted a study in Malaysia which revealed that gender-based teaching approaches have a notable positive impact on female pupils. According to Butt et al. (2010), female may also choose teaching as a career due to their perceptions in terms of the desire to acquire new skills and knowledge, and the desire to balance work and family obligations. Conversely, men decide to become teachers for more external factors, including vacations, social lives, or financial security (Alpaslan & Damli, 2022; Balyer & Özcan, 2014; Struyven et al., 2013). In a study, Elacqua et al. (2018) discovered that gender is a crucial factor influencing a person's willingness to pursue a career in teaching. In this context, new research by (Akar, 2019; Akpochafo, 2020) has revealed that choosing to become a teacher is influenced significantly by one's gender. It is true that the objectives and perspectives of male and female student-teachers about instructional techniques differ (Eghtesadi- Roudi, 2021; Gratacós & López-Jurado, 2016). In their study, Bhana and Moosa (2016) discovered that male and female students have different motivations for selecting teaching as a career. Therefore, it is the duty of both pre-service

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teachers and teacher educators to prepare students for teaching practice. It is the responsibility of teacher educators to set up appropriate learning materials, instructional strategies, and assessment procedures to get their pupils ready for this kind of program. Enough exposure of the pupils to courses that will improve their on-field performance is required. As important as professional development for educators is in producing qualified instructors, pupils' attitudes about self-adequate preparation for upcoming tasks are equally important. One of the main components of their professional training is teaching practice exercises, for which the students must be ready. In addition to personally preparing for the exercise, they must submit to the instruction and direction of their educators.

Main and Specific Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study is to investigate the perception of teaching practice exercise among mathematics education students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to examined

1. The level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise in Cross River State
2. The difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise in Cross River State

Research questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise?
2. What is the difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested, at 0.05 significant level, to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference between perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant difference between perception of male and female Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State.

Methodology

The research area was public Universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was used adopted for this study. The researchers used this design because the researchers were able to draw large sample of student-teacher in their various institutions, described, examined their perception and gender difference toward teaching practices exercises. The population for the study consisted of all the 410 final year students in science Mathematics education Department in public Universities in Cross River State (University of Calabar and Cross River State University) were used for the study. A sample of 410(195 male and 215 female) science education students during 2021/2022 academic year were selected via Census approach. Census sampling was used because the population is small enough to handle by the researchers for the study. The break down of the sample shows that 298 students were selected from University of Calabar while 112 were selected from Cross River State University.

One instrument was used for data collection titled “perception of teaching practices Questionnaire”. Parts A and B made up the questionnaire. Part A needed information on students’ demographic data such as sex; while section B was consisted of 20 items to test students’ perception on teaching practice exercise. The instrument was based on four-point Likert Scale of strongly agreed which was scored 4 points, agreed scored 3 points, disagreed scored 2 points, and strongly disagreed scored 1 point. The questionnaire items were developed by the researchers and was face-validated by two experts in both Measurement and Evaluation and Science Educators in the University of Calabar. Corrections were pointed up by the experts and adjusted by the researchers and the document was considered legitimate or valid. The reliability of the questionnaire was established using 50 final year students in public Universities in Akwa Ibom State who were not part of the main study but however shared similar characteristic with the study population. After the trial test, Cronbach Alpha method was used and the internal consistency estimates which gives 0.89. These were adjudged high and guaranteed the use of the instrument for the research. Since the reliability index is above 0.50, the estimates were considered high enough for the study. The Statistics Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer programme was used to analyze the data collected. Research questions were answer using descriptive statistics. The hypothesis one was tested using population t-test while hypothesis two was tested with independent t-test.

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Results

The result of the analysis is presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while population t test and independent t-test were used to test the null hypotheses at .05 significant level.

Research Question 1

The level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise.

To provide answers to this research question, overall expected mean and observed mean of the 20 items constructed were compared and the result is presented in table 1

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise.

Variable name	Number of items	Expected mean	Observed mean	Decision
Perception of teaching practice	20	50.000	53.621	Agreed

Sources; Field work, 2023

The result from table 1 showed that the overall observed mean of 53.621 was higher than the expected mean of 50.000 which agreed with the high level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State.

For the Mathematics education student-teacher perception on disposed to teaching practice exercise to be significantly in public Universities in Cross River State, the score on perception of disposed to teaching practice exercise should be significantly greater than 50.0 which is the expected average for the perception on disposed to teaching practice exercise. This hypothesis was tested with a test of one sample mean (population t-test) and the result is shown in table 1

Table 2: Population t -test analysis on the extent of Mathematics education student-teacher perception on involvement in teaching practice exercises (N= 410) Expected mean=50.0

Variable	Observed mean	Mean error	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Perception of teaching practices	53.621	0.211	4.267	1.161	.000	Significant

*Significant at the .05 level, df =409, t-critical =1.96

Sources; Field work, 2023

The information in table 2 also revealed the computation t-value of 17.161 associated with p-value of .000 at .05 level of significant shows that there is a significant difference in the mathematics education student- teacher perception on involvement teaching practice exercise .. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research Question 2

What are the difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise?

Table 3: Mean of perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise (N=410)

Gender	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Decision
Male	195	48.17	11.23	Agreed
Female	215	59.40		

Sources; Field work, 2023

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The results presented in Table 1 reveals that the mean score of female Mathematics student teacher toward teaching practice exercise was (59.40) which higher than their male counterpart with mean score (48.17) which implies that there is a difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise with favour of female student teacher. Female student- teacher with the mean score of 59.40 have more positive perception on involvement in teaching practice than their male counterpart with mean score of 48.17.

H02: There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers to teaching practice exercise in tertiary institution in Cross River State.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is gender while the dependent variable is student –teacher perception on teacher practices . In testing this hypothesis, the mean scores of the male and female education student teacher perception to teaching practice exercise in public universities in Cross River State their mean, standard deviation were computed and compared using independent t-test and the results is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Results of independent t - test analysis of the significant difference between perception of male and female Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State(N=410)

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Perception of teaching practice	Male	195	48.17	4.889	22.591	.000	Significant
	Female	215	59.40	5.173			
	Total	410	50.56	4.267			

*Significant at the .05 level, t-critical =1.96, df =408

Sources; Field work, 2023

The result presented on Table 4 shows that the t value of 22.591 associated with p value of .000 shows that there is a significant difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers to teaching practice exercise in tertiary institution in Cross River State.. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected at the 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of findings

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant difference in perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State. In public University in Cross River State. This is in line with Escribano and Hervis, (2018) who noted that the quality of educational systems is closely connected with the quality of its professors. The finding concurred with García-Poyato et al., (2018); Goller et al., (2019); Watt et al., (2017) who stated that student –teacher with high perception of motives is more devoted to their professional development. According to Abós et al. (2018), there is universal consensus that student-teachers who exhibit higher levels of professional commitment, lower levels of burnout, and extraordinary adherence to teaching techniques are the most motivated. The finding is in line with Han and Yin, (2016) who found that student-teacher perception on involvement in teaching practice exercise to be significantly high

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant influence of gender on Mathematics education student-teachers perception on involvement of teaching practice exercise in Public Universities in Cross River State. The finding is in line with Ibok, et al., (2022) who see differences in characteristics, attitudes, and abilities of male and female student-teacher who could influence their active participation in teaching practices. This is in line with Fray and Gore, (2018) who found gender influencing the decision to teach or teaching practices The finding agreed with the finding of Klassen et al. (2011) who discovered that gender roles strongly influenced choosing teaching as a vocation. Conversely, men decide to become teachers for more external factors, including vacations, social lives, or financial security (Alpaslan & Damli, 2022; Balyer & Özcan, 2014; Struyven et al., 2013).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded from this study that there was significance difference in perception of mathematics education student-teacher on involvement in teaching practice exercise. However, female students have more positive perception toward involvement of exercise exercises than their male counterpart in students in public

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universities. Therefore, students' positive perception and gender are important factors to be considered by educational authorities among other strategies to promote and motivate students in involvement in teaching practices exercises in Cross river state any tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this investigation, the following recommendations were made:

1. Mathematics education students should be better directed as to the relevance of teaching practice exercise to their preparation as prospective professional teachers.
2. More information about the necessity to alter one's perspective and adopt a positive attitude about the activity should be provided to male education students. They would eventually be able to use their pedagogical abilities on the field more effectively and learn more from the program as a result.

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Comparative Relationship between Leadership Role and Job Satisfaction among Senior Public Secondary School Teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined comparative relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses were framed to guide the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 3,360 teachers (male, 2,062 and female, 1,298) during the 2016/2017 academic session in FCT, Abuja. A total of 360 teachers (male, 206 and female, 130) were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire was validated and a logical validity index of 0.71 was obtained. The questionnaire was also pilot tested and yielded 0.87 reliability coefficient. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that, there is a significant relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Based on the findings, it was concluded that, there is significant relationship between leadership role of provision of instructional materials and maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. It was recommended that, management of FCT Secondary Education should provide enough funds to enable school principals provide instructional materials and maintain school facilities for job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Keywords: Relationship, Leadership role, teachers and job satisfaction

Introduction

Secondary education does not only occupy an important place in the Nigeria education system; it also serves as a link between the primary and tertiary levels. The Federal Republic of Nigeria in National Policy on Education, (2004) defined secondary education as the education a learner receives after primary education and before the tertiary stage. Secondary education prepares the individual for useful living within the society as well as the pivot on which the pursuit of higher education is built. Considering its importance, members of the public, therefore, places much importance to its development and hold high expectation of this level of education.

The head of secondary school leadership in Nigeria is the principal, who administers the school with other teaching and non-teaching staff. Accordingly, the principal is regarded as the chief executive of the school, who is responsible for all that, happens in the school. He or she is the accounting officer of the school and his position in the school is so germane to the extent that, the school cannot exist without that position (Babayemi, 2021). The principal is expected to provide leadership by performing certain roles as legally defined targeted at achieving efficient teaching and learning in the school.

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These roles according to Igwe (2018) among others include, provision of adequate instructional materials and resources, maintenance of school facilities, assigning teaching load and other responsibilities to teachers, communication with teachers on job expectations, and supervision of teaching and learning activities,

Principal is expected to perform his leadership roles by providing adequate instructional materials and resources for effective teaching and learning, reward and provides incentives for teachers who are outstanding in the discharge of their duties, carryout regular supervision of teaching and learning activities to ensure that the right teaching method, relevant materials and content are used (Igwe, 2018). Igwe, (2018) further stated that, he or she is equally expected to maintain school facilities to create conducive environment for both teachers and students to be able to teach and learn adequately and effectively, assign teaching load and other responsibilities to teachers with the skill and training to do them. More so, the principal is to communicate regularly with teachers on job expectations to ensure that teachers are adequately informed of what is expected of them and work enthusiastically towards goals attainment. These according to Ogunsanju (2022) will boost teacher's morale and ensure effective teaching and learning. Igwe, (2018) summed it up that principal performing his leadership roles will ensure teachers perform their jobs effectively for the smooth running of the school and the realization of educational goals as well as ensure teachers' job satisfaction.

Since leadership is an interactive relationship between leaders and followers, which is characterized by influence and identification according to Nwankwo (2019), the principal needs the co-operation of the teacher who is the key facilitator for the realization of educational goals. The teacher according to Ukeje (2018) is a professional, who in a morally accepted manner imparts knowledge and learning experiences at his disposal to stimulate, guide, direct and facilitate learners to acquire adequate mastery of the skills being imparted. Ukeje (2018) defined a teacher as someone who causes learning to take place, someone who imparts knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. Section 8 (6) of the national policy on education (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2004), stated that, no educational system may rise above the quality of its teachers. The teacher is therefore an important factor in the quality of education and the realization of educational goals in any nation including Nigeria. For quality service delivery to be achieved in any endeavour, job satisfaction of employee is a key component (Spector, 2010). Accordingly, for the teacher to provide quality education required for the ultimate advancement of the society, his job satisfaction should be guaranteed.

The impact of teachers' job satisfaction is very crucial to the long term growth of any educational system around the world. Man tends to render certain services if he is reasonably satisfied in his chosen career. Job satisfaction is desired in virtually all human organizations such as family, church, industry, civil service and the school for the purpose of attaining their stated objectives. Fafunwa in Popoola (2023), noted that both boys and girls in the traditional education settings performed their best in the art of hunting, farming and cooking when their morale were boosted by their parents through praises, incentives and other forms of motivation. However, those who excelled in the discharge of their duties or functions were normally praised and guided for better performance in future while those who performed below expectation were cautioned, assisted and guided for a good performance in future. The efficiency of any school system depends to a large extent upon how effectively human resources are utilized.

Locke (1986) in Popoola (2023), observed that job satisfaction refers to the pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experience. Eneasator (1990) in Emaikwu, (2018), defined job satisfaction as the totality of an individual's psychological, social and physical well-being with regard to his work and job performance Teachers need to enjoy positive job satisfaction in order to be more functional and contribute meaningfully to the teaching and learning process in the school. In the context of this study, job satisfaction connotes teachers' pleasurable or positive and emotional state resulting from their job experiences in terms of availability of teaching and learning materials, supervision of teaching and learning activities, functional school facilities among others as provided by the principal to make teaching and learning condition very conducive for the teachers and students as well. Komolafe, (2020) stressed that if teachers lack job satisfaction their physiological needs will rarely be met and this will negatively influence their productive capacity, but if teachers enjoy job satisfaction, they tend to exhibit unprecedented love to their students through adequate teaching and research. Oluremi, (2019), observed that falling standard of education in Nigeria could be attributed to lack of job satisfaction among practicing teachers. He noted that the deplorable condition of teachers, is likened their low moral which invariably affects teaching and learning. Ogunsanju (2022) reported that the public is worried over this lack of job satisfaction among practicing teachers in the secondary school system in Nigeria. This according to him placed the government in Nigeria and union of teachers (NUT) in constant face – off over lack of job satisfaction resulting in the incessant strike action embarked by the teachers in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. This ugly trend in the school system is evidently shown in the frequent work stop and long closure of schools resulting in truncated academic calendar and the complete breakdown of discipline, learning and scholarship.

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Fagbemi in Popoola (2023) noted that these days, teachers are found outside their school premises and even within the school premises, selling goods to the detriment of their duties. Part of the reasons for these actions of the teachers could be absence of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

However, it is widely believed in Nigeria that, teacher's job satisfaction is directly related to teachers' salary that is the quality of teachers' take-home pay. As a result of this, the Federal Government had made frantic efforts in the past to improve the quality of teachers' take-home pay. The most recent is the 27.5 percent increase in salary of teachers in public schools in Nigeria in line with the new teachers salary scale through the Governor's forum in 2009 (Komolafe, 2020). In addition, the Federal Capital Territory administration in 2005 approved special allowances for teachers posted to the rural areas, science teachers and a 100 percent payment of housing allowance in advance annually (federal capital secondary schools education board 2022). Again, the president of the National Union of Teachers (NUT) when making suggestions on how to improve the educational system, in Nigeria, said, "Government must develop a remuneration and reward system that will promote job satisfaction of teachers" (Komolafe, 2020). Despite the effort by the government teachers' still exhibit lack of enthusiasm and commitment for the job, absenteeism, truancy and engaging in petty trading within and outside the school, above all leave the profession suddenly in search of greener pastures. (Huberman, 2023) This according to Huberman (2023) may affect the quality of teachers in schools and students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations (SSCE, WAEC NECO and JAMB).

More so, in recent times, principals of secondary schools in Nigeria have been accused by stakeholders in the education sector (parent, teachers, students etc) of failing to provide effective and adequate leadership role for their schools. They are said to be inefficient in performing their leadership roles practices and accused of various lapses and offenses that result in teachers not deriving satisfaction with their job (Dubi 2018). Also, the instructive competence of the school principal is the engine that motivates teacher's performance and job satisfaction, but most principals are not effective in their leadership behaviour, they treat teachers as tools believing that teachers can be treated anyhow; their query to them after a minor mistake; they do not recommend them for promotion as at when due; don't reward teachers and provide incentives to motivate them; they supervised teachers only to find fault without providing useful advice, fails to communicate with teachers on job expectations regularly and so on. In addition, Government at all levels have been accused of concentrating more on improving the quality of teachers' take home pay without doing much on other areas that may have impact on teachers' welfare. All these according to Bussinge, (2019) may have significant effect on teachers attitude to work and job satisfaction. These issues have been a source of concern to this researcher to go into this area to unravel whether principals' leadership roles practices have any significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Over the years the government both at Federal and State level had put in more efforts in the past to improve the quality of teachers' take-home pay (salary) with the believed that in Nigeria, teacher's job satisfaction is directly related to teachers' salary, which is the quality of teachers' take-home pay. The most recent is the 27.5 percent increase in salary of teachers in public schools in Nigeria in line with the new teachers salary scale through the Governor's forum in 2010. Also, the Federal Capital Territory administration in effort to improve the welfare of its' teachers in 2018 approved special allowances for teachers posted to the rural areas, science teachers and a 100 percent payment of housing allowance in advance annually (federal capital secondary schools education board 2018). In spite of this teacher's still exhibit lack of enthusiasm and commitment for the job, they exhibit absenteeism, truancy and engaging in petty trade within and outside the school during school hour and above all leaving the profession suddenly in search of greener pastures. All these attitudes may be a clear demonstration of lack of job satisfaction among teachers in Nigeria in general and Federal Capital Territory in particular. This lack of job satisfaction among teachers despite improvement in their take home pay (salaries) may have been attributed to poor leadership role performance by school administrators (Principals) in providing good and conducive working environment particularly leadership role of providing adequate instructional materials and maintenance of school facilities for effective teaching and learning. In recent times, principals of secondary schools in Nigeria particularly in FCT have been accused of failing to provide effective and adequate leadership role for their schools. That they are said to be inefficient in performing their leadership role and accused of various lapses in the discharge of their duties. They fail to provide adequate and relevant instructional materials to enable teachers teach their lessons with ease and maintain school facilities to provide teachers with conducive classrooms and furniture for both teachers and students, comfortable office accommodation etc It is in lieu of the above premise that the study sought to determine whether besides salary there is significant relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory.

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Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study was to determine the comparative relationship between leadership roles and job satisfaction among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfactions among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.
2. The relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. What is the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary School teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary School teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and the type of survey design was correlational design. According to Emaikwu (2018) correlational research design attempt to established relationship between two or more variables. The design is suitable for this study as the study sought to establish or determine the relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Population of the study consists of 3,360 teachers (male, 2,062 and female, 1,298) during the 2016/2017 academic session drawn from all the 59 public senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. A total of 360 teachers (male, 206 and female, 130) were sampled from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher titled Relationship between Leadership Role and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (RLRJS) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Management and Test and Measurement from the Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. This enabled the researcher to obtained logical validity index of 0.71 and the value so obtained was considered sufficient to use the instrument. The questionnaire was pilot tested using 50 teachers from two (2) schools that were part of the population but not part of the sampled population. The data collected was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient which yielded 0.87. The coefficient indicated high internal consistency which proved that the instrument was reliable for the study. A total of 360 questionnaires were administered, 336 were filled and returned representing 86% return rate. The data collected was analyzed using simple descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. A mean cut-off point of 2.50 was used for decision. The research hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

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Table 1: Mean and standard deviation showing the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria **Scale = 2.5**

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Instructional materials	3.07	1.87	High
2	Low relationship	2.98	1.77	High
	Aggregate	3.03	1.82	High

Field work

Table 1 shows the aggregate mean of 3.03 and standard deviation of 1.82 is above the scale mean of 2.50. The result from the analysis shows that, the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction is high among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among senior public secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria. **Scale = 2.5**

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Maintenance of school facilities	3.09	1.87	High
2	Job satisfaction	3.17	1.87	High
	Aggregate	3.13	1.87	High

Field work

Table 2 shows the aggregate mean of 3.13 and standard deviation of 1.87 is above the scale mean of 2.50. The result from the analysis shows that, the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction is high among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Testing of the hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional materials job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient showing relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria

S/N	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)	Level of Significance (0.05)
1-	Availability of instructional materials		
2-	Job satisfaction among Teachers	0.70	Significant

df= 334 $\alpha = 0.05$,

Table 3 shows the result of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) analysis of availability of instructional materials and its relationship with job satisfaction among teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. The calculated r is 0.70 and is found to be significantly high when compared with the table value of 0.05 at degree of freedom. Since the calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

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Table 4: Correlation Coefficient showing relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria

S/N	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)	Level of Significance (0.05)
1.	Maintenance of school facilities		
2.	Job satisfaction among Teachers	0.80	Significant

df= 334 $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 4 shows the result of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) analysis of maintenance of school facilities and its relationship with job satisfaction among teachers. The calculated r is 0.80 and is found to be significantly high when compared with the table value of 0.05 at degree of freedom. Since the calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary schools' teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. This follows that availability of instructional materials gives job satisfaction to teachers. The above finding corroborates with the view of Alio and Ezeamaeyi (2019) who stated that, availability of instructional materials not only support and reinforces teaching, also provides the teacher with interesting compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to learn more and that, when the students are given the chance to learn through more senses than one, they can learn faster and easier. According to them, when the students learn faster and easier the teacher feels satisfied. Alio and Ezeamaeyi (2019) went further to elaborate that, availability of instructional materials assists teachers in overcoming physical difficulties that could have hindered their effective presentation of a given topic and a shift from teacher to student-centered classes. This according to them removes stress from the teachers and that teacher whose work is not stressful derived some level of satisfaction and fulfillment in their jobs.

Again, it was discovered that there exists a strong positive correlation between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among teachers in the study area. This means that, school facilities, has a strong relationship with job satisfaction, by implication; it is evident that job satisfaction among teachers depends to a large extent on good and functional school facilities. It is important to note that teachers and indeed their students need conducive environment to be able to teach and learn adequately and effectively. The above finding correlates with the opinion of Ntukidem (2022) who submitted that, since man loves beauty and becomes relaxed and comfortable within a beautiful environment, it is therefore imperative that school principal should endeavour to put the existing structures into proper function by either renovating or do regular repairs to meet with expected standards. He further maintains that attractive school plants with superior lighting, attractive decoration, comfortable seating and useful service facilities such as libraries, multi-purpose room give teachers a sense of belonging, fulfillment and satisfaction. Supporting the opinion of Ntukidem (2022) National Clearinghouse for Educational Facilities, (2023) stated that, teachers want to work in quality facilities and have access to appropriate and needed materials and resources. An important factor in the employment decisions made by individual teachers is the quality of school facilities, that poor school conditions increase the likelihood that teachers will leave that school and even the teaching profession. North Carolina State Board of Education, (2019) is in agreement that, teachers must have working conditions that allow them to do their jobs, and facilities must be designed, well-maintained, and utilized to support job satisfaction. Teachers who leave their teaching assignment cite opportunities for a better teaching assignment, professional development, leadership, empowerment, and facilities and resources and dissatisfaction with workplace conditions as the main reasons they seek additional employment.

Conclusion

In view of the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. The study further reveals that there is significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Comparative Relationship between ... (Onabe, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737816>

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of Federal Capital Territory Secondary Education Board and other stakeholders should provide enough funds for the provision of adequate instructional materials to enable teachers perform their duties effectively to give them Job satisfaction.
2. The management of Federal Capital Territory Secondary Education Board and other stakeholders should provide enough funds for the maintenance of school facilities to give teachers a comfortable environment to carry out their duties and have Job satisfaction.

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Influence of Infrastructural Facilities on Academic Performance among Government Secondary School Students in Dutsin-ma Local Government Area, Katsina State

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma, Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina State. A Cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of 2376 (male 1234 and female 1142) students of government junior secondary school class two (JSS11) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Dutsin-MA local government area of Katsina State. A sample size of 146 (Male 86 and female 60) Students were selected from the target population using stratified sampling technique as the respondents. Three research questions and one hypothesis were used to elucidate information from the respondents. Self-structured questionnaire was used to generate information from the respondents. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Administration and Planning and the other from Educational Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was 0.76. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level using Chi-square statistics. The findings of the study revealed that school facilities influence students' academic performance. The study concluded that there is a Positive and significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Dutsin-Ma LGA Katsina State. It therefore recommends among others, that the government should make available all the necessary school facilities to enhance teaching and learning as well as students' academic performance.

Keywords: School facilities, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials.

Introduction

This study is to examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-MA local government area of Katsina State. Education is a fundamental pillar in the development of any society, serving as a catalyst for individual growth, social progress, and economic advancement. Nigeria, like many other developing nations is faced with various challenges in its education sector. While efforts are being made to improve access to education, most concerned stakeholders in education still advocated for increase in the quality of education provided. One crucial aspect influencing the quality of education is the state of schools and its facilities. The adequacy and functionality of these facilities play significant roles in shaping the learning experiences and consequently, students' academic performance.

School facilities are materials used directly or indirectly for the benefit of influencing teaching and learning in education. They are described entirely as the school plant and examples are the school classroom blocks, staffrooms and offices, laboratories, workshops, libraries, laboratories equipment, consumables, audio-visual aids, electricity, water, chairs, tables, stationeries, playground, storage spaces and others which school has (Sabitu, Babatunde, & Oluwole, 2012). Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo, (2021) also referred to school facilities as the school site, the buildings, the playgrounds, the equipment and other material resources provided in the school for effective teaching and learning operations. They continued by referring to School

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facilities as that comprising the location, weather, lighting, ventilation, floor, space per pupil, health, and safety conditions, play areas, cafeteria and library.

Recognizing the pivotal role of education, nations worldwide invest substantial resources in developing and maintaining an effective educational system. An integral component of this system is the physical infrastructure of schools, encompassing classrooms, libraries, laboratories, recreational areas, and other facilities that collectively contribute to the overall learning environment. According to Bimler (2009), infrastructural school facilities includes; buildings such as administrative block, (which comprises, the principal's office, vice principal and staff rooms, classroom) laboratory, sick bay, music room, typing pool, school gymnasium, cafeteria, security post, school farm, sport field, school shop, storage house, computer room, language laboratory, constant water supply and more. Dusabemariya, Andala and Ochig. (2020) opined that the purpose of teaching aids is to facilitate meaningful communication between the teacher and the teacher. They are intended to make learning process more engaging and interactive, and to help learners better understand and retain information.

According to Dusabemariya et al., (2020) teaching aids play a great role in enlightening the learners' academic performance in classroom. This is because of the increasing participation and involvement due to the motivational effect created on the teachers and learners in classroom setting. Ngirabakunzi (2017) opined that teaching aids are usually perceived to be motivational materials and deliver enthusiasm in lesson, and that real use of teaching aids results into an interesting learning situation. The use of graphics including charts, posters, sketches, cartoons, graphs and drawings, graphics, communicate facts and ideas clearly through combination of drawings, words and pictures.

In the context of junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria, examining the influence of school facilities on students' academic performance becomes imperative. Dutsin-Ma, situated in the northern part of the country, represents a microcosm of the larger educational landscape in Nigeria. Understanding the dynamics between school infrastructure and academic outcomes in this specific region is crucial for designing targeted policy reforms and interventions. There is a growing body of research that suggests a strong relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance. Adequate and well-maintained facilities have been associated with positive learning experiences, enhanced teacher-student interactions, and improved overall educational outcomes. Conversely, deficiencies in infrastructure may hinder the teaching-learning process, impeding students' ability to reach their full academics potentials. Inadequate facilities will surely affect the smooth teaching and learning process in all schools. The major factor that seems to contribute to poor academic performance is inadequate provision of educational facilities in schools. Akhihero (2011) posited that educational curriculum cannot be sound and well operated with poor and badly managed school facilities, most especially the physical resources that facilitate effective teaching and learning process. These included classrooms blocks, laboratories, workshops, libraries, equipment, consumables, electricity and water among others. Various dimensions of school facilities need adequate and urgent examination. These encompass the physical condition of classrooms, availability of libraries and laboratories, access to modern technology, and the overall safety and hygiene of the school environment. Understanding how these factors interplay in the specific context of Dutsin-Ma will shed light on the unique challenges and opportunities faced by student in the area. Moreover, the socio-economic context of Katsina State, coupled with the prevailing educational policies, adds layers of complexity to the relationship between school facilities and academic performance. Economic disparities, cultural factors, and government initiatives all contribute to the educational landscape, shaping the experiences of students in junior secondary schools.

As stakeholders continue to advocate for educational reforms in Nigeria, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the nuanced relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. By doing so, it seeks to inform policymakers, educators, and community leaders, paving the way for evidence-based interventions that can enhance the educational journey and future prospects of students in the study.

There has been so much outcry about the academic performance among junior secondary school students in Dutsin-MA Local Government Area of Katsina State, State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB, 2023). This problem may have originated from poor and inadequate school facilities in the schools. Some of the identified problems include poor infrastructural facilities, such as; administrative block, inadequate classrooms, laboratories, computer laboratories and its accessories and school gymnasium. Also identified are lack or inadequate instructional facilities such as teaching materials, laboratory equipment, television, projectors cardboard, science practical facilities, pictures, maps and the rest. Improper school physical environment, such as school playground, sport field and equipment, agricultural farm for practical and school bus and the rest (Ngirabaunzi, 2017).

Inadequate school facilities affects teaching and learning processes in school. This is because of the large class size. It is a known fact therefore that students' academic performance depend purely on their level of exposure to the learning facilities within the school environment, (Oasigbovo & Oasigbovo, 2021). In this case, the classroom condition, like

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overcrowding, noise, few desk, lack of ceiling fans, appropriate doors and windows for ventilation and the aesthetic condition of the school, making teaching and learning uncondusive within the environment. Irrespective of the fact that some of these facilities are available in some schools like the Government Pilot junior secondary school, in Dutsin-MA, the expectation was that these facilities should be enough and effectively used for teaching and learning, but the reverse is the case in Government Pilot junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma LGA.

This has also brought lack of interest in the practical/demonstration activities on various subjects by the students and has also resulted to their poor academic performance and failure. This is the reason why the authors decided to examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma Local Government Area, Katsina State

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma local government area, katsina state. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance of government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA
2. Examine the influence of instructional facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA
3. Identify factors affecting management of school facilities and academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA

Research Question

1. What is the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?
2. What are the instructional facilities influence Students' Academic performance of government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?
3. What are the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma LGA?

Research Hypothesis

1. H_{O1} : There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance of government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA.

Methodology

A Cross-sectional survey research design was used for this study. The population for the study consists of 2376 (*male 1234 and female 1142*) Junior Secondary School (JSS) Students in Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina state. A sample size of 146 (Male 86 and female 60) Students were selected from the target population using stratified sampling technique as the respondents. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Influence of School Facilities on Student Academic Performance Questionnaire" (ISFSAPQ). The questionnaire was made up of two sections; Section A and Section B. Section A consists of the respondents' demographic data, while section B consists of fifteen (15) items based on the research questions. The questionnaire items were structured using Four (4) Likert point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2, Strongly and Disagree (SD) 1 scales of measurement. Self-structured questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents face to face with the help of some teachers, and this was done to ensure that at least 99% of the questionnaire items was returned. Weighted mean was used in the study as a method of data analysis. A criterion mean of 2.5 is used to judge the mean response from the respondents. Mean response above 2.5 cut-off level is accepted and mean response below 2.5 cut off-level is rejected.

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Results

The descriptive socio-demographic characteristics of the sample are presented in

Figure 1: Sex Distribution of the Respondent (Source: Fieldwork 2024)

This is because in the northern Nigeria only male gender were given much privilege to attend school while female gender was encouraged to go into marriage the at the younger age Figure1.

Figure 2: Age Distribution. (Source: Fieldwork 2024)

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About 50.7 % of the respondents were between ages (15-16), followed by those between ages (13 -14) whom constitute 35.6%. Ages 17 and above constitute 12.3 while ages (10 -12) constitute 1.4%. The majority were those within ages (15 -16) this is because of the nature of the school enrolment in the region where Child start secondary education between ages (12-13), by the time they will reach JSS 3 they will be around ages (15-16).

Research Question 1:

What is the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?

Table 1: Impact of school Infrastructural Facilities on junior secondary school students' Academic Performance

S/N	Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
1	Enough classrooms influence academic Performance.	146	3.21*	1	1.47	Agree
2	Equipped school library influences academic Performance.	146	2.76*	2	1.18	Agree
3	Adequate school playground.	146	2.69	3	1.17	Disagree
4	The presence of computers helps students to expand their knowledge and skills.	146	2.56	4	1.17	Disagree
5	Adequacy of Laboratory Equipment in the Schools affect performance.	146	2.30	5	1.08	Disagree

Cumulative Mean: 2.70 (Disagreed)

Results presented in (Table 1) revealed the influence of school infrastructural facilities on academic performance. The variables were as follows; enough classrooms influence academic performance (MS = 3.2) was ranked first. This is because having a conducive place for the students sit down and learn may enhance their ability and concentration for effective academic activities. Equipped school library influences academic Performance (MS =2.7) was ranked second among the infrastructural variables that influence academic performance. This is because after having adequate classrooms where teaching and learning is been taken place, the next place is the library where student use to go and read and master what they learn in the class room. Having adequate school playground (MS = 2.6) was ranked third among the infrastructural component the influence academic performance, having a playing ground make the student to relax and learn some physical activities. The presence of computers helps students to expand their knowledge and skills (MS= 2.5) was ranked fourth among the factors, now a days there are a lot of E-learning materials and programs that aid student academic performance. Adequacy of laboratory equipment in the schools affect performance (MS=2.3) was ranked fifth among the variables, adequacy of those equipment will enhance students' knowledge while conducting practical. In summary, Table 3.1 revealed the mean score results on the influence of school infrastructural facilities on academic in performance Dutsin-Ma, where three (3) statement out of five (5) items (3, 4, and 5) had their mean score below the critical mean of 2.70 (2.69, 2.56 and 2.30) and two (2) had their mean score above the critical mean score of 2.70 indicating that the respondent in items (1 and 2).

Research Question 2:

What are the instructional facilities influence Students' Academic performance of government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?

Table 2: Influence of Instructional Materials on Academic Performance

Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
6 The use of typewriters as teaching aid help in learning process and academic performance.	146	2.86	4	1.09	Agree
7 Visual aids teaching and learning process and academic performance	146	2.88	3	1.11	Agree
8 Graphics, posters and charts aids influence teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	3.23	1	1.03	Agree
9 Use of audio aids teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	2.99	2	1.00	Agree

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10	The use of projectors influence teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	2.45	5	1.23	Disagree
Cumulative Mean:					2.88	Agreed

Table 3.2 revealed the mean score results on Influence of Instructional Materials on Academic Performance in Dutsin-Ma, where one (1) statement out of five (5) items had its mean score below the critical mean of 2.88 (2.45) and four (4) had their mean score above the critical mean score of 2.88 indicating that the respondent in items (6, 7, 8 and 9). The use of graphics, posters and charts aids influence teaching and learning process and academic performance (MS: 3.23), Use of audio aids teaching and learning process and academic performance (2.99), visual aids teaching and learning process and academic performance (MS: 2.88), the use of typewriters as teaching aid help in learning process and academic performance (MS: 2.86) were rand (1, 2, 3 and 4) respectively.

Research Question 3:

What are the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma LGA?

Table 3: Factors Affecting Management of School Facilities

	Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
11	Inadequate funding affect management of school Facilities.	146	3.27*	2	1.09	Agree
12	Nature of Schools' physical facility affect its management.	146	3.45*	1	0.97	Agree
13	Lack of equipped laboratory technicians affect its management.	146	3.01*	3	1.166	Agree
14	Political factors management of school Facilities.	146	2.60	5	1.27	Disagree
15	Use of poor-quality components and materials by the maintenance department and contractors.	146	2.99	4	1.26	Disagree
Cumulative Mean:		3.06				Agreed

Results presented in Table 3.3 are the factors affecting management of school facilities. From the Table 3.3, two (2) out of five items were below the critical mean of 3.06. These are items (19 and 20). Political factors management of school Facilities (MS: 2.6) which was ranked fifth, use of poor-quality components and materials by the maintenance department and contractors (MS: 2.99) which was rank forth. While three (3) out of the five items were above the critical mean of 3.06. These include items (16, 17 and 18). Inadequate funding affect management of school facilities (MS: 3.45), lack of equipped laboratory technicians affects its management (MS: 3.45), political factors management of school facilities (MS:301) and they were ranked (1st, 2nd and 3rd) respectively. This means that those with mean score above the critical mean have agreed with the statements while those below the critical mean disagreed with those statements.

Discussion of findings

Research question one aimed to investigate the correlation between infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in a government junior secondary school in Dutsin-Ma LGA. The respondents supported the notion that school infrastructural facilities have a substantial impact on students' academic performance. This aligns with the perspective of Davis-Langston (2012), who asserted that the school environment holds the most significant influence on learning and academic performance. In addressing research question two, the study revealed that the use of instructional materials plays a crucial role in influencing student academic performance. The respondents agreed that instructional materials significantly affect students' academic outcomes. Aman's (2021) research supported these findings, emphasizing the notable positive impact of instructional materials on student performance compared to those who did not utilize such resources. Moreover, the study underscored the importance of educational facilities in the teaching and learning process, contributing to improved student retention, assimilation, and overall students' academic performance.

For research question three, the investigation sought to identify the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government Junior Secondary School Dutsin-Ma LGA. The respondents acknowledged that inadequate funding, a lack of equipped laboratory technicians, and political factors are major contributors to the challenges in managing school facilities. Semako (2019) and Mewomo, Ndlovu, and Iyiola (2022) supported these findings, citing factors such as the provision of equipped laboratories, adequate funding, and the condition of physical facilities as significant elements affecting the effective

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management of public secondary school facilities. Additionally, issues like the availability of funds, occupants' knowledge of facility management, absence of policy guiding facility management practices, the state of deterioration of facilities, design concepts, poor or inadequate funding in education, and economic factors were identified as causes for the improper management of educational facilities. Furthermore, political influence was noted to impact the provision of funding for the management of educational facilities.

Conclusion

This research has delved into the critical relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria. The findings underscore the significant influence that well-equipped school facilities have on shaping students' educational outcomes. As educational stakeholders consider strategies for improving academic performance, it is clear that prioritizing the development and maintenance of school facilities should be a central focus. This study contributes valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on enhancing educational quality and effectiveness in the local context, providing a basis for informed decision-making and targeted interventions to benefit the students in junior secondary schools

Recommendation

With reference to the findings from the study, the following recommendation were made;

1. Proper and adequate infrastructural facilities should be provided in the school.
2. Adequate use of instructional materials by the teachers should be encourage.
3. Government should create good school environment for effective learning.
4. Proper funding of educational sector and employing qualified technicians by the government.

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Influence of Psycho-Demographic Variables on Academic Resilience among Secondary School Students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstracts

Resilience in an academic context is known as academic resilience. Academic resilience is a term that refers to a student's capacity to overcome difficulties that are considered severe or chronic in the educational process being undertaken. The study investigates influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ibadan, Oyo State. 350 (200 male and 150 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Questionnaire titled IPVARASSS was content and face validated by experts in the field of psychology and analysed with a high reliability index of a .91. The generated five null hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significant. The findings of the showed that level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan is high ($\bar{x} = 4.01 > 3.00$), there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan ($T_{(348)} = .352, p < .05$), interest in schooling ($r(348) = .424p < .05$), learning orientation ($r(348) = .415p < .05$) and psychological flexibility ($r(348) = .502, p < .05$) had relationship to academic resilience among secondary school students. Based on findings of the study, the researcher concluded that psycho-demographic variables such as gender, interest in schooling, learning orientation and psychological flexibility are potential predictors of influences on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The researcher therefore, recommends among others that teacher and parents should assist students to find ways and means of enhancing their resilience in education and provision of adequate resources for teaching and learning that is capable of giving hope to students should be a requirement.

Keyword: Academic resilience, Interest in Schooling, Learning Orientation, Psycho-demographic, Psychological flexibility

Introduction

Resilience is the ability to maintain psychological stability in dealing with stress (Keye and Pidgeon, 2022). Resilience is one of the characteristics that enable academic achievement and also what distinguishes individuals who succeed from those who do not. Grotberg, (2017) explains that resilience is a combination of three sources (acceptance, purpose and flexibility), one of which is I am, which is a source that comes from within a person, resilience can be increased if someone has a power that comes from within themselves. In the academic context, resilience is characterized by students who have the ability to reverse academic failures and achieve success even though other things are performing poorly and failing, where this ability is called academic resilience (Cassidy, (2016)

Academic resilience has the ability to successfully cope with changes or adversity in academic situations; and dynamic processes of overcoming the negative effect of risk experiences with positive outcomes, avoiding negative trajectories associated with such risk. The literature on resilience among children and students shows that resilience tends to be dichotomized (Aldridge, Fraser, Fozdar, Ala'i, Earnest, and Afari, (2016) into individual focused characteristics and protective factors. In general, individually focused characteristics are identified through strategies directed towards modifying internal goals, problem solving strategies, and feelings of self-worth. Protective factors, on the other hand, focus on coping, and are reflected in strategies directed towards regulating or modifying external resources or support. Research has provided evidence for the significant role of resilience, when it is conceptualized as successful adaptation despite risk. For example, resilience has

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been used to characterise individuals who overcome difficult and challenging life circumstances and risk factors (Croson, and Elder, 2018).

The development of children in schools is threatened by all sorts of adversities such as lack instructional materials, incompetent teachers, bad school environment and poor teaching facilities that bear life-altering consequences for school going students. In the face of threats to human development, an integrated and global science of academic resilience informed by evidence based research is very much needed to inform government and international policymakers and intervention matters that mitigate risks and build academic resilience in children. Generally, the dynamic process of school going students show adaptive functioning in the face of significant adversity (Martin and Marsh, 2016).

In other words, this academic resilience will lead to an inferential concept conditional upon two major criteria. Firstly, there ought to be exposure of “serious risk” and secondly, there must be evidence of “good adaptation” in school environment. Unfortunately, despite strong scholarly interest in the study of students’ resilience, there is still a general lack of integrative understanding on the processes leading to academic resilience in development. A student may have an excellent academic record yet be experiencing chronic adversities in their personal life which could cause a major impediment to their academic success. Or, a poor test result could be crushing to a student who has never received anything other than good results, and could thereby cause a major impediment to their academic resilience if they have never learned how to bounce back from what they may perceive as a major failure (Agasisti and Longobardi, 2017). A common academic experience such as receiving a poor grade in a test or a piece of homework could require academic resilience if it constitutes an acute adversity for a particular student, given their circumstances, which could cause a major impediment to their academic success.

Interest of students in schooling occurs when "students make a psychological investment in learning. They try hard to learn what school offers. They take pride not simply in earning the formal indicators of success (grades), but in understanding the material and incorporating or internalizing it in their lives (Shapiro, Dundar, Wakhungu, Yuan, & Harrell, 2015). Students are engaged when they are involved in their work, persist despite challenges and obstacles, and take visible delight in accomplishing their work. Interest of students in schooling also refers to a "student's willingness, need, desire and compulsion to participate in, and be successful in, the learning process promoting higher level thinking for enduring understanding that leads to academic resilience (Taylor and Parsons, (2020)" Interest of students in schooling is also a usefully ambiguous term for the complexity of 'interest' in school and it is beyond the fragmented domains of cognition, behaviour, emotion or affect, and in doing so encompass the historically situated individual within their contextual variables (such as academic performance and resilience) that at every moment influence how engaged an individual (or group) is in their learning.

Interest of students in schooling is frequently used to, "depict students' willingness to participate in routine school activities, such as attending class, submitting required work, and following teachers' directions in class (Balwant, 2017)." However, the term is also increasingly used to describe meaningful student involvement throughout the learning environment, including students participating in [curriculum](#) design, [classroom management](#) and school building climate. It is also often used to refer as much to student involvement in extra-curricular activities in the campus life of a school/college/university which are thought to have educational benefits as it is to student focus on their curricular studies and enhance their academic resilience.

In a number of studies interest of students in schooling has been identified as a desirable trait in schools; however, there is little consensus among students and educators as to how to define it (Taylor, & Parsons, 2020). Interest of students in schooling is used to discuss students' attitudes towards school, while student disinterest identifies withdrawing from school in any significant way. The construct of student interest and its accompanying theories can better explain the linkage between communication and learning. Student academic resilience can be fostered by school factors such as immediacy and clarity and stimulated by student interest (Kahu, 2018).

Over the years, gender differences in academic resilience may explain the aforementioned differences in academic achievement. Gender plays an important role in resilience. Examining the gender perspective in academic resilience provides an insight regarding how male and female students conceptualize and express academic resilience in order to overcome setbacks. According to Morales (2008) gender has been identified as a crucial aspect of resilience yet gender differences in the resilience process have not been the focus of resilience studies. The combined effect of social background and gender is not analyzed frequently. Women and resilient students, who use education as a channel of mobility, are similar in that they tend to follow the manifest regulations of the education system.

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This is demonstrated by their effort towards better grades and maximizing class attendance (Ceglédi 2018; Fényes 2010b; Fényes and Ceglédi 2015). The strategy seems effective in public education: females graduate from secondary education with better results and enter higher education in larger proportions, while resilient students, a subset of those who face social disadvantages, can also be regarded successful. After higher education, however, inequalities arise again: the literature shows the glass ceiling phenomenon for both women and disadvantaged students compared to less disadvantaged and male students, which may materialize in earnings or in the obtained positions (Laurison and Friedman 2019).

This category of orientation is characterized by students who are primarily interested in studying a particular subject 'for its own sake'. They are intellectually interested in the subject and are interested in studying at a higher level. Most students with this orientation already had some experience of the subject before coming to school and so tended to enhance their academic resilience (Bentley, 2022). They want to follow up aspects of the subject beyond the defined syllabus. Four distinct types of orientation and these were academic orientation, where the student's goals involved the academic side of school life; vocational orientation, where the student's goal was to get a job after school; personal orientation, where the student's goals were concerned with their personal development; and social orientation where the student's goals focused on the social side.

The first three of these orientations could be divided into two sub- types according to whether the student was directly interested in the content of the course or whether they were studying the course more as a means to an end. These sub-types distinguished in each case between intrinsic and extrinsic interest in the resilience of students in their academics. Agasisti and Longobardi, (2017) found that the concerns that students had while studying at school were intimately connected to the type of orientation they had, and that these orientations and their concerns helped to make sense of the amount of effort the student put into different aspects of their academic resilience.

Psychological flexibility affects individual problems. Kashdan and Rottenberg (2017), state that psychological flexibility has actually been known for more than 50 decades, but has different names such as resilience and self-regulation. Literature shows there are similarities and differences in the conceptualization of constructs, there are similarities in behavior changes (actions or thoughts) in response to changes in the environment. Whereas the difference in cognitive flexibility involves adjusting to changes in cues in the environment, while psychological flexibility does not only involve adjusting more aspects. According to Hayes in Bloombury (2022), psychological flexibility is defined as a person's ability to change or persist in conditions of behavior that benefit personal values. Rutter (2020), describes psychological flexibility as an individual's ability to adapt to stressful or adverse events. Kashdan and Rotterburg (2022) defining psychological flexibility as a measure of how a person: (1) adapts to the demands of the situation, (2) reconfigures mental resources, (3) shifts perspective, and (4) balances desires, needs, and domains life.

Psychological flexibility is more recent than cognitive flexibility and psychological flexibility studies can be done in clinical and non-clinical conditions while cognitive flexibility focuses on neuropsychology which is a clinical part (Whiting et al, 2015). There are several studies related to psychological flexibility, findings conducted by Foote et al (2016) show that someone who has psychological flexibility can reduce academic failure and increase academic resilience. Psychological flexibility can help a person have prosocial behavior which can help to improve their academics. Psychological flexibility is also closely related to self-efficacy, optimism and hope. The study of Montiel (2016) explains that psychological flexibility can prevent increased psychological distress such as anxiety and depression.

All this studies has been done to address the possible reasons behind the high failure rate and school dropout, however there still appears to be an increase in the rate of this worrisome dropout. Could psycho-demographic factors which has to do mainly on students' personal factor be the reason behind this lack of commitment and engagement to academic resilience? Therefore, the study tends to examines influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience among students in Ibadan, Oyo, Nigeria.

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Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to investigate influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience of Secondary School Students in Ibadan Nigeria.

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Research Questions

One research questions was formulated to guide the conduct of this study:

What is the level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between academic resilience among secondary school male and female students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between level of interest and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
3. There is no significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
4. There is no significant relationship between Psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Methodology

This study used the descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design was selected because it is appropriate for this study and there was not manipulation. The target population for this study consists of all secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ibadan, Oyo State. 350 (200 male and 150 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. This is in three stages; the first stage randomly selections of 3 local government (Ibadan North, Ido and Akinyele) from the 11 local government areas that make up Ibadan, which lead to the stage two, six (6) schools (two schools from each local government) were selected through simple random sampling techniques from the earlier selected local government, and at stage three, purposely sampling techniques was adopted in selecting participant (in secondary school students) students from the sample schools.

After face and content validation of the instrument by experts in the area of psychology, Questionnaire titled IPVARASSS was appropriately administered to the selected respondents and collated for analysis.

. The data collected was analyzed through the use of frequency distribution, hypothesis 1 was analysed using T-test while hypothesis 2, 3 and 4, respectively were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

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Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between academic resilience among secondary school male and female students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

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Table 2: Summary Table of t-test for independent measures showing comparison of Academic resilience based on gender

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	Sig
Academic resilience	Male	136	100.79	10.95	348	.352	.549
	Female	214	99.92	11.19			

From Table 2, the result showed that there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state ($T_{(348)} = .352, p < .05$). From the table above, a mean score of 100.79 for male participants while female participants had a mean score of 99.92 with a mean difference of 0.87 and statistically significant.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between level of interest and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 3 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Interest in schooling	350	97.89	13.35	348	.424	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 3 show the significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .424, p < .05$. This implies that interest in schooling had moderate influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 4 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience of students

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Learning orientation	350	38.02	5.67	348	.415	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 4 show the significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .415, p < .05$. This implies that learning orientation had moderate influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between Psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 5 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Psychological flexibility	350	45.11	7.01	348	.502	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 5, showing the significant relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .502, p < .05$. This implies that psychological flexibility had strong influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

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Discussion of Findings

Table 1 research question 1 is in line with the study of Brookhart, & Durkin, (2013) found that self-selected texts increased the readers' positive feelings about reading and improved achievement scores. The study found that self-selection was important when attempting to motivate students to read and that non-fiction could be just as motivating as fiction (Moss & Hendershot, 2014). The importance of student interest was a key take away from that study, and this is an important factor for teachers to remember, although not just with middle school students. Hargrove's (2014), results of this teacher's study and determined that the student-directed assignment was successful, resulting in increased energy and output. The teacher-led assignment showed the same results that led to the teacher's initial frustration and motivation to begin the study in the first place. The teacher viewed students as individuals and took their interests and personalities into consideration when creating the assignment.

In table 2 hypotheses 1, the result indicated a significant relationship which is in support with the study of Scales et al in Jonson (2019), whose work showed that resilience has a high correlation with students' achievement index in America at various schools at the high school level. Various studies have also shown that the various resilience skills developed by students can have a significant effect on academic performance (Christine, 2010). Several studies related to academic resilience focus on specific ethnic groups or groups of students (Gizir & Aydin, 2009; Borman & Overman, 2021). However, research on academic resilience is relevant to all students, including students at the university. All students at all academic levels tend to experience various difficulties, challenges, pressures, or poor performance in the academic process (Martin & Marsh, 2020). Resilience should be a concern for universities considering this can be a factor in student survival in studying at higher education. On the other hand, this study contradicts a study by Khalaf (2014). The study shows that men and women have significant differences in the level of academic resilience. Research conducted by Sarwar et. al. (2010) in Pakistan also identified that men are more resilient than women. Research conducted by Morales (2020) also shows that there are significant differences between men and women in academic resilience where women are more resilient than men. Somchit and Sriyaporn (2010) also stated that women have higher resilience than male students.

Also, table 3 hypothesis 2 is in accordance with the study of Hardr, Sullivan, and Crowson (2012), that state that when students saw value and relevance in what they were learning and how it could help achieve their goals, they were more likely to have increased interest, put forth effort, and graduate going on to post-secondary opportunities (Hardr, Sullivan & Crowson). In addition, the more competent they felt about their abilities, the more likely they were to commit to continued study and education. Therefore, the interest these students felt in their learning had a significant impact on their feelings of success, and, ultimately, their performance. It is important that students view their learning experiences as authentic and meaningful. Marks (2010) purported that three factors influence student engagement and learning: personal background and orientation toward school, school initiatives, and subject matter. She looked at 24 schools undergoing restructuring, specifically grades 5, 8, and 10. Students completed surveys about their attitudes, behaviors, and experiences, their general school experience, and their personal/family background. She was able to draw several conclusions from her study. First, like Skinner et al., student engagement decreased as grade level increased; high school students reported the least positive orientation toward schools. By contrast, feelings of being supported in the classroom were highest among elementary school students. Subject matter did have an effect on reports of authentic work (that is, student feeling that the work is challenging and relevant). Successful students were more engaged, but students who reported feeling alienated were less so (Marks).

Furthermore, the result of table 4 hypothesis 3 is in accordance to the work of Csikszentmihalyi, Schneider, and Shernoff (2023). Their study found that student engagement increases when students find the task challenging, balanced, relevant, and under their control. They determined this by asking 526 students to track their academic activities throughout the course of the school day and record how they felt during those activities. Students felt most engaged when participating in a group activity or discussion as opposed to listening to a lecture. They concluded that, based on Csikszentmihalyi's (1997) flow theory, concentration, interest, and enjoyment in an activity must all be present. All of the studies above support the argument that student interest plays a key role in student success. Interest is necessary for continuing motivation and learning. Like Hardr, Sullivan, and Crowson, Shernoff et al. found that challenge and satisfaction in task completion will motivate students and engage their interest.

Lastly, result of table 5 hypothesis 4 is in line with the study of Zepke and Leach (2010), which states that when students have some semblance of control over their learning, they are more likely to be engaged and achieve academic success. Tella, Adeniyi and Olufemi (2018) support this claim with the conclusions of their study. They found that locus of control, interest in schooling, and self-efficacy are all factors in predicting academic achievement. Locus of control refers to an

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individual's belief of what causes success. It can be internal, where the student believes success is due to personal effort and ability and is more likely to work hard. Students who believe in an external locus of control will attribute their success to luck or fate, and may not put forth as much effort. More significant to this review are the results that analyzed student interest in schooling. Several studies have shown that differences in resilience between men and women are also influenced by biological factors (Rinaldi, 2010), socio-demographic factors (Wardhani et al., 2017), and socio-emotional factors (Sunarti et al., 2018). Generally, women tend to use emotion-focused coping more often in dealing with pressure when having problems, namely by placing more emphasis on overcoming emotional impacts that arise (Brougham et al., 2018). Physical differences also have an impact on the resilience of men and women. Women are considered more difficult to manage and access resources that can help them solve the problems they face, so they are more easily swayed than men (Kumar & Quisumbing, 2014). If analyzed more simply, it can be concluded that resilience is formed and influenced by at least three things, namely: personality factors, biological factors, and environmental factors (Herrman, 2016).

Conclusion

The weighted mean is greater than the standard mean. This implies that the level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan is high. There was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan. Also, interest in schooling had significant relationship to academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. There is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan, there is significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. More so, there is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, the result indicates that there was a significant contribution of of interest in schooling, psychological flexibility and learning orientation to academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan and lastly, factors such as interest in schooling and learning orientation predict and determine academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The teachers and parents should help students to find ways and means of enhancing their resilience in school
2. Provision of adequate resource for teaching and learning should be a requirement.
3. Enough time should be given to the implementation of new innovations.
4. Full parent participation in the welfare of their children should be seriously considered in schools (strengthening the PTA).
5. The school leadership should play a leading role when it comes to students' performance and resilience since it is believed that a school is as good as its head.
6. Findings of the present study may help to improve academic resilience of students as they are a wakeup call to students, teachers, school managers and parents among many education stake holders.

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Analysis of the Perception of Teaching Methods at Laval University by Senegalese Students

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the perception of pedagogical methods by Senegalese students of Laval University. To achieve this objective, a research problem was developed around teaching methods. The theoretical framework is based on teacher-centeredness and actualizing pedagogical methods. The methodology employed a qualitative approach, using a case study as the research tradition. The participants consist of students enrolled at the University who began their university studies in Senegal. Three students were selected using purposive sampling. To gather data, a semi-structured interview guide was created. Finally, regarding the results, they indicate that Senegalese students have a certain perception of the pedagogical methods used by teachers at Laval University. These students also encounter difficulties in adapting to these methods.

Keywords: students, pedagogical methods, teacher-centeredness, actualizing pedagogy, case study.

Résumé

Cette étude a pour objectif d'analyser la perception des méthodes pédagogiques par les enseignants de l'Université Laval de l'Université Laval par les étudiants sénégalais. Pour atteindre cet objectif, une problématique a été développée autour des méthodes d'enseignement. Quant au cadre théorique, il repose sur le magistro-centrisme et les méthodes pédagogiques actualisantes. Pour la méthodologie, c'est l'approche qualitative qui été utilisées avec l'étude de cas comme tradition de recherche. Les sujets sont constitués des étudiants inscrits à l'Université, mais ayant entamé les études universitaires au Sénégal. Au nombre de trois, les étudiants ont été sélectionné par la méthode d'échantillonnage à choix raisonné. Pour recueillir les données, un guide d'entretien demi-dirigé a été confectionné. Enfin concernant les résultats, ils montrent que les étudiants sénégalais ont une certaine perception des méthodes pédagogiques utilisées par les enseignants de l'Université Laval. Ces derniers rencontrent également des difficultés pour s'adapter à ces méthodes.

Mots-clés : étudiants, méthodes pédagogiques, magistro-centrisme, pédagogie actualisantes, étude de cas.

Introduction

In Francophone Africa, the traditional teaching model strongly influences pedagogical practices. Consequently, the emphasis often lies in knowledge transmission rather than empowering learners. The designed curricula aim for general objectives without considering learning outcomes (Kahn & Rey, 2008). According to Vienneau (2006), a learning outcome is neither an objective nor a strategy. It approaches teaching from a different perspective: while objectives specify what the teacher should do, outcomes describe what the student should have learned by the end of a year (Vienneau, 2006). In this type of teaching, the student is seen as a mere subject to act upon. As stated by Not (1979, p.7), "one wants to teach, instruct, train. One teaches a subject to children, meaning one faces two objects: the subject matter and the child; the student is taken out of their child state, directed, shaped, and equipped." These are the teacher-centered or traditional pedagogical methods. In other words, it's a "transmissive mode with normative orientation (MTP1), describing knowledge as objective and cumulative, a pedagogy of the model (and deviation from the model) justifying a positive detour to access it" (Astolfi, 2006, p. 8).

Traditional pedagogical methods correspond to those often prevalent in schools and universities in Senegal. Indeed, most Senegalese educational institutions employ a teaching approach based primarily on the teacher transmitting knowledge to the learner (Gauthier, 2005). With these methods, the learner becomes passive and relies on the teacher for everything. In this type of learning, the teacher prepares the material they will dictate to the students after some explanation of the content (Ndoye, 2000). According to Ndoye (2000), this is often due not only to the attachment to traditional teaching methods but also

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to the often-overcrowded class sizes. In Senegal, it's not uncommon to have classes with over 2000 students in the first and/or second year of university.

On the other hand, in North American universities like Laval University, pedagogical methods prioritize the learner. In these universities, the knowledge transmission process relies on learner independence. Here, teachings are more individual-oriented, taking into account the student's background and experiences. The objective is to assist the learner in constructing their own knowledge with the support of the teacher (Gauthier, 2005). Furthermore, several studies, including Viens, Lepage & Karsenti's (2010), mention a correlation between socio-cultural background and students' difficulties in adapting to certain aspects.

Presenting the context of pedagogical methods allows us to perceive a difference in the teaching approaches used in Senegalese universities and at Laval University. This difference is experienced by Senegalese students currently attending Laval University. This has motivated us to conduct this study, whose objective is to analyze the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students.

Theoretical Framework and Methodology

Theoretical Framework

To study the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students, a theoretical framework is constructed around traditional (Houssaye, 2014 and Gauthier, 1997) and modern (Luckerhoff, Johnson & Guillemette, 2020 and Landry, 2002) pedagogical methods. It is observed that the majority of Senegalese schools and universities practice a teaching approach primarily based on magistro-centrism. This pedagogical tradition is characterized by "seven traits: centrality of the teacher, impersonality of the relationship, strict asymmetry, transmission of knowledge detached from life, highly normative educational ideal, bureaucratic arrangement, charismatic model" (Houssaye, 2014, p. 212). This teaching method primarily relies on lectures, where the teacher is the sole authority in the classroom (Gauthier, 1997).

However, traditional pedagogical methods need to evolve as learners have become increasingly demanding. We are now in an era of innovative pedagogical methods. Indeed, "students are required to discover realities through systematic observation of facts and experiences, and then use conceptual and theoretical tools to construct an understanding of those realities. This approach breaks away from traditional teaching, which discloses theories, and engages students more in constructing their learning" (Luckerhoff, Johnson & Guillemette, 2020).

With the new teaching methods, the learner becomes the architect of their own knowledge. As for the teacher, they act as a facilitator who coordinates the pedagogical activities in the classroom. This marks the rise of actualizing pedagogy, which "encourages problem-solving in groups and the development of social skills conducive to teamwork" (Landry, 2002, p. 20).

In Senegal, the reliance on traditional pedagogical methods can be attributed mainly to two essential reasons. Firstly, introducing change into any system is not an easy task. Resistance to change is common, with many individuals continuing to adhere to traditional teaching methods, as mentioned earlier, where the teacher is the sole authority of knowledge. The other reason for difficulties in changing pedagogical methods in Senegal relates to class sizes. From kindergarten to secondary school, class sizes are often very large (it's not uncommon to have 80 students in a single classroom). In this context, the most suitable pedagogical model for teaching children is the traditional one. However, things are gradually changing, especially in vocational training schools where innovative methods are increasingly being used. Additionally, since the advent of COVID-19, some teaching is conducted remotely.

Methodology

As per Johnson & Christensen (2008), research methodology should not only allow readers to judge the researcher's approach but also enable its replication if needed. It must be precise and comprehensive. In this regard, our methodological approach will revolve around the following aspects: research type, research subject identification, sampling, data collection, data processing, and analysis. Considering the limited number of participants, this research employs a qualitative approach. According to Mays & Pope (1995, p. 43), "the goal of qualitative research is to develop concepts that help us understand social phenomena in natural (rather than experimental) settings, focusing on the meanings, experiences, and viewpoints of all participants." Furthermore, qualitative research comprises five traditions : Biography, Phenomenology, Grounded Theory, Ethnography, and Case Study (Creswell, 1999).

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Unlike quantitative approaches, qualitative methods often study small groups. Therefore, within the scope of this research, we have chosen a case study. This is particularly justified by the small number of participants in the study. According to Creswell & Miller (2000), a case study involves collecting multiple sources of information, including observations, interviews, audiovisual material, and various documents. After analyzing this information, the next step involves a thorough description of the studied cases (Creswell & Miller, 2000).

In other words, a case study allows for exploring a specific question through one or more precise, delimited, and contextualized cases (Creswell, 2003). In this study, the cases consist of three Senegalese students enrolled at Laval University. The number of cases is sufficient; in fact, according to Stake (2010), an sample size is never small in qualitative research. Thus, the study could even focus on a single individual or case (Stake, 2010). For the selection of these three research subjects, the non-probabilistic purposive sampling method was employed. According to Royer and Zarlowsk (2014), sampling refers to methods of selecting a subset of individuals from a population to estimate its characteristics. Regarding data collection, it was conducted individually with the research subjects. In other words, we conducted interviews with each student using a semi-structured interview guide specifically designed for this purpose. The guide predominantly consisted of open-ended questions to avoid mutual influences on participants' responses. According to Savoie-Zajc (2009, p. 340), "a semi-structured interview involves a flexible interaction between the researcher and the participant. The researcher allows the rhythm and unique content of the exchange to guide them, aiming to approach the general themes they wish to explore with the research participant. Through this interaction, a rich understanding of the phenomenon under study is jointly constructed with the interviewer." Each interview lasted between five (5) to ten (10) minutes. Finally, to maintain the anonymity of respondents, we assigned them codes. Thus, ERQ1 represents the first student, ERQ2 the second, and ERQ3 the last student. The interviews were recorded with the students' consent. After the interviews, the participants' statements were transcribed, coded, and categorized before undergoing analysis.

Analysis and Discussion of Results

In this section, the analysis and discussion will revolve around the verbatim content derived from the interviews conducted with the three students. The work will be organized around three themes as outlined in the interview guide. These themes include the description of teaching methods used in Senegal, those employed at Laval University, and the subjects' comparison of these two teaching methods.

Teaching Methods Used in Senegal

Regarding the pedagogical methods used in Senegal, it must be highlighted from the outset that the interviewed students characterized them as directive or transmission-based methods. As mentioned in the introduction, the teaching methods frequently employed in Senegal are primarily centered around the transmission of knowledge from the teacher to the student. In this type of teaching, the student is passive and relies heavily on the teacher (Gauthier, 2005).

This characterization is confirmed by the Senegalese students with whom we conducted interviews. To illustrate this, here is what ERQ2 stated: "Teaching methods in Senegal are essentially transmission-based, with a near absence of group work." However, while ERQ2 is clear about the transmission-based nature of the pedagogical approaches used in Senegalese universities, this is not the case for the other students, namely ERQ1 and ERQ3. ERQ1 indicated that there are two pedagogical approaches used in Senegal: the participatory approach and the directive approach. They stated, "I would say that in Senegal, in terms of teaching methods, two main tendencies emerge."

In discussing directive methods, ERQ1 confirmed the stance of ERQ2 regarding the existence of directive pedagogical methods where students are passive. In these methods, the teacher is the main holder of knowledge and imparts it to the students. This implies that with such teaching methods, students contribute little effort as they receive almost everything from their teacher. To support this analysis, ERQ1 mentioned, "The first (pedagogical approach) is a directive tendency where the teacher imparts most of the teachings and guides the students, and students tend to engage with this approach. It's thus a directive approach." Additionally, alongside this directive or transmission-based approach, there exists a more flexible participatory approach. Here, the learner is fully engaged in constructing knowledge. In this context, it's the students themselves who build their own knowledge, in contrast to the directive approach. ERQ1 stated, "There have also been more flexible approaches, let's say active approaches that encourage student participation." ERQ3 concurred with their compatriot ERQ1, emphasizing that the pedagogical methods used in Senegal are at times active or participatory. ERQ3 even went further to suggest that these methods are almost the same as those practiced at Laval University. ERQ3 stated, "(...) but it's mostly the teaching methods we

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use, meaning methods that are primarily centered on active student participation in the process of knowledge acquisition." However, it's noticeable that ERQ3 exercises caution when saying "mostly the teaching methods," which implies that there might be differences.

The varying perceptions that Senegalese students hold about the pedagogical methods used in Senegal can be explained by the fact that both ERQ1 and ERQ3 attended vocational training schools where students are selected through a highly competitive process. In these schools, teachers can afford to use active or participatory teaching methods as their student numbers are limited. ERQ2, on the other hand, attended Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar, where class sizes can be extremely large, sometimes exceeding 2000 students. With such numbers, it becomes challenging for teachers to implement active or participatory teaching methods. In fact, ERQ3 even mentioned, "(...) since we don't have many universities, class sizes are massive, and there aren't many professors, so we end up with professors teaching in lecture halls with over 2500 students (...)." This situation reaffirms the notion that the number of students determines the teaching methods employed.

Teaching Methods Used at Laval University

According to the three students we interviewed, the teaching methods used by instructors at Laval University are rooted in active pedagogy. These are methods that grant more autonomy to learners. With these methods, the teacher becomes a facilitator who guides students through the process of knowledge acquisition. In other words, the teacher's presence in the classroom involves guiding and directing students who are the builders of their own knowledge. This observation was unanimous among the interviewees. To illustrate this, ERQ1 stated, "(...) but if I try to characterize the teaching methods at Laval University a bit, I do notice that there is a significant part where there is guidance that allows the student to develop their autonomy." This indicates that student autonomy is highly developed in the pedagogical approaches practiced at Laval University. According to our respondents, this can be largely attributed to the availability of resources. Unlike the universities they came from, Laval University provides students with abundant documentary resources. These include electronic documents as well as physical resources like course materials, textbooks, periodicals, etc. Referring to this abundance of resources, ERQ3 mentioned, "(...) I can say that here students have more resources, more textbooks, more reference materials; in short, they have more opportunities to access information."

However, in their perceptions of the pedagogical approaches used at Laval University, some students also raised criticisms. This is noteworthy as it is known that not everything is always perfect in the pedagogical approaches at any institution. Thus, for these students, the teaching methods depend on the instructors. Indeed, in their view, some professors at Laval University are often inactive, leading to frequent student presentations. In essence, students end up doing most of the work instead of the professor. This shows that students are not indifferent to what professors do. They mention the lack of effort put forth by some instructors during classes. The words of ERQ3 below exemplify this sentiment : "(...) I don't appreciate it at all because sometimes I think it's a bit too easy..., the professors don't put in enough effort, it's the students who do everything."

Comparison between Pedagogical Methods

Regarding the differentiation between the pedagogical approaches used at Laval University and those practiced in Senegal, the participants in this study emphasized student autonomy and personal development. In Senegal, students often remain reliant on the knowledge transmitted by instructors, while in North America in general, and specifically at Laval University, the teaching aims to foster personal development among students. This is reflected in the role of the instructors as facilitators during classes. ERQ1 mentioned, "However, here at Laval University, from the start, you are provided with tools, guidelines, and directions that give you the opportunity to enhance your intellectual capacities, your potential. To gather information, to develop the habits of work and intellectual production." This indicates that at Laval University, instructors encourage students to take pleasure in constructing their own knowledge.

The comparison of the two pedagogical approaches reveals a significant difference between Laval University and Senegalese universities, particularly in terms of the organization of the academic year and program configuration. ERQ2 stated, "No, it's not the same at all; it's even linked to the program structure (...)." In Canada, the academic year is organized into sessions and courses are divided into credits, unlike in Senegal where teaching takes place throughout the year (9 to 10 months). To emphasize this difference, ERQ2 mentioned, "Here (at Laval University), it's by session, and each session lasts for 4 months, unlike back home where it's 9 months."

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Moreover, Senegal has also implemented the LMD (Bachelor-Master-Doctorate) reform. With this reform, the academic year is organized into semesters, and courses are organized into teaching units with credits. ERQ2 illustrated this point, "With the LMD reform, we are moving towards the concept of credits, semesterization, and dividing the year into multiple sessions."

Furthermore, this study revealed that there are no significant differences between the pedagogical approaches of Laval University and those used in Senegal, especially in higher vocational training schools. This is primarily due to the relatively small number of students attending these institutions. ERQ3, who is a teacher at one of these schools, mentioned, "In fact, between the pedagogical methods used at Laval University and those used in the department where I work, there aren't major differences." However, he acknowledged that there is a difference in approach between Senegalese universities and Laval University. He attributed this difference to the overcrowded student populations found in Senegalese universities, saying, "But if you compare the pedagogical methods used at Laval University and those used in Senegalese universities, there are indeed significant differences."

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to analyze the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students. To achieve this goal, a research problem was developed around traditional and innovative pedagogical methods. In terms of methodology, the study employed a qualitative approach with the research tradition of a case study. The selection of students for interviews was done using purposive sampling.

The results reveal that the students interviewed hold a positive view of the teaching methods used at Laval University. For some, these methods are considered active, fostering student empowerment. Moreover, students appreciate the availability of documentary resources that enable them to independently seek out and construct their own knowledge. However, while some students view the teaching methods positively, others offer a more critical perspective. For these individuals, there is a perceived connection between teaching methods and the instructors who employ them. Consequently, certain professors at Laval University are seen as inactive, leading to a reliance on readings and student presentations during classes.

Furthermore, it would be interesting to delve deeper into two points raised by the respondents: program flexibility and the lack of effort by instructors. While the respondents appreciate the flexibility to take courses outside their program, they remain critical of the teaching methods of certain professors. These aspects will be subject to further analysis in a forthcoming article.

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